

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST *of* SCOTLAND

**The Role of Arts and Culture in the Colombian
Peacebuilding Process**

By

Greis Steffany Cifuentes Tarquino

University of the West of Scotland

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ABSTRACT

Recent research on arts and culture has shown that artistic and cultural practices are a trigger for social transformations towards peacebuilding (Lederach, 2005; Liebmann, 1996; LeBaron, 2011). Colombia is ending a fifty-year-long conflict, and an opportunity exists for arts and culture to play an essential role in rebuilding memory, social relations, community, bringing people together, raising awareness about past suffering and promoting healing.

This thesis explores the role that arts and cultural interventions can play in the aftermath of the Colombian conflict, and the opportunities and limitations of applying arts-based practices in communities dealing with its legacy. Notably, this thesis is intended to assist and inform policymakers and those making funding decisions of the social impact of arts and culture, providing a review of theoretical debates alongside evidence of current arts and cultural programmes that are taking place in Colombia.

In order to examine the role of arts and cultural interventions in peacebuilding efforts, two specific research questions guide the study: i) what role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict? and ii) what design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture? Utilising interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), along with participant observation of two arts and cultural projects in Colombia (Casa Kolacho in Medellín, and Sensory Expedition in Montes de María), this study illustrates how these interventions can address and ameliorate the effects of conflict on people in different geographical settings. The findings of this study demonstrate that collective cultural activities can further promote the building of social capital, providing opportunities for people to interact and strength social networks that facilitate mutual understanding and dialogue, and can also encourage a sense of belonging and place identity that contributes to long term peacebuilding process. However, the study also reveals the need to develop evaluation and impact studies to measure the peacebuilding outcomes of arts-based and cultural projects, in order to strengthen their case for funding. I demonstrate that there are a range of conditions that are essential for constructive conflict resolution: the establishment of a culture of peace, based on respectful relationships, and the development of collective cultural practices, which must be set according to the context and local reality of the area of conflict.

The study concludes by arguing that paying greater attention to cultural grassroots initiatives and participatory art offers a hitherto largely untapped opportunity for peacebuilding. Nevertheless, any decisions with regard to its deployment will inevitably depend on the interaction between the policymakers and the communities affected by the armed conflict.

DECLARATION

This research project represents partial submission for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy at the University of the West of Scotland. I confirm that the work presented here is my own. Where information has been derived from other sources, I confirm that this has been indicated in the thesis.

During the period of registered study in which this thesis was prepared the author has not been registered for any other academic award or qualification. The material included in this thesis has not been submitted wholly or in part for any academic award or qualification other than that for which it is now submitted.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	I
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	IV
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	VII
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	IX
LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES.....	X
CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.0 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Colombia: A History of Conflict.....	3
1.1 Colombia and Culture.....	6
1.3 Culture and Peacebuilding.....	9
1.4 Research Aim and Research Questions.....	12
1.4.1 Research Aim.....	12
1.4.2 Research Questions.....	12
1.5 Organisation of the Thesis.....	13
CHAPTER 2. ARTS, CULTURE, CAPITAL AND VALUE.....	16
2.0 Introduction.....	16
2.1 Arts and Culture: A Contested Terrain.....	16
2.2 The Social Value of Art and Culture.....	21
2.3 Culture and Social Cohesion.....	28
2.4 Valuing Culture or Cultural Value.....	34
2.5 Conclusion.....	38
CHAPTER 3. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ARTS AND CULTURE IN PEACEBUILDING PROCESSES.....	40
3.0 Introduction.....	40
3.1 Understanding Conflict and its Effects.....	40
3.2 Reconciliation and Peacebuilding through Arts and Culture.....	44
3.3 The Role of Creativity in Resolving Peacebuilding Problems.....	52
3.4 Cultural Conversations: Dialogue and Peacebuilding.....	54
3.5 Mutual Understanding towards Empathy.....	60
3.6 Conclusion.....	63
CHAPTER 4. METHODOLOGY.....	65
4.0 Introduction.....	65
4.0 Ontological, Epistemological and Paradigmatic Considerations.....	66
4.1 Focusing on ‘Experiences’.....	69
4.2 Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA).....	71
4.3 Research Design: Two Cases.....	74
4.3.1 Case Selection.....	75
4.4 Participant Observation Approach.....	76
4.5 Semi-Structured Interviews.....	80
4.5.1 The Interview Guide.....	84
4.6 Data Analysis.....	85
4.7 Ethical Considerations.....	86
4.8 Trustworthiness and Authenticity.....	90

4.9 Conclusion	91
CHAPTER 5. PEACE ON THE GROUND, CASA KOLACHO	92
5.0 Introduction.....	92
5.1 Casa Kolacho, Comuna 13.....	92
5.2 Casa Kolacho as a Peacebuilding Strategy	96
5.3 A Culture of Peace	101
5.4 Determinants of Social Capital	103
5.4.1 Social Cohesion and Rebuilding Community.....	106
5.5 The Value of Culture for Policymakers	114
5.6 Conclusion	121
CHAPTER 6. SENSORY EXPEDITION: PEACE FROM THE BOTTOM TO THE TOP	124
6.0 Introduction.....	124
6.1 Montes de María: The Face of Armed Conflict.....	125
6.2 Sensory Expedition: A State-Led Effort towards Peacebuilding.....	129
6.2.1 Sensory Expedition’s contribution to peacebuilding	131
6.2.2 The Structure of the Arts-Based Project	134
6.2.3 A Local Social Transformation.....	135
6.3 Sensory Expedition: Through the Eyes of the Community	136
6.4 Conclusion	149
CHAPTER 7. CULTURE, PEACEBUILDING AND THE POLICYMAKING PROCESS	152
7.0 Introduction.....	152
7.1 A Historical Disconnection with Culture.....	153
7.2 Public Support for Arts and Culture	156
7.3 Conclusion	165
CHAPTER 8: RETURNING CULTURE TO PEACEBUILDING	167
8.0 Introduction.....	167
8.1 The Strengthening of Social Capital through Peacebuilding.....	167
8.2 Peaceful Ways of Dealing with Conflict	172
8.2.1 Creative Solutions	173
8.2.2 Peaceful Dialogue	175
8.2.3 Mutual Understanding and Empathy	176
8.3. Rethinking a Peacebuilding Model.....	177
8.3.1 Civic Engagement and Participatory Art at a Local Community Level	178
8.3.2 Culture through the Policymakers and Politician’s Lens.....	181
8.3.3 Shaping the Role of Public Funding in Arts and Culture	185
8.4 Conclusion	188
CHAPTER 9: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	190
9.0 Introduction.....	190
9.1 Thesis Summary.....	191
9.2 Key study findings	193
9.3 Contribution to Knowledge.....	198
9.3.1 Methodological Contribution.....	198
9.3.2 Theoretical and Policy Contributions.....	200
9.4 Recommendations from the Research	203
9.5 Limitations of the Research	206
9.6 Implications for Future Research.....	208

9.7 Chapter Summary	209
REFERENCES	211
APPENDICES	234
A1: Participant Information Sheet	234
A2: Consent Form.....	238
A3: Interview Structure for Policy Makers.....	240
A4: Interview Structure for Cultural Agents	243
A5: Interview Structure for Research Participants	246

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For me, the last four years have been a rollercoaster, not only in terms of emotions but also in terms of the changes I have experienced. Living in Berlin, while doing my PhD, being a mother, studying German and working at the same time, has been the biggest of challenges. The woman who finishes this PhD is not at all the same woman who started it. My dreams have been fulfilled thanks to my effort and perseverance and belief that I can do it. Love for what I do has also been hugely important, that was the starting point for this doctoral research adventure. Working in the Ministry of Culture of Colombia and witnessing the low budget for cultural projects, while — at the same time — seeing the positive impact such ventures had on the communities where they took place, motivated me to study. I wanted to have more, and more nuanced, arguments to be able to justify the significance of investment and the importance of culture for my country. This driver, that the arts and culture have transformative power in society, has motivated me to hold management positions at national and municipal level, putting into practice what I value and what I study. And, in 2021, it has led me to be one of the 30 most influential young women in politics in Colombia.

Over four years, I have lived in three different cities, Berlin, Bogotá, and Ibagué, my hometown. I have had three important jobs in the cultural sector that gave me a unique opportunity to put my thesis research into practice. I was a project assistant at Fulbright in Germany, and when I returned to Colombia, I held the position of national development manager of the Batuta Foundation and as secretary of Culture of the city of Ibagué, leading a team of more than 100 people, overseeing programmes and policies that should benefit more than 500,000 citizens. By holding these positions, I have not only confirmed my belief that the arts are a tool for peacebuilding, but I have also been able to implement public policies to enhance a culture of peace.

It is not easy to write a thesis, it requires time, concentration and will. It is unlikely that these three factors are present at the same time, but the secret ingredient — I think — is to know why and what you are doing it for. If this is clear, you will have the engine to finish it, because you have an objective.

This thesis would not have been possible without the determination and endless support of my family, my parents and sisters. You have always stood behind me, and this was no exception.

I am the first in my family to undertake a PhD degree, and I am sure I will not be the only one. Dad, I couldn't have done this without you, thank you for being an example of discipline and excellence. Thanks to my mother for showing me that things are done with love; to my *irmã*, for being my unconditional support and friend; and to Geral, for showing me that life is now.

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This is not over yet; this is just the start of my journey.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AUC	United Self-Defence Groups of Colombia (Autodefensas Unidas de Colombia)
BACRIM	Criminal Bands (Bandas Criminales)
CERAC	The Resource Centre for Conflict Analysis
DANE	National Administrative Department of Statistics (Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística)
ELN	National Liberation Army (Ejército de Liberación Nacional)
FARC	Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia (Fuerzas Armadas Revolucionarias de Colombia)
GPD	Gross Domestic Product (Producto Interno Bruto)
INDEPAZ	Institute for Development and Peace Studies (Instituto de Estudios para el desarrollo y la paz)
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UNICEF	United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund
WGI	World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1. Travelling by different means in the region of Montes de María during field work	78
Figure 2. Debriefing session with Casa Kolacho members	88
Figure 3. Map of Comuna 13 in Medellín	93
Figure 4. Number of homicides in Comunas 8, 13 and 16 in Medellín.....	95
Figure 5. Intra-urban displacement in Comunas 8, 13 and 16 in Medellín	96
Figure 6. Message of fear from insurgent groups: Dead to the ‘sapos’	110
Figure 7. Casa Kolacho member painting over the threatening message	111
Figure 8. Wisdom graffiti from Casa Kolacho	111
Figure 9. Participatory budget allocation for Comuna 13 by sectors	116
Figure 10. Investment on culture by the Comunas in Medellín.....	117
Figure 11. Annual investment in culture.....	118
Figure 12. Percentage of the annual budget invested in culture 2004-2019	118
Figure 13. Map of Montes de María	126
Figure 14. Music instrument made by the instructor	133
Figure 15. Libertad Music Process	139
Figure 16. The vicious cycle of culture in policymaking	187
Figure 17. The co-design strategy.....	202
Table 1. Policymakers interviewed.....	82
Table 2. Number of interviews disaggregated by the groups interviewed	84

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

Being from the department of Tolima, located in central Colombia, has allowed me to witness the period of violence that the country has experienced. Tolima is one of the regions most affected by the armed conflict, with a history of guerrilla activity, paramilitary violence, and drug trafficking. In addition, the region is recognised as the Department where the former FARC was born in the 1960s. The passage of violence through its territories triggered an increase in the rates of political violence and poverty. The region experienced the birth and strengthening of the war with the presence of actors such as the former FARC¹ and the AUC², and the civilian population was caught in the middle of the fire.

Although I have not been a direct victim of the Colombian armed conflict, I have seen how the culture of violence has become normalised and naturalised in our society, and how it has permeated the different areas of Colombians' life, leaving deep and lasting effects on people's mental and physical well-being. This experience and working in the cultural sector as an advisor in the Ministry of Culture of Colombia and as Secretary of Culture of Ibagué, capital of Tolima — my hometown — gave me insight into the cultural actors at local and national level. Likewise, it led me to understand from other points of view the reality of the armed conflict in Colombia, and the relationship with culture as a way to promote peace and resolve conflicts, which was also one of the motivations to write this thesis. This also allowed me to have a multilevel commitment with the research project and its design.

In these circumstances, I have come to realise that culture and the phenomenological approach are interconnected, as the phenomenological approach emphasises the subjective experiences of individuals and how they are shaped by cultural and social factors. For example, cultural norms, beliefs, and values can influence how individuals perceive and interpret the world around them. In line with this, the phenomenological approach emphasises the importance of cultural context in shaping individual experiences. By recognising and understanding cultural differences, individuals can achieve a deeper understanding of themselves and others, and

¹ Acronym for Fuerzas Armadas Revolucionarias de Colombia.

² Acronym for Autodefensas Unidas de Colombia.

establish more positive relationships. In sum, prior knowledge of the cultural sector and my high-level decision-making positions were one of the key factors in determining the that phenomenological approach was the most appropriate methodology for this research.

On the other hand, as the Portuguese sociologist and researcher Boaventura de Sousa Santos (2014) argues, there is a dominant Eurocentric perspective that has shaped Western social theory. He also mentions that the knowledge and experience of the Global South, including Latin America, can offer alternative perspectives and insights that can enrich and transform social theory and that can be transformative and contribute to a more just and equitable society. As Sousa Santos explains, epistemologies from the South have the potential to promote social and political transformation by giving voice to marginalised communities and challenging dominant power structures, which is one of the objectives of this research.

Within this general context, the purpose of this study is to explore the contribution of arts and cultural interventions to peacebuilding in post-conflict Colombia. This study is committed to the idea that the repair and rebuilding of social relationships represents a realistic path towards peace in a country in which stable peace agreements between its conflicting parties have yet to be reached.

This research utilises two case studies to draw attention to some of the lessons evident in their practice and approaches. Through exploration of the work undertaken by Casa Kolacho in Medellín and Sensory Expedition in Montes de María, this study highlights the mechanisms that have contributed to transform victims' environments and lives, leveraging arts to change perceptions of the future, encourage empathy, promote dialogue, and empower individuals to leave aside feelings including mistrust, hate, and fear. This thesis provides a clearer delineation of the relationship between arts and the pursuit of peace, exploring how arts serves a key role in preventing the outbreak of — or healing from — violence, trauma, and conflict. In this regard, the focus on grassroots initiatives within an arts approach explores how certain projects can, with participation of local actors, enhance or moderate emotions that could activate new cycles of violence.

1.1 Colombia: A History of Conflict

Colombia is a nation that is fragmented (Palacios & Safford, 2002) for a number of reasons. The geography of Colombia resulted in the formation of regions that were isolated for a long time. Historically, the State has been weak in fiscal terms and regulatory capacity, and instead has relied on the monopoly of force. The precariousness of the Colombian State has been the key element that explains the persistence of violence (Uprimny, 2001).

For more than five years, Colombia was labelled as a ‘fragile State’ according to the annual Fragile States Index, created by The Fund for Peace in 2000 and published by Foreign Policy³. In 2005, Colombia ranked 27th out of 178 countries and, as such, was among those States at the highest risk of instability. Since then, Colombia has significantly improved in this ranking, reaching its best score in 2019, when a score of 75.7 placed it 70th in the index. However, in 2020 the country experienced a decline in its scores, returning to 65th position in the rankings. This backsliding was due to increased violence in the country, threats to civic leaders and the ongoing social reintegration of former guerrilla members.

Despite the fact that poverty has fallen (DANE⁴, 2016), Colombia remains one of the most unequal countries in the world. According to the GINI Coefficient Index⁵, in 2013 Colombia had a GINI coefficient of 53 (11th position in the world and 4th among Latin American nations), and in 2015 it had improved slightly to 51.1 (14th position in the world and 4th in Latin America). Although the country reached its best historical coefficient in 2017 (49.7), it has also experienced a deterioration in this indicator in recent times, reaching 51.3 in 2019. Furthermore, according to 2019 figures, the top 10% of Colombia’s richest people earned 40.3% of the country’s income, a number that increased to 56.2% when considering the richest

³ “The Fragile States Index is an assessment of 178 countries based on 12 social, economic, and political indicators to analyse how wars, peace accords, environmental calamities, and political movements have pushed countries towards stability or closer to the brink of collapse. The index then ranks the countries accordingly, from most fragile to least” (The Fund For Peace, 2000).

⁴ Acronym for Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística (National Administrative Department of Statistics).

⁵ “The GINI index measures the extent to which the distribution of income (or, in some cases, consumption expenditure) among individuals or households within an economy deviates from a perfectly equal distribution. A GINI index of zero represents perfect equality and 100, perfect inequality” (World Bank, 2017).

20% (World Bank, 2021). Additionally, according to Oxfam (2017), 81% of the land in Colombia is owned by only 1% of the country's inhabitants.

Additionally, corruption continues to be a significant problem for the country. According to the 2016 Corruption Perception Index reported by the NGO Transparency International, Colombia is ranked 90th (out of 175), with a score of 37 — where being close to zero indicates a highly corrupt country and close to 100, a transparent country. Similarly, in terms of control of corruption, the World Bank's Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) place Colombia in the lowest half of the percentile ranking, with a score of 44.23. The same indicators reveal that the rule of law in Colombia has not improved, with points accrued remaining broadly similar: moving from 46.63 in 2015 to 41.35 in 2016 (World Bank, 2016b).

The sum of these factors provides a picture of a society that continues to suffer from the ravages of conflict. For more than 50 years, the Colombian population has been the victim of extortion, land grabbing, kidnapping, torture, manslaughter, selective killings, and massacres (more than 260,000 dead), illicit recruitment of children and adolescents, crimes against freedom and sexual integrity and forced disappearance (estimates put the numbers of disappeared people in the tens of thousands). As a result, the country has faced one of the world's most acute internal displacement situations arising from conflict and violence over five decades and resulting in almost eight million internally displaced people (Grupo de Memoria Histórica, 2015).

Furthermore, the Colombian population has been polarised since the beginning of the peace negotiations between the FARC guerrilla group⁶ and the government, that were carried out in Havana, Cuba. While many support the peace process, there are still some who do not. A tangible example of the political turmoil Colombia has faced is the result of the October 2nd, 2016 referendum on the Peace Agreements with the FARC guerrilla. The public was asked: "Do you support the final agreement for the ending of the conflict and the construction of a stable and lasting peace?", and 50.2% rejected the motion with 49.8% voting in favour. Fewer than 60,000 votes separated the 'No' from the 'Yes' camps in the Peace Agreements poll. After five decades, and despite the failed efforts of previous governments to negotiate with the FARC guerrilla, this conflict finally came to an end in 2016. In spite of the popular pronouncement in

⁶ Acronym for Fuerzas Armadas Revolucionarias de Colombia, or Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia, a Marxist guerilla group active between 1964 and 2016.

the public vote, the Peace Agreements were approved by the government after politicians were forced to negotiate with the sectors and organisations that had supported a ‘No’ vote; the definitive Peace Agreements were signed on November 24, 2016, at the Teatro Colón in Bogotá.

While other armed groups still operate in the country, the conflict with the FARC guerrilla group is over, and the agreement establishes the terms that will end confrontations with the guerrilla group in the form of a bilateral ceasefire and a definitive end to hostilities (Colombian Government, 2016). The Peace Agreements with the FARC guerrilla provide the basic conditions to achieve stable and lasting peace in Colombia. According to the agreement, peace must be built with the participation of all Colombians in order to promote a culture of tolerance, coexistence, and reconciliation. Also, the agreement acknowledges that decades of violence have caused distrust within Colombian society — this is especially the case in the territories most affected by the conflict. In seeking to address distrust, section five of the agreement, ‘Victims of the Conflict’, commits the government to open spaces for citizen participation that foster the recognition of victims and of what happened by the whole society. All these components have been integrated into the System of Truth, Justice, Reparation and Non-Repetition, and in the “Commitment to the promotion, respect and guarantee of human rights”. These commitments include relevant settlements, such as the creation of the Commission for the Clarification of Truth, Coexistence and Non-Repetition, the Special Unit for the Search for Disappeared Persons in the Conflict, and the Special Jurisdiction for Peace. It is argued by the government that these measures will help to achieve coexistence, reconciliation, prevention of repetition, and the transition from an armed conflict to peace (Colombian Government, 2016).

At the same time, thanks to the high degree of compliance with the bilateral ceasefire agreement, the number of civilian and military victims, as well as those victims of violent actions directly associated with the armed conflict between the FARC guerrilla and the Colombian State, have fallen to its lowest level in 52 years. The CERAC⁷ shows that civil deaths have fallen 98% (from a daily average of 0.19 to 0.003 deaths), and combatant deaths have fallen 94% (from a daily average of 1.08 to 0.07 dead). Unfortunately, since 2016, this pattern has not been sustained over the succeeding years. Subsequently, human rights violations have risen since the Peace Agreements were signed. In 2017, there were 170 deaths

⁷ Acronym for Centro de Recursos para el Análisis de Conflictos, or Resource Centre for Conflict Analysis.

of social leaders, human rights defenders, and peace advocates (an increase of 45.29% compared to 2016), and during January and April 2018, according to the Institute of Studies for Development and Peace (Indepaz, April 13th, 2018), 56 leaders were killed.

However, former Minister of Defence Luis Carlos Villegas and former President Juan Manuel Santos have indicated that at least 35% of homicides of social leaders have been perpetrated for personal reasons (Noticias Uno Colombia, December 16th, 2017; Howland, 2017). On the other hand, a report prepared by NGO Indepaz asserts that the majority of the murders occurred systematically for control of the land and because of the resurgence of violence in territories dominated by the FARC guerrilla that are now controlled by criminal gangs (Delgado, 2017). Likewise, the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, Todd Howland (2017), stated that half of the murders were committed by hitmen in areas vacated by the FARC guerrilla and now disputed by criminal gangs and the ELN guerrilla⁸. According to Indepaz (April 13th, 2021) between 2020 and 2021 there were 50 massacres with 189 victims, and more than 250 ex-combatants have been killed since the signing of the Peace Agreements. Even though the numbers do not compare with those of a decade ago, these incidents can be seen as signals of the urgent need to effectively implement the agreements.

Further, according to a report on the efficacy of the Peace Agreements implementation in Colombia, published by the Kroc Institute for International Peace Studies (2019), the peace process implementation is still fragile, and Colombia needs to prevent the emergence of different forms of violence by addressing the roots of the conflict: access to and use of land, social and economic development for those living in poverty, armed violence, and institutional weakness (Kroc Institute for International Peace Studies, 2019). This scenario led me to examine innovative approaches and best practices that can be used in promoting dialogue, tolerance, and mutual understanding, and that can contribute to the construction of peace in the aftermath of violence.

1.1 Colombia and Culture

Colombia is a country with an exceptional natural and cultural heritage, incomparably rich and geographically heterogeneous, with diverse cultural and social conditions and different levels

⁸ Acronym for Ejército de Liberación Nacional, or Nacional Liberation Army, a guerrilla group active since 1964.

of regional development. This is reflected in a multiplicity of cultural forms in which the identities, memories and practices of its citizens, social groups and cultural agents are expressed (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013). The Colombian State guarantees the cultural rights in their most general sense: through access, availability, quality, and participation.

Access is understood as the State's obligation to provide ample and diverse spaces for the right to enjoy art, culture, and heritage. The obligation of access is fulfilled when it is possible to choose from the wide range of existing artistic and cultural expressions. The State fails to comply with this obligation when it decides to limit the diversity of expressions, in a country characterised by multiple cultural manifestations, enriched by ethnic, territorial, and cultural differences.

Citizens have the right to access spaces (physical or virtual, permanent, or temporary, centralised, or decentralised) that enrich them artistically and culturally. Second, for citizens to have guaranteed access to these spaces, a wide and representative artistic and cultural diversity needs to circulate, and that will fulfil the general recognition of diversity as a value of the country. The State fulfils this obligation when it provides management platforms, infrastructure, training, dissemination opportunities, creation, and entrepreneurship, that allow the practice, knowledge, and enjoyment of culture for citizens. The third element in guaranteeing rights is quality. Quality implies the State's obligation to ensure that the cultural offerings in the country meet minimum quality standards. It is also imperative that quality cultural offerings are made available for all citizens, and not restricted to those with existing access to cultural capital. In short, the context of cultural rights is fundamental in guiding the design, execution, and evaluation of public policies in the cultural sector, since it is this condition that allows culture to be positioned in its role as a constitutive element of cultural development (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013).

The Colombian Political Constitution also obliges the Ministry of Culture to act as a facilitator of community development processes in the country. To achieve this goal, the Ministry of Culture makes every effort to integrate culture into sustainable development policies and programmes. Their contribution includes: mobilising cultural investments to foster peace and reconciliation, poverty reduction and economic progress; securing cultural rights to promote inclusive social development; safeguarding and disseminating manifestations of cultural heritage; and strengthening innovation and cooperation through culture. Following this

trajectory, in 2013, the Ministry of Culture facilitated a participatory exercise in the 1,101 municipalities of Colombia to recognise and systematise extant information on culture in the country. The *Diagnosis of Cultural Development in Colombia* study was designed to improve policy formulation and decision making, and to qualify the information available on the sector. Following this process, culture in Colombia has gone from being understood as a consumer good to being considered an important factor in social and economic development, contributing to the wellbeing of society and social cohesion (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013).

Six study areas emerged from the *Diagnosis of Cultural Development in Colombia* study: cultural diversity, cultural access, economic dimension, artistic practices, cultural governance, and social capital. Some tensions also arose from this research, especially between the public policies implemented at the territorial level and the cultural practices that occur in the territory but are not mediated by these policies. There is a clear disconnection between national policies and local cultural practices, which means that they are incongruent with lived realities. A second tension is evident between formalised artistic and cultural practices, such as the so-called “high culture” (e.g. the fine arts) and mass popular cultural practices. A third tension exists between the dynamics of the cultural industries and local entrepreneurship that occurs as a feature of community financial support, or as alternative production and distribution initiatives. Here, the Ministry of Culture recognises that the production of cultural goods and services is characterised by local practices in which cultural entrepreneurship is an essential component of the shaping of the social fabric (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013).

In order to (re)build the social fabric after more than five decades of armed conflict, in collaboration with local people and policy actors, in 2018 the Ministry of Culture outlined a set of strategic actions for the cultural sector to facilitate reconciliation, inclusion and equity processes in the most remote regions of the country. This initiative was motivated by the conviction that culture can transform lives, help rebuild social fabric, encourage tolerance, generate opportunities for development, and contribute to happiness (Ministerio de Cultura, 2018). One of the initiatives that benefitted from the Ministry’s strategic actions is the Sensory Expedition project, which began in the Montes de María region of Colombia. This region was selected as a site for a laboratory to develop a comprehensive model for cultural activity outside of the municipal capitals, working in an interdisciplinary fashion with rural communities. The intention behind creating interdisciplinary cultural spaces was to rebuild bonds of affection in

conflict-ridden communities, revitalising the knowledge and capacities of the communities by valuing their cultural richness.

The Sensory Expedition project responded to the need to broaden government action by working hand in hand with the communities most affected by the armed conflict. In this context, progress towards a lasting peace involves collective work and the construction of a joint cultural intervention in line with the needs of the territory. The Sensory Expedition project is one of the case studies that provides the empirical basis of this research.

1.3 Culture and Peacebuilding

Peacebuilding requires the guarantee of fundamental human rights in a context that values tolerance and respect for plurality and diversity. Over the past two decades, artists, educators, sociologists and peaceworkers across the world have been researching the role of arts and culture in conflict recovery. Theorists including Johan Galtung, Paul Lederach and Tatsushi Arai have identified creativity as a crucial axis of conflict transformation and peacebuilding. The United Nations has defined peacebuilding as “range of measures targeted to reduce the risk of lapsing or relapsing into conflict by strengthening national capacities at all levels for conflict management, and to lay the foundation for sustainable peace and development” (2008, p. 18).

According to The Transcend approach proposed by the Norwegian sociologist Johan Galtung, peace is the capacity to handle conflicts with mutual understanding, dialogue, and creativity, aiming to counteract the attitudes, behaviours and contradictions that arise during and after conflict situations. Galtung also argues that after the end of conflict, 3Rs must be set in motion: reconstruction, reconciliation, and resolution (Galtung, 1996). Similarly, Lederach (2005) presents The Moral Imagination as the art and soul of building peace that is needed for sustainable peace and social change. He argues that social change is not linear, since it must be focused on scenarios in which deep-rooted patterns of violence are experienced. He also suggests that the tools to achieve social change cannot be linear either. The Moral Imagination is linked directly with creativity as it is the capacity to generate what does not yet exist but can arise out of artistic processes. For Lederach, art has a transformative power to move people toward reconciliation; he argues for a focus on art and imagination as the soul of social change. Furthermore, he claims that a peace process does not end when the formal peace agreement is

signed between an insurgent group and the government; rather, peace is achieved when each citizen assumes respect for difference and establishes constructive relationships with each other (Lederach, October 24th, 2015).

Peacebuilding is a long term process of creating the essential conditions for a lasting peace. It needs to address the structural causes of conflict. It also, address the capacity of the State to guarantee greater effectiveness and efficiency in its actions, as well as the possibility of generating trust and credibility in the territories that have endured the armed conflict.

Tatsushi Arai also states that “to be useful for conflict resolution, unconventional visions and actions must be viable” (2009, p. 2), thus advocating for creativity as a conflict resolution practice. The aforementioned scholars have sought to introduce arts and cultural interventions into conflict resolution research. Malvern Lumsden (1997) has also suggested that the arts have a crucial role in peacebuilding, as they can promote a creative process to restore social connections. The arts stimulate creative problem solving and innovation within a group or community and tread a different ground (British Council, 2012).

Culture, creates the space where individuals can express, explore, and re-imagine difficult problems (Howson & Dubber, 2014). The formation of a *culture of peace* is important in a peacebuilding context, like the one in Colombia. Culture is defined in the United Nations Resolution A/RES/52/13 as a set of values, attitudes, modes of behaviour and ways of life. In line with Cohen (2011), it is essential to shift human behaviour; and arts and culture can contribute to meeting this challenge. Lederach (2005) argues that the construction of peace begins with the rejection of violence as a way to solve conflicts. Thereby, peace ought to be internalised culturally, which means eliminating the culture of violence as a way of solving conflicts.

Historically, through its transformative and conciliatory possibilities, the spread of arts and culture has made an important contribution to peacebuilding in different countries, including Ireland (Wallace Consulting, 2016), Bosnia-Herzegovina (Zelizer, 2003), South Africa (McIntyre, 2012) and Uganda (Hanebrink & Smith, 2013). These cases demonstrate that peacebuilding is a process where mechanisms and spaces must be established so that the wounds and emotions generated by conflict, such as hatred, resentment, fear, guilt, and uncertainty, are left behind (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009). In order to have reconciliation,

coexistence, reparation and forgiveness, authors have argued (Fukushima, 2011; Cohen, 2005) that arts and culture are needed as an inherent vehicle of peace. Arts and culture also have an important role in social reconstruction (Guetzkow, 2002; Matarasso, 1997; Lumsden, 1997), given that they can engage and empower people which can lead to the strengthening of community, sharing of common cultural experiences and giving opportunities for cooperation. Evidence suggests that the use of creative tools, such as music, performances, festivals, exhibits, visual art techniques, storytelling, dance, spoken word, photography, and community gatherings, enables engagement and participation in a community. It also reinforces cultural values, restores cultural identity, preserves heritage and history, rebuilds memory, and helps to build stronger communities (Zelizer, 2003; Shank & Schirch, 2008).

Lederach (1997) argues that the way to sustain peace is to engage all sides of the conflict in a reconciliation and forgiveness process that raises awareness about past suffering, creates trust, and heals trauma (Liebmann, 1996). This also requires fostering empathy, promoting dialogue, inspiring tolerance for difference, changing perceptions (Galtung, 1996) and increasing mutual understanding and acceptance, (Bornstein, 2015) in order to heal the past and build the future (Salzburg Global Seminar, 2014). Hence, it is necessary to explore the role that artistic processes and activities can play in providing context-specific solutions, bringing out perspectives and voices that otherwise might not be heard in prevailing approaches to peacebuilding. This, in turn, can lead to personal fulfilment, emotional reparation and transformation (Premaratna & Bleiker, 2016).

And yet, despite the possible role of arts and culture in post-conflict peace building, culture continues to be relegated from the government priorities in Colombia. The budget for the Ministry of Culture in Colombia fell 23% in 2017, going from 390,793 million Colombian pesos in 2015 to 302,024 million in 2017, and for 2020 this figure was 343,236 million pesos. On average, during the last 10 years the budget allocated to the cultural sector by the Ministry of Culture has been 317,614 million pesos, which suggests that culture has been assigned a minor role in the post-conflict landscape in Colombia. Regardless of this impoverished budget, the former Minister of Culture Mariana Garcés Córdoba stated in 2016:

[...] that the cultural sector has a fundamental role in our society. A person approaching a public library can resolve their conflicts peacefully. So, betting on investment in culture has no losses.

[Exposure to the] culture forms individuals capable of living in society [who] will be unable to wield a weapon. (Ministerio de Cultura, 2016)

In the light of these expectations, culture can play a fundamental role in the construction of a stable and lasting peace, strengthening the social fabric of communities, and generating spaces for reconciliation, memory, encounter, and trust. According to the Ministry of Culture, the violence in Montes de María resulted in the loss of social and cultural practices (Ministerio de Cultura, 2016). In turn, this was reflected in needs and problems, such as the lack of recognition and the weakening of artistic, cultural and heritage practices; the low generation of collective capacities and the weakness of social participation for the transformation of living conditions; the low levels of social capital; and the permanent need to build scenarios for reconciliation and peace.

This reality and the relation between culture and peace is the first axis of work presented by the former Minister of Culture, Patricia Ariza “to give social change a cultural and artistic dimension in order to transform the imaginary and re-establish in Colombians the culture of peace and the need for peace so that we know how to live together” (Ministry of Culture, August 9th, 2022). Besides, in the government plan of the president Gustavo Petro, one of the pledges is to place the culture of peace at the centre of the national agenda. As President Petro’s political programme mentions “this policy will integrate alternative conflict resolution, the strengthening and development of the cultural centres, museums, places of memory and observatories of indigenous peoples' thinking in order to promote a culture of peace, the recognition of cultural difference, diversity, knowledge of peoples and the construction of a common project for a nation” (Petro & Márquez, 2022, p. 1). Petro’s mission in the coming years is to consolidate a *total peace* and this research is a tool for that purpose.

1.4 Research Aim and Research Questions

1.4.1 Research Aim

The overall aim of this study is to explore the role that arts and cultural interventions can play in peacebuilding processes in the aftermath of the Colombian armed conflict.

1.4.2 Research Questions

In addressing the overall research aim, two specific research questions guide the study:

RQ1: What role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict?

RQ2: What design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture?

1.5 Organisation of the Thesis

This research intends to assist and inform policymakers and those making funding decisions about the social impact of arts and culture. To this end, the theoretical background and evidence from ongoing arts and cultural programmes that are taking place in Colombia is reviewed. With this in mind, the thesis is structured into nine chapters. Chapter 2, which follows this one, provides an extensive review of the extant literature on the conceptualisation and synergy of arts and culture with social and cultural capital. Moreover, it explains participatory arts as a way to engage people in the creative process, empowering them to express their ideas and experiences through art. It also examines academic debates about valuing culture or cultural value, and outlines evidence for the social impact of arts and culture. Finally, it concludes outlining the current challenges to evaluate and measure the impact of culture.

Chapter 3 explores the evidence for the use of arts-based approaches as a driver or enabler for social cohesion, providing a space for victims to acknowledge pain, heal, and contribute to reconciliation in the post-conflict period. In outlining the evidence, several examples of arts and cultural practices that facilitate peacebuilding are presented. Finally, the chapter discusses examples of arts and cultural programmes implemented in countries that have experienced conflict, in order to contribute to reconciliation and social transformation after the Peace Agreements in Colombia.

Chapter 4 discusses the philosophical foundations and research methods that underpin the study. First, a brief overview of the ontological and epistemological considerations that inform the study is provided. Thereafter, the choice of interpretivism as a research paradigm is discussed. Then, an explanation of the phenomenological approach and its development into

Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is set out, justifying the reasons why this approach is appropriate for the study. Finally, a detailed description of the qualitative research methods that formed the research design is provided, focusing on the rich description of experience, case study, interviews and participant observation, and the data collection processes.

Chapters 5 and 6 outline the study findings, drawing on two case studies: Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition. These cases are presented to help understand the context in which arts and cultural interventions are utilised in Colombia to address the outcomes of conflict. These chapters describe the cultural projects in depth, including their conception, design, delivery, and legacy. Each chapter draws on interviews conducted with the cultural managers of the case study projects and with the project beneficiaries.

Chapter 7 outlines the policymakers perspective, starting with their perceptions of the Peace Agreements and the role that different artistic expressions can play in the post-conflict period. Notably, through the interviews it is possible to answer the primary research questions and the implications of this research for the political agenda. This chapter explains the two values that dominate cultural policy and the tensions between them: economic impact and the social value of culture. In other words, the will to commission for studies to assess the impacts of arts and culture, in order to establish the need for government support of any art project as a contribution to the human wellbeing effects of artistic activities that are not captured by the market.

Chapter 8 is the main analysis chapter, addressing the guiding research questions and findings of the two case studies within the context of the wider literature review. The chapter analyses the data collected through semi-structured interviews from Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition and compares their impact and organisational operation. This chapter acknowledges the contribution of arts-based projects to the Colombian peacebuilding process, and the need for empowering spaces through the support and creation of grassroots cultural initiatives and participatory art within local communities that promote social cohesion, social capital, and a culture of peace.

Chapter 9 concludes the thesis. This chapter presents the key study findings and its contribution to knowledge in three main areas: methodological, theoretical, and policy. I express the need for the cultural sector in Colombia to show quantifiable results to generate greater interest from

politicians, which is reflected in greater funds. Additionally, I argue that the success of projects relies on the development of participatory methodologies that better understand the needs and realities of the people living in those contexts. I also outline a set of recommendations emerging from the findings. The recommendations are addressed to policymakers and cultural agents and aim to improve the implementation of cultural interventions by civil and public organisations in post-conflict situations as a way of restoring social fabric. Further, I suggest avenues for further research.

CHAPTER 2. ARTS, CULTURE, CAPITAL AND VALUE

2.0 Introduction

This chapter explores the conceptualization and synergy of arts and culture with social capital, social culture, and social cohesion. It addresses the role that political institutions and communities play in the creation of spaces that allow the generation of values for a culture of peace, trust, solidarity, and tolerance. First, the review explores best practices in art-based initiatives from other countries affected by conflict, identifying the ways in which these have helped to build strong networks and relationships between individuals and groups, and highlighting the importance of understanding each individual community context for the success of the processes.

The chapter also examines academic debates about valuing culture or cultural value (Crossick & Kaszynska, 2014), as well as its commodification and questions about the social impact of arts and culture. In doing so, the review addresses the main research questions: ‘What role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities that are dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict?’, and ‘What design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture?’. These two questions form the main focus of this study. Finally, the chapter concludes with a summary of the current challenges in assessing and measuring the value of culture. This is an important consideration to establish the need for government intervention, especially in places where cultural investment may not be a priority.

2.1 Arts and Culture: A Contested Terrain

The definition of the term *culture* has been broadly discussed worldwide for more than a century by sociologists and anthropologists in the field of humanities. Nevertheless, this has failed to produce commonly accepted definitions. One of the most prominent writers on culture, Raymond Williams, notes that it is:

[...] one of the two or three most complicated words in the English language. This is so partly because of its intricate historical development, in several European languages, but mainly

because it has now come to be used for important concepts in several distinct intellectual disciplines and in several distinct and incompatible systems of thought. (1983, p. 87)

Likewise, art “is historically related to the development of culture and aesthetics” (Williams, 1983, p. 42). And Tolstoy, when he defines art activity in the book *What is Art*, suggests it is:

To evoke in oneself a feeling one has once experienced, and having evoked it in oneself, then, by means of movements, lines, colours, sounds, or forms expressed in words, so to transmit that feeling that others may experience the same feeling. It is a means of union among men, joining them together in the same feelings, and indispensable for the life and progress toward wellbeing of individuals and of humanity. (1904, p. 51-52)

Art can then be viewed as a part of culture, as a way to create and transform it. In the essay *Culture is Ordinary*, Williams (1958) suggests that culture is something that happens and occurs in everyday life and refers to culture as a whole way of life and to arts and knowledge as a creative and innovative process, being aware of the implications of culture in historical processes and social change. Similarly, according to the anthropologist Edward Tylor, the concept of culture is “that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society” (1971, p. 1).

Although until now there has been little academic consensus on the definition of culture, advances have been made by UNESCO⁹, founded on November 16, 1945 as part of the United Nations system, with 195 countries members worldwide. UNESCO’s mission is “to contribute to the building of peace, the eradication of poverty, sustainable development and intercultural dialogue through education, the sciences, culture, communication and information” (2009); and it defines culture as “a set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual, and emotional features of society or a social group, and that it encompasses, in addition to art and literature, lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs” (UNESCO, 2001). The organisation’s definition of culture asserts that it can be linked to identity and values, and that it is a necessary part in daily life. As García-Canclini (2004) suggests, it is not just a sum of objects, signs, symbols, works of art or books.

⁹ Acronym for United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation.

In terms of inclusion in the arts, internationally, culture is increasingly viewed as a right. For example, it is included in Article 27 of the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights, in Article 15 of the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, in Article 5 of the 2001 UNESCO Declaration on Cultural Diversity, and in the 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions. Each of these publications advances the idea that everyone has the right to have access, to participate and to enjoy a cultural life through the arts.

In Latin America, State cultural policies have also shifted towards the democratisation of culture, with the aim of disseminating cultural interventions to a public that does not have easy access to them due to lack of economic means or knowledge derived from education (Evrard, 1997). Policy interventions have sought to generate and protect conditions so that culture reaches every individual, without discrimination. Here, the foundation of public intervention is the reduction of cultural inequality, defended by UNESCO in its Mexico City Declaration on Cultural Policies, Article 21, as: “A programme for the democratization of culture calls, in the first place, for the decentralization of access to leisure pursuits and the arts. A democratic cultural policy will provide for enjoyment of artistic excellence by all communities and the whole population” (1982).

Arts and culture can also have the characteristics of merit goods. This means that they are “goods which some persons believe ought to be available and whose consumption and allocation are felt by them to be too important to be left to the private market” (Cwi, 1980, p. 39). In this regard, in the 1970s some British authors, such as David Mercer and Stephen Mennell, associated culture with leisure and recreation, and claimed that it represented a social need. Mennell (1976) suggested that people do not have innate and fixed cultural needs. Instead, he claimed that their cultural demands are dialectically linked to the possibilities offered to them, arguing that the tastes of individuals depend on their past and present experiences. These experiences and cultural aspirations are strongly influenced by the services and facilities offered by the public and private sector, mainly. According to Mennell (1976), the best way to know if there is a need for a cultural service is to create such a service and see if people use it. In that sense, governments must create the need for culture, present new forms of experience to the public, so they can recognise and start demanding ‘cultural needs’ of which they were not aware before. Mercer (1973) also claimed that the role of governmental institutions is to take into account the different types of need (felt need, expressed need and

comparative need) and transform them into public policy in order to democratise access to recreational activities, including culture.

Mercer and Mennell illustrate that culture is not equally experienced by all social groups, and that it is important to ensure that the right to access culture is available to everyone. This call to action is evident in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, Article 27, which states that “everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits”. Similarly, UNESCO’s Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity (2001) proclaims that the defence of cultural diversity and the link between culture and human rights is a right of all people to access, participate in and enjoy as an integral part of human rights. In this regard, equal access to culture and art is essential to guarantee cultural diversity, as well as the universal achievement of human rights.

While the last half century has seen a greater awareness of culture as a right (mostly in so-called Western countries), that does not ameliorate the fact that, historically, the demand for culture has been influenced by levels of education, and “ignorance of the arts is keeping many people from experiences that they would greatly enjoy, if only they knew about them” (Heilbrun & Gray, 2001, p. 243). There is a significant body of literature that contends that enjoyment of the arts is an acquired taste, and “the ability to enjoy the consumption of art appears to be a return on an investment” (Klamer, 2002, p. 454). If arts and culture are merit goods, then it is argued that governments should intervene to subsidise the arts, in order to promote equitable access and to enable the accumulation of valuable cultural and social capital.

According to this perspective, there is evidence that the social benefits derived from culture and arts are public goods with ‘positive externalities’ alongside education and health, although it does not fully meet the terms outlined above: non-rivalry nor excludability (Snowball, 2008), because social benefits are owned by a limited number of people, excluding others. Likewise, culture is also defined as a common good. From Klamer’s approach, common goods cannot be owned by a single person. In fact, their benefits are shared by a group of people. He also compares art to a conversation and indicates that a piece of art exists (be it music or a painting) because it is recognised in the conversation of art (Klamer, 2004).

In terms of peacebuilding, not all artistic works or expressive cultural practices build peace (Cohen, 2005). This means that the creative act needs to be socialised by sharing, collaborating

and getting involved in other forms of collective actions of a social and political nature, which means that some forms of art meet these characteristics, such as music, theatre or dance, as they can establish synergies for collective creativity in processes of conflict, resistance, memory and reconciliation. This way of understanding arts and culture recognises that everyone can be an artist (Parramon, 2017), as it relies on the capacity for social action. López *et al.* (2015, p. 214) echo this understanding and consider participatory artistic practices as a possible space for resistance. In this context, the Argentine researcher Bang (2013) asserts that collective artistic work makes it possible to take action, and offers the possibility of transformation of one's own realities by collectively imagining and creating other possible worlds.

This resonates with the meaning of community art that seeks an involvement with the social context, that pursues social benefits over aesthetic achievements and conceptions, that favours the collaboration and participation of the communities involved in the realisation of the art-based work. Here, the goal is to work towards a more accessible, participatory, decentralised culture that reflects the needs and particularities of different communities (López *et al.*, 2015).

This is what participatory arts is all about, artistic work for social transformation, far from formal or aesthetic conceptions, it is a form of creativity at the service of the community to promote a community benefit. Here the social context plays a central role in defining the interest of the public and the ways of involving them in the work of art. According to Bang (2013), this type of work facilitates community participation, the generation of social ties and community meeting spaces, along with the support of collective creative work for transformation. Regardless of the art form, there is one characteristic they all have in common that makes them participatory art: they were created through the participation of people, community members and non-artists through their interaction and collaboration to create an artwork. In short, it is not the art itself that generates value or change in society, it is the way in which it develops, it all depends on the participation of community members, on the shaping of links and spaces for creative encounters. Participatory action describes itself as art.

In this regard, Hofstede's (2023) theory of cultural dimensions identifies six categories that define culture: Power Distance Index, Collectivism vs. Individualism, Uncertainty Avoidance Index, Femininity vs. Masculinity, Short-Term vs. Long-Term Orientation, and Restraint vs. Indulgence. Here, two categories are important for understanding the role of arts and culture in

a post-conflict environment. The first one is Individualism vs. Collectivism, as it recognises teamwork, group goals and well-being rather than the pursuit of personal goals, ultimately meaning the degree to which societies are integrated into groups. The second dimension is Long-Term Orientation vs. Short-Term Orientation, which understands the importance of achieving long-term success, oriented towards long-term growth, rather than expecting quick results. If we take the different dimensions of the term ‘culture’, we see that they influence the arts from a participatory approach.

2.2 The Social Value of Art and Culture

This section examines the capacity of culture and social capital in promoting social goals (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013; Kliksberg, 1999; Klamer, 2002). It goes beyond accounting for economic capital alone and include forms of social and cultural capital. As Klamer has discussed: “The values of cultural goods are more than economics can account for” (2002, p. 455).

This research focuses particularly on two cultural projects in Latin America. Colombia has suffered violence for decades, experiencing serious problems of poverty and inequality that — in turn — have weakened the bonds of trust and dialogue among its inhabitants, especially those who have been affected by the armed conflict. In these circumstances, cultural and artistic practices represent appropriate strategies to enhance positive attitudes towards civic behaviour, which contribute to general wellbeing. Also, this section examines different perspectives of social capital and some reflections on the possible contributions of culture to promote high levels of associativity in a society where individuals have the capacity to act cooperatively, building networks, partnerships, and synergies of all kinds. As Matarasso claimed: “It is beyond question that art has a profound impact on society” (1997, p. 12).

According to the French sociologist Pierre Bourdieu, social capital “is the sum of the resources, actual or virtual, that accrue to an individual or a group by virtue of possessing a durable network of more or less institutionalised relationships of mutual acquaintance and recognition” (Bourdieu & Wacquant, 2005, p. 178). For him, social capital facilitates connectivity and collaboration among people provided by their social networks and relationships. Contrary to the Bourdieusian articulation of social capital, some authors (Coleman, 1988; Putnam, 2001) explain the social capital concept as a public good, in which this term is a “key outcome of

communities that have developed cohesion, as well as a key input for collective action” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 84). Coleman (1988) recognises the value of social capital for all kinds of communities, not only the powerful elites, leading to a broader view that includes a focus on the marginalised. In his analysis, he argues that the generation of social capital depends on the formation of relationships and social integration, and also argues that the sense of confidence, self-esteem and identity that emerges out of social capital can allow people to be successful in society.

Fukuyama (1995) sees trust as a key measure of social capital and as a factor that tends towards democracy. According to him, civic duty and moral obligation are essential for a successful and stable society. Robert Putnam (2000) echoes this understanding, with a differentiation between inclusive and exclusive forms of social capital. For Putnam, social capital consists essentially of the level of trust that exists among members of society, the norms of civic behaviour and the level of associativeness, related to the goodwill of individuals that engender norms of trust, reciprocity, tolerance, and cooperation. In this order of ideas, as the prominent Cuban-American sociologist Portes indicates, “the social capital created by tight community networks is useful to parents, teachers, and police authorities as they seek to maintain discipline and promote compliance among those under their charge” (1998, p. 10). To elaborate on this last point, the Argentinian sociologist Kliksberg (1999) observes that social capital is associated with social cohesion and cultural expressions. Furthermore, Kliksberg suggests that government institutions should stimulate the generation of social capital, considering that it can contribute to the strength of values that promote identity and solidarity in society.

Bourdieu also argued that there are two more kinds of capital (economic and cultural), each suggesting different advantages: *economic capital* relates to wealth and income; and *cultural capital* is understood as the ability to engage with and benefit from the possession of cultural goods. He proposed three different means through which people can attain cultural capital. The first is by education or through family pedagogy, called the *embodied State*. The second is the *objectified* form that is presented in goods such as paintings, books, and instruments. It is a capital transmitted by its materiality. Finally, the third is an *institutionalised* cultural capital that offers a constant and legally guaranteed value, acquired with academic and educational degrees.

In Bourdieu's terms, cultural practices are directly linked with education, social status, and the wealth of people, in the three forms of cultural capital, and therefore the work of art "only exists as such for the person who has the means of appropriating it, or in other words, to decipher it" (1984, p. 7). According to Bourdieu (1986), people need to acquire cultural capital to engage in the consumption of specific forms of art. In this sense, cultural and social capital can be exclusionary, used as tools that enable elite or dominant classes to retain their dominant societal positions:

In the case of activities like the visual arts, or playing a musical instrument, which presupposes a cultural capital generally acquired outside the educational system and (relatively) independent of the level of academic certification, the correlation with social class, which is again strong, is established through social trajectory (which explains the special position of the new *petite bourgeoisie*). (Bourdieu, 1986, p. 14)

Supporting this line of argument, Klammer states that "like social capital, cultural capital can be conceived as representing earning power" (2002, p. 461). However, sociologists and economists have argued that arts and culture can cut across the dimensions of social capital (confidence, positive civic behaviour and associativeness). Through artistic and cultural activities, it is possible to strengthen and encourage people individually and collectively, promoting social cohesion, establishing networks and, in this way, enabling the construction of a more inclusive society (Kliksberg, 1999; Hangzhou International Congress, 2013). As Kliksberg notes:

Mobilising social capital and culture as active agents of economic and social development is by no means a utopian proposal: it is perfectly viable and gives effective results. In order to carry out this mobilization on a major scale —a great challenge for the future— comprehensive policies and broad consensus between the State and civil society will be needed. (1999, p.14)

This is important, as it is argued that active participation in the arts, as opposed to cultural consumption or audience development, is linked to strengthening connections between people, allowing them to expand their social network and build social capital. This relates to Stokowski's (1994) study of leisure time, in which she stresses that the consumption of time should be studied as a socially shared practice, because leisure behaviours change the system of relationships and social leisure is a decisive factor in an individual's quality of life —

assuming that the quality of life is mostly determined by the quality of relationships and, thus, by the level of satisfaction at the way leisure time is spent.

Indeed, McCarthy *et al.* (2004) suggest that art and cultural activities can foster community cohesion between diverse social groups and thus promote tolerance, trust and cooperation, contributing to build social capital. As Stern and Seifert point out, culture itself is a form of social capital: “When a community comes together to share cultural life, through celebration, rites and intercultural dialogue, it is enhancing its relationships, partnerships and networks — in other words, developing social capital” (2009, p. 23).

Even though social capital may carry positive externalities related to community cohesion and social inclusion, it can also have negative results. From this point, various authors recognise some exclusionary aspects of social capital, and suggested two theories to analyse this phenomenon: bonding and bridging social capital (Putnam, 2000, p. 22; Putnam & Goss, 2002, p. 11-12). *Bonding social capital* can exacerbate exclusion because it involves connections being made between people who are already similar/homogeneous populations (existing family and friends, for example), promoting homogeneity, increasing in-group solidarity and loyalty, and generating benefits only for those that are part of a particular group. On the other side, *bridging social capital* reinforces inclusion because it involves connections between diverse people, promoting links and resources across different groups, outside of the family and the usual social circle, which requires people to transcend existing social barriers.

However, Leonard notes that there are also exclusionary aspects in bridging social capital because it “does not benefit the community as a whole rather than perhaps some individuals in the community” (2004, p. 930), and it might reinforce existing social, economic, and political inequalities. Also, he points out that the role of the State is fundamental to facilitate or inhibit the conditions for the development of social capital. This argument resonates with the consideration that social capital is not equally available to all (Edwards & Foley, 1999), given that social isolation limits access to this resource and its acquisition partially depends on the socio-economic status of people. From this premise, it is possible to extrapolate that the promotion of bridging social capital in a post-conflict environment, usually characterised by tension, uncertainty, and distrust, may sometimes be what is needed in order to transcend the polarisation between political adversaries and start bonding people with different backgrounds,

generating more opportunities to build resourceful bridging ties with dissimilar others (Widmalm, 2006).

Finally, social capital can be seen as a resource that should be used for public good or for the benefit of individuals. In large part, cultural exposure focused on collective practices (where there are high-level interactions and equal partnerships) can generate social capital by promoting social cohesion, social skills, and community building in a diverse community (Lee, 2013). Likewise, such processes also contribute to the construction of citizenship for several reasons. First, collective practices bring about collective thought, a mental skill that can be enhanced or extended to the notion of “what is public”, while promoting appreciation of common benefit from personal effort and group work. In this regard, governments and international actors should foster the socially cohesive relations for conflict prevention, rehabilitation, and reconciliation. This view of social capital (Putnam, 2000; Coleman, 1988; Kliksberg, 1999) is connected with social cohesion and cultural interventions, as people can recognise each other’s qualities, grow together, and develop collective self-esteem, generating a force of networks and solidarity. As Stiglitz (1998) notes in this respect, preserving cultural values is very important for development, because such values serve as a cohesive force at times when many others are flagging.

Various lines of research (Kliksberg, 1999) have addressed the relations between social capital and dimensions of development, including some contributions that culture can make to social development efforts. Only a few studies (Colleta & Cullen, 2000a) have examined the role of social capital within a violent conflict. Yet, as conflict weakens social fabric, changes in social capital are likely to occur as a result of violent conflict within a State. This directly relates with the legacy of the conflict in Colombia, since violent conflict not only divides the population by undermining communal group trust, it also damages and destroys the norms and values that govern interactions among people and destroys the institutions linking communities and collective action for the common good. This, in turn, impedes a State’s ability to recover after hostilities cease. Colleta and Cullen’s work (2000b) consider that once social capital is restored, it can strengthen the overall cohesiveness of society. In other words, it can be said that social capital is the glue that holds societies together, and without it, economic growth or human wellbeing are impossible.

This view is also stated by Putnam (2001), who indicated that this form of capital requires a level of confidence among the social actors in a society, the norms of civic behaviour and the level of associativeness they exhibit. All of which means that a society that exhibits such features exemplifies the strength of social fabric as a foremost element of societal cohesion. To summarise, where there are high levels of associativeness there is a capacity to act in a cooperative manner. The Colombian case is a good example of this, as discussed in the remainder of this thesis.

In parallel to the concept of social capital, Igor Stokfiszewski (2016) proposed a new term, *social culture*, referring to characteristics that include — among others — interaction, collaboration, trust, and empathy. This conceptualization views arts and cultural initiatives as sites within which people can come together to create collective bonds, build trust through activity, achieve consensus, and reconcile differences, antagonisms, and conflicts. By utilising processes that respect individual qualities, desires, preferences, and interests, it is possible to arrive at an outcome that belongs to all of those who participate in the process. In this conception of social culture, artists and cultural workers create situations that allow self-expression. In turn, self-expression functions as the transformative power that allows participants to experience fundamental change in their outlook. Further positive benefits of social culture approaches are the impact on wider social realms (both political and social), influencing the social community and their position related to the institutional circulation of culture.

For Stokfiszewski (2016), the circulation of social culture includes autonomous institutions, movements and organisations driving their actions for the sake of the community. In other words, the foundation of the approach to culture within social culture is the idea that culture can transform individuals and their reality, empowering others, focusing on participants and their creative process rather than relating to them as consumers of culture. Here, culture matters in a different way. What matters is the culture's role in creating a sense of belonging, and relationships. This concept is important because it associates culture with the social domain, closely related to social cohesion and community rebuilding, which are subjects of this research. Notably, culture is understood as a factor in connectedness and participation.

In order to understand the positive social benefits that arts and cultural interventions can have, the next section reviews empirical evidence across the world of the social impact of arts and

culture. A report by Landry *et al.* defines the social impact of the arts as “those effects that go beyond the artefacts and the enactment of the event or performance itself and have a continuing influence upon, and directly touch, people’s lives” (1993, p. 50). Several authors (Liebmann, 1996; Cohen, 2005; Shank & Schirch, 2008; LeBaron, 2011; Crossick & Kaszynska, 2016) acknowledge that cultural practices, assets, and expressions play a crucial role in ameliorating and maintaining individuals’ and communities’ quality of life, sense of identity, trust, integration, cooperation, and tolerance (UNESCO, 1996).

Sometimes, arts and culture are seen as a resource to be harnessed to promote the sustainable economic progress of a region or country through generation of revenues from the creative and cultural industries. However, in other cases the benefits of arts and culture are related to the cognitive or wellbeing realm: improving academic performance and student concentration skills (Winner *et al.*, 2013), preventing crime (Belfiore, 2004), promoting development (Cevallos, 2005), generating employment, revitalizing neighbourhoods, promoting local economic development (Cohen, 1994), and improving physical and psychological wellbeing (Baklien, 2009).

The empirical evidence for the social impact of arts and culture has been subject to extensive debate, illustrating that arts and culture have a transformative effect on society, contributing to social cohesion, to community engagement (Flinn & McPherson, 2007), to the creation of social and cultural capital (Matarasso, 1997), and developing creativity not only in the creation of artworks, but also in the ability to solve daily life problems (Johnson, 2006). Repeatedly, arts are seen as a legitimate tool for social improvement and the development of social capital. As stated by Laaksonen:

Policies of any kind should not be implemented, planned, or designed without the participation of those whom they are going to effect and in a shared cultural space it is the access and participation in cultural life that forms an essential part of making policies successful. (2008, p. 50)

Nevertheless, according to some authors (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004), the benefits of the arts differ depending on how the community is involved in their creation. For these authors, the creation of art can lead to social interactions and development of social bonds among groups of people who regularly participate together in an activity over a period of time (for example: rehearsing as a choir, symphonic orchestra members or dance class). Activities in which the outcome

depends on a group of people function according to the group phenomenon, whereby “the individual feels that the power of the group somehow transcends or at least exceeds the sum of the individual parts” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 29). In this sense, the impact of the cultural intervention depends on how the cultural practice is carried out. According to Hofstede (2011), it can be process-oriented as opposed to outcome-oriented, which is the aim of participatory art, the focus is on the process of creating and engaging with others, rather than on the final product or outcome. Participants are invited to be part of the creative process and to contribute to the artwork itself. A clear example is collaborative murals or interactive performances and workshops, such as songwriting among a group of people, a feature of this art form is that it engages with real social and political issues.

As Bishop stated, participatory art “tends to value what is invisible: a group dynamic, a social situation, a change of energy, a raised consciousness. As a result, it is an art dependent on first-hand experience, and preferably over a long duration (days, months or even years)” (2012, p. 6). According to her, participatory art has the ability to communicate on two levels: to the participants and to the spectators, which brings social benefits.

Similarly, McCarthy *et al.* (2004) argue that appreciating art also has social benefits that are instrumental (especially, listening to music to stimulate tranquility). In this sense, “the arts are a form of shared passion that might engender a sense of community among frequent attendees of different social and economic backgrounds and occupational status, ethnicity and race, and age and geography” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 29). Finally, according to the mentioned authors, when people are supporting the same project, share the same goals and are committed to the same arts institution, this enables the construction of a sense of community that can produce social capital.

2.3 Culture and Social Cohesion

The Colombian Peace Agreements state that “the participation and dialogue between different sectors of society contribute to building trust and promoting a culture of tolerance, respect and coexistence in general” (Colombian Government, 2016). Decades of conflict have opened gaps of mistrust within society, especially in those territories most affected by the conflict. In order to break these barriers, the Colombian government recognises that it is necessary to open spaces for more varied citizen participation. These spaces need to function to promote the recognition

of victims, and the recognition by the whole society of what happened and of the need to grasp the opportunity for peace.

Violent conflict within a State weakens its social fabric because it affects the cohesiveness of society, as mentioned in the Colombian Peace Agreements. Conflict damages the norms, community trust, values, traditions, and social relations that bind communities together and are the basis for cooperation and collective action for the common good (Kliksberg, 1999). In these circumstances, the erosion and destruction of social networks require a rebuilding of self-determination, cooperative caring, community participation, and mutual aid of the community. This is also about a strengthening of social cohesion because low levels of social cohesion increase the possibility of potential violent conflict (PNUD¹⁰, 2020). Social cohesion is defined by the willingness of individuals to cooperate and work together at all levels of society to achieve collective goals (Jeannotte *et al.*, 2002, p. 3), focusing on non-coercive relationships that hold people together. Social cohesion is also understood as the absence of a conflict, or other form of polarization, and the presence of strong social bonds. Rebuilding community is a key task for strengthening overall social cohesion and the ability to manage, prevent and mitigate conflicts. For the purposes of this study, community is a social group with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, have a sense of belonging to the group and share a common territory (Stebbins, 1990). This perception is corroborated with the definition of social cohesion by Chan *et al.* as:

[...] a state of affairs concerning both the vertical and horizontal interactions amongst members of society as characterized by a set of attitudes and norms that include trust, a sense of belonging and the willingness to participate and help, as well as their behavioural manifestations. (2006, p. 290)

The definitions above resonate with Jenson's (2002) notion of social cohesion, which he describes as a process more than a condition or end state, involving a sense of commitment and capacity to live together. In this regard, arts and cultural interventions can play a prominent role, because they allow people to work together in achieving a common goal, facing shared challenges and being members of the same community. That kind of activity involves building shared values, which is a crucial element of social cohesion. Jenson elaborates five dimensions

¹⁰ Acronym for Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (United Nations Programme for Development-UNPD).

of social cohesion: belonging, inclusion, participation, recognition, and legitimacy; he also identifies five threats: isolation, exclusion, non-involvement, rejection, and illegitimacy.

Bernard's (1999) conceptualization of social cohesion introduces three values which, he argues, are necessary for successful realisation of social cohesion: freedom, equality, and solidarity. In order to manage social conflicts, Bernard argues that governments should invest in interventions that promote these three values. This echoes Jenson's approach on the important role that public and private institutions have as mediators, which facilitates collaborative action and activities where individuals can interact with each other, promoting trust and commitment. Not surprisingly, communities have a responsibility too, since they must "actively nurture their capacities for participation, interaction and association" (Jenson, 2002, p. 20). From this angle, it is clear that settings and context have an important role in the creation of social capital. Social cohesion and social capital are related, which means that social capital can be considered a precondition for the development of greater social cohesion. In concrete terms, the lack of social cohesion is directly associated with lack of social capital.

In the light of these claims, there is also some evidence that cultural rituals and practices can represent valuable ways to rebuild social cohesion and social capital through community-based programmes, which aim to increase local awareness and strengthen social networks and community ties (Colleta & Cullen, 2000). Creative arts are valuable conduits for the expression of emotions, feelings of solidarity, the search for meaning and the development of meaningful community narratives, which pose common challenges that forge unity and social cohesion and help to form a collective consciousness. For Jeannotte (1999), the term "social cohesion" as used by the network is an outcome of investments in social and cultural programmes and in social capital. Thus, social, and cultural programmes and policies can play a central role within this process.

Various studies in the United Kingdom and Canada have attempted to make explicit the links between social cohesion and culture. For example, François Matarasso's influential study on the social impact of the arts, *Use or Ornament* (1997), presents 50 different benefits that are attributed to participation in arts and culture using a survey methodology that assess participatory arts projects. He demonstrated that participatory arts programmes were a successful approach of contributing to "a stable, confident and creative society" (Matarasso, 1997, p. 6). Also, in this line, Jeannotte (2003) explored the contribution of cultural capital to

social cohesion and sustainable communities, recognising a clear link among altruistic behaviour and various forms of cultural participation.

Similarly, research conducted by Gielen *et al.* (2015) has elaborated a conceptual framework on the measurable impact of arts and culture on society. Within this framework is the role of culture in socialisation, which helps individuals to integrate into a social, political, and economic order. These authors refer to culture as “an all-encompassing human practice, with creative activities forming a substantial part of it in our fast-changing society” (Gielen *et al.*, 2015, p. 23). The social effects are primarily tied to culture’s contribution to social cohesion, defined as “the bonds and connection between different entities, the smallest included, in a social system” (Gielen *et al.*, 2015, p. 62). They conclude that “participating in social-cultural work, amateur arts, cultural heritage and the arts contributes among other things to the forming of a community, strengthening the social fabric, emancipation and empowerment” (Gielen *et al.*, 2015, p. 62).

Applying this debate to the context of this study (Latin America), the value of creative activities is acknowledged in an analysis commissioned by the European Union, *Culture and Art as Factors of Sustainable Social Cohesion and Urban Development* (LAIC¹¹, 2017), which identified 20 good artistic practices across different countries (Brazil, México, Colombia, Ecuador, Chile, and Argentina). The report suggests that cultural and artistic interventions in public places are able to change the behaviours or positions of people in the face of certain situations. Further, such interventions provide means and languages of expression, which open spaces for consensus or social dialogue. Findings also suggest that artistic practices have a high potential to bring about positive changes in educational and cultural processes, and even to support resilience. The findings of this study highlight that good artistic practices depend on communities and their appropriation. According to the study, this occurs because, in order to be qualified as ‘good experience’, programmes implemented at the institutional level need the active participation of the community to give them support and legitimacy. Gielen *et al.* (2015) illustrate that artistic practices rooted in the community succeed in making problems visible through communication strategies, which have an impact on urban policies or education. In this context, in order to develop effective community change interventions that are culturally

¹¹ Acronym for Latin American Arts for Inclusive Cities.

appropriate, the specific characteristics of the targeted group (e.g. expectancies, values, norms and attitudes) need to be taken into consideration.

Gielen *et al.* (2015) highlight that citizens are not just important in terms of providing legitimation or consultation for an intervention. Instead, development dynamics require citizens to be an integral part of the whole process, right from the conception of the idea. Achieving this successfully involves understanding the community as a subject of knowledge that knows its environment better than any other external agent, and as a subject of action without which it is not possible to transform their realities. In these scenarios, art-based initiatives can play an important role in generating processes of self-knowledge, re-significance, understanding of their environment, and expression of their will.

In the light of the research evidence on the value of artistic and cultural practices, in Colombia processes of artistic training for children and young people have been developed as a strategy aimed at preventing or counteracting the effects of social problems in specific contexts (e.g. drug trafficking and violence). Examples of this type of process include the National System of Youth and Children's Orchestras and Choirs "Batuta", and the National Music Plan for Coexistence; as well as, at the urban local level, the Training Artistic Networks of the City of Medellín, which includes the Network of Schools of Music, Dance, Theatre, Plastic Arts, and Libraries.

In these cultural programmes, social cohesion can be encouraged since there are open spaces where arts and cultural initiatives act as agents that increases trust, tolerance, and acceptance of diversity. That is because these initiatives focus on the collective interaction of participants, and the success of the intervention relies on each one of them. A clear example is Batuta, which for more than 30 years has been implementing a strategy of musical training and psychosocial care that has enriched the daily lives of thousands of children, adolescents and young people, and their families living in places of violence and inequity. In this programme, music training is based on a model that follows collective music practice. Those music spaces ensure a temporary musical identity that restores participants' place in society and helps them to attain emotional relief, rebuild their networks, and circulate cohesive intangible resources to regain trust in themselves and others (Centro de Estudios Regionales Cafeteros y Empresariales, 2008). Here, the music centres have become spaces of care and protection for children in the face of the risks that exist in the territories: they represent places of welcome, of community

meeting, of promotion of meaningful bonds of friendship and of permanent learning for the improvement of existence through the arts.

Another art form is dance, which can be both a form of expression and therapy. An example is the Corporación Chocó Chicos Negros, a dance group that has emerged in the Pacific region of Colombia as a form of resistance to the armed conflict. This cultural organisation brings together children and adolescents — many of them children of displaced families from other parts of the country — from the El Reposo neighbourhood and the northern area of the city of Quibdó. The collective was created to prevent young people from becoming victims of forced recruitment and to help them dream of a peaceful future.

Throughout its three-year mandate, the Truth Commission in Colombia promoted various artistic expressions as a means to tell the world the story of the armed conflict (Comisión de la Verdad, 2022)¹². However, most of these initiatives were activities that were designed to generate a product rather than a process, and thus their realisation was short-lived. One of them was a documentary *Memory and Skin (Memoria y piel)*, which narrates the experience of three communities in Bolívar that managed to create a collective account of the pain, memories and resistance of its inhabitants. This documentary was committed to telling the hidden truths of the internal armed conflict in Colombia through different audiovisual narratives.

In a similar vein, a project fully funded by UNESCO was the Intangible Cultural Heritage as a basis for resilience, reconciliation and construction of peace environments in post-agreement Colombia, which aimed to use intangible cultural heritage as a basis for resilience, reconciliation and reintegration in Colombian department of La Guajira. This project was carried out for over fourteen months as a way to promote new forms of coexistence, reconciliation and integration around the community's local intangible cultural heritage. The participants — residents and ex-combatants — achieved a sense of symbolic reparation and forgiveness (UNESCO, 2018).

¹² Comisión de la Verdad is a state entity that seeks to clarify the patterns and to explain the causes of the internal armed conflict in Colombia. Its purpose is to guarantee the right of victims and society to the truth, to promote the recognition of what happened and the coexistence in the territories, and to contribute to laying the foundations for non-repetition, through a process of broad and plural participation for the construction of a stable and lasting peace.

Another study from the Centre of Expertise on Culture and Communities in Canada explores the role of culture in terms of sustainability, acknowledging its positive potential to transform society in significant ways (Duxbury & Gillette, 2007). Under the different models of sustainability proposed in the study, an Australian cultural analyst, Jon Hawkes (2001), proposed culture as the fourth pillar of sustainability. Here, Hawkes placed culture at the same level as the three established pillars of sustainability (economic, social, and environmental responsibility), and also highlighted the discussion of culture as a process rather than a product. Hawkes argues that the value of culture lies in its doing, in other words, in the process rather than the outcome. For Hawkes, there is a direct relation between public planning and culture, as the quality of cultural engagement contributes to the construction of a vibrant city.

To summarise, it can be argued that increasing social capital and improving social cohesion rests on norms and values that guide these processes. Increasing cultural capital, specifically through arts and cultural interventions, could give agency to these elements: honesty, trustworthiness, integrity — which build trust— norms and values that are required to enable the formation of networks.

However, the importance assigned to arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process depends on the value that governments and institutions place on them, which makes it vitally important to understand their value and its conceptualisation.

2.4 Valuing Culture or Cultural Value

There is a multiplicity of meanings related to arts and culture, which can have a negative consequence in establishing its value and measurement, but this “immeasurability, at least as for now, does not signify their irrelevance. On the contrary, the cultural and social values that they generate are crucial for the worth of our lives and the communities we live in” (Klamer, 2002, p. 467). However, the debate about how culture should be valued and measured remains heated, particularly in the United Kingdom (Gray, 2009; Belfiore, 2004; Gibson, 2008). It is to this debate that the discussion now turns.

Cultural value is grounded in the capacity of arts and culture to effect change. Thus, cultural value is “used to refer to the effects that culture has on those who experience it and the difference it makes to individuals and society” (Crossick & Kaszynska, 2014, p. 124).

According to John Holden (2006), there are three complementary forms of value generated by culture: intrinsic, institutional, and instrumental. Intrinsic value is “the set of values that relate to the subjective experience of culture intellectually, emotionally and spiritually” (Holden, 2006, p. 14). In this definition, all of these values (historic, social, symbolic, aesthetic, and spiritual) are inherent characteristics arising from the object. Cultural heritage comprises a clear example of intrinsic value; it does not have an end in itself, but its importance lies in what it symbolises and represents. Paintings, sculptures, landscapes, archives, museums, and cultural expressions can be considered in the same vein as they provide a sense of cultural identity, communality and belonging. It is each person, individually, who ascribes value to each of these items/settings. This value, in turn, can be captured in “personal testimony, qualitative assessments, anecdotes, case studies and critical reviews” (Holden, 2006, p. 14). However, cultural heritage has recently been related to commodification, where tourism and handcrafts are playing an important role in the economic development of the host community (Chang, 1997). At the same time, this commoditization is widely criticised, because it can contribute to the denigration of social customs and lead to the falsification of histories and identities (Machlis & Burch, 1983).

In contrast, institutional value refers to the work practices that cultural organisations such as museums, galleries and theatres have to perform in order to provide a good service and experience to the public. Successful fulfilment of these roles can lead to the integration, tolerance and strengthening of the community involved. According to Holden, these cultural organisations are the active agents and creators of value, “trust in the public realm, transparency and fairness, are all values that can be generated by the institution in its dealings with the public” (2006, p. 18). Finally, in Holden’s theory, instrumental value is understood as the effect, impact, and significance of culture with a social or economic outcome. It is what the majority of governments employ to justify public funding of arts and cultural activities, to achieve outcomes including integration, social cohesion, education, employment, development, regeneration, and healthy communities — objectives that properly belong in other policy areas (Gibson, 2008; O’Brien, 2010).

However, disagreements regarding which elements constitute the intrinsic values and which constitute instrumental values have generated tensions between scholars. An example of this is that, for Holden (2006), education is part of an instrumentalisation of the value of culture, while Gray (2009) disagrees. Instead, Gray argues that in the specific case of museums, education is

part of an intrinsic value, *raison d'être* to the museum's role, but it is not an extrinsic benefit of culture. In the context of instrumentalisation, some authors have suggested that the cultural sector is under increasing pressure to demonstrate evidence and provide stronger justification for arts and cultural activities, generating a benefit over and above the aesthetic quality of the artform itself. In this order of ideas, investment and expenditure in the arts and culture is tied to positive results denoted by secondary public benefit effects in society. There is a recognition that culture needs to compete with other sectors (such as education or health) for government allocated expenditure (Belfiore, 2004; Gray, 2009; Holden, 2004), and that it needs to offer solutions to problems "that are originally economic, social, political or ideological" (Gray, 2007, p. 207).

This complementary relationship to wider institutional agendas has generated misunderstanding and mistrust between policymakers and the cultural sector in a number of countries, including Colombia. One of the reasons for this problem is the disconnection and disarticulation that exists between the public (understood as ordinary citizens), politicians and cultural practitioners (Holden, 2006). Holden suggests that there is a strong relationship in the three forms of value and proposes that balance and coordination are required between them in order to solve arts and funding policy dilemmas. He notes that "society needs culture more and more to make sense of our lives, and to construct our individual and collective identities" (Holden, 2006, p. 23); and the public's main concern is the aesthetic value of culture. Likewise, professionals are also inspired by the intrinsic value of culture and are concerned about creating their own institutional value. Finally, politicians are interested in having large-scale results; the greater the number of people who benefit, the better it is, making it clear that their major interest is financing the instrumental aims of culture. For Gray, this is related to the:

Lack of political interest and power associated with the sector, that leads to the development of policy attachment strategies whereby funding for the sector can be gained by demonstrating the role that it can play in the fulfilment of the goals of other policy sectors. (2007, p. 206)

Following this perspective, Geir Vestheim has defined instrumental cultural policy as the tendency "to use cultural ventures and cultural investments as a means or instrument to attain goals in other than cultural areas" (1994, p. 65). Furthermore, he suggests that "arts and cultural policies cannot achieve what governments want, or that they achieve it at an irresponsible cost" (Vestheim, 1994, p. 114). Supporting this idea, in her paper *Auditing Culture*, Belfiore (2004)

concluded that the arts sector should try to build a concept of the intrinsic value of arts to society. She suggested that arts and culture should not be used as instrumentalization tools, because they were not conceived to fulfil that purpose.

In contrast with Vestheim and Belfiore, Gibson (2008) defends the instrumentalization of culture, illustrating that there is “nothing remotely new about instrumentalism in cultural policy and that it has always been integral to cultural policy, and that instrumental cultural policies are in fact policies of production” (2008). Gray (2009) concurs, arguing that instrumentality has been an element in public policies, and the focus should be on how it is used more effectively to strengthen the value of arts and cultural activity.

Acknowledging this polarised and repeated debate, and with the intention of transcending it, Crossick and Kaszynska proposed a fresh approach, focusing on putting “the experience of individuals back at the heart of ideas about cultural value” (2016, p. 5). Such an approach means that individual engagement with arts and culture is the focal point for “understand[ing] the kinds of benefit that culture may have for society, for communities, for democracy, for public health and wellbeing, for urban life and regional growth” (Crossick & Kaszynska, 2016, p. 5), rather than the secondary benefits that follow. The authors also identify six components of cultural value: the reflective individual, the citizen engagement, the regeneration of space, the economic impact, wellbeing, and arts in education. These factors open up a new discourse about the impact of arts and culture in personal development, social cohesion, and community empowerment, relevant to this thesis. Such an approach is crucial to the cultural value definition discussed above, particularly as it is understood as an active process of effecting change, positive or negative. According to O’Brien and Oakley: “[...] there must be a relationship between cultural value and those being affected, [indeed] we can think of cultural value as being part of the process of valuing culture” (2015, p. 5).

From this angle, Kaszynska affirms that there is a need to “reposition first-hand, individual experience of arts and culture at the heart of enquiry into cultural value” (2018, p. 6). She also points out that “cultural value needs to give far more attention to the way people experience their engagement with arts and culture” (Kaszynska, 2018, p. 6) and that means revising theoretical and methodological frameworks to place the individual experience at the centre of the discussion. Yet, despite the contribution of Crossick and Kaszynska (2016) report to the field, Stern and Seifert argue that “their theoretical approach seems to put them squarely on the

intrinsic side of the logjam” (2017, p. 278), because the report proposed “the reflective individual” as a core component of cultural value. From this perspective, and in my research, the experience of the individual is at the core of the study. This is necessary in order to gain a deeper understanding of the impact of the cultural projects in people’s lives, and in the legacy of the armed conflict in Colombia.

From another perspective, Randazzo and Torrent’s work on conflict and post-conflict reconstruction relates to the instrumentalism of policies in post-conflict scenarios, considering that it is time to “move from top-down policies of transformation to decentralised approaches informed by the principle of adaptation to complex scenarios” (2021, p. 10). Randazzo also explains the need to conceive a comprehensive understanding of the behaviour of actors in their realities, and acknowledges that outcomes cannot be predictable and linear, meaning that the goal-oriented peacebuilding mentality must gradually be replaced by an understanding of the “uncertainty of the effects of the interactions between a varied range of actors” (2021, p. 11). That limitation in peacebuilding planning is, according to Randazzo, what has contributed to the numerous failures of peacebuilding. In this sense, peacebuilding scholars have increasingly sought to reflect on the objectives of local actors, recognising their realities and avoiding externally (and top-down) implemented and imported policies, norms and projects.

To conclude, it is time to transcend the discussion of those who are in favour of the intrinsic or instrumental value of culture, using the argument “that there is a clear distinction between private benefits, which accrue to individuals, and public benefits, which accrue to society as a whole” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 4). For the last few decades, research evidence the positive impact of cultural involvement for the wellbeing of individuals and communities. Although further research is needed in order to design cultural policies and to articulate the intrinsic and instrumental benefits of engagement in the arts.

2.5 Conclusion

In this chapter I have provided an overview of the debates currently associated with the meanings of arts and culture, both intrinsically and instrumentally. Different definitions of culture were outlined, highlighting art as an expressive form created by individuals or ensembles with or without specialised training, alongside a more holistic view of culture as a set of beliefs.

At the same time, the chapter developed the social interpretation of culture. It showed that even if there are arguments that undermine the instrumentalism of culture and the commodification of art, there are positions in favour. Further, it was noted that this can be a consequence of limited policy funding and lack of public interest. The claim was made for embracing the social benefits of culture in society and the value of culture in explaining social transformation. In parallel, the chapter highlights the evidence of artistic and creative practices in developing social capital and social cohesion in divided societies, understanding that culture crosses all dimensions and can contribute to a society's social capital.

Culture underlies the basic components that comprise social capital and social cohesion. These include trust, civic behaviour, and degrees of associativity, which makes it crucial to ensure the creation of spaces that allow the generation of those values. This is especially so as there is no culture without creation, and there is no creation without resources. The chapter concluded that social cohesion could be viewed as the positive outcome of social capital formation for a community that — in return — could lead to more social capital formation. Equally, the public good feature of social capital could be viewed as a positive attribute. Similarly, it is evident that social capital creation can be easily destroyed and can take years to build. It is here, that arts and cultural practices can contribute to building community cohesion around projects in which people from different backgrounds can work together.

In the foregoing chapter, the argument is also made that capturing, evaluating, and measuring the intangible is complex due to the difficulty of pinning down the term 'arts and culture', and because there is no consensus in research methods regarding the best approach to this matter. As a consequence, evaluation and measurement continue to be largely focused on monetary measures. This gap also gives space for new approaches that can provide insights into the assessment of the social impacts of cultural activities and identifies the demand to account for other dimensions of culture's transformative power. Following on from this reasoning, the next chapter directly addresses the relationship between peace and culture, exploring the effects of arts-based projects as contributions to peacebuilding, presenting non-violent solutions to problems affecting societies recovering from conflict.

CHAPTER 3. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ARTS AND CULTURE IN PEACEBUILDING PROCESSES

“The potential contribution of art to peace is great” (Gal-Ed, 2009, p. 97)

3.0 Introduction

This chapter explores the main theoretical assumptions about conflicts and their dynamics. Additionally, it identifies the actors and causes of conflicts, and explores how artistic and cultural expressions represent an appropriate means of addressing the effects of violent conflict. Evidence is presented on the value of arts-based approaches as drivers and facilitators of creativity, contributing to the development of mutual understanding, social cohesion and dialogue, while also providing a space for victims of conflict to acknowledge pain, healing and contribute to reconciliation. Several case studies are presented to highlight how arts and cultural practices have contributed to international peacebuilding processes. For the purposes of this study, a particular emphasis is given to experiences deployed in countries that have similar characteristics to the Colombian armed conflict, in terms of their duration and intensity: Guatemala, Northern Ireland, and South Africa. Finally, the chapter outlines the results and impacts of the arts and cultural programmes implemented in those countries in order to contribute to reconciliation and social transformation after peace agreements have been signed.

3.1 Understanding Conflict and its Effects

Many regions in the world are suffering from increasing tensions and conflicts, while others are searching for, building, or maintaining peace (UNDP, 2009). Whatever the scenario, peace is always the goal. According to the Norwegian sociologist Johan Galtung (2000), conflict is a manifestation of the clash of incompatible material interests and objectives. Additionally, it is an outcome of different actors fighting to maintain political, economic, and social power. Ways of achieving these objectives may include displacement and exclusion of a social group from possession of land, access to goods, resources or rights, and differences in ideologies or identity. These elements produce tensions and frustrations that trigger violence, in what Galtung (2000) calls the “lifecycle of a conflict”. The sum of these factors is constantly changing and influencing one another: attitude (hatred) + behaviour (violence, discrimination) + contradictions (causes of the conflict) produce a fully articulated conflict. In a simplified form, this represents the content and the escalatory dynamics of a conflict, and at the end

violence breeds violence, and “deep inside every conflict lies a contradiction, something standing in the way of something else” (Galtung, 1996, p. 70).

Galtung also distinguishes between three types of violence: cultural violence, direct violence, and structural violence, which are correlated with the three elements previously mentioned: attitude, behaviour and contradiction. In Galtung’s opinion, *cultural violence* involves the attitudes and inherited beliefs that surround everyday life e.g. the use of violence and the legitimization of that use, seeing repression and exploitation as normal; this type of violence can be ended by changing cultural attitudes. On the other hand, *direct violence* is understood as the use of physical force (torture, rape, sexual assault, etc.) and/or verbal threats/assault (humiliation, coercion, and intimidation); this type of violence can be ceased by changing behaviour. Finally, *structural violence* is perceived as the discrimination, political oppression and inequality created and perpetuated by the institutional system against some groups; this type of violence can be stopped by changing contradictions. Galtung points out that the cultural and structural aspects of conflicts are invisible, while direct violence is visible as a behaviour that strengthens the two other types of violence. A conflict can have, as a starting point, cultural and structural repression, but over time structures, attitudes and behaviours interact and reinforce each other, producing traumatised parties and actors with psychological and physical wounds.

Conflict is an ever-changing process with three phases: before, during and after violence (Galtung, 2000). As Galtung mentions, in the last phase, reconciliation, reconstruction and resolution must be set in motion, but dealing with this is a long-term process. Taking into account the previous elements, and since direct violence is often built into the social structure, Galtung argues that a *positive peace* requires the absence of structural violence — the absence of direct violence alone is not sufficient. In Galtung’s formulation, this incomplete situation is called *negative peace*. Positive peace allows the causes of conflict to be revealed and responded to. In summary, Galtung promotes transformation of conflicts by peaceful means as the only way to achieve a state of lasting peace.

So far, most studies of conflict seeking to explain the effects of civil wars have focused on economic consequences¹³, only a much smaller proportion analyses the impact on social development. However, civil conflicts have harmful social and psychological effects too (Sánchez & Díaz, 2005). The consequences of conflict and violence, including the displacement of populations, death and injury, sexual abuse, and systematic discrimination, creates a fragile post-war environment (Broome & Collier, 2012).

A number of authors have highlighted the psychosocial effects that arise from conflict, including a loss of trust and dignity, with people often feeling they have been humiliated (Power, 2011). There is also evidence of intergroup threats to wellbeing that can arise due to conflict exposure (Schmid & Muldoon, 2013), alongside high levels of stress (Mohammed, 2015), distrust (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009), and desire for revenge (Byrom, 1999). These negative, indirect impacts may remain for several years post-conflict. Moreover, the diversion of public investment to create mechanisms to alleviate these effects may be seen as an attempt to undermine efforts to promote social justice, discourage prospects for reconciliation, and result in a decrease in the overall wellbeing of a population (UNICEF, 2005). These issues are related to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal number 16, ‘Peace, justice, and strong institutions’, intended to promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development.

Researchers have also argued that the psychological consequences of conflict fuel anger and hate towards the ‘other’, dehumanising the other and sustaining feelings of victimisation and the need for vengeance (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009). In this regard, the psychologists Long and Brecke (2003) suggest that in the aftermath of a violent conflict, purposeful rationality is not sufficient to achieve reconciliation. They conclude that, “at least in the case of reconciliation following civil wars, an evolutionarily determined, emotionally driven patterns, not purposeful rationality, transforms aggression into empathy and desire for revenge into desire for affiliation” (Long & Brecke, 2003, p. 28). This negative psychological consequence is what UNESCO (1996) calls the culture of violence — based on intolerance, hatred, mistrust, fear, disagreements, and hostility between various social groups — that emerges during the period of conflict. Thus, a culture of peace, understood as the “creation of peaceful, non-violent

¹³ The aggregate economic and financial cost of conflict worldwide in 2014 was estimated to be \$14.3 billion, or 13.4% of the global economy, according to the Institute for Economics and Peace.

behavioural patterns and skills” (UNESCO, 1996, p. 13), that promotes empathy, cooperation, mutual understanding, and tolerance, is necessary in order to transcend the incompatibilities in the aftermath of a conflict.

Under this definition, scholars and philosophers increasingly see arts and culture as useful mechanisms to promote social change in post-conflict environments (Stephenson Jr. & Zanotti, 2016). Thus, arts provide creative responses to break the cycles of violence by offering a different perspective on conflict and encouraging peaceful solutions. Cultural practices can address some of the challenges related to coexistence and reconciliation by involving people in sensory experiences, in teamwork, through non-verbal or verbal communications such as music or dance, emerging as one dimension of peacebuilding efforts, which I will explain in detail in the next section.

Although there is a significant body of evidence to support the argument that arts and culture can contribute to societies emerging from violence, there are still difficulties when it comes to producing robust data (and gaps in the data), research, evidence, and evaluation (Michelle, 2002). This is one of the reasons it is not viable to expect that the positive outcomes of arts programmes that promote dialogue, tolerance and community rebuilding can be generalised across all cultures and communities. The specific context where the artistic and cultural intervention is taking place is of great significance; each country has different conditions and contexts, which alters the impact of the process (Merli, 2002; Galloway, 2006). This resonates with Premaratna and Bleiker’s conclusion on the significance of art for peacebuilding: “There is no blueprint about how art works, for its very essence lies in creativity and the ambition to break through conventional ways of seeing, hearing and sensing the world” (2016, p. 92). Beyond that, they go on to suggest that “local artistic engagements can provide context-specific solutions” (Premaratna & Bleiker, 2016, p. 83) in peacebuilding contexts, which differs from other methods to peacebuilding that depend on models, sometimes imposed from outside, that are not adapted to the specific needs of the context to achieve positive impact.

In view of the above, arts and culture emerge as tools that can promote “understanding, preventing, mitigating and recovering from conflicts” (Preis & Stanca Mustea, 2013, p. 2). At the same time, they can process “trauma, healing, dialogue, forgiveness, and reconciliation” (Gal-Ed, 2009, p. 102), as culture creates paths to healing (Preis & Stanca Mustea, 2013) by offering neutral and safe spaces where, through different art forms, people can raise their voice

and express feelings, emotions or issues they face in daily life, raising awareness about past suffering but being open for a new future.

Michelle LeBaron states that “in post-conflict societies, there is always art. People sing their sorrow, paint their grief, dance in the shadows of what once was” (2011, p. 20). Indeed, according to LeBaron it is important to recognise that emotions are “powerful motivators toward transformation just as they are central drivers in conflict escalation” (2011). This argument aligns with that of Zembylas’, as “emotions connect people’s thoughts, judgments, and beliefs, and it can be said that emotions are the ‘glue of identity’” (2003, p. 222). In this regard, Premaratna and Bleiker suggest that “people engage in creative activities, no matter where they are and what challenges they face” (2016, p. 82). In conflict situations, artistic and cultural activities provide powerful ways of expressing essential human experiences. There is some evidence that engagement with art or cultural processes produces a direct relationship with emotions and feelings because it engages people on sensory and cognitive levels (Cohen, 2005). In other words, art and cultural activities invite people to open up their depth of feelings, that otherwise would be difficult to deal with. These processes also “provide support for survivors of violence to confront and work through painful history that might otherwise be too overwhelming to face” (Cohen, 2005, p. 6). There are many empirical studies showing where art and cultural activities have contributed to peacebuilding processes. These activities create a safe and neutral environment where political and ideological differences are put aside, foster a new kind of communication between opposing groups, enable the reconstruction of the social fabric, promote tolerance and mutual understanding, and manage differences without conflict. These examples will now be the focus of discussion.

3.2 Reconciliation and Peacebuilding through Arts and Culture

In the aftermath of violence, the term *reconciliation* appears to be crucial. As Galtung (1996) notes, the core concept of reconciliation needs to be established first. Reconciliation, which can sometimes be confused with forgiveness, can be understood as a “set of deep processes designed to transform relationships of hatred and mistrust into relationships of trust and trustworthiness” (Cohen, 2005, p. 10). Reconciliation reflects a change of focus from attributing the other to taking responsibility for the attitudes and actions of one’s self. It is a long term, inclusive process that is not imposed, and through which a society moves from a divided past to a shared future. It is needed in order to build a pathway for peacebuilding.

According to some authors, “it is a necessary requirement for the long-term survival of that democracy” (Blommfield *et al.*, 2003, p. 15). Cohen mentioned that the reconciliation process involves both sides of the conflict, acknowledging each other’s humanity and replacing the fear that violence generates with coexistence, which means empathising with each other’s pain. To understand reconciliation as a process means dealing with how things are, “building a reconciliation process is the means to work, effectively and practically, towards that final goal — and is invaluable in itself” (Blommfield *et al.*, 2003, p. 12). In contrast, forgiveness is an internal release and involves just one individual. Indeed, reconciliation may open the door to forgiveness and close the door on revenge, by embracing a different interpretation of justice, as reconciliation restores individual rights rather than just punishing the group of perpetrators (Byrom, 1999). Besides, according to some authors, “political processes and strategies aimed at reconciliation are important in establishing the context for individual healing and coming to terms with violence, each individual’s healing path is personal and unique” (Blommfield *et al.*, 2003, p. 80).

The ideal for conflict transformation and lasting peace is “to have offenders and victims come together to dialogue, understand each other’s points of view, and focus on the future rather than on the past. That is what reconciliation is all about” (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009, p. 6). This resonates with psychologist Lumsden’s view on how it is possible to break the cycle of violence: to achieve peacebuilding it is necessary “that individuals negotiate shared meanings, including coherent but compatible identities and patterns of social relationship and it is shared meanings that form the core of group identity and culture, as well as peaceful interpersonal and intergroup relations” (1997, p. 57). Lederach (2005) echoes this understanding, as peace is a dynamic social construct that must integrate the parties involved. This resonates with López and Taylor (2021) since community-led practices can facilitate the construction of a lasting peace. Despite this, there is no singular prescription to attain reconciliation and heal the wounds in the aftermath of a sustained conflict. In fact, it is important to acknowledge that reconciliation programmes cannot be imposed from outside, because every context is different, and each society must discover its own route.

Besides, factors that are vital in the reconciliation process include truth and justice. Transitional justice mechanisms like the establishment of the Truth Commissions¹⁴, for example in Colombia (created by the Legislative Act 01 of 2017 and Decree 588 of 2017), not only serve to help resolve conflicts, but also to achieve reconciliation, guaranteeing the effectiveness of the victims' rights and society's wide commitment to the idea that the atrocities of the past will not be repeated. For example, Guatemala established the Commission for Historical Clarification (1994); South Africa set up the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (1995), and Northern Ireland took 10 years to create the Commission for Victims and Survivors (2008), in order to promote awareness of the interests of victims and survivors of their own conflict. As Gawn mentions, "at some stage, to move towards reconciliation in Northern Ireland, the truth will have to come out or the issue will be a potential seed for further conflict" (2007, p. 359).

A 2019 report commissioned by the British Council explored the 'art of peace' through a review of the academic evidence for the role that arts and culture can play in mitigating conflict and building peace. The authors found emerging evidence of programmes in Colombia, Syria and Rwanda, showing how arts and cultural programmes can be adapted to local contexts and used to engage communities in their own cultural language (British Council, 2019). The available evidence suggests that reconciliation can succeed by creating new beginnings with newly defined social relations.

As Goldstein (2011) has noted, social relations are crucial in peace theory. Social relations at a personal and national level within society become the foundation for lasting peace, with open dialogue as a vital condition to disclose the truth of the past, which has been already identified as fundamental to achieve reconciliation. In a similar vein López and Taylor (2021) argued that individuals and communities play a crucial role in peace transitions.

According to Brounéus (2003), there are six different aspects of reconciliation (socio-cultural, religious, psychological, economic, political, and legal), and all of them play a role in achieving peace. Arts and culture are one of the factors to be considered to achieve reconciliation, because feelings of fear, violence and hatred need to be transformed. When stereotypes and prejudices

¹⁴ "Truth commissions focus on fact finding. They are temporary non-judicial bodies. Truth commissions are normally established by the State in times of democratic or post-war transition, sometimes with the offer of amnesty for perpetrators in return for a full and complete admission of guilt and truth. They can also focus on the investigation of patterns, as well as instances of human rights abuse committed during a defined period" (Gawn, 2007, p. 341).

need to be removed, arts and cultural activities based on common values, traditions and heritage can facilitate the construction of a lasting peace.

This argument has been asserted by several authors, including Blommfield *et al.*:

The way in which a community deals with a violent past is intimately linked to its more general customs and culture. One key element is the way in which the culture influences the system of collective memory. Some societies embody a natural urge to forgive the injustices inflicted on them in the past; others display a strong aversion to letting bygones be bygones. (2003, p. 46)

Kramer *et al.* have suggested that “the key to conflict transformation is therefore fostering a culture of rehumanisation and responsiveness” (2013, p. 33). This is because in violent conflicts people usually lose the inner link to their humanity and victims often find themselves ostracised, marginalised and excluded, feeling the psychological need to restore their self-image as a moral people. As Cohen suggests:

Engaging with the arts can generate, for both individuals and collectivities, for creators and spectators, special qualities of attention and response — such as disinterestedness, committed participation, meta-cognitive alertness, receptivity, and blissful serenity. These qualities of attention and response afford unique opportunities for learning, empathy, reflexivity, creativity, innovation, and experimentation. (2005, p. 5)

One of the most important roles of arts and cultural participation in peacebuilding is the capacity to heal collective and individual trauma, to transform negative energy into positive energy, to access and restore the victim’s emotions, and to inspire creative problem solving (Shank & Schirch, 2008). From this perspective, Fukushima (2011) examines four roles of culture in conflict resolution, which were identified after analysing the effect of arts and cultural projects in countries experiencing significant conflict (e.g. Palestine, Israel, Timor-Leste, Indonesia, Kosovo, and Afghanistan). He considered the value of theatre, painting, and music workshops in helping individuals to transcend memories of war, and suggested that:

As catalyst for peacebuilding, tool to relativise armed conflict; means of building peace in the hearts and minds of local people — by building tolerance, mutual understanding, trust, confidence and, ultimately, achieving reconciliation; encouraging the sublimation of identities

changed by war; caring for and healing those traumatized by conflicts — finally device to empower those in conflict-ridden areas. (Fukushima, 2011, p.7)

The first role is associated with the importance of dialogue as a key tool to understand and listen to others' perspectives, which increases empathy and promotes tolerance. The second role is related to the relevance of cultural processes for victims. This is because, during conflict, victims are deprived of cultural rights; war means the cessation of festivals and all artistic manifestations, so when they are involved in these activities, their self-esteem improves, and they feel appreciated. Also, this enhances the appropriation and protection of their heritage. As mentioned earlier, in the aftermath of a conflict people have psychological wounds, and peacebuilding requires spaces to facilitate communication between conflicting parties. Fukushima suggests that arts and cultural processes contribute to heal the wounds of the past, which is imperative because “without peace in the hearts and minds of the people, there can be not lasting peace” (2011, p. 9). The last role is the empowerment of local people to prevent conflict from happening again. Here, cultural education is essential, and arts and cultural activities (theatre, films, radio are good examples) are used as a channel to deliver a message, a peace message, so those people who have been victims of the violent conflict can understand and be aware of their new reality. In this respect, Cohen illustrates with powerful examples of the Middle East and Burundi how arts and culture shape and create pathways for mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion in the aftermath of a conflict, in order to achieve lasting conflict-resolution and healing.

The role of arts and culture in peacebuilding processes allow communities affected by the armed conflict to come together through common activities that might lead to understand and recognised each other better in a form of *bridge-building*, because it is only when community understands what had happened, that it is possible to move forward to a peaceful future. It is embracing the past and using arts-based interventions to gain greater capacity for reflection that such experience can bring. These assertions are supported by Galtung (2000), who suggests that moving towards a reconciliation scenario involves using a range of artistic activities to introduce mutual understanding, creativity, and dialogue. These factors are — he argues — the main conditions to change attitudes and behaviours, necessary to transcend the incompatibilities after the conflict.

However, it is important to indicate that reconciliation is a long process: “If a society has invested years of energy, time and money in creating division, it will take years to invest energy, time and money to rebuild the relationships that have been broken” (Lederach, 1996, p. 40). Likewise, the construction of peace is a responsibility of all citizens. As Galtung indicates, there are “tasks for everybody” (1980, p. 396), and that includes both positive peace (overcoming structural violence) and negative peace (overcoming direct violence). Therefore, “peacebuilding necessarily involves an array of actors who come from many governmental departments, numerous professions and an array of disciplines” (Alger, 2014, p. 55). In light of this knowledge, reconciliation is a process in which more actors and elements intervene, and where it is important to solve the causes that originate the violent conflict and take steps to deal with them. It is common that, after a period of war, governments have priorities like “the establishment of truth, the prosecution and punishment of perpetrators, the search for missing people and the restoration of homes” (Cehahic-Clancy & Bilewicz, 2017, p. 288), although “their best efforts will be totally undermined if they do not also address the broken relationship between the communities they represent, as well as the issues that broke it” (Blommfield *et al.*, 2003, p. 15).

The available evidence suggests that different art forms can facilitate reconciliation. For example, music can be a form of storytelling, a way of re-imagining lives and realities that engages all senses and can help people relate to each other and be emotionally moved. Lyrics can create a deeper connection, helping help to recall the message, and represent a starting point to affect behaviour. Similarly, music can contribute to generate trust, empathy and even forgiveness between groups, trying to find a way to build lasting peace (Blommfield *et al.*, 2003). As Doyle (2016) states in the report *Creativity in Conflict*:

The performing arts are uniquely equipped to create order out of the chaos of conflicted societies. The arts are comfortable in that otherwise tumultuous space between justice and reconciliation and have the potential to stimulate changes in attitudes and behaviours in the service of more balanced and inclusive societies (2016, p.3).

The findings of the pilot project: *Memory, Arts, and Culture, Gender Justice and Reconciliation*, undertaken in 2016 by students of the University of Cape Town (UCT) School of Dance with a group of women in Warrenton (Virginia, USA), show that dance movement and performance, when focused on *storytelling*, might contribute to “catalyse key moments of

increased understanding between historically disparate groups” (Doyle, 2016, p. 3). In the same way, it was acknowledged that the use of arts in different forms transformed the attitudes and behaviours of participants, facilitating dialogue, and increasing mutual understanding and community-level reconciliation after the end of the Apartheid regime in South Africa.

According to this project, dance movement therapy (DMT) “is perhaps one of the most thoroughly researched applications of the performing arts to trauma healing” (Doyle, 2016, p. 4), as it is a nonverbal method that helps overcome the somatic dimensions of trauma. Moreover, there is evidence that drama therapy based in music and movement helps victims’ recovery from post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), the psychological and physical effects of violence. It also reduces feelings of isolation and enhances confidence between participants (Dunphy *et al.*, 2014).

Fundamentally, drama therapy has the potential to reconnect people with their traditional culture and ritualistic practices through dance and music as forms of healing. In these therapy sessions across body-based exercises, participants were able to explore their body boundaries, learn breathing techniques, explore themselves, and through storytelling, compare their lives before and after Apartheid. The project findings suggest “performing arts in formal theatre spaces can breach contentious issues related to reconciliation because they have entertainment value and effectively capture audience attention” (Doyle, 2016, p. 13). Also, they noticed that honesty is needed to encourage reconciliation, and that improvisational movement offered a neutral and positive space where participants can break down prejudices and feel free to say what sometimes is difficult to say.

This perception was also corroborated by Dunphy *et al.* (2014) within a series of community-based activities that, post-conflict, achieved positive change with survivors of mass trauma in Timor-Leste. Once the dance movement therapy workshop ends, participants were relaxed and comfortable enough with the group to share their personal stories and open up about their feelings towards others, recognising the potential of arts performance in enabling social cohesion and empathy that might contribute to reconciliation and peacebuilding in Timor-Leste. As a result, dance therapy became a mechanism to “support a transcultural encounter where both parties co-create a healing process. This co-creation is an essential element of DMT’s potential to contribute to the recovery and wellbeing of participants” (Dunphy *et al.*, 2014, p. 203).

The experiences in South Africa and Timor-Leste are supported by Rohr in Guatemala, for whom “an exciting verbal play might develop, deliberately crossing mental boundaries, exploring new thoughts, creating new perspectives” (2013, p. 280). Rohr concurs with the idea that conflict gradually changes, allowing an integration process that can potentially contribute to mutual understanding. Likewise, in Northern Ireland, to establish a new relationship on a different plane with the protagonists of this armed conflict, the Arts Council of Northern Ireland funded ‘Building Peace through the Arts: Re-Imagining Communities Programme’ across 32 locations in the country, supporting 54-community art-based projects. According to one participant:

Building Peace Through the Arts is an incredibly important programme, helping us embrace our shared past, but also to move on in a more positive direction, to re-imagine areas which have suffered, to change these areas for the better and to allow pieces of public art to truly represent the community and its residents today. (Arts Council of Northern Ireland, 2015)

The Evaluation Report for the programme showed that 78% of the participants felt that the arts projects helped them to be part of their community, as well as to express their feelings and different perspectives. Also, 95% of respondents considered that the projects contributed to social cohesion with people from different religions and nationalities. These findings indicate that the main objective of the programme was fulfilled, because it was able to promote tolerance and understanding between people with different backgrounds, building peace and reconciliation (Wallace Consulting, 2016). In sum, by highlighting and examining work in this arena, there is evidence that different forms of art might create new insights, facilitate reflection, develop body awareness, have the potential to manage emotions, and can even motivate behavioural change that might contribute to reconciliation and peacebuilding — understanding peacebuilding as the actions that are carried out to prevent a relapse into conflict after a peaceful solution has been achieved. Another relevant study in Northern Ireland (2021) makes a contribution suggesting that including young people -for and against the conflict- in the peace process is important as sharing a social identity may make them more willing to build a future together and leave the conflict behind (Taylor *et al.*, 2021).

However, to achieve reconciliation, authors (Galtung, 2000; Lederach, 2005; Blommfield *et al.*, 2003; Fukushima, 2001) have suggested several stages that need to be followed. The first

one is dialogue, which is a strategic factor in understanding, sharing, and listening to different perspectives. The second one is empathy, built from confidence and trust, that allows people to have respect for each other's ideas and opinions. The last stage is creativity, as a new and innovative vision that allows people to build a common and better future, giving solutions to preserve peace. In sum, to achieve reconciliation in conflict affected contexts, trust, mutual understanding, empathy, and dialogue are key elements to build greater social cohesion. By promoting social inclusion through arts-based programmes, it is possible to develop social capital in all its forms, cultivating an environment of peace.

3.3 The Role of Creativity in Resolving Peacebuilding Problems

Many scholars (Galtung, 1996; Lumsden, 1997; Lederach, 2005; Arai, 2009; LeBaron, 2011) have concluded that creativity can contribute to peacebuilding, because through the creative process, people who have been affected by a violent conflict can invent new languages that facilitate problem-solving and understanding. From this perspective, creativity and problem-solving are linked, and “culture offers the basic language and knowledge base for the creativity. The culture influences both the interaction between the creators and the subject to be created” (Lund & Chemi, 2015, p. 7). Besides, within the creative process, people can develop a new vision and overview to see their problems. As Runco points out, “the situation that was once a problem has become something completely different, namely, an opportunity or challenge” (2007, p. 277). Indeed, Lederach (2005) argues that peace is an organic process that cannot be imposed or imported from outside; instead, people who have lived through conflict need to be able to imagine a new reality, and he proposed creative strategies to transcend the conflict. What he calls ‘conscientization’ needs to be set in motion. Here, the victims’ communities should be self-reliant in dealing with conflicts, and that means that they need to interact, reflect, share their ideas, experiences, and problems, because that is maybe the only path that could lead them to find an innovative peace solution to their problem (Lederach, 2005).

In order to use creativity for productive purposes, the evidence suggests that people must be engaged in creative situations. Here is where art forms (music, drama, dance, and painting) can play an important role that provoke new ways of thinking, being an alternative path to wisdom and, finally, coming up with innovative ideas and solutions to face the challenge of reconstructing people's lives in the aftermath of violence. Stout echoes this understanding

claiming that “the arts, with their inextricable ties to imagination, have the capacity to provide an unlimited source of possibilities for connecting self to other and for creating a disposition for sympathetic awareness” (1999, p. 33).

LeBaron highlights this view noting that “in increasing numbers of conflict interventions, experiential work is being used to help enliven conversations, foster originality and generate imaginative possibilities for shifting intractable conflict” (2011, p. 22). She argues that where cultural processes are being implemented, people are more open to listen, imagine and create, helping adversaries shift the dynamics of conflict in unconventional ways, and this is important because “when perceptions change, understanding, acceptance and empathy often follow” (LeBaron, 2011, p. 23). This was acknowledged by the study *How Creativity Works in the Brain* (National Endowment for the Arts, 2015), in which psychologists and neuroscientists were able to explore the articulation of human creativity with the arts to explain how and why people can connect so powerfully with the arts, and how through arts “the mind comes up with something new that did not exist the day before”.

Indeed, the working group concluded that “it is not so much what artists are that is of interest to science; it’s what they do... It’s the idea that art is concentrated experience” (National Endowment for the Arts, 2015, p. 28). According to the artists interviewed for the project, “creativity represented the struggle to communicate or to invent new languages to illuminate new meanings and contexts; for these artists, creativity is fuelled by a basic desire to better understand ourselves and our place in the world” (National Endowment for the Arts, 2015, p. 7). Beyond that, Tepper (2004) notes the importance of collaborative circles and teamwork to evoke creativity, because in these spaces individuals can feed off the potential and energy of others, and the arts provide an environment where this can be achieved.

From this perspective, Robertson (2016) suggests that music can open paths towards creativity, dialogue and understanding between opposing groups. That was the case in Sarajevo (Bosnia-Herzegovina), where he investigated how musical engagement affected group behaviours and attitudes. Choirs were the medium used to pave the way for discussions beyond a music-focused setting. Since making music is a social activity, the participation of the group is necessary to perform, and communication plays a crucial role in composing songs and creating music. This *creation space*, where music is a vehicle to find solutions to common problems, is an open space where imaginary thinking of possible solutions from the community can happen:

“The continued musicking of Pontanima enabled this process to develop at least on a small scale, as was demonstrated by how attitudes of audiences in traumatised areas positively changed between when Pontanima first began performing and now” (Robertson, 2016, p. 259).

In the same way, the musical experience is considered vital for the Colombian researcher Zapata (2017), as it has the following characteristics: it arises from the interaction of the subject with the surrounding world articulating perception, sensation and emotion; it has the fundamental values of self-growth, self-knowledge and enjoyment; it is influenced by the emotions that give a sense of uniqueness to the human experience; it can have an individual or collective character; this experience is something that usually affects and transforms the life of the person, making it possible to change the course and look at life with a different perspective.

In peacebuilding, Zapata’s research showed that the creative musical experiences enhance the interaction and expression of emotions without having to go through the definition and precision required by words and avoiding the fear of being judged or recriminated. As a result, the musical experience has a hermeneutic component that enables different interpretations of the same artistic event. In parallel to this, DeNora states, music “may serve as a resource in daily life, and it may be understood to have social ‘powers’ in relation to human social being” (2004, p. 151). The author highlights the link between music and ‘awakening’, in the sense that music “provides a basis of reckoning, an animating force or flow of energy, feeling, desire and aesthetic sensibility that is action’s matrix”. In other words, music can facilitate an environment where creativity takes place. Lederach (1997) also suggests that new perspectives — underpinning creativity — are needed to build peace, that is, “we are not merely interested in ‘ending’ something that is not desired. We are oriented toward the building of relationships that in their totality form new patterns, processes, and structures” (Lederach, 1997, p. 84-85). It is, however, important to note that creative processes can be affected positively or negatively by the social and environmental conditions in a society. Therefore, it is important to take into account the context of the people engaging in the arts and cultural processes.

3.4 Cultural Conversations: Dialogue and Peacebuilding

In a conflict situation, groups are often confrontational, and they find it difficult to communicate with one another. When moving towards post-conflict, trauma can inhibit discursive communication, and former enemies are often reluctant to listen to one another

(Cohen, 2003). Therefore, creating the conditions for dialogue is important if communication is to be improved. More recent studies have been conducted on the importance of dialogue as a necessary mechanism to build relations between groups and contribute to long term peacebuilding processes (Cohen, 2005). Some authors note that “art is a unique form of communication, one capable of creating intrinsic benefits that enhance the lives of individuals and often contribute to the public welfare as well” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 5). The special communicative nature of the arts and “the trust associated with revealing one’s creativity to others may make joint arts activities particularly conducive to forging social bonds and bridges across social divides” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 29).

Some scholars have suggested that it might be possible to find creative solutions to common problems and to go beyond the image of conflict, acknowledging harms, but also empathising with each other’s suffering, leading toward reconciliation and forgiveness (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009). According to Fukushima, communication “is the first step in conflict resolution, and culture often can be a medium that helps build confidence to that end”, and, further, “cultural initiatives do serve as a common language that allows adversaries to communicate” (Fukushima, 2011, p. 8-11). Given that art and cultural activities can enable common, interactive and neutral spaces in which adversaries with different points of views can communicate, tell the truth (Cohen, 2005) and share their own ideas in a non-aggressive way, many arts and cultural projects are devoted to amplifying the voices of those who are unheard (Cohen, 2005).

For example, painting, drama and music have been successfully utilised as expressive activities to communicate and translate the language of trauma for those who survived the violence of the Apartheid regime in South Africa. Under these circumstances, a pilot project was set up in 2000 with Drama Studies at the University of Natal and KwaZulu-Natal Programme for Survivors of Violence, in order to explore the potential of the creative arts (painting, drama and music) to restore the connection between survivors and their community, thus contributing to personal healing (Barnes & Peters, 2002). These authors emphasise the importance of artistic approaches to engage many different audiences in dialogue:

It invites the audience to create personal meaning through relating what is seen and heard to their own understanding. Performance, because it is created in the presence of the audience, has the ability, like ritual, to remind us of our communal existence and values, and our connections

to each other. For these groups of survivors of violence, the experience of creating and performing has challenged their original perceptions of themselves and shown them the possibility for change and growth. (Barnes & Peters, 2002, p. 178)

The project allowed the participants to share their stories and perspectives in matters of common interest, which led to solve problems and transform the experiences of trauma into hope and growth. Although the programme made an important contribution to address the physical and psychological legacy of segregation, the problem is yet to be solved, that is, “while black people have been liberated in the political sense, this liberation has not been extended to the realm of socio-economics” (Adonis, 2017, p. 53), as poverty and social exclusion are still present in large sectors of the South African population. Also, as The Institute for Justice and Reconciliation (2014) has confirmed, racism is still a characteristic of the South African social structure.

Even so, art and cultural programmes can be relevant for the construction of peace and reconciliation. That is evident in the case of the Create Syria Project. Formed in 2014, with the support of the British Council and the Independent Cultural Organisation Ettijahat, the project allows artists and members of the Syrian diaspora to play an important role in the country’s peacebuilding process through artistic activities that encourage dialogue, cooperation and mutual understanding between Syrian refugees and the Lebanese society. One of the project’s most important objectives is to ensure that the voices of Syrian civil society organisations are heard. The various artistic initiatives employed (children’s choruses, painting, storytelling) contribute to overcome psychological and social problems that have arisen as consequence of the Syrian conflict. These activities have created a hopeful future in Syria and have facilitated reconciliation (International Alert, 2020). In the same line, Prophecy is an organisation that used theatre to reflect the current conflict and how Syria’s civilisation has survived previous periods of turmoil. According to the Art of Peace report, the play they produced increased empathy and a sense of shared identity among audience members (McPherson *et al.*, 2019).

Theatre is another activity recognised worldwide for providing the space needed to promote dialogue and develop communication. There is evidence that theatre can create an environment where people can express their thoughts, “use their imagination to communicate the meanings they associate with their pasts to themselves and others” (Stephenson & Zanotti, 2016, p. 346), and also provide creative tools to address critical problems that can improve their reality

directly. It is argued that the storytelling incorporated in drama can give voice to the voiceless. It also allows to build individual and collective capacities, listen sensitively, rethink war identities, learn how other people think, construct and share an understanding of their lives, foster teamwork, encourage self-expression, and facilitate reflection (Stephenson & Zanotti, 2016).

According to Brazilian theatre practitioner Augusto Boal (2008), oppressed communities can use theatre to bring about social and political change. Boal developed a form of theatre called 'Theatre of the Oppressed', designed to empower oppressed communities by giving them a platform to tell their stories and raise awareness of issues often ignored by mainstream society. This approach was based on the idea that theatre could be used to challenge existing power structures and give a voice to marginalised communities; its aim was "to change the people — 'spectators', passive beings in the theatrical phenomenon — into subjects, into actors, transformers of the dramatic action" (Boal, 2008, p. 97). Under this interpretation, the spectator assumes the "protagonist role, changes the dramatic action, tries out solutions, discusses plans for change — in short, trains himself for real action" (Boal, 2008, p. 98). In short, the "spectator", which refers to an audience member who not only attends a performance, but also actively participates in it, is an example of participatory art. Through this approach, Boal believed that theatre could be transformed from a passive form of entertainment into an active tool for social change:

If formerly he interpreted the solitary author locked in his study, to whom divine inspiration dictated a finished text, here on the contrary, he must interpret the mass audience, assembled in their local committees, societies of 'friends of the barrio', groups of neighbours, schools, unions, peasant leagues, or whatever; he must give expression to the collective thought of men and women. The actor ceases to interpret the individual and starts to interpret the group, which is much more difficult and at the same time much more creative. (Boal, 2008, p. 112)

Drama depends on the assumption of another identity, and that allows multiple perspectives to be brought to bear. Premaratna and Bleiker reassert this argument noting that "the expression of different voices and perceptions and the consequent co-creation of inclusive narratives allow communities to restore through re-enactment the fragmented meaning and lives in post-conflict contexts" (2016, p. 91). Therefore, a play, a mural or an exhibit can present the stories from both sides of the conflict, and together they can re-think and interpret their stories in a nuanced

way (Cohen, 2005). Indeed, some authors (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004) suggest that pro-active involvement, particularly in performing arts, is beneficial for positive attitude and behavioural changes. This is because when people are creating their own performance, there is an open space for dialogue, they need to be able to work in teams, collaborate with others, hear, and trust each other, and that dynamic also develops various skills needed to plan a performance.

In parallel with this, Doyle (2016) suggests that the social benefits of formal theatre are not only for those who perform, but also for the audience. Although the performers control the content of the play and sometimes attempt to challenge the audience's perspective, the audience has an important role in consenting, reflecting, and dialoguing on the real-life situations presented. For Doyle, the theatre is a space that:

Facilitates positive audio-visual experiences that involve listening and observation. There is a power dynamic present in which performers control the content. Audiences are, in a sense, consenting to be fascinated for a period of time, and they often expect to be entertained. (2016, p. 13)

An example is the Non-Governmental Organisation based in Jamestown, Act for Change whose aim is to transform and improve people's lives through theatre, using performance as a tool to facilitate dialogue and through a collective process find creative solutions to human rights abuses. As noted by Collins (2022) the work of Act for Change had opened a space for expression to address the challenges and risks of modern slavery (e.g sex trade and human trafficking), subjects that are difficult to discuss, but it is precisely the power of theatre, to put individuals in another role - in the shoes of another person - to see things from a different point of view, that can contribute to raise awareness on that matter. Here, through the performative element of theatre it is possible to educate audiences and generate positive changes in behaviour and attitudes. In this context, theatre can be interpreted as social change through art.

Similarly, music can also work as an alternative form of dialogue (Pruitt, 2011). Pruitt demonstrates the potential of music to create mutual understanding, engage in dialogue and encourage confidence with three different projects: Youth Movement (YM), Musical Exchange of Culture (MEC) and Project Movement (PM), all three of them implemented with the participation of young people in Northern Ireland. Her findings corroborate the idea that music "can be used as a nonviolent way to share and even challenge opinions from different

perspectives” (Pruitt, 2011, p. 213). This project used different music genres and instruments in collaborative music-making workshops, followed by discussion sessions that allowed participants from different backgrounds (religion, ethnic, political, economic) to transform their perceptions, build trust, and contribute to change the perspectives from those around them. The essence of music (both speech and non-verbal communication) facilitates young people to manage their differences without conflict — everyone can get involved regardless of their ethnicity, political and ideological positions, and transcend cultural and demographic boundaries; “it may have unique insights to offer for the alleviation of conflict” (Pruitt, 2011, p. 213). As DeNora concludes in her book *Music in Everyday Life*, “music is much more than a decorative art; that it is a powerful medium of social order” (2004, p. 163).

However, it is important to note that the type of music or genre depends on the people involved in the process, their preferences, culture and, of course, context. Nevertheless, despite the arguments for music, theatre and other cultural forms providing the basis for meaningful dialogue, their success depends on effective facilitation, on the credibility of the people that lead the artistic projects, and on the inclusiveness of the cultural activities. As Schaffer *et al.* indicate:

Those dialogues deemed substantive and transformative have deft guides who are able to create a sense of trust, respect, and safety; make perceptive connections between the art and the issue; assist participants to link personal experiences and universal themes; and provide the type of welcome and orientation that encourage audiences/participants to find a reason to engage in the dialogue in the first place. (1999, p. 46)

In sum, those projects that effectively incorporate dialogue work with an artistic process open up a nonthreatening path to communication that appears as a spontaneous part of the artwork, turning dialogue and the arts into a tool that contributes to reconciliation: “[...] the communicative nature of the arts, the personal nature of creative expression, and the trust associated with revealing one’s creativity to others may make joint arts activities particularly conducive to forging social bonds and bridges across social divides” (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 29).

In this section, I have highlighted the relevance of arts-based programmes in creating better relationships between people from different backgrounds, providing common ground around

activities they can work on together. This is an important area of community cohesion. As a result, the strategies presented above strengthen the social capital of the individuals involved in those cultural projects, supporting the social networks that connect groups, developing a common sense of belonging, a shared vision of the future, building trust and fostering respect. These are all key factors for conflict recovery.

3.5 Mutual Understanding towards Empathy

Despite the discouraging post-conflict context, arts and cultural activities have the potential to encourage social interaction, and collaborative arts projects can make emotional connections that induce compassion and develop meaning and significance, which results in empathy (Broome, 2009).

For the purposes of this study, empathy is “the ability to understand and enter the feelings, thoughts and motives of another; it does not imply acceptance or agreement, or losing oneself to become another, but rather identifying with and understanding another’s reasons and reactions” (Ishaq, 2006, p. 3). Arai (2006) presents four components of cultural influence. One of them is the expressive capacity directly linked to empathy, an ability to imagine the feelings and sensations experienced by others and to understand them in context. In this regard, Nussbaum (2001) that arts and culture enable the development of empathy, another key to peacebuilding, to be able to sincerely care for others.

This resonates with LeBaron’s (2013) findings, in which empathy with others occurs through ways that transcend verbal language. She evokes dance and theatre as instruments that can foster empathy and suggests that creating collective experiences “enables people to identify and establish bonds that facilitate openness, empathetic communication, and mutual ownership” (LeBaron, 2013, p. 146); furthermore, people are “neurologically wired for mutual understanding and feeling” (Beausoleil & LeBaron, 2013, p. 144). In this regard, art forms can enable the development of the processes that empathy involves: “[...] emotional literacy, defined as the ability to identify and express one’s own emotions; and emotional intelligence, defined as the ability to correctly and comprehensively read another person’s emotions” (Ishaq, 2006, p. 4).

Recent research has been done on the impacts of music on social cohesion, enhancing mutual understanding and promoting empathy (Koelsch, 2013; Bang, 2016). In fact, according to Koelsch, collective music-making can facilitate social cohesion as “individuals have contact with other individuals, engage in social cognition, participate in co-path (the social function of empathy), communicate, coordinate their actions, and cooperate with each other” (2013, p. 204). Likewise, Bang states that “music can help people see and connect with each other in new ways” (2016, p. 360), driving attention to the positive effects of empathy improving intergroup attitudes and relations.

In this sense, the authors mentioned above have argued that artistic engagement can provide people with a supportive environment in which the empathic connection can take place, strengthening the ability to learn from and engage with others, leading to mutual understanding and trust without damaging relationships. From this perspective, “the artistic engagement constitutes a whole body or somatic (integrated mind, body, and spirit) experience that could foster transformation, or at the least an enhanced capacity, for more constructive engagement with conflict and cooperative relationships even in contexts outside of the artistic activity itself” (Bang, 2016, p. 358).

From another artistic and cultural perspective, the American psychologist Lykes (2001) used photography as the art-form that enabled psychosocial accompaniment for women victims of violence within the indigenous tribe “Maya-Ixiles¹⁵”, in Guatemala. At the same time, photography was used to recognise the different perspectives of the conflict, as well as the realities of the most vulnerable and excluded sectors. It was a process that increased levels of understanding, empathy, and contributed to healing within and across communities. In this context, photography was also used as a tool that enabled communication, because some women did not speak Spanish or write or read other languages. In this situation, they took pictures to communicate, share human rights violations and social injustices, telling their own stories of violence, and gradually overcoming their pain and suffering (Lykes, 2001).

During a process that lasted two years, the women participants were accompanied by a facilitator who guided the project. Each participant was given a camera, and some topics to focus their photos on (mainly culture, work, family, religion, and war). Then — with

¹⁵ One of the smallest surviving Mayan groups in the country.

neighbouring villages — each participant presented their story through images, sharing their emotions and creating a public testimony. Other participants had different perspectives and experiences to tell in response to see the same picture. This stimulated a process that led to a collective construction of the facts, collaboratively building a unified account of what happened and learning from each another. As a consequence, “[the women] developed an understanding of the different forms of violence experienced in the municipality, as well as the analysis of the complex challenges faced by the region as it develops recovery strategies in the emergence of trauma from the war” (Lykes, 2001, p. 21).

One valuable factor was that, for the first time, these women were the spokespersons of their own history, and photographic exhibitions became a powerful storytelling mechanism of peacebuilding, reweaving the social fabric in the post-conflict scenario. Nevertheless, and despite the presence of Peace Agreements in place for over two decades, there are still secondary effects. Drawing on findings of research into visual narratives such as photography, it is argued that the visual qualities of photographic imagery provide specific benefits for social change. This was highlighted by Valentina Baú (2015) in the project *Lenses of Conflict and Peace*, delivered in Kenya in 2014 with youngsters from different tribes who suffered the post-election violence period from 2007 and 2008. Baú’s project was able to create “further understanding between different tribes and identify ways forward” (2015, p. 81). When participants presented their pictures to different tribes, sharing their story and telling how they were affected by the violence, they built a path of understanding between themselves, solidifying their sense of community, fostering moving forward and the restoration of trust. As highlighted by Carlson *et al.* (2006), the storytelling that includes each image generates an emotive situation that is crucial for people restoration. Indeed, “bearing witness to others and doing the same allows us to understand that we have all suffered and can relate to each other’s humanity” (Bush, 2011, p. 15), helping to rehumanise the ‘other’.

Despite the fact that the protagonists of these projects were telling their story using different art forms, it is relevant that the *listeners* are also actors in this process. The audience receiving the message can be a multiplier of the message, and the message can affect them in many ways (challenging their view of history or reinforcing those views). This includes broadening their understanding of what happened in the past, which is one of the purposes of storytelling, between seeking justice, preserving memory, healing, and acknowledgment for their version of history (Bush, 2011).

In the Irish Peace Centres' series of experiential learning papers, Bush (2011) presented an evaluation of storytelling as a peacebuilding methodology, collecting experiences from more than ten different projects, including artistic projects that contribute to peacebuilding in post-conflict (South Africa, Northern Ireland, Cambodia, Nicaragua, Germany, Sri Lanka): "I think we have to be very careful that we make sufficient trauma counselling and therapies available to people who are engaging in storytelling, because at a personal level it can actually reengage with trauma again" (Bush, 2011, p. 9). In other words, there must be close and professional supervision throughout the storytelling process, which should never be taken lightly. Also, the different art forms and processes used during storytelling differ between countries, and between cultures. For example, as this chapter has explained, theatre and performance are common in Syria as is music in Colombia.

3.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have explored the nature and dynamics of conflict, identifying that its roots are always a contradiction, an incompatibility or clash of goals that then results in a clash of parties and violent behaviour. Negative attitudes can occur at any stage of this process. These negative attitudes influence behaviour and contribute to a vicious cycle. Reconciliation was also highlighted as one of the essential elements in the peacebuilding process, to improve social relations.

I then reviewed an emerging body of literature on the use of arts-based approaches in post-conflict peacebuilding processes, presenting the power of cultural programmes to de-escalate tensions and contribute to conflict prevention. Arts and cultural activities do not have the power to end violence directly. However, they can promote community collaboration and provide a platform for dialogue that brings different people together. Other effects include increasing individual trust and facilitating understanding, which makes it possible to rebuild social fabric and restore social capital through community arts projects.

I also stress that not all art forms are suitable for conflict resolution, because each context has its own reality, and the affected community must be involved creating solutions to the problem or causes of the conflict. However, the diverse and varied nature of the arts makes it possible to adjust their use according to the specific context in which projects are implemented and the

objectives of the intervention. Nevertheless, more empirical work is needed to explore which art genres, which interventions and what time period are necessary to contribute positively to reconciliation processes.

In addition, more effective evaluation tools are needed to better understand the effects of this engagement in building mutual understanding, dialogue, creativity, and social cohesion. Furthermore, in the light of the research evidence presented, it is recognised that the social benefits derived from the arts are transversal, whereby an arts project can address different outcomes: facilitating dialogue, creativity, and mutual understanding. Finally, the arts are just one of the tools that can be used to stimulate reconciliation and promote peacebuilding. If peace processes fail to address the structural roots of violence, direct violence may resurface. To promote peace, it is necessary to combine a range of peace strategies simultaneously and consistently in the pursuit of peace in the long run.

CHAPTER 4. METHODOLOGY

4.0 Introduction

As discussed previously, several authors (Lederach, 2005; LeBaron, 2011; Doyle, 2016) have acknowledged the important role played by arts and culture in post-conflict scenarios. Reported positive effects include the promotion of social change. The evidence presented in the preceding literature review suggests that artistic and cultural activities can awaken emotions, memory, and feelings, and represent a neutral and peaceful means for people to express their fears, remorse, forgiveness, pain, guilt, sadness, worries, ideas, and hopes. Moreover, there is also some evidence that engagement with arts and culture can help to appreciate the humanity of others, acknowledge injustices and harms, tell truths, and empathise with others, facilitating reconciliation (Preis & Stanca Mustea, 2013), mutual understanding (Cohen, 2005), and dialogue (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004). In other words, the engagement with arts and culture influences patterns of social relations and human interaction, giving victims space away from the trauma of violence. This is important for the purpose of this research, which is to explore the claim that arts and culture are a crucial component in peacebuilding processes (Cohen, 2005; Lederach, 2005; Preis & Stanca Mustea, 2013). To reiterate, the research questions guiding this study are the following:

RQ1: What role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities that are dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict?

RQ2: What design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture?

This study focuses on the social implications and outcomes of artistic and cultural experiences in a post-conflict situation, rather than on the economic value of arts and culture. It goes beyond quantifiable results and examines qualitative issues, recognising the importance of the intrinsic benefits of arts and cultural activities, and exploring their contribution to community wellbeing (e.g. taking part in music, dance, painting classes). The study seeks to understand the relationship between participation in arts and cultural activities and wellbeing, analysing the contribution of the cultural sector to facilitating positive social change in Colombia. Economic

valuation techniques are unable to capture all the dimensions of cultural value (Throsby, 2001), representing an inadequate framework for understanding cultural value benefits in their entirety. As Holden suggests: “[...] the value of culture cannot be expressed only with statistics” (2004, p. 1). Culture is a complex term, and in some cases, it has an incommensurable and intangible meaning, which is part of the reason it has been a difficult area to value. As Selwood argues, “the concept of the arts itself is indefinable, and any attempt to measure it cannot begin to represent its essential quality” (2006, p. 38).

In this chapter, I discuss the philosophical foundations and research methods that underpin the study. First, a brief overview of the ontological and epistemological considerations informing the study is provided. Thereafter, the choice of interpretivism as a research paradigm is discussed. Then, an explanation of the phenomenological approach and its development into Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is next, justifying why this approach is appropriate for the empirical element of the thesis. Finally, a detailed description of the qualitative research methods that formed the study’s research design is provided, focusing on rich descriptions of project experience: case study, interviews, and participant observation.

4.0 Ontological, Epistemological and Paradigmatic Considerations

In Rowland’s (1995) opinion, research study shows a worldview created of: ontological beliefs, epistemological assumptions, and methodological choices. Questions concerning the nature of reality are addressed by ontology (or being, or existence, or what it is), which refers to beliefs regarding reality, what can exist and what is real. In this regard, social ontology, the study of the nature of the social world, is concerned with the examination of the nature of social phenomena and how they relate, to the natural world and, to the lives of individuals (Archer, 1995), which means that ontological analysis seeks to characterise the realm of the fundamental.

For epistemology, on the other hand, the sphere of the primordial is represented in the subject-object schema. In other words, ontology works with the nature of reality (because being is everything that exists or can be thought); while epistemology is concerned with analysing the relationship between the being and its reality (i.e. how it apprehends it). It is a process whereby the researcher gains knowledge about object of study. Similarly, specific epistemological

beliefs guide to the choice of particular methodologies, and those methodological preferences are the means by which researchers seek to achieve desired ends.

In epistemology there are two different philosophical positions: empiricism and rationalism. Empiricism claims that knowledge is derived from sensory experience, conversely, rationalism affirms that it is acquired through human reason. In turn, there are several different research paradigms. One of the most influential paradigms over the last century has been positivism. The positivist approach, which appeared with sociologist Auguste Comte, founder of positivism, suggests that explanation of reality is based on observation and on experience. Which means that the only acceptable knowledge is scientific reality. Among its most salient features is its quantitative nature, utilised to ensure the precision and rigour that science demands (Vasilachis de Gialdino, 2009). In this regard, Martínez points out that:

Quantitative analysis with the most complex techniques of the great statistical programs [...] reached a peak and leaves unresolved the most serious behavioural human problems, many prominent researchers of quantitative circles [...] they begin to explore with interest and to promote the implementation of qualitative methods. (2004, p. 7)

Alternatives to the rationalist or positivist paradigm include interpretivism, which is based on a life-world ontology, “since there are different problems in the disciplines of the social field, issues and restrictions that cannot be explained or understood in their whole extension from the quantitative methodology” (Pérez, 2004, p. 26). Interpretivist approaches are directly opposed to positivism as it involves researchers interpreting the elements of the study. Thus, interpretivism integrates human interest in a study through social constructions. These can be language, consciousness, and shared meanings. Consequently, this paradigm emphasises qualitative over quantitative analysis.

Schwandt (2001) echoes this understanding, arguing that the human sciences aim to understand human action, but interpretivism rejects the idea of any permanent fixed reality without the mediation of human structuring. In that sense, knowledge of what people are doing or saying is directly related to people’s specific background. The environment partly influences people’s behaviour. They are also influenced by their subjective perception of their realities.

Linking to the specific objectives of the present study, according to the interpretivist paradigm, what the world *means* to the victims of the Colombian conflict is critically important to good research in the social sciences.

The interpretivist paradigm foregrounds and values subjectivity, interaction with participants, and the voice of the researchers (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). It is also more concerned with understanding social phenomena in natural environments, through the application of ethnographic and phenomenological methods to understand the subject of study. This assigns importance to the intentions, ideas, feelings, motivations, and opinions of all participants, and to how they perceive, experience, and live their everyday realities. Thus, to understand a particular action (in this case how engagement with arts and cultural activities produces social change in a specific post-conflict community and setting) the interpretivist researcher must comprehend the meaning of that action, because that is the way actors engaged in particular situations make sense of their lives. In that sense, actions can be interpreted differently depending on the context (Schwandt, 2001, p.191).

According to Schwandt (2000), there are three ways to achieve an interpretive understanding of the social actor. The first is *empathic identification* through the discovery of the intentions, beliefs, and motives of the actor. The second is *phenomenological analysis*, which focuses on experiences, events, and occurrences, but the meaning depends on its context of use. The third is *language games*, which means understanding and analysing the systems of meanings or languages (institutional and cultural norms) that might vary depending on the cultural context. Like all research paradigms, interpretivism also has its limitations and critiques. For example, Gadamer (1993) states that traditions and associated prejudgments condition interpretations, because they shape what we are and how we understand the world, hence, it is not easy to set aside and escape from preconceptions. However, it is possible to manage and control those biases in interpretation, since understanding is attained through questions and answers (Bernstein, 1983). In sum, the interpretivist paradigm was chosen for this study. Interpretivism provides an avenue into the life-world concept in the realm of the human sciences, considering that there is not just one reality, and that the phenomenon can only be understood by studying the context in depth.

4.1 Focusing on ‘Experiences’

Phenomenology, also known as non-positivism, can be considered a subset of interpretivism-constructivism. This approach assumes that there are as many realities as there are participants, in the same way the meaning of reality is often co-constructed by participants and researchers implying a transactional and subjectivist epistemology. In order to examine the capacity and potential of arts and culture to contribute to peacebuilding processes in Colombia, it is important to work closely with the victims of violence and to facilitate deep conversations and dialogue that foreground their subjective experiences. As Peter Bazalgette, chair of Arts Council England, posits: “[...] when we talk about the value of arts and culture, we should always start with the intrinsic — how arts and culture illuminate our inner lives and enrich our emotional world. This is what we cherish” (2014, p. 4).

The phenomenological approach is a non-positivistic qualitative philosophy, which aims to study people’s perception of their lived experiences in their fullest breadth and depth. This means that the approach is mainly focused on the lifeworld of research participants and policymakers. It creates a framework that allows the observer to understand complex human interactions (Creswell *et al.*, 2007, p. 253) and capture the ‘essence’ of their experiences. This is a suitable approach for this study because it facilitates access to experiences and meanings, and to capture as closely as possible the way in which the phenomenon under investigation has been experienced. In the same line, Scott (2014) argues that in order to understand culture’s unique value, it is important to capture the meaning of the experiences produced by arts and culture. From this angle, Crossick and Kaszynska (2016) claim that providing a clear understanding of the value of culture will require a phenomenological approach, which focused on the first-person perspective – aspects of ‘inner life’, that are not easy to reach.

By starting with this phenomenology of culture, the study sought to examine which artistic and cultural interventions reflect more accurately what is uniquely produced by cultural engagement in a post-conflict setting. There are two main approaches to understand phenomenology: i) descriptive or transcendental, and ii) interpretive or hermeneutic. The German mathematician Edmund Husserl stated: “[...] as far as phenomenology is concerned, it wants to be a descriptive science of the essences of pure transcendental experiences in phenomenological attitude” (1949, p. 166). Husserl (1992) established a way to know reality, giving importance to the internal sphere of things. The main rule of descriptive or

transcendental hermeneutics is to let things become apparent in their essential content, through an intuitive gaze (Husserl, 1949). This descriptive phenomenology is contrary to the interpretive or hermeneutic form initiated by the German philosopher Heidegger (1962) and continued and recreated by Gadamer (1993). For Heidegger: “Phenomenology is not only a description but also an interpretive process in which the researcher makes an interpretation of the meaning of the lived experiences” (Creswell *et al.*, 2007, p. 253).

From the perspective of Heidegger (1962), qualitative data never speaks wholly for itself and needs the researchers to give it meaning. For the purposes of this study, the hermeneutic phenomenological methodology was employed, since it provided the tools to interpret the language of human interactions, for example interviews (Scott, 2014), and because it gave importance to the essence of the experience (the ‘how it is experienced’), recognising that descriptions also involve interpretation (Heidegger, 1962). In the same line, Sloan and Bowe contend that “hermeneutic phenomenology, employed as a research methodology, provided us the best opportunity to ‘give voice’ to the experiences that we found that lecturers had, in the context of the study” (2014, p. 3), since it is not possible to separate the experiencing subject from what is experienced in the world (Husserl, 1992).

Things and people become what they are only against a background, that is, a context that is taken for granted by historical and cultural practices, which means that what is real is what our cultural practices define. For Heidegger, a phenomenological analysis means that the investigation of ‘what’ sustains all the particular entities and allows them to show themselves. In other words, *being* is possible thanks to the practices in which it circulates; there is no way to understand *what something is*, outside the human context. In solid terms, we do not experience the world thinking about it, but through practical participation in concrete activities. In the light of the previous arguments, IPA is applied in this research, largely, because it seeks to capture the quality of an experience, understand the stories as they are experienced by the participant, explores in detail how participants are making sense of their personal experiences, and interprets the context the research participant is part of. As Heidegger notes, interpretation is a further development of understanding: “In interpretation, understanding does not become something different. It becomes itself” (1962, p. 188).

4.2 Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA)

By utilising an IPA approach, the study does not pretend to show absolute truths, or guidelines of general application, since it recognises the diversity and plurality of scenarios, conditions and situations that are presented in reality, which are therefore unique and unrepeatable, so the observations and results of the research are only valid for the particular case being studied. Therefore, IPA is fundamentally “ideographic” (Shinebourne, 2011), which means that its focus is on the analysis of a small number of participants who have experienced a common phenomenon, exploring in detail their experience to identify patterns of similarity and difference, and to decipher the meaning that a particular phenomenon has for them. This means that it is a ‘participant-oriented’ qualitative research approach that helps analyse and understand the social reality of individuals, specifically how people give meaning to their experiences. Evans makes the valuable and insightful point that, by studying the individual, it is possible to affirm “[...] the centrality of certain general themes in the lives of all particular individuals” (1993, p. 8), which brings the researcher closer to noteworthy aspects of what is general by connecting the individual unique life with a common humanity.

Using this approach, it is possible to reveal the behaviour, perspectives, feelings and experiences of people and what lies at the core of their lives, investigating social processes and interactions (Pickering, 2008). This is what this study is seeking to understand from the participants involved in arts and cultural activities in Colombia, exploring the ‘meaning’ of their individual perceptions, and the impact or contribution of cultural engagement to their lives, in a post-conflict period. It is worth restating that the intrinsic benefits of the arts are experienced at an individual level (pleasure, stimulation, meaning), making them difficult to articulate it in terms of mass ‘outcomes’. For this reason, it is important to grasp the ‘essence’ of the experience to ensure that it can emerge from the research participants themselves. According to this, Holden’s theory claims “these kind of values can be capture in personal testimony, qualitative assessments, case studies and critical reviews” (2006, p. 14).

McCarthy *et al.* (2004) advocate for a non-economic approach to appreciate the intrinsic dimension of art and culture using non-quantitative methods and a more in-depth qualitative method. This assertion is supported by Clift when he suggests that “qualitative methods of data gathering including observations, interviews and focus group discussions, together with

analytical techniques such as narrative, thematic and content analysis, are important tools for a deeper analysis of arts-based interventions” (2012, p. 123).

Following Clift’s ideas, Crossick and Kaszynska advocate for employing more qualitative research in arts-based interventions. Recognising the need to capture the personal and individual experiences of the participants, in other words, the phenomenological aspects of experience, which focus on understanding lived experiences, “expressed in their own words, as one key element in the research process were appropriate to the subject” (Crossick & Kaszynska, 2014, p. 124). That said, it is precisely this experiential value, in terms of meaning, the raw material for the implementation of IPA (Smith, 2009), what makes it an appropriate approach to use in getting to the root cause of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013, p. 47).

In view of the above, IPA can serve to make ‘suspicious’ interpretations that make sense of the data by forming theoretical concepts from outside, or in contrast, ‘empathic’ interpretation that make sense of phenomena by leaving aside any expert knowledge and theories the researcher may already have about them (Willig, 2017). Given that the purpose of employing a phenomenological approach is to get as close as possible to the quality and meaning of participants’ experiences, it explicitly aligns itself with an empathic approach to interpretation, which is predominant in this study. However, it is important to recognise that the literature review conducted for this study does bring a pre-existing theoretical dimension to the study, although to avoid influencing the data too much, a rigorous, transparent process that focused on illuminating the participants’ major life experiences was carried out. In parallel to this, the IPA approach is concerned with garnering an in-depth understanding of a phenomenon and is focused on the use of smaller sample sizes.

An approach defined as methodological triangulation (Denzin, 2006), which consist in the application of different methods can be a useful research option, even if many IPA studies utilise one method. In this study, this approach is used in an attempt to provide a complete picture of the explored phenomenon. The emphasis is not necessarily to corroborate one source and method with another, but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon. Thus, one set of qualitative methods inspired by phenomenological philosophy were employed, enhancing the analysis and the interpretation of findings.

The most used research method for IPA study is the semi-structured interview, which allows the researcher to adopt an “insider’s perspective” (Conrad, 1987) and to see what it is like from the participant’s view, to stand in his or her shoes. Moreover, it is also possible to utilise participant observation to observe the person in their natural setting, capture context specific situations and perceive the reality of the participants, become familiar with them and the cultural projects under research, being present in the place where they live in, and develop artistic and cultural activities. The IPA method attempts to produce relevant findings, allowing broad-based knowledge to be contextualised within a social and cultural context, since the phenomenological interpretation needs to pay equal attention to the historical and socio-cultural aspects of the phenomena under study. Hence, we are attempting to understand, both in the sense of “trying to see what it is like for someone” and in “analysing, illuminating, and making sense of something” (Smith, 2009, p. 36).

The selection of the methods was based on the fact that they are consistent with each other and allow exploration of the contextual conditions where the artistic and cultural processes are taking place in Colombia. Similarly, to develop an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon, it was essential to collect the different perspectives of a number of participants to describe what they have in common and learn about the meaning of being involved in arts and cultural programmes in post-conflict scenarios. Thus, case studies, interviews and participant observation provide adequate and sufficiently rich material for interpretation to be reasonably well grounded in it, thus the validity of the study will emerge only in the context where those meanings were generated (Smith & Shinebourne, 2012).

As Nutt and Morrow argue: “[...] quantity of data is key to filling out categories or themes in such a way that the reader is able to grasp the richness and complexity of the constructs under investigation” (2009, p. 578). The methods mentioned above helped examine the process of construction of meaning in relation to the arts and cultural activities and provided the elements to answer the research questions of whether engagement with the arts facilitates social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities that are dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict, and what design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture.

4.3 Research Design: Two Cases

To translate the commitment to interpretivism and the interest in using phenomenological techniques to access the lived experiences of conflict-affected people in Colombia, the research takes a case study idiographic approach, including a series of research methods (interviews and participant observation) undertaken within each selected case. This approach is consistent with IPA since it allows phenomenological interpretation of personal experiences.

Taking into account that the purpose of this study is to gain an in-depth understanding of the role of arts and culture in a real-life setting (Colombia), a case study approach is an appropriate one to adopt. Case study research is designed to examine the context and the dynamics of a particular situation. The defining feature of case study research is its focus on ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions (Myers, 2009), and for this reason is appropriate for descriptive and exploratory studies (Mouton & Babbie, 2001). The case study method is an appropriate method for this study, largely because the phenomenon under investigation cannot be studied outside of its natural setting, focuses on contemporary events, and the theoretical knowledge in the field is limited and not yet mature. As the psychologist Stake noted, “the power of case study is its attention to the local situation, not in how it represents other cases in general” (2006, p. 8). This argument highlights the key role that local context plays in the case study, because it recognises complexity and situational uniqueness as it operates in real time. In this thesis, the beneficiaries of the art initiatives are people in vulnerable conditions, with few opportunities for study and work, and with limited access to basic services. In terms of infrastructure, their territory is distant and, in many cases, difficult to access. Having been taken over by guerrillas years ago, it also has a stigma that makes it undesirable to visit. This context affects participants’ lives, and the conditions in which I collected the data, the setting and the situation are all important.

The case study is a widely recognised, robust research method in many social science studies, particularly when in-depth investigation and explanation of a social behaviour are required, on the grounds that a researcher is able to go beyond the “quantitative statistical results and understand the behavioural conditions through the actor’s perspective” (Zainal, 2007, p. 1). The case study examines data within a specific context, with the intention of embracing contextual conditions and exploring a study phenomenon that involves researchers immersing themselves in the culture being studied. As Stake asserts, “qualitative case study was developed to study the experience of real cases operating in real situations” (2006, p. 3), considering that

relying in a quantitative method alone would obscure some of the important data that needs to be uncovered. Likewise, one of the ways of looking at the social impacts of an activity is to consider its effects on people and the way they relate to it (Lingayah *et al.*, 1996). Moreover, some authors (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004) have argued that case studies are the most widely used approach to demonstrate the social benefits of the arts at the community level. Even though, they mentioned:

The time that elapses between the initial arts activity (e.g., attendance) and the desired social outcome of social capital is often so great, and the number of other factors so large, that researchers can at best measure intermediate outputs from the activity (e.g., interactions among strangers or becoming a subscriber) that might eventually produce social capital. (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004, p. 16).

Despite the arguments mentioned above, case study research is sometimes criticised for its lack of theoretical depth and rigour, that might lead to “fuzzy generalizations” (Bassey, 1999), 1999). To overcome the problems that this embodies, this research adopts two cases for study (Sensory Expedition and Casa Kolacho). This approach is considered more compelling to achieve the robustness of the study (Herriott & Firestone, 1983), and it also enables the identification of common themes or patterns to emerge across the cases (Punch, 2009). Selecting and analysing two case studies provides a route into understanding how their work contributes to social change, as well as to understand some of the broader lessons for the use of art and culture in peacebuilding and reconciliation processes.

4.3.1 Case Selection

Based on the identification of case studies in Colombia that are developed or conceived in contexts of destruction and violence, the Colombian Truth Commission (Comisión de la Verdad, 2022) collected around 400 works by classical and contemporary artists on the peace-war dichotomy, and has also selected different art-based projects derived from the Colombian conflict.

In addition to this rigorous work, in my research work I identified other arts-based projects that work for the well-being of people in the midst of conflict or as a means for peacebuilding (more information in chapter 2). Among the different art-based initiatives that were found, few have

been conceived by communities or through a participatory process, the vast majority are projects developed for a short period of time, or do not take into account the realities and contexts of the beneficiaries.

In order to select the most cases to address the study's two research questions, selection criteria were developed in terms of time, scope, and the way the art initiatives were designed and financed. This process led to the selection of two case studies in areas particularly affected by violence and where cultural and artistic interventions are being carried out to facilitate the construction of peace. The chosen cases enabled in-depth analysis of the artistic and cultural interventions taking place to contribute to peacebuilding practices in rural and urban locations. Funding for the respective projects came from different sources — one is State funded, and the other is not.

Some researchers state that identifying the impact and benefits of arts activities on health and wellbeing takes some time, and “the longer the projects are available to people, the more this benefit is consolidated and sustained” (Kilroy *et al.*, 2007, p.60). While projects can only operate with long term funding, the ability to follow objectives towards an agreed goal or vision meant that the two selected cases were in operation for more than four years: Casa Kolacho in Medellín and Sensory Expedition in Montes de María.

Casa Kolacho is located in Comuna 13, once one of the most violent areas in Medellín. Here, a group of rappers decided to take over their neighbourhood with art. They have earned the respect of the entire city, after a decade of offering young people an alternative to violence and drug trafficking through hip-hop culture. On the other hand, Sensory Expedition was a project developed by the Ministry of Culture in one of the most dangerous rural areas during the armed conflict. For the first time, the Ministry decided to design a comprehensive art and cultural strategy that, from the beginning, included communities in the territories to build scenarios for reconciliation and peace.

4.4 Participant Observation Approach

As a ‘participant-oriented’ research approach, IPA researchers are able to develop bonds with their participants; these bonds are settled through interpersonal and interactive relationships (Smith, 2009). It would be very difficult to establish a basic trust with the interviewees without

being on site for a period of time before the interview takes place. I was able to spend time familiarising myself with the participants, which ensured me to have a more spontaneous and comfortable interview when required. Moreover, as Mason (2002) claims, the experiences of people are essentially context-bound, which means that their context (social, cultural, political, historical, artistic) can influence the research study. For that reason, researchers must understand the socially constructed nature of the world and must realise that values and interests become part of the research process. This resonates with Taylor *et al.* (2020), as they claim that “research designs should also be attuned to the communities’ everyday realities, and in particular, an in-depth understanding of individual experiences of harm in the context of the conflict” (p.13). In this respect, the phenomenon cannot be isolated from the context (Yin, 1984; Stake, 2006), but instead it generates a deep understanding of the beliefs, values, and lifeworld of people.

A participant observation approach can facilitate empathy, allowing a greater flexibility of coverage and tends to produce richer data (Smith & Eatough, 2007). This approach supports the interpretation analysis process, because there is no better way to understand people’s lived reality than to be part of it. Employing participant observation makes it possible to discover the ‘hows’ and ‘whys’ of human behaviour in a particular context, correcting assumptions or predispositions from the researcher, and increasing the validity of the study (Nightingale, 2008).

As Crossick and Kaszynska highlight, “approaches concerned with how the world is experienced, in specific situations by specific people at specific times, seems an essential element in most approaches to the value of arts and culture” (2014, p. 123), acknowledging that capturing what happens in cultural experiences is not an easy task. Participant observation has some challenges (Kawulich, 2005), including being an insider in the group under study and, at the same time, interacting with the social context. Furthermore, the researcher has two different roles: one as a participant observer and other as a researcher, which means that while the researcher is participating in the daily life of the local community, they must also continue collecting data through interviews, notes, recording voices, and images.

Several techniques were employed to address these challenges in the research for this study. In order to develop trust in an environment defined by mistrust and fear, a fluid and constant communication with the directors of the case study projects was initiated six months before the

fieldwork took place. As Taylor *et al.* (2021) suggested, the research study can be put at risk if it is not considered to have collaboration and connections with local actors in post-conflict settings, since they are involved in the daily life of the communities.

Brayan Moreno, from the Ministry of Culture of Colombia, Rafael Ramos, a local leader and the coordinator of Sensory Expedition, and Jehico Castaño, founding member and director of Casa Kolacho, were informed by e-mail and telephone of the nature of the research and the interest in visiting and participating in their activities for two weeks. They knew enough about my proposed research in advance and were able to discuss it with me before I arrived on site to undertake data collection.

The two cases also had different expectations of my visit. The Sensory Expedition participants had high expectations of the visit. This was because those communities have been forgotten by the State, with some municipalities still not having access to basic services such as electricity, water, sanitation, health, and education. It is also an area that is difficult to access (I had to take a plane, boat, bus, and moto-taxi to get to some areas, as Figure 1 shows), far from urban areas and still dealing with problems derived from insecurity and drug trafficking.

Figure 1. Travelling by different means in the region of Montes de María during field work

Source: Photos taken by the author

Casa Kolacho participants had different expectations of my research because Comuna 13 is a highly visited destination, which is why the leaders felt optimistic that the findings of the study could be used to strengthen its cultural processes. In both cases, the participants expressed

gratitude that their voices and experiences were being taken into account. Likewise, Rafael Ramos and Jehico Castaño agreed that it was vital to visit the territory and get to know the context in which the arts and cultural process evolved, as well as the reality of its beneficiaries. In this way, it was possible to have a clear picture of the remnants of the war and the role that arts and cultural activities have been playing in facilitating dialogue, mutual understanding, and social cohesion.

In order to document the participant observation process, a descriptive narrative record technique was employed. While in the field, I kept a diary that included notes of everything I saw and a detailed description of the activities that took place. In the field diary, I also documented my fears, confusions, doubts and impressions of the participants, and their realities. This exercise was useful for understanding how my feelings influenced the research. This process also helped to record what behaviours occurred and to understand the context in which they took place. I was also able to document the different types of activities and perspectives related to the participants' experience with arts and culture, and to make an interpretation of the meaning of their lived experiences.

Spending two weeks in each case study location meant that I captured the richness and variety of participants' cultural experiences in a way that would not have been possible using other methods. For example, it was evident that in the case of Casa Kolacho their interactions were like a family — reflected in the use of the word '*casa*' or 'house' in their organisational name. In fact, participants called each other 'brother' or 'partner'. Participants clearly shared very strong and close relationships, which meant that a problem of one person was also a common problem. If any participant had economic or family problems, they would support each other in finding solutions. Also, if someone wanted to leave Casa Kolacho and start a new project, they supported each other to do so. It was interesting to see how strong bonds and a support network were built over time yet acknowledged that art was the path that brought them together.

To summarise, participant observation is a useful method for arts and cultural research, because it provides a route into nonverbal expressions of emotions, understanding how participants communicate with each other, and verifying for how much time is spent on different activities (Schmuck, 1997). This method allowed me to understand the perspective of the people under study, making visible the participants' worlds of experience, and observing events and situations that informants may be unable or unwilling to share or have described slightly

different in interviews (Marshall & Rossman, 1995). It also allowed me to have a full understanding of the context of the study, providing sufficient information about how transferable it may be to other contexts (Morrow, 2007).

4.5 Semi-Structured Interviews

The interview is probably the most widely used method employed in qualitative research, and semi-structured interviews are often understood as the best way to collect data for an IPA analysis (Smith & Eatough, 2007), because they open up and develop a relationship with the participants so that their ‘lived experiences’ can be explored and analysed. Their value lies in the fact that interviewees can tell their story in their own voice, and express their own thoughts and feelings (Smith, 2009).

Within this general context, individual face-to-face semi-structured interviews were undertaken in the two case study locations. IPA studies are normally conducted on small sample sizes (usually fewer than 15 participants). The aim of IPA is to explore perceptions and understandings of particular groups, providing a detailed and rich account of their experience and reflecting on it, rather than making more general assertions (Smith & Eatough, 2007). The focus is on quality, not quantity. For this study, a purposive sampling strategy with a sample group of three different informant groups was developed: direct beneficiaries, civil society representatives, policymakers, and donors (all the participants were adults, over 18 years-old). Three different interview schedules were designed, though the IPA narrative interview technique was implemented only for the direct beneficiaries of the art-based programmes, as it was here that the focus on grasping the essence of their experience was most important. As Taylor *et al.* argued, “conducting research in Colombia requires an in-depth understanding of the levels and forms of violence that have been and still are part of peoples’ everyday lives” (2020, p. 5).

Building on Holden’s theory (2006), the articulation between the public (understood in this study as individuals engaged in arts and cultural interventions), politicians and professionals are required to solve arts and fund policy dilemmas, avoiding misunderstanding and mistrust among them. That is why the point of view of all the different actors was within the scope of the study, in order to be aware of the dynamics of those groups, the synergies between them, and their knowledge in the area. With this information, a broader and deeper knowledge of the

value of the arts and culture in the particular area where the cultural programme was taking place, could be accessed and enabled the research questions to be explored in a more concrete way.

The first group of interviewees were the *direct beneficiaries* of the arts and cultural interventions in both case study sites, since they were those directly exposed to, and involved in, the arts activities developed in each setting. These beneficiaries had heard, felt, and lived situations related to their cultural experiences, and were best placed to articulate the meaning and impact of these. The recruitment process for these participants was initiated during the participant observation work in the field, which allowed me to meet local people and explain my research to them directly. Twelve people from Montes de María (two women and ten men) and ten people from Comuna 13 in Medellín (all men) were recruited for the interview based on their involvement in artistic activities (music, dance, or graffiti) for at least four years. Orientation and support from the local cultural agencies helped recruit participants and early enrolment led to recommendations for others to join too. To understand the effect of involvement in the arts and cultural programme in their lives, it was important to recruit people who had been involved in the project from the beginning.

The second group of interviewees was drawn from those responsible for leading and designing each cultural project in the region. Each project had one local leader and one cultural agent who implemented and coordinated the artistic and cultural activities. Both were contacted in advance to discuss the study. They expressed their willingness to participate and provided access to their project staff and participants. The objective of those interviews was to explore the strengths and weaknesses of the projects; the challenges they faced in developing the cultural activities, and the solutions they had implemented to address these problems.

Finally, eight further interviews were conducted with key *policymakers* representing the highest decision makers in the cultural and artistic field related to the case studies. These were people who designed public policies, were involved in the peacebuilding process, and played an influential role on the distribution of public resources. Because of their public status their quoting of the interviews is not anonymous, in fact their names and their job titles have been listed in this thesis.

NAME	POSITION
<i>Guioamar Acevedo</i>	Former arts director of the Ministry of Culture for eight years.
<i>Sergio Fajardo</i>	Former mayor of Medellín, former governor of Antioquia, and presidential candidate in 2018 and 2022.
<i>Frank Pearl</i>	Negotiator of the Colombian Peace Agreements, former High Commissioner on Peace, and presidential candidate in 2018.
<i>Juanita Goebertus</i>	Former congresswoman that was part of the Colombian government delegation in the peace process. Currently, Goebertus is the director of Human Rights Watch's Americas division.
<i>Gabriel Santos</i>	Former congressman, son of the former Vice-president Francisco Santos. Santos belongs to the party of President Iván Duque: Centro Democrático (Democratic Centre). Politically, Centro Democrático is on the right of the political spectrum.
<i>Álvaro Andrés Martínez</i>	Director of the Villa Mayor Theatre, who previously worked in the Ministry of Culture
<i>Miguel Barreto</i>	Director of the Observatory on Peacebuilding of the Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano
<i>Jairo Rivera</i>	One of the six leaders chosen by the FARC guerrilla in Congress with voice but without vote, in the development of the Peace Agreements.

Table 1. Policymakers interviewed

Source: Author.

Table 1 lists the interviews that sought to gather information about the priorities of the Colombian government, the reasons why they have reduced the budget to the cultural sector, and the strategies to use arts and culture as a tool for peace. In sum, 29 interviews were conducted for a maximum of two hours in duration. Recordings were made using an audio recording device. In addition to the recordings, I took methodological, theoretical and descriptive notes that contained information regarding the feelings and emotions expressed by interviewees during the interviews. Notes also allowed me to record procedural factors, including the problems encountered and subsequent modifications that were made. Theoretical notes were made to document the connections with existing literature. Finally, descriptive notes were taken to represent the story of the interviewees, including non-verbal communication cues, the tone of the interview, feelings, impressions, and emotions of both the participant and the researcher (Deslauriers & López, 2011). These notes were helpful to interpret the data.

The interviews with policymakers were conducted in the city of Bogotá. In the week these interviews were scheduled, ELN guerrilla led a terrorist attack with a car bomb that left 21

people dead and 68 wounded. As soon as I heard about the attack, I contacted my lead supervisor to let him know that I was fine, and that I would have to reschedule the interviews for the next week. Of course, he was concerned about my wellbeing and proposed the option of conducting the other interviews on a virtual platform, but it was very important for me to do them in person. This attack revived fears of past conflict; however, Colombians have grown up in a culture of violence and have become used to continue with their lives despite this type of situations. After being in Bogotá for a few weeks, I took a flight to Medellín to interview members of Casa Kolacho and — after that — I went to Cartagena to start my journey to Montes de María. In Medellín and in Montes de María, I had the opportunity to interview both participants of the projects and local leaders. The reason for the research design in this order was to allow the passage from a global frame to a specific one, listening to opinions and thoughts from the Minister of Culture and members of Congress, and to experiences and feelings from the direct beneficiaries of each project.

Two other factors in my choice to implement the research design were my nationality (Colombian) and my previous work experience with the Ministry of Culture. This helped me to get access to key contacts and to travel around the territory. Nevertheless, throughout the research process I experienced the reality of my country, encountering poverty, inequality, and communities forgotten by the State. This experience was very different from the privileged environment in which I grew up. All interviews were digitally recorded and then transcribed. This process was completed to catch the detailed content of what interview respondents were saying. All interviewees gave informed consent for the recordings, and notes were made during the interviews. Table 2 shows the number of interviews conducted and the interviewees categorised according to the groups outlined above.

CATEGORIZATION	CASE STUDY	NUMBER OF INTERVIEWS
<i>Direct beneficiaries and participants</i>	Casa Kolacho	8
	Sensory Expedition	11
	Total number	19
<i>Local leaders</i>	Casa Kolacho	1
	Sensory Expedition	1
	Total number	2
<i>Policymakers</i>	Total number	8
TOTAL NUMBER		29

Table 2. Number of interviews disaggregated by the groups interviewed

Source: Author

4.5.1 The Interview Guide

As is common for semi-structured interviews, an interview guide was developed with clear topics to be addressed. In order to make the process repeatable and documentable, the same interview schedule was used for all interviews within a defined interviewee group, because as Seidman notes, “the method of in-depth, phenomenological interviewing applied to a sample of participants who all experience similar structural and social conditions give enormous power to the stories of a relatively few participants” (2006, p. 55).

The interview guides were made up of 21 questions¹⁶. Policymakers and local leaders of the projects had the same interview guide, which consisted of four sections: i) *context*, here interviewees talked briefly about their position and their knowledge of the cultural sector; ii) *programmes and projects*, at this stage they explained the arts and cultural projects they associate with peacebuilding and reconciliation; iii) *successful measures*, at this stage they discussed the impact and benefits of art-based interventions; and iv) *lessons*, here interviewees shared their views on the cultural sector and the improvements required to strengthen their contribution to peacebuilding processes.

¹⁶ See Appendices 3 and 4 for interview guides.

The interview guide for the direct beneficiaries of the cultural activities had five sections¹⁷. The first two sections, i) *about themselves* and ii) *Colombian context*, allowed me to explore the daily reality of their lives, including routines and fears. The next section, iii) *engagement with the arts*, explored their level of involvement in arts-based interventions, and the changes participation in projects had brought about, if any. The following stages, iv) *programmes and projects* and v) *lessons learned*, addressed in more detail the strengths and limitations of the projects they had experienced.

As mentioned above, individual face-to-face interviews were the chosen method. The one-to-one interviews allowed interviewees to express their opinions more freely than if they had been interviewed in groups. Additionally, I was collecting personal stories, which are particularly suited to a one-to-one setting.

4.6 Data Analysis

Since the data was gathered in a non-English speaking country, all the interviews were translated into English, which means the study had to address the complexity of translation. As Seidman noted: “Finding the right word in English to represent the full sense of the words spoken in the native language is demanding and requires a great deal of care” (2006, p. 104). Besides, the fact that I am from Colombia, allowed me to identify words and expressions that may have double meanings, and that can be misinterpreted, as Taylor *et al.* (2020) mentioned, that can facilitate the translation work.

Once the interviews were transcribed in full, they were analysed using the IPA coding method, which focused on the structures of individual experiences and helped to provide rich descriptions of the impact of arts and cultural engagement.

For data coding, Alase (2017) suggests the application of three generic cycles that help to break down responses from participants into a manageable format. The first cycle was undertaken once the interview audio and written transcripts were listened to and read at least twice. Using this approach, it was possible to identify common themes and key words or phrases that were repeated or expressed by the participants. These were gradually transformed into meaningful

¹⁷ See Appendix 5

statements or sentences. The second generic cycle involved the identification of similarities between the first statements or sentences, in order to condense them into fewer words to move closer to the core essence or central meaning of the participant's lived experience. The final generic cycle was a phase that helped to narrow down the responses of the participants to extremely few words. This process serves to condense in one or two words the core essence or central meaning of the participants' lived experiences. The connections between these conceptual groups were explored in order to generate information that allowed the research questions to be answered.

After the themes were identified, each one of them was described and exemplified with extracts from the interviews, which allowed me to assess the pertinence of the interpretations and to retain the voice of the participants' personal experience. This was followed by a discussion section that related the identified themes to existing literature. Here, context played an important role, because it provided meaning to the analysis and interpretation of the interview material, helping to achieve an accurate analysis and interpretation of the responses aligned with the research questions.

As Alase indicated, "utilizing the generic coding method allows the researcher to meticulously and methodologically break down the participants' responses without diminishing or misrepresenting the core meaning of their responses or lived experiences" (2017, p. 88-89). To ensure the accuracy of the codes, they were previously discussed with my lead supervisor and thesis advisor. Also, both supervisors had access to my project in NVivo, which allowed them to follow my draft analyses and make recommendations based on their independent reading of the transcripts.

4.7 Ethical Considerations

The research was approved by the School Ethics Committee of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) School of Media, Culture & Society. Beyond the formal institutional ethical approval process, the following ethical issues were also considered: informed consent, issues of privacy, and whether deception was involved (Bryman, 2008).

The first ethical principle considered was the importance of being transparent about the purpose of the research. Once I met the participants for the first time, I introduced myself and informed

them of the scope of research. I also answered any questions they had about the research topic and my presence in the field. Additionally, distribution and explanation of the Participant Information Sheet¹⁸ was undertaken, assuring participants that all the collected data would be strictly confidential and anonymous. Some of my respondents — the directors of the cultural projects and the policymakers listed in Table 1 — waived their anonymity. I also communicated that respondent participation in interviews was entirely voluntary, and that interviewees could withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any questions they were not comfortable with. Appropriate consent forms were designed and translated into Spanish to be distributed among the participants to sign, thus participants were able to provide their informed consent before participating in the interview. Related to the first point, all the data were protected under the principles of the General Data Protection Regulations 2018. I alone kept, secured and had access to the data. All documentation was securely stored in a locked cabinet and on a password-protected computer.

The second ethical consideration was how to communicate findings with those people involved in the research. Out of respect and care for all participants in research, interview transcripts were shared with each respondent by email. This provided the interviewee with the opportunity to clarify the points they had made. Particularly, for the direct beneficiaries of the arts and cultural projects (many do not have Internet access), a debriefing session (see Figure 2) was organised after the fieldwork was completed, which provided them with an opportunity to comment on the early analysis of the data. By inviting them to a face-to-face meeting, it was possible to share the results of the interviews and receive feedback on their perceptions. It was interesting to hear how they all endorsed the results and agreed with what their peers had said. Everyone asked to see the thesis once it was published, as they were excited that their views were deemed important enough to be included in a case study.

¹⁸ See Appendix 1

Figure 2. Debriefing session with Casa Kolacho members

Source: Author

Content redacted due to lack of consent from photographed individuals

To disseminate the initial results of the research, a public conference was also organised, which included the participation of public policymakers, academics, researchers, beneficiaries of artistic processes, and cultural agents. This conference was designed to facilitate discussion on the value of arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process. Once completed, this thesis is going to be translated into Spanish. Furthermore, in addition to leaving copies of my work with the Ministry of Culture and the Colombian Peace Observatories, copies will be sent to all research participants and cultural agents so that the results are widely available to the general public.

Taking into account the social context where the research took place, and to reduce the potential vulnerabilities of the interviewees and the risks to the researcher, Rafael Ramos and Jaihco Castaño, from Sensory Expedition and Casa Kolacho, agreed to join me during the fieldwork. This facilitated access to the participants, their environment, and the projects. Furthermore,

their presence helped reduce the risks of visiting areas that have been severely affected by violence. The work completed in the field was to compensate for the relatively short time period in which it was undertaken (imposed by the challenging circumstances regarding safety in the field). Although some field work is carried out with police bodyguards and military accompaniment (Taylor *et al.*, 2020), it seemed to me very challenging and disruptive, as there is no state presence in these areas, and it could cause a negative side effect, as they are not always welcome in the territory.

The two case studies were located in different regions of Colombia: Comuna 13 is in Medellín, an urban area; in contrast, Montes de María is a rural territory. Nevertheless, both zones were highly affected by the armed conflict in Colombia and there are still traces of violence in these areas. The humanitarian crisis in Montes de María adversely impacts the lives of its inhabitants in terms of human rights, health, education, and basic sanitary conditions. Lack of electricity, running water, communication and health care did not represent a big challenge for me since my stay was not too prolonged, but lack of familiarity with the location meant I had to rely on local advice from Rafael Ramos, from Sensory Expedition, to secure accommodation and access transportation, particularly in the rural area on the seaside.

My research did not expose interviewees to any kind of risk. Precautions were taken in terms of data collection and analysis, ensuring the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants. The research protocols approved by UWS, such as informed consent¹⁹, were implemented in order to ensure that interviewees understood the scope of my research, the ways to contact me, and the promise to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Moreover, the approval and adherence to UWS protocols ensured my personal safety. The administrative procedures from the Resilience & Safety Team at UWS, to get approval to travel to Colombia and do the fieldwork, allowed me to identify possible risks to ensure they were mitigated to an acceptable level to allow insurance to be placed.

As I was travelling to remote rural areas where mobile and Internet connection is often limited, I arranged a very detailed and specific itinerary, whereby UWS knew my exact location, the time of my trip, where I was, with whom, and how I was travelling (flight number, hotel name/address and contact information of the people who were with me). Since I am from

¹⁹ See Appendix 2

Colombia, I was aware of the security problems and how to be cautious. However, I was in contact with my lead supervisor at each stage of my journey. Besides this, inhabitants and beneficiaries of the art-based interventions were enthusiastic about my research because they enjoyed the benefits of arts and cultural activities and wanted the interventions to continue. Some other rewards came from the development of friendships with people in the field, many of them thought I could not be from Colombia, as Colombian people never usually visit Montes de María.

I experienced strong emotions of impotence related to the precarious conditions experienced by some of the people I met and the atrocities they had experienced or witnessed, which they shared with me during conversations and interviews. However, at the same time, hearing about their experiences provided more motivation to continue my research, as the arts and cultural interventions were almost the only thing that change the impoverished lives of children, young people, families, and communities for the better.

4.8 Trustworthiness and Authenticity

Some scholars have argued that it is more suitable to evaluate qualitative research according to trustworthiness and authenticity (Bryman, 2008). Measures were taken to increase credibility and to ensure trustworthiness in my research. As “there can be several possible accounts of an aspect of social reality” (Bryman, 2008, p. 377), an important task for any researcher in social sciences is to ensure that the findings represent the lived reality of the research subjects. It was important to my study that the voices of the direct beneficiaries of the art projects were represented objectively, so as to ensure that even if the findings of one method were influenced by me as the researcher (thus, misrepresenting the reality and opinions of the participants), findings of other methods would steer me to the most appropriate conclusions. In addition, the data and coding process was auditable and checked by my lead supervisor and advisor to ensure that I have analysed it appropriately.

Authenticity is concerned with the wider political impact of the research. The research generated awareness around the importance of arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process. I was invited to present my preliminary findings in a variety of spaces (academic, professional, and political), and I was also invited to write at a local newspaper a few articles about the role of arts and culture. I was also part of a national radio programme talking about

the cultural sector in Colombia Blu.4.0. I have accepted for one year a role as development director of Batuta, an NGO that uses musical training (with a focus on collective practice from a perspective of social inclusion, rights, and cultural diversity) to contribute to improve quality of life for children, teenagers, and young adults in Colombia. Then for two years I was the Secretary of Culture of Ibagué, where I was in charge of coordinating and implementing the city's cultural policy and agenda. Currently, I am the Director of Batuta in Bogotá, the capital of Colombia. Through my research and my work, I have been able to amplify the importance of arts and culture as a tool that has an impact on the surroundings and lives of those who practice and enjoy it.

4.9 Conclusion

In this chapter I have explained the methods used in order to address the study's two research questions. Using the interpretivist paradigm, IPA engagement with participant observation helped me to get closer to the essence of participants' experience, to capture from the participants' perspective the role of arts and cultural activities in addressing the effects of conflict on people in different settings and contexts, by exploring how individuals perceive the particular situations they are facing and how they make sense of their personal experience. So, it was important to get closer to the participant's personal world and capture their insider's perspective. Here, one-to-one interviews facilitated an understanding of the human experience beyond artistic merit, the involvement with arts and cultural activities, and the attitudes towards it.

Using IPA helped produce in-depth findings from a local context (Colombia), which is a benefit for this study considering it allowed me to document the lives of groups of people who have shared particular experiences. Besides, the approach recognises that the power of arts and cultural interventions should not be overstated, which is why the aim of the in-depth interview work was not concerned with making generalisations to a larger population of interest, but rather was more inductive-oriented and emergent in its process. After explaining the methodological strategies for collection and analysis of the information, I discussed the decisions taken in order to deal with issues of research(er) risk in the field. The findings of the case studies will now be presented in the following chapters.

CHAPTER 5. PEACE ON THE GROUND, CASA KOLACHO

5.0 Introduction

This chapter is the first of two that present the case study findings that contribute to the analysis of the impact of art and culture in peacebuilding processes. The findings presented in this chapter focus on the case of Casa Kolacho, a cultural centre located in one of the most violent and dangerous neighbourhoods in the city of Medellín, Colombia. The findings are structured according to themes developed from the literature review, alongside others emerging from the fieldwork. Overall, findings provide a rich description of the role played by arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process in an urban context. Findings are drawn primarily from semi-structured interviews with local leaders, members of Casa Kolacho, and Dr. Sergio Fajardo, who is former mayor of Medellín (2004-2007), former governor of Antioquia (2012-2015) and former presidential candidate.

5.1 Casa Kolacho, Comuna 13

Casa Kolacho is a cultural centre created in 2009 as a mechanism for the social and cultural transformation of a territory that had experienced a stigma of violence for decades. The cultural centre is located in San Javier, one of the 19 neighbourhoods in the centre/west of the city of Medellín that, collectively, make up the Comuna 13²⁰. Comuna 13 is commonly known as a territory of artists and has become a mandatory destination for those visiting Medellín. In the Comuna 13 area, the sound of music has replaced the sound of gunfire, robberies have decreased as dance has increased, and the walls now carry colourful stories narrated by paintings, rather than painful memories imprinted in blood stains. The *comuna*'s inhabitants have laid down their weapons and have taken up aerosol sprays instead as a means of being heard and noticed. Cultural activities seem to be making a difference to people's lives in this area. The homicide rate in 2017 was 23 per 100,000 inhabitants, the lowest rate in three decades. The comparable rate in 1991 was 395 per 100,000 (Restrepo, January 1st, 2018).

²⁰ In Colombia, the concept of "*comuna*", reflecting the widespread notions attached to "*favela*" in Brazil, frequently evokes the idea of the precarious and dangerous places in a city. An expression of what Hélio Silva (2014) calls "stigma of localization", a conjunction between prejudice, absence of public power, segregation, geographical distance, and lack of guarantees of citizenship, among other aspects.

Comuna 13 is located at the western limit of the city of Medellín, on the city's border with the small villages of San Cristobal and Altavista. According to official figures, Comuna 13 is home to over 140,000 citizens — however, local authorities estimate that the real number of inhabitants is higher, a result of under-registration in some areas of the *comuna*.

Figure 3. Map of Comuna 13 in Medellín

Source: Author

Due to its situation in the world-famous hills of Medellín, the majority of the ground covered by Comuna 13 is located in the steepest parts of the city, reaching the highest point of altitude in Medellín at over 1,600 m.a.s. ²¹. The *comuna*'s geographical situation makes it particularly difficult for both civilian authorities and armed forces to cover the area, a factor that explains the configuration of Comuna 13 as one of the hotspots of violence and crime in Medellín.

Historically, Comuna 13 has been known as the most violent area in Medellín, and a strategic point for the transportation and commercialisation of drugs and weapons. Starting in the 1980's, the Colombian drug trafficker Pablo Escobar, head of the Medellín Cartel, took advantage of the experience of poverty and lack of opportunities that characterised the *comuna* to promote the culture of easy money among its inhabitants, particularly youngsters, who became interested in the profitable business of drug trafficking. For these youngsters, often members of families displaced by the local armed conflict, joining criminal organisations was the only feasible route to social mobility. Furthermore, as an upgrade from drug trafficking gangs, the *comuna* saw the formation of a network of hired assassins (*sicarios*) at the service of the drug business. These networks rapidly became the main source of personnel for activities such as kidnapping, extortion and orchestrated attacks against armed forces by the Medellín Cartel.

By the 1990s, Comuna 13 was the epicentre of violence and many other criminal practices including drug trafficking, robberies, selective homicides, and multiple human rights violations, which sparked large-scale confrontations between illegal groups and public forces. As a result of this context, poverty, misery, fear, and generalised violence intensified, becoming a unifying element within Comuna 13 (Sánchez, 2011). Also, fuelled by an absent State, characterised by a lack of capability to occupy territories with institutions other than the armed forces, these conditions rapidly absorbed the daily routines of Comuna 13 and its inhabitants.

In the mid-1990s, the Medellín Cartel was fragmented, but did not disappear completely. In the early 2000s, it was estimated that around 650 armed gangs continued to operate in Medellín, these included: three divisions of the self-defense groups (José Luis Zuluaga, Metro Block and Cacique Nutibara Block); two armed fronts of the ELN guerrilla; the independent militia

²¹ Meters above sea level.

People’s Armed Commandos, and diverse structures of the José María Córdova division of the FARC guerrilla, most of them located in Comuna 13 and its surrounding areas (Grupo de Memoria Histórica, 2011).

As a result, in 2002, Comuna 13 faced “the largest armed action [to take] place in an urban territory and in the context of the armed conflict in the country” (Grupo de Memoria Histórica, 2011, p. 80). Ordered by former President Álvaro Uribe Vélez, this action, Operation Orion, was carried out with the objective of dismantling insurgent organisations and retaking control of Comuna 13. In contrast to its objective, this operation left several detainees, missing persons and dead civilians who had become targets of armed forces (police and military) and paramilitary groups with influence in the area. According to official data, after Operation Orion violent displacement spiked to 1,259 displaced individuals, which represented a 797% increase in comparison to the previous year (2001), when this phenomenon affected 158 individuals (Historical Memory Group of the National Commission of Reparation and Reconciliation, 2011).

Operation Orion and its effects on the inhabitants of Comuna 13 undoubtedly shaped the history of the *comuna*. Years after the operation, episodes of violence continued, as Figure 4 and Figure 5 show, and, although youngsters led efforts to provide alternatives to war through music and other artistic expressions, these efforts were destroyed by the shadow of violence that transformed social leaders into victims of the armed conflict.

Figure 4. Number of homicides in Comunas 8, 13 and 16 in Medellín

Source: Adapted from material provided by Medellín Mayor’s Office

Figure 5. Intra-urban displacement in Comunas 8, 13 and 16 in Medellín

Source: Adapted from material provided by the Medellín Mayor’s Office

One victim of this violence was Colombian rapper Héctor Pacheco Marmolejo (a.k.a. Kolacho), who was murdered in the *comuna* on August 24th, 2009. In order to honour the work of Héctor Pacheco, a group of youngsters decided to create a cultural centre where they could continue and grow the legacy of their mentor. They created Casa Kolacho, an initiative which carries Pacheco’s artistic alias, and which allows children and teenagers of Comuna 13 to have a space in which they can escape the harsh realities of their *comuna*.

In the remainder of this chapter, I outline the importance of arts and culture in the construction of peacebuilding scenarios in Medellín’s Comuna 13. I foreground the role that the community plays in the consolidation and growth of cultural activities, including Casa Kolacho, and explore the way in which the local State has contributed to the promotion of culture as a tool for social development.

5.2 Casa Kolacho as a Peacebuilding Strategy

As the preceding section has shown, historically, Comuna 13 has been affected by a context of violence, crime, and despair. It is in these circumstances that Casa Kolacho came to fruition as a community-led effort in which local artists invest their work and resources to promote art and culture as tools for social transformation, despite the city’s violent context, and the ongoing

risk posed to social and community leaders. Through this initiative, artists promote the hip-hop movement (breakdance, rap, and graffiti) as a means for young people to express their voices and give visibility to the different problems that affect Comuna 13.

Casa Kolacho is a good example of the way some artistic expressions can become a tool for communities to work together towards common goals in the process of peacebuilding. It has been chosen as a case study because of the impact that their work has had in Comuna 13, contributing to the transformation in perceptions of the *comuna* from within its community, as well as nationally and internationally. Comuna 13 is no longer the most violent place to be in Medellín and has been transformed into one of the city's most important venues for outdoor tourism. Tourism to the *comuna* grew by an estimated 224% between 2017 and 2018 alone (Alcaldía de Medellín, 2018). This transformation can be partly attributed to grassroots efforts, including those by Casa Kolacho, which, through various forms of art and culture, works to provide children and youngsters with the tools to overcome violence and grow both personally and socially.

Using different forms of art, including graffiti and rap, Casa Kolacho has been able to reconstruct the narrative of violence in Comuna 13 from the perspective of the community, allowing members of the community to promote a narrative that contrasts with the previous narrative of violence in Comuna 13. For this reason, *comuna* residents have produced songs of resistance to the period of violence they lived through, denouncing violence in a democratic and non-violent manner. 'Almas en guerra' (in English: 'Souls at War') is one of the many songs Casa Kolacho beneficiaries have released that focuses on the armed conflict and their role in it, denouncing atrocious acts (Casa Kolacho y Jeihhco Caminante, March 9th, 2012). Furthermore, using visual arts as their main expressive tool, Casa Kolacho has given residents a voice through paintings, in which they portray the atrocious events that Comuna 13 has experienced. Casa Kolacho also promotes itself as a space in which memory-building can become the key resource to ensure that these atrocities are not repeated.

As a result of these efforts, the community has made it possible to promote spaces of tolerance and coexistence, strengthening and empowering young people. The participants engaged in these activities are being moved away from the world of crime, replacing violence with art as the perfect weapon, and immersing themselves in a peaceful environment that facilitates dialogue. These processes allow them to tell their own story in a non-violent manner and

denounce the social and political reality of the Colombian armed conflict. Remarkably, even without being recipients of any governmental aid, and after more than a decade, Casa Kolacho still offers free cultural and artistic activities to more than 250 youngsters annually. Here, these beneficiaries find an opportunity to escape the scenarios of violence and crime that remain in the city.

Many interviewees had witnessed violence at close quarters or had family members or friends affected directly by the conflict. From the observations and interviews I conducted in the *comuna*, it was clear that living in that area, in those conditions, had affected people's lives significantly. As a result, narratives of fear appeared repeatedly in the interviews conducted with local inhabitants. However, it was also clear that members of the community had developed resilience over the years, demonstrating a strong will to overcome anger and hate, and translate negative emotions into positive attitudes. These are the main features from which the construction of a culture of peace starts, rejecting violence as a way to solve conflicts. For example, a young artist from Comuna 13 that has lived in the zone since birth, worked as a visual artist for Casa Kolacho for eight years, and left his career as an engineer to pursue arts as his vocation, highlighted the impact that Casa Kolacho had in his personal growth:

Casa Kolacho taught me never to fail; it taught me what friendship and family means, it taught me that I am not alone and that conflicts can be resolved, with love, through arts. It taught me that everything can be achieved too, and that we have the power to transform our reality.
(Personal interview, January 2019)

After so many years of not being able to say what you think, or just trying not to be noticed for fear of reprisals, being visible was important to those interviewed. The self-esteem that comes from the recognition of being on a stage, painting a mural for the whole community to see or writing a song has made the community of Comuna 13 value the work that Casa Kolacho has done through the years, offering free workshops to bring children closer to art and keep them away from violence. A member of Casa Kolacho, who grew up with the organisation, and whose life project was to become a musician thanks to the project, mentioned:

Casa Kolacho is the opportunity to be someone, to say something and to express ourselves, to be referents. Through guidance, example, fun, colour, dance steps and beats, we attract people

to say what they want to say. Casa Kolacho saved my life, at a time when I didn't have many possibilities. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Jeihco Castaño, who is also a local leader of Comuna 13 and comes from a family displaced by violence, suggested that “when you are silenced, you explode” (personal interview, January 2019). Jeihco experienced the forced displacement of his family from the small village of Anorí, in the department of Antioquia. They had to move to Comuna 13 as a result of the violent conflict that directly affected his close family members. Jeihco remembers having arrived to the *comuna* when it was only a hill of dirt and little houses, an illegal invasion with “no rights and no duties”. He was there to see Comuna 13 fill up with families that, very much like his, came to Medellín to pursue new opportunities. He saw Medellín as a dream city, but rather found — in reality — a dark city with difficulties. Jeihco's story reflects the importance of finding a means to express and interact with others through words, rather than the violence that usually comes from silence and frustration.

Living in the *comuna*, observing the behaviour of residents and interviewing participants in Casa Kolacho's work allowed me to see how artistic activities led by this cultural group facilitated experiences that promoted contact between people. These encounters were important to develop a shared value system that focused on the regulation of emotions, optimism for the future, and finally, the acknowledgement of others. Each of these values makes a contribution to the consolidation of community-rebuilding in the *Comuna*. It also became evident that involvement in arts empowered local people, allowing them to grow stronger and more confident. Participants mentioned being able to exploit the talents they already had or that they wanted to develop further.

J. H., a young musician from Comuna 13 who saw three of his friends murdered for crimes related to drug-trafficking, and who found his future in music, said: “I was once talking with a guy who was affected by war and other very violent issues, and when I asked him ‘What is the biggest change in your life now?’, he said it was to be able to go out at night and take photos”. Statements like these would not have been possible during the period of violent conflict, when the risk of fear and violence enforced by local gangs was ever-present, particularly at night. Moreover, J.H. also said: “These kinds of events motivated me to turn to songwriting as a means for me to detach of all these negative feelings about what happened to my friends and the cruel reality of my *comuna*” (personal interview, January 2019). Finally, J.H. also stated:

All forms of art contribute in a different way, but arts related to expression through words not only contribute, but also avoid isolation. When someone writes literature, sooner or later they are going to get together with someone who writes literature because they want them to read it. The same thing happens with a songwriter, he must find people who listen to his pieces, and that interaction creates a relation between him and his audience, as well as with the environment that surrounds them. (Personal interview, January 2019)

This is a story that was repeated by youngsters who have lived their whole lives immersed in the context of Comuna 13, and who became tired of having criminal gangs or public forces taking control of their territory and their lives. In the post-conflict *comunas*, involvement in arts and cultural activities became a means of giving voice to all its inhabitants, encouraging the expression of feelings and emotions, and sharing them with others. Music and graffiti became highly important tools that youngsters started using to express their desires, dreams, hopes, and fears. The importance of having these alternative tools to express both positive and negative feelings is that they are key in the process of transforming conflict into personal growth. This is a principle suggested by Frank Pearl, one of the lead negotiators of the Colombian Peace Agreements and former presidential candidate, who in an interview suggested that:

When a society does not have democratic mechanisms to express those feelings, they are channelled through violence, the people who have those feelings are usually victimisers or victims, sometimes they express them by harming others, here is where art expressions can play a crucial role. You can perform a play where you express fear and anger, but you are not hurting anyone, you can compose a song about the conflict in which you express very hard feelings, but you do not hurt anyone, and in that process, you can also heal your spirit. (Personal interview, January 2019)

This idea that involvement in arts and cultural activities can act as a pacifying force for good, and as an outlet for other (sometimes negative) emotions, was also reinforced by Jeihco Castaño, who claimed that:

Art forms can help to make catharsis of so much shit that they've put you in your head. On the other hand, they help us develop a sense on how to connect. I believe that art allows anger, fear and pain to come out, without having to attack one another, and that is undoubtedly important.

The importance of the art of Picasso, for example, is not a matter of showing blood, but if you have a degree of consciousness, you see it reflected in a painting and you will know that it is not something you want to repeat. I feel that art can also mean memory, by telling and narrating a story. If you want to understand Medellín, or much of it, listen to rappers. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Emotions are an essential part of conflict and conflict transformation (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009). The regulation and understanding of emotions can foster new opportunities for productive conflict transformation. This perspective resonates with the responses of the members of Casa Kolacho, whereby their cultural interventions with young people created an environment where it is possible to interact freely and express complex emotions through different forms of art. In this context, conflicts can be transformed creatively, positively, and in a non-violently manner. Which means that all expressions of violence can be prevented or mitigated, and at the same time alternatives for the visions of the future can be offered, thus contributes to create a culture of peace, starting with the idea of a new reality (Galtung, 1996).

5.3 A Culture of Peace

A number of cultural practices, including mural paintings, music festivals, graffiti tours, art workshops, and producing or recording music, contribute to the transition from a divided past and terrible experiences to a sustainable peacebuilding process, where culture becomes a resource to alleviate anger, resentment and disillusion, and to guide individuals towards more productive emotional states such as trust, hope, and forgiveness, which is the basis for the construction of a culture of peace (Lebaron, 2011; DeNora, 2004). This new creative mindset implies a new way of solving problems, eradicating the culture of violence and war. This can be drawn out from the affirmations of a young visual artist from Comuna 13 and member of Casa Kolacho, who mentioned:

I did not choose the transformation only of the walls, but of my lifestyle, my way of seeing life and my way of acting, because when I started painting in my neighbourhood and with others from the community, I discovered that what I did with the graffiti was not only to paint a wall, but to transform the space; the need for people to leave fear behind, fear to cross walls and live there again. People were afraid to delete the messages that they had eliminated from the armed groups, they said that they were going to kill us for deleting that with graffiti, and now the *comuna* does not imagine a grey neighbourhood, but one full of colour. Here, graffiti is not only

a decoration, but part of the environment, and a resource to build memory, a part of being able to mourn, and to remember what happened; it also becomes a way of transcending beyond death. Seeing graffiti as a healing object has been one of the most important processes here. (Personal interview, January 2019)

This quote illustrates how the arts promoted a culture of peace and tolerance, allowing individuals to see beyond barriers and envision a future where past difficulties represent stepping-stones to future opportunities. As the participant suggests, painting not only transformed the artist, but also the space and the community around them. He also explained how the message communicated through the graffiti encouraged the wider community to overcome negative feelings and to consider a future free from the culture of fear experienced in the prolonged period of violent conflict.

In a similar manner, the appropriation of the cultural infrastructure provided by the government was a key element in this transformation. Some of the interviewees mentioned the Library Park²² as an important milestone in their lives. It was a public space, aesthetically pleasing, to which they were not accustomed, a space that was different to their previous reality. Two participants mentioned that when the library was inaugurated, they became interested in becoming librarians and others suggested that they had started reading books, which led them to be inspired to create songs. Finally, a member of Casa Kolacho from a low-income household, and who found a family in Casa Kolacho, said that the library helped them disconnect from their previous lived reality, creating an oasis — a quiet, healthy, and pleasant place — that they had the opportunity to visit:

We were not used to having beautiful spaces, and that represented the library, in addition to being a space of peace, of calm, and when you live in a house full of people — parents, siblings, uncles, nephews, grandparents — you need a space for yourself, and the library represented that for me, a place to connect with myself. (Personal interview, January 2019)

²² Library Parks, whose objective is to provide the city with quality public spaces that have cultural, recreational, educational, leisure and training for the city's less favoured communities. The Library Parks are not conceived as mere containers for books but as cultural centres, which are also connected with the social reality and offer development opportunities to the community according to the needs of the community. The first Library Park was built in San Javier in Comuna 13 in 2006.

The library offered access to a new cultural imagination for many and opened a new space where activities such as book discussions took place and where seminars and conferences were organised. Some interviewees mentioned these activities as important features that they had never experienced before: “I started participating in the books discussion sessions, and I meet smart people, this motivates me to be at their level and to have the habit of reading, which helps me be inspired to write songs”, said J.H., a young member of Casa Kolacho who has greatly appreciated the access to the Library Park and its activities.

Some people emphasised the way these initiatives motivate affirmations such as: “[...] art moves the membranes of my body; it motivates me in daily living. When it comes to understanding that there is a world outside waiting for you, erasing and ignoring negative thoughts, opening up to infinite possibilities if you wish”, suggested J.J., a 29-year-old father and boyfriend, informatics student, and Casa Kolacho founding member, who has grown as a musical producer and who coordinates the organisation’s artistic training processes. J.J. had been a close friend of ‘Kolacho’, the social leader whose murder was the point of origin for Casa Kolacho. He had had to navigate situations where schools had closed because the simple act of walking there was highly dangerous. J.J. had even witnessed the assassination of two people when he was on his way to a sports training session (personal interview, January 2019). This last quote aligns with the next section of the chapter, which explores the ways in which grassroots initiatives such as Casa Kolacho can be a determining factor in the strength of social fabric, along with the existence of a high level of associativity in the *comuna* where the art-based activities are implemented.

5.4 Determinants of Social Capital

In this chapter, it can be seen that Casa Kolacho is an organisation built on relationships of trust and reciprocity. This, in turn, contributes to the cohesion, development and wellbeing of the community in Comuna 13. The ability of their members to act and meet their needs in a coordinated way for mutual benefit has led to the creation of social capital. These interactions are the first step to bring divided parties together, working towards the same goal, rebuilding the social bonds broken during and in the immediate aftermath of the conflict. Others have shown that initiatives that generate cooperative interaction are a necessary ingredient for successful peacebuilding (Cohen, 2005).

The particular characteristics of Casa Kolacho's artistic and cultural interventions are founded on the principles of collective action. This means that having people from the *comuna* together in a peaceful-creative space opens up social skills for citizenship and promotes community involvement. Moreover, the study findings reveal that individuals were keen on the possibility of building social capital or becoming more involved in the community. Interviews with members of Casa Kolacho revealed the positive impact that arts had on them, and their families, making them feel competent by stimulating the acceptance of their self and by fostering the construction of positive peer relations. On this subject, J.H. said:

Being in Casa Kolacho gave me the tools to be more optimistic and make new friends. The most interesting thing was being able to meet others and know that they also had their art and skills, respecting our differences without any discrimination. (Personal interview, January 2019)

In this regard, LeBaron (2011) reached similar conclusions when arguing that artistic practice benefits some population groups more than others when it comes to wellbeing. Ultimately, Casa Kolacho's case demonstrates that the role of culture in peacebuilding is more effective if community-oriented values are promoted rather than focusing on individual motivation. This case corroborates art and culture's main function in peacebuilding, primarily through its ability to stimulate a system of networks, especially by building social capital and enhancing leadership and organisational skills, which in turn can foster bottom-up processes of collective action and revitalisation. This case exemplifies the way in which the collective practice of art, where all participants have a common goal, enables social interactions, and allows meaningful connections to be formed to help build relationships of trust, solidarity, and confidence. As D.C., a graffiti artist from Comuna 13, suggested:

I have managed to generate confidence in myself. When you finish painting graffiti and visualise it, you realize that you can solve many problems. Besides, it has led me to meet many friends, because since I started making art on walls, many friends and people from other cities came to me to tell me that they liked and admired my work. (Personal interview, January 2019)

As a spin-off effect of building community networks, Casa Kolacho's work with other local social organisations that work for the promotion of youth rights, such as Casa Morada and YMCA, promote new social organisations that demand freedom of expression, neighbourhood

autonomy and the withdrawal from the territory of armed actors, such as residual paramilitary criminal groups known as BACRIM²³ or the guerrilla-dissident criminal organisations. As a result, collective action shapes the construction of identity and a sense of belonging, which has allowed the creation of new community dynamics within Comuna 13, where violence and conflict are not only words, but also concepts that take second place when compared to cultural activities in the territory.

Hence, all members of Casa Kolacho see friends as family, and the cultural process actively provides guidance, mentoring and companionship to promote wellbeing within the *comuna*. In line with this, the amount of time and energy youngsters spend participating in cultural activities at Casa Kolacho also contributes to address other components of peacebuilding, including behavioural change, agreeing on common values and facilitating mutual understanding (as opposed to apathy, hate, fear, anger, resignation, and hopelessness). Since the transformation of emotions depends on situational conditions and processes, Casa Kolacho has used place-specific resources, including street art, to strengthen social bonds and encourage positive emotions of joy, recognition, belonging, confidence, trust, and enthusiasm in young people. They also seek to change young people's perception of their future, emphasising possibilities and hope over fatalism. These efforts to develop positive outlooks are important because emotions are related to attitudes and transforming negative emotions into positive ones can help to develop feelings of solidarity among young people.

The observation of Casa Kolacho and the interviews corroborated the idea that arts and cultural interventions can positively influence people's emotions and actions in relation to the conflict. Participants frequently described Casa Kolacho as their house, and their friends as their family. This illustrates how the collective practice of art generated a sense of community and solidarity towards an imagined better future. That is the case of one member of Casa Kolacho who has been part of the group since its creation, he is C.O. from Comuna 13:

Casa Kolacho is my house, my family. We needed to believe that this territory was from us, that it belongs to us. Fortunately, the rap band C-15 of Casa Kolacho help us build that path.
(Personal interview, January 2019)

²³ Acronym for *bandas criminales*, or criminal bands.

During my visit, I could see the respect that the community has for the members of Casa Kolacho, the affection — and, above all, the gratitude — for what they have done for the community. They greet them warmly, with a big smile on their faces, they know all Casa Kolacho’s members by name, and the members know all the children in the area by name too: they take care of each other. This sense of ownership and belonging has also spread to other citizens of Comuna 13 who — in turn — began to mobilise, supporting the initiatives of Casa Kolacho, and encouraging them to continue their work. Besides the reduction of crime in Comuna 13 since the creation of Casa Kolacho has been remarkable (See Figure 4).

5.4.1 Social Cohesion and Rebuilding Community

Findings from the Casa Kolacho case study also highlight the fact that it was conceived as a grassroots initiative gave it independence and autonomy in its functioning, and also provided it with legitimacy and sustainability over time. Its legitimacy came from not being recognised as a government-funded programme or a project that depended on the mandate of political actors to continue. However, because of a lack of State funding, Casa Kolacho’s cultural programme is often threatened by — mainly financial — structural constraints. The group is constantly having to fundraise in order to be self-sustainable. Fortunately, members of Casa Kolacho have transformed this potential limitation into a strength, as they have grown to be very resourceful and practical. By diversifying their sources of income, they have been able to assure their economic independence from government for almost ten years. This was confirmed by C.R, a 28-year-old artist who is a lifelong member of Comuna 13:

For many people in these neighbourhoods, the options are very few, and the violence will always look for you to give you easy money because everyone has a hard time here. For organisations like us, it is hard to run completely self-financed, however, we are here, not committing an act of vandalism, but making this our lifestyle and a way of subsidising our lives and our families. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Another crucial factor in the success and sustainability of Casa Kolacho is that its members are all well known in Comuna 13. This means that their words and actions have credibility across the community. Casa Kolacho members understand the everyday reality of living in the *comuna* where the cultural initiatives are organised. This credibility and recognition of their

work has allowed them to operate outside State control and to consolidate their work over a long period of time. As Jehico Castaño observes:

I see it as something that the community needed and asked for. For example, the creation of the Graffiti Tour was never meant as a means to earn money. So that is the magic of Casa Kolacho, which was not created only *for the community*, but also *from the community*, and us, with our experience we have learned to manage it and meet the needs of the community through it. In short, this is the little piece of creation that the *comuna* lacked. For me, the dream was always [for Casa Kolacho] to become a cultural point of reference, and that happened. For example, on December 24th (Christmas Day), many young people bought the *Comuna 13* T-shirt that we created, it is through those little signs that we perceive that we are creating some sort of a movement. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Repeated mentions of signs of belonging to the community and appropriation of the territory represent evidence of the ways in which culture has begun to play a transformative role in the life of individuals, shaping their past, present and future realities. In sum, through different spaces of cultural expression and social interaction, Casa Kolacho generates the conditions to create community, contribute to the construction of meaningful relations, and build opportunities for dialogue. In the case of Casa Kolacho, values such as trust, awareness of civic duty, and associativity, are strengthened and then used as facilitators of change in the community.

This argument supports Stokfiszewski's (2016) association of culture with the social domain, related to social cohesion and inclusion. From this angle, the empowerment of local people in peacebuilding has been a guiding principle for some scholars and practitioners (Fukushima, 2011; Lederach, 1996) to resolve disputes and promote consensus, which has a positive impact on the quality of peacebuilding interventions. Here, through arts interventions, Casa Kolacho has promoted a higher degree of local involvement and engagement, encouraging the diverse voices and supporting the establishment of other cultural organisations in the *comuna*. Moreover, the artistic activities developed under the leadership of Casa Kolacho transformed inhabitants of Comuna 13 into indirect beneficiaries of the arts performed by the project's members, thus enhancing the community-transformation effects of this initiative. This is evidenced in the words of members of the community such as D.P., who said:

With graffiti I also leave a message of peace, of union through colour, a message that is not exclusive, it is not for people who can go to a museum or pay the entrance to an exhibition, but the walls of the neighbourhood where they have to pass every day, brighten their life. Passing by walls with messages from armed groups is not the same as passing by walls full of colours with messages, full of love and wisdom; messages that are intended for children to grow up, with the true sense of neighbourhood that encourages them not to forget what has happened and not to repeat it. (Personal interview, January 2019)

In parallel to these processes, ownership and localised capacity building can have significant positive potential for the consolidation of peace. Lederach (2005) argued that peacebuilding cannot be imposed from outside, and that solutions need to come from within. In other words, interventions have to be grounded, and structures have to be built from below, involving people from all social levels. It often appears that State peacebuilding initiatives are applied nationwide as a homogenous formula for all the territories involved, rather than supporting local initiatives and adapting peacebuilding approaches to specific and contextual needs. As such, state-building becomes an uncoordinated effort, and becomes isolated from other socio-political dynamics in the territories. As argued by Miguel Barreto (director of the Observatory on Peacebuilding of the Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano), this approach must be avoided:

Another frequent problem is the relationship between “micro” and “macro”. You can perform wonders in a community, but if all the public policy of the country goes in the opposite direction, then the efforts end up failing to address the needs of the community. The way in which it should work, would be for the Ministry and the government to start contributing to the growth of an initiative that is already being executed. In contrast, the way it usually happens is that the government comes up with another “macro” idea, that is not in coordination and harmony with the initiatives that are already being implemented in the territory. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Measures taken at the central level to influence communities often fail to understand the reality of the situation experienced by the inhabitants of these territories, as the case of Sensory Expedition (Chapter 6) repeatedly shows. Moreover, given that the circumstances in which conflict occurs, or has occurred, are often emotionally charged, resolution and reconciliation efforts work best in emotionally rich situations. This offers a notion as to why people are sometimes reluctant to move forward and engage in initiatives, despite the fact that doing so would seem to be in their best interest.

This study's findings demonstrate how cultural activities can provide opportunities for people to enjoy public spaces, interact, and establish social networks. Forms of cultural expression, including music and graffiti, worked as stimulants of social interaction, helping the community to tackle isolation, and contributing to the creation of bonds among members of the community. At the same time, they also encourage a sense of belonging and place identity, based on their cultural values and common backgrounds. By bringing people together, they helped to increase public awareness, which is a core base of community empowerment for collective action. As statements from interviewees confirmed, Casa Kolacho became effective not only in providing an alternative for its participants, but also in producing community-wide effects such as positive public space appropriation (by using local infrastructure to tell stories through painting and graffiti) or public resource awareness by actively promoting the interaction between members of the community and public resources in Comuna 13, with the Library Park being the principal example.

This empowerment is what comes to define an active community, capable of acting together for collective profit and social change. In Casa Kolacho, music lyrics, colours and paints became the tools for members of the community in Comuna 13 to express themselves, become visible and transform their everyday realities and those of their friends, family, and fellow community partners. This can be seen through the perspectives of the beneficiaries themselves; for example, C.O., a visual artist, and member of Casa Kolacho, mentioned:

I find peace in my mind by transmitting the message of what I am doing to others through painting and art workshops, and by telling them that what we do here is done with love, and for love, that is the way to really transmit things. Art gives you the chance to work with the subconscious of the human being, providing you with a sense of calmness that blurs all other problems. Art is also an alternative for many young people to grow personally. Also, graffiti has helped improving the landscape in the *comuna* by generating community; art is also very beautiful because, especially in young people, it gives them an opportunity to open up to the world. (Personal interview, January 2019)

Along with graffiti, rap music was also used in Comuna 13 to create a sense of appropriation of the *comuna*. Here, rap lyrics are touched by the sensibility of many stories about home, the street, and the government, allowing a more direct approach to communities and individuals,

quieting fears and breaking barriers. This musical process had led to question a way of living that is different from the one they have been taught, it is the process of unlearning and having new visions. When seen from this perspective, these practices had a very particular role in fostering social connections and encouraging cooperation for mutual benefit. As an example, Jeihco Castaño said:

Something I came to understand about rap, which is very special, is that we did not want to be part of the problem, because in the 90s many (rap artists) were part of Escobar's cartel, or the guerrilla groups. Rap music in Medellín is now sounding and proposing, it does not stop in the resistance. In fact, that word bores me, because to resist is to *hold on*, and we are not just resistance, we go further and try to find happiness. If you are not happy, you are not able to go out and do your things, because when you feel shitty, you can't do anything. (Personal interview, January 2019)

24

Figure 6. Message of fear from insurgent groups: Dead to the 'sapos'

Source: Photo taken by Casa Kolacho

Content redacted due to lack of consent from copyright owner.

²⁴ It is a common and understood word in Colombia that means to be a snitch, a whistleblower, a traitor.

Figure 7. Casa Kolacho member painting over the threatening message
Source: Photo taken by Casa Kolacho

Figure 8. Wisdom graffiti from Casa Kolacho

Source: Author

Content redacted due to lack of consent from copyright owner.

The act of taking control by painting the walls of the *comuna* neighbourhood with positive messages, such as ‘*wisdom, breathing*’ (see: Figures 6, 7 and 8), or with stories related to what happened in the time of violence, allowed participants to develop ownership of the *comuna*,

which evolved to a sense of responsibility to take care of it and to encourage others to do the same. Casa Kolacho played a key role in this transformation, by becoming a point of reference for young people in the territory, earning the respect of the community, and motivating young people to join the initiative to participate in a community transformation that they could see and acknowledge. As a young musician member of Casa Kolacho contended, “I always say that living is more than breathing. I believe that hip-hop and arts can help build humanity and empathy. Contrary to violence, art makes a presence; that side of art, the possibility of becoming more human is the most important thing, the intimate” (personal interview, January 2019).

Making culture profitable is a way out of poverty and a way to avoid the temptation to join criminal gangs. The participants in Casa Kolacho started to do graffiti, which made them popular and aroused the interest of companies that wanted to hire them to make murals. In turn, members of the community became very proud of their *comuna* and invited their friends to visit, because for them Comuna 13 was not what newspapers were showing.

Using graffiti, they re-signified the *comuna*, and months later they created the graffiti tour to prove it. The graffiti tour, created by youngsters themselves, was initially conceived as a way of reducing the fear and stigma associated with Comuna 13 to show the other side of the community and how it had changed. Then came the idea of monetizing the tour and generating income from tourist visits, and then, the graffiti tour business was created. Through these earnings, Casa Kolacho has grown, and now functions as an organisation with a solid financial base. The house has a recording room, and continues to offer free workshops for young people, organising festivals and selling merchandise (pins, shirts, CDs, stickers) to be self-sustainable.

This self-sustainable business model has the characteristics of a social enterprise (Barrera, 2007), since there is an explicit aim to benefit the local community, and by doing so, they promote a sense of social responsibility at the local level. Although Casa Kolacho does not recognise itself as a social enterprise but as a solidarity economy, the organisation demonstrates the creation of economic and social value, where — because of their mission to catalyse social change — the latter predominates.

It is imperative not to underestimate the importance of public investment to address the systematic problems associated with conflict in the cultural sector. In the case of Casa Kolacho,

the promotion of a community ownership model empowered people to change their lived reality. Through its essence as an initiative that was created from and within the community, rather than an imposition or provision created by the local or national government, Casa Kolacho was able to build a sense of ownership around social development initiatives. This has proven to be more popular (and thus successful) than political patronage or short-term State investment. Sharing an experience, and being a part of its growth, rather than merely participating in an experience that has already been created, brings meaningfulness and purpose to the participants' engagement. As one visual artist from Comuna 13, and member of Casa Kolacho, stated:

Arts should not be instrumentalised to achieve a goal, but people should invest in art simply because it is good, not waiting to seek a specific return. I was born with people who were displaced from other places in southwest Antioquia, who arrived in very precarious conditions, and who came in search of new opportunities. And it was through art that they — and I — were able to overcome that. I believe that my art moves people in a very positive way, and that through it, people can realize that the world is an endless number of opportunities to work more on themselves. (Personal interview, 2019)

Despite access to available evidence from the community about the value of cultural initiatives in the *comuna*, for some national policymakers (even for those who recognised the transformation of Comuna 13) it always comes down to measurable indicators. As Congresswoman Juanita Goebertus said:

[...] a clear example is Comuna 13 where, in reality, establishing baselines has been a successful effort, in this way, it is possible to study the impact in a much more quantifiable way, to see how effectively it contributes to reduce violence, generate spaces for passive coexistence, and promote scenarios to solve conflicts in a concerted way, among others. (Interview with Juanita Goebertus, 2019)

Contrary to this approach, other politicians and researchers believe that not being able to quantify impact does not mean that the effort does not exist or that it did not happen. As Guiomar Acevedo asserts: “There is an element of peacebuilding that has to do with symbolic, intangible elements. When you get to a place and hear comments about how this changed their life and how they have broadened their horizons, you see culture as a flower in the desert, that’s when we see a real result” (Interview with Guiomar Acevedo, 2019).

Casa Kolacho can be seen as an example of the latter, in the sense that regardless of indicators measurement, or even policy evaluation, it has evidently produced an impact in the community. Moreover, thanks to Casa Kolacho's young members, community residents now recognise the importance of culture, public space appropriation, and the construction of meaningful narratives on memory and peacebuilding. The recognition of these factors and the importance of individual and communitarian participation is, by itself, a non-measurable indicator that shows a growing will to overcome a history of conflict and pain, and an evolving effort to enable the development of Comuna 13 and its inhabitants. Even if these efforts are not translated into positive numbers in a spreadsheet, they are key to the transformation of the spirit of a community.

5.5 The Value of Culture for Policymakers

To comprehend the role that the community has played in the (re)construction of social development in Comuna 13, it is paramount to analyse the role that the local government has played in supporting these initiatives and other policies dedicated to the socio-economic growth of Comuna 13. This can help to shed some light on the way in which the city has embraced arts and culture as valid mechanisms for the promotion of peace and reconciliation.

According to the Medellín Municipal Office, between 2016 and 2018, 33% (170 million pesos) of the total investment made by the local government in Comuna 13 was allocated to educational initiatives in the *comuna*. A similar figure, 32%, was allocated to health insurance for citizens of the lower strata (1 and 2). Similarly, social and family inclusion initiatives received 14% of the public budget destined for the *comuna*. Preservation and construction of sports and recreational infrastructure benefitted from over 2.2 billion pesos in investment (Alcaldía de Medellín, 2018). These numbers are important, because they demonstrate a consistent volume of social investment from former Mayors Sergio Fajardo (2004-2007), Alonso Salazar (2008-2011) and Aníbal Gaviria (2012-2015). Despite different political affiliations, each mayor understood the importance of social investment in the city and the need to turn it into a city-wide policy rather than a personal or temporary effort.

Between 2016 and 2019, Comuna 13 also received over 44 billion pesos through the Participatory Budget Programme. The Participatory Budget Programme was an initiative

created by Mayor Sergio Fajardo in 2007 and maintained by every city mayor since. Formalised through Decree 0697 in 2017, this programme is a mechanism through which the Mayor's Office can maintain a constant and meaningful dialogue with the community, by allowing selected members of each *comuna* to work alongside officials to plan how to spend up to 5% of the budget assigned to the *comuna*. Through this programme, decisions on which projects and sectors will be prioritised are taken by the community itself. Participatory budgeting is an example of a process that enables residents to take a greater stake in a bottom-up public policy scheme in which they become key stakeholders, ensuring that community needs, and demands are addressed effectively.

The existence of the Participatory Budget Programme is an example of active democratic participation from citizens in city building and public resource management. For the past decade, it has proven to be one of the most popular policies initiated by the local administration. Through its implementation, members of the community have been able to decide on the allocation of up to 13 billion pesos annually. The process of budget planning and allocation, encompasses six stages: i) dissemination of projects, ii) prioritisation of projects through a discussion-decision process between local government officials and local citizens, iii) allocation of the budget, iv) support and incorporation of Participatory Agreements, v) inclusion of the results of Participatory Prioritisation in the Annual Investment Operating Plan, and vi) registration of projects, initiatives and allocated resources to the Project Bank. Once these six stages have been completed, the resources are invested in accordance with the community-Mayor's Office agreements and are monitored by traditional accountability reports carried out on an annual basis.

Upon review of local investment reports facilitated by Medellín's Mayor's Office, it was possible to assess how the community of Comuna 13 allocated resources through the Participatory Budget Programme. As shown in Figures 5 and 6, the inhabitants of Comuna 13 showed a noticeable preference for investment in social development programmes over more traditional approaches to public spending, including defence and police.

Figure 9. Participatory budget allocation for Comuna 13 by sectors

Source: Adapted from material provided by the Medellín Mayor’s Office

As shown in Figure 9, the resources allocated to Comuna 13 through the Participatory Budget Programme were heavily focused on areas related to social development, while security corresponded to barely 0.3% of the total expenditure. Similarly, as the sixth most important sector, and taking 7.5% of the total expenditure over a 4-year period, culture was one of the sectors with the highest funding expenditure.

Figure 10. Investment on culture by the Comunas in Medellín

Source: Adapted from material provided by the Medellín Mayor’s Office

Figure 10 compares the resources invested by each of the *comunas* over the 2016-2019 period. Comuna 13 allocated the sixth highest budget to investment in culture. This is perhaps surprising when bearing in mind that security and criminality continue to represent the biggest challenges to Comuna 13. Furthermore, this commitment to cultural investment also stands out when compared to Comunas 7, 8, 11 and 16, which are also peripheral and representative of violence and crime hotspots in the city of Medellín. Investment in culture in these *comunas* is significantly lower than the investment undertaken by Comuna 13 (Figure 10). The increasing interest to invest in culture is not only limited to the *comuna*’s local context, it is also shown in the investment made by Medellín’s Mayor’s Office. Further, this commitment is not only seen during the 2016-2019 period, but also — even more significantly — between 2004 and 2011.

Figure 11. Annual investment in culture

Source: Adapted from material obtained from the Medellín Mayor’s Office, the Ministry of Culture, and the National Planning Department

Figure 12. Percentage of the annual budget invested in culture 2004-2019

Source: Adapted from material obtained from the Medellín Mayor’s Office, the Ministry of Culture, and the National Planning Department

Figure 12 shows the level of resources assigned to Secretariat of Culture of Medellín, compared to the resources allocated by the Ministry of Culture and the national government. The same data is presented in Figure 12, but in terms that show the percentage of the total annual budget invested in culture. Over the 2004-2007 period (which corresponds to Sergio Fajardo's administration in Medellín), the investment in culture was almost equal to the amount of resources allocated by the national government to the Ministry of Culture for the whole country. The city of Medellín, therefore, invested significantly more in culture than Colombia as a whole in any region of the country. This trend is also found in Figure 12 that shows that in Medellín the percentage of budget invested in culture was significantly higher between 2004 and 2011, when compared to the investment made by the national government in the cultural sector. The following years show a similar trend of expenditure between the local and national governments with almost identical fluctuations between years. The years of 2007 (Sergio Fajardo) and 2009 (Alonso Salazar) stand out as those in which the gap between the national government and Medellín's Mayor's Office was the greatest.

Despite the different political ideologies that have characterised the elected mayors, these investment figures clearly demonstrate that the local mayors in Medellín strongly believe in the value of cultural activity for the city. Significant expenditure in Medellín's cultural sector has been a constant feature of every recent city administration. This commitment is also corroborated by the empirical enquiries carried out for this study in Comuna 13. For example, Jeihco Castaño noted that "the Secretariat of Culture of Medellín has doubled the budget of the Ministry of Culture of Colombia since the time of Fajardo, because these guys bet on it without fear" (personal interview, January 2019). Although official figures show that the proportion does not match the claims made by Jeihco, it does show that the inhabitants of Comuna 13 believe that the local government is committed to strengthen the provision of culture in the city, significantly surpassing the efforts made by the national government in the same sector.

Former Mayor Sergio Fajardo was emphatic in his defence of how his administration understood culture: not only as a right for a good quality of life, but also as a permanent exercise of citizen pedagogy, self-regulation, respect, and solidarity (Instituto Cervantes, 2010). Fajardo was aware that a process of learning that took place through the encounter and interaction with others was necessary for the city to be able to meet these expectations. For this reason, his administration identified the need to build new public spaces that facilitated the coexistence —

and the dialogue — of members of the community both in the *comunas* and in the city as a whole. These spaces, and the exchanges that can occur within them, are seen as ideal tools for peacebuilding through dialogue and the acknowledgement of others and their interests.

With these ideas in mind, Fajardo spoke of large investments in specific urban projects located in the peripheral areas of the city, under the slogan “The best for the humblest”. These projects were put in place as a way to ensure social justice and social inclusion, and as a means to repay what was interpreted as a historical debt to Comuna 13, which had been marginalised and stigmatised for years. Fajardo said that the construction of these facilities was an effort to “change the skin of the city” in the long run. Consequently, in 2006, during his administration, the first Library Park in Medellín was opened in Comuna 13. The library was subsequently named “José Luis Arroyave Restrepo Library²⁵”, in honour to one of the most important community leaders, and to characterise the venue as an open space to express art in all its forms. According to Fajardo, the Library Parks have managed to give the most deprived communities a sense of identity, pride, and progress.

Investments of this kind became more and more frequent in the territory of Comuna 13, continuing through different administrations that saw these efforts as central to urban policy, rather than a politically motivated investment programme. Anibal Gaviria (2012-2015) invested more than 65 trillion pesos²⁶ in 20 infrastructure works in Comuna 13 alone. Perhaps one of the most well-known investments was a complex of outdoor electric escalators. These were the first of their kind in the country and had resulted from an investment of 10 trillion pesos. This feat of social infrastructure construction has improved mobility for more than 12,000 people, who no longer had to go up and down 350 steps to get to Comuna 13.

Local government investment paved the way for culture to become a key element in the rebirth of Comuna 13 as a territory where the narrative of violence and crime could be progressively replaced and overcome by the use of arts as a tool for social transformation. Like many other initiatives that benefitted from this investment, the founders of Casa Kolacho saw an opportunity to contribute to and lead the process of re-building Comuna 13 by using music and

²⁵ José Luis Arroyave was one of the priests who knew most about Comuna 13, which has been violently disputed between militiamen and paramilitaries, was murdered seeking peace in Comuna 13. There, more than a peace advisor, he was a community leader. A man loved and respected by all the community in Comuna 13.

²⁶ Converting to euro currency would be equivalent to 15 Billion Euros.

visual arts as a means for young people in the community to express their feelings, needs, expectations and stories in an attempt to create dialogue through the construction of memory and free expression.

The transformation of Comuna 13 through art and culture represents a hybrid between public investment to revitalise the area physically and a commitment to the right to culture as a means of social transformation. This commitment to culture was endorsed by a 24-year-old visual artist, a member of Casa Kolacho, who has always lived in Comuna 13 and who began his career as a photographer with a mobile phone camera. He said: “It is not the same to invest in art to see results than to invest in art to help build that result” (personal interview, January 2019). This quote illustrates the strength of will of the community, and it is this will that eventually led to the creation of projects such as Casa Kolacho; a group of young people who experienced violence, but who also worked to promote the dynamism and appropriation of their *comuna* through art, thus creating a peaceful territory. This transformation took more than a decade and it required both government assistance and the efforts of the community itself.

5.6 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have illustrated the importance of grassroots collective initiatives to empower people and revitalise neighbourhoods, recognising arts and culture as a force that motivates conflict resolution and enables peacebuilding. The case of Casa Kolacho demonstrates that investment in capacity building, developing local ownership and emphasising sustainability, can lead to the empowerment of residents affected by conflict. Empowering local people to participate in shaping their own future is crucial to the successful design and implementation of peace operations, to prevent future conflict and to rebuild societies that overcome violence, which is exactly the work that Casa Kolacho has been doing for ten years: creating a space for empowerment.

The Casa Kolacho case demonstrates the importance of empowering local actors to take the lead in planning and implementing programmes. This local capacity pushed members of the community to have an active local ownership of the territory and of the cultural process developed from within. Furthermore, it is paramount that this increased local ownership is channelled through a form of collective action, thus facilitating the emergence of social

interactions that can become crucial in re-establishing community relationships and bonds that may have been damaged by conflict.

Moreover, the findings of this case study demonstrate that cultural activities can further promote the building of social capital. Here, the positive influence of the key components of social capital, such as the ability to act cooperatively, involving norms of reciprocity and trust, contributes to foster social cohesion and community rebuilding. Notably, it was possible to promote a sense of belonging, civic awareness, and civic responsibility through such means as shared community values and a widespread desire to promote social transformation through the cultural activities carried out by Casa Kolacho.

Ultimately, the process plays a crucial role in the formation of new young community leaders within the territory, who are committed in expanding and replicating grassroots initiatives similar to Casa Kolacho, and who are able to nurture and promote a new vision of what the future should be. These new leaders also develop leadership traits that enable them to motivate others to transform their reality as well. In a practical sense, the cultural interventions in this case develop collective self-esteem and allow the beneficiaries of the process to recognise each other's qualities, which is a decisive factor in building a culture of peace.

The findings of this case study also demonstrate that while emotions can energise conflict, they can also neutralise it. In order to neutralise conflict, specific and intentional attention to healing, growing or transforming is required. This is necessary to ensure that sufficient strength will emerge to bear the weight of what reconciliation requires in a post-conflict environment. Moreover, based on the information obtained through the personal interviews, it can be inferred that cultural activities are more significantly associated with the social capacities of citizenship. The coming together and amalgamation of these efforts have played key roles within the *comuna*, reinforcing the idea that the arts, education, and social development are (and will continue to be) the tools that drive the transformation of this highly conflict-affected area.

Finally, government-led initiatives such as participatory budgeting, the creation of the public library park, and initiatives led by community organisations such as Casa Kolacho (that promote the appropriation of public spaces and the creation of a sense of civic responsibility and a shared interest in social development), have also been key in promoting spaces in which dialogue, acknowledgement of others, the construction of memory and reconciliation are all

possible. It is through these processes that the way is opened for the construction of peace scenarios in Comuna 13.

CHAPTER 6. SENSORY EXPEDITION: PEACE FROM THE BOTTOM TO THE TOP

6.0 Introduction

In the previous chapter, I presented the case of Casa Kolacho as a grassroots initiative created by community leaders in Comuna 13, one of the most violent zones in the hills of the city of Medellín and in Colombia. I also showed how social initiatives born within a community can successfully transform the social realities of people in a particular place. I illustrated the importance of governmental investment in Comuna 13 to promote spaces and initiatives that allowed social transformation and social development to take place, along with the work of local advocates and activists.

In this chapter, I present the case of Sensory Expedition, a project delivered by the Ministry of Culture since 2016 in the area known as Montes de María, located in the northwest of Colombia, between the coastal departments of Sucre and Bolívar. In this case, I highlight governmental efforts to tackle an historic disconnection between local projects and national politics, and a lack of strategic coordination between different grassroots projects trying to address local peacebuilding processes. Sensory Expedition represents an attempt of the national government to address that disjuncture, inviting the local community to play an active role in the construction of a social project implemented in the peacebuilding context.

There are three main differences between these two peacebuilding initiatives. First, Casa Kolacho operates in an urban area, while Sensory Expedition runs in a rural area, and in Colombia this is a very marked difference due to the low level of development in rural areas. A second factor is the people who carry out the project: Sensory Expedition is executed by a public entity (the Ministry of Culture), while Casa Kolacho is a community initiative. A third factor lies on the artistic practices carried out in each project, which correspond to the realities and traditions of each context. The music and dance practiced in Montes de María are not the same as in Comuna 13. Although both areas were direct victims of the armed conflict, and both projects were conceived to establish a culture of peace, the ways of doing so are different. These differences make it interesting, since it shows the diversity and adaptability of the arts-base practices in various contexts.

The chapter is divided in four sections. First, the context of the territory known as Montes de María, and its importance in the armed conflict of Colombia, are outlined. Second, the Sensory Expedition project is summarised, describing the way in which its construction and execution is informed by the circumstances of the local communities that benefit from it. Third, I present findings drawn from personal interviews and observations that shed light on local inhabitants lived experiences of the project. Finally, I conclude the chapter by arguing that this project represents an innovative attempt by the State to tackle the effects of the perpetration of violence in the region of Montes de María.

6.1 Montes de María: The Face of Armed Conflict

The region known as Montes de María is a sub-region of the northwestern departments of Sucre and Bolívar that cover an area of 6,297 square kilometers, distributed evenly between both departments. The region consists of three geographically distinctive areas: a coastal area that connects the region with the Atlantic Ocean, a mountainous area with hills of over 1000 m.a.s.l., and an area of plains delimited by the Magdalena River, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Map of Montes de María

Source: Author

Due to its geographical location, Montes de María is a natural transit zone for goods and people travelling between the centre of the country and the Caribbean Sea coastal area. Commercial roads run through the territory, and the Magdalena River (the main commercial waterway of Colombia) is the natural limit at the east of Montes de María. As a result of the combination of these features, the region has long been one of Colombia's key zones in matters of trade and commerce (Comisión Colombiana de Juristas, n. d.). Although these characteristics would normally be perceived as positive signs for the economic development potential of a region, they have been the basis of intense armed conflict in the country. There are two significant factors that explain the importance of the region for the historical development of the armed conflict in Colombia.

First, the region of Montes de María is crisscrossed by crucial commercial roads; it is home to two routes that facilitate the transit of both people and commercial goods between large industrial cities in the centre of the country and large port cities on the Caribbean coast. As a point of connection between the centre and the Atlantic coast, Montes de María has always been a natural crossing point for the illegal transport of goods. These practices usually start in the rural areas of the south of the country, where guerrilla and paramilitary groups carry out drug production activities. They also include the Caribbean coast, where drugs and weapons are smuggled through illegal ports and the Caribbean Sea. As a result, control of the area was paramount for illegal groups during the 1980s and 1990s, when drug trafficking became one of the main activities that armed groups used as a means of financing their paramilitary activities (PNUD, 2010).

Second, the bordering departments of Córdoba, Sucre and Bolívar have traditionally engaged in economic activities related to cattle and livestock farming — activities that require the ownership and control of large areas of land. The origins of the conflict in Colombia are related to land control and the historical expropriation of land, a factor that explains the reason why, when guerrillas focused on land control, the country's ranchers and farmers became their main targets (PNUD, 2010). Consequently, these factors also explain another reason why paramilitary groups, heavily financed by livestock production businessmen, began to grow considerably in the Montes de María region, particularly during the 1990s. The emergence of paramilitary groups as a third actor of the armed conflict subsequently proved to be one of the factors that aggravated the violence experienced in the region.

Even though paramilitary groups had been a part of the armed conflict in the country since the 1980s, their activities were closely linked to business relations between rural businessmen and drug cartels that provided security to these businessmen in exchange for money and properties (Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica, 2018). The first attempt to create an organised paramilitary group originated in the departments of Córdoba and Sucre, where the Castaño family²⁷ created the Autodefensas Campesinas de Córdoba y Urabá²⁸ in 1994. By 1996, a total of seven paramilitary organisations had already been created in the region (Comisión Colombiana de Juristas, n. d.), and in the late 1990s these groups had already grown and merged to form what became known as the AUC, with influence across the entire national territory.

In the specific case of Montes de María, the configuration of this three-sided conflict (that included the national armed forces, the regionally established guerrilla groups, and the newly-formed paramilitary groups) made the region of Montes de María the epicentre of bloodshed, death, and power disputes. As a result, the region was the site of over 50 massacres between the late 1990s and the early 2000s. One of the best-known among these was perhaps the massacre of El Salado. This massacre was perpetrated by 450 paramilitary soldiers from 16th to 22nd February 2000, in the small town of El Salado (department of Bolívar). It is estimated to have claimed the lives of 60 people in what is considered to be one of the worst acts of violence by a paramilitary force in the country's history. The town of El Salado became a ghost town after the massacre, all the inhabitants left the territory to escape the episodes of violence that had become so frequent in the region (Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica, 2009). The episode of El Salado is just one of over 40 massacres perpetrated by the paramilitary groups during a 5-year period between 1996 and 2001, in which 354 people lost their lives (Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica, 2009) in small towns just like El Salado. These included the massacre of San Juan Nemopuceno (12 dead), the massacre of María La Baja (11 dead) and the massacre of Macayepo (12 dead).

The violence of the 1990s continued, with an average of 400 deaths for the year 2000. This morbid trend impacted negatively on the once prosperous region of Montes de María, which saw a 49.5% reduction in its population, from 867,891 inhabitants in 1986 to 438,119 in 2011 (Fundación Ideas para la Paz, 2011). A total of 158,000 people were reported to have been

²⁷ Brothers Carlos, Vicente and Fidel Castaño Gil.

²⁸ Peasant Self-Defenders of Córdoba and Urabá Córdoba and Urabá.

displaced for reasons directly related to the armed conflict, and over 82,600 acres of land were completely abandoned as a result of the escalation of violence experienced by local populations (Consultoría para los Derechos Humanos y el Desplazamiento, 2018). As a result of the context of violence that the region endured during the 1990s and the 2000s, in 2017 reports showed that, on average, 41.3% of the population was affected by poverty, compared to a national average of 28%. Further, rates of illiteracy in the region were 23% on average (DANE, 2017).

The national government recognised the severe and long-term impact that events leading to the late 1990s had on the region. Consequently, the government invested heavily in the territory in order to mitigate the effects of violence and conflict on the different towns and municipalities of Montes de María. As a result, numerous government-led initiatives were established during the 2000s and 2010s. The Sensory Expedition project was one of these. To better understand the significance of the Sensory Expedition project for the communities themselves, I travelled to different towns in the region of Montes de María (see Figure 13) to conduct a series of face-to-face interviews with project participants who shared their personal experiences of the project's impact on their lives and their communities. The lived experiences they shared with me form the basis of the following section.

6.2 Sensory Expedition: A State-Led Effort towards Peacebuilding

As an early response to the escalation of violence experienced in Montes de María, the departmental governments of Bolívar and Sucre, along with the Office of the High Commissioner for Peace and the Ministry of Education, launched an initiative called 'Plan for the Integral Development of Montes de María'. This initiative, completed in the year 2000, was meant to be a locally designed strategy that would serve as a roadmap for all initiatives that the national government wanted to carry out in the region.

What is also remarkable here is that in Colombia peacebuilding efforts often have been overwhelmingly top-down and state-centric, concentrated on enhancing and consolidating the power of the State. This assertion is supported by Nilsson, who agrees that "Colombian efforts have been focused on strengthening the State's capacity, legitimacy and control over its territory, rather than on inclusive peace" (2018, p. 41). She also implies the ongoing debate on the relationship between state-building and peacebuilding, and the need for a top-down rather than bottom-up approach to increase resilience.

In line with the National Development Plan of *Seguridad Democrática*²⁹, the national government named the region of Montes de María as a ‘Conciliation and Rehabilitation Zone’. This recognition translated into a significant increase in the presence of armed forces and military operations in the region. As a way of maintaining a form of social investment within these strategies, the national government received the assistance from the United Nations. This helped to create a sustainable human development programme in 2002. Further, the assistance was obtained from the UNDP to create a Peace and Development Programme in the region. These strategies guided social investment projects delivered in Montes de María.

During the remaining period of former President Uribe’s administration, government-led efforts in the region focussed on addressing the conflict by strengthening defence capacities and deploying military force to dismantle criminal organisations. Between 2007 and 2010, the national government spent a total of 44,697 million pesos on social initiatives focused primarily on economic development, emergency humanitarian aid and the protection of property. At different stages of the armed conflict, the type of investment changed. Governmental investments increased with successive peace dialogues between the national government and the FARC guerrilla, and with the subsequent signature of the Peace Agreements by the parties.

Following the end of the armed conflict, governmental efforts in Montes de María have made a positive impact over the years. Sensory Expedition is the latest of these efforts and is the outcome of an evolution in how social investment projects have been designed and implemented in the region. The Sensory Expedition project is one national government-led initiative that aims to address the spiral of violence that started in the 1990s in the Montes de María region. The project uses arts and culture as a way to build new relationships among communities affected by violence, and to foster community reconciliation to deal with the legacy of the past.

As in other regions of the country where high numbers of illegal armed groups were present, in Montes de María there was a clear transformation in the national government’s approach to

²⁹ *Seguridad Democrática*, or ‘democratic security’, denotes the security doctrine established by former President Álvaro Uribe Vélez during his administration (2002-2006 and 2006-2010). Created in 2002, the doctrine was intended to focus governmental efforts on strengthening national defence capacities. It positioned military operatives as the principal exponents of its strategy to combat guerrilla groups throughout the country.

social development programmes as a response to the armed conflict. Rather than being formulated at a desk in Bogota, the government moved towards formulating projects with the communities expected to benefit from them. As a result of this change in thinking, the Sensory Expedition project was established in 2016. Led by the national government through the Ministry of Culture, Sensory Expedition is intended to strengthen cultural capacities in towns and municipalities that have been significantly affected by violence in the region. When established, the project acknowledged two key issues that needed to be addressed:

- 1) the negative impact that the armed conflict had on rural communities, which produced a generalised uprooting of cultural heritage and traditions, and
- 2) an absence of a consolidated institutional offering to address the needs and interests of the regions' citizens.

As a result, the project was established to focus on strengthening culture as a key resource to enable communities to rebuild social trust networks, promote human development, and protect the universal right of access to culture (Ministerio de Cultura, 2016).

6.2.1 Sensory Expedition's contribution to peacebuilding

From its conception, Sensory Expedition was intended to contribute significantly to the transformation of the Montes de María region. Its main goal comprised establishment of a peaceful and democratic society that can transform relationships between members of the community. Hence, the project sought to support collective research (i.e. co-production) for the reconstruction of cultural memory and the recognition of the region's cultural assets. Since cultural traditions and celebrations had been ceased during the conflict, one of the project objectives was to revitalise the artistic and cultural practices of the communities. Considering that bringing the community together again around a celebration of a dance or music festival, or a training artistic process, can help to re-establish the social fabric of the community that was broken during the period of violence.

In the Montes de María region, the effects of violence produced a fracture of social and cultural bonds. This was reflected in the absence of recognition for extant cultural and heritage practices. This circumstance also led to a lack of collective capacity building and limited levels of the social participation required to transform people's living conditions. Furthermore, these

factors also contribute to low levels of social capital and to a lack of the sense of belonging and rootedness in the place. Sensory Expedition faced a major challenge when it came to building trust and the acceptance of difference as the basis of future reconciliation and peace. Using art and cultural practices as tools, the project sought to facilitate peacebuilding, inter-community bridging, intra-community bonding, and confidence building. The project's methodology and approach acknowledged that local contexts have specific needs. If they aim to engage suspicious communities and address effectively the long-term consequences of conflict, artistic and cultural interventions need to adapt to these specificities (Ministerio de Cultura, 2016).

A pilot for Sensory Expedition was carried out in 33 of the 137 municipalities of Montes de María, between 2016 and 2018, with a total of 1,872 children and young people involved in dance and music training sessions. The training programme was equipped with 647 traditional music instruments, 55 band instruments and 1,352 dance costumes. In addition, the training programme and festivals organised in association with them contributed to the local economy, through the recruitment of 483 people between 2016-2018 in event production, stage make-up, costume making, and maintenance of instruments.

The region had suffered the direct consequences of the armed conflict. As one of the very few governmental initiatives ongoing in a region where half of the population does not have sufficient resources to cover their most basic needs, the project also faced various challenges (*Verdad Abierta*, October 10th, 2021). Concurrently to the implementation in Montes de María, Sensory Expedition was also established in the Pacific and Catatumbo regions (both significantly conflict-affected territories). From 2016 to 2018, the Ministry of Culture invested 4,094 million pesos in Sensory Expedition. This has supported the local economies, for example, by hiring local manufacturers for the production of traditional music instruments (see Figure 15) and dance costumes, and for the preparation of meals with traditional cooks.

Figure 14. Music instrument made by the instructor

Source: Author

Content redacted due to lack of consent from photographed individuals

With the aim of contributing to peacebuilding scenarios with culture as the core element, Sensory Expedition promotes artistic expressions including dance, music, theatre, and other visual arts. In this project, collective practice becomes the centre of the pedagogical strategy. It implies permanent reflection on the application of methodologies and techniques aimed at finding collaborative solutions to specific problems in repertoire learning. The artistic result, as a paradigm of social achievement, gives relevance to the input of all participants in the artistic training process and the showcasing of the results.

Moreover, the fact that the instructors were from the same community and territory meant that there was a sense of ownership of the project, which brought together children, adolescents, and adults. The project became the only space for the community to come together and share, offering not only a safe space for the community to gather, but also a sense of belonging, because the children were learning about their traditional culture, music, and dance. The selection of the dances or instruments they played were context-related, which means that they varied between municipalities.

Besides, in a place like Montes de María, where there is a lack of social cohesion and poor physical and social infrastructure, there are few or sometimes no opportunities for a better and

stable future, which in some way is what the project aims to achieve: encourage awareness of having the right to better opportunities in a healthy environment. The project supported the community in the organisation of festivals that served the purpose of spreading cultural expressions to the region. All these actions sought to encourage bonding and bridging among members of the community. Thus, rebuilding the bonds of trust, as well as achieving the consolidation of memory and reconciliation in the region.

6.2.2 The Structure of the Arts-Based Project

In order to gain a better understanding of the Sensory Expedition project and its impact, it is important to explain its structure. First, the Ministry of Culture held meetings and workshops with the proposed beneficiaries. This was done to learn first-hand about their expectations, desires, fears, and to build a project for the region together. Some important points were identified in these meetings. It was decided, for example, that workshop leaders should be drawn from the same community as the attendees to ensure credibility and ownership. For this reason, the Ministry of Culture selected artists from each of the municipalities where the project was implemented. These artists were hired as teachers or workshop leaders, and the Ministry provided them with training on pedagogical techniques and the objectives of the project.

The recruitment of teachers from the area where the activity was to be implemented also served to ensure capacity and sustainability after the end of the project intervention. Based on this training, and in the local knowledge of these recruits, the project could be shaped and influenced by the specific context of each area. For example, while the Ministry hoped that each workshop would have a minimum of 30 children's attendees, in some areas numbers were lower due to the composition of that municipality. Additionally, each community chose to utilise specific art or cultural forms depending on their traditions. These choices included the instruments played and the genre of music or dance that they preferred to practice and safeguard. Thus, although municipalities mainly practiced dance or music, they could select the type of dance or music they wanted to safeguard.

When the Sensory Expedition project began, communities were both expectant and grateful that, after more than 50 years, there was a commitment to investing in art and culture in their area. The project opened up channels of communication between people within communities who had lost trust in each other. The dance and music classes encouraged children to learn

about their cultural traditions and safeguard the cultural practices of their ancestors. Adults accompanied and supported these processes. Sensory Expedition also supported entrepreneurship, traditional kitchens, weavers, and wise men who narrated their stories in order to transmit and safeguard their local and regional knowledge.

6.2.3 A Local Social Transformation

These efforts have produced important outcomes, giving Montes de María's inhabitants the ability to make their expressions visible; not only at the regional level, but also countrywide. Some of the successful products of the project include the musical production *Maestros y juglares de Montes de María*, the theatrical play *Mako: retorno sin fuego*, and the art exhibition *Donde trinan los mochuelos*. Further, thanks to the efforts made through the project, the results of the creative collaborations and production processes have been showcased at Bogotá's International Book Fair in both 2017 and 2019, and annually, at the Caribbean's Cultural Market from 2017 to 2019 (Ministerio de Cultura, 2016). This is important, because when an armed conflict is prolonged, local people become isolated from the outside world. According to some scholars (Lumsden, 1997; Gielen *et al.*, 2015), cultural activities serve as a means to connect the area of conflict with the rest of the world. The platform created by art and culture provides links between citizens in conflict zones and those beyond the shackles of war. As armed conflicts often destroy or distort self-identity and demolish cultural traditions, cultural interventions can help restore and re-establish symbols of cultural identity, whether tangible (i.e. a historical monument) or intangible (i.e. performing art).

In Sensory Expedition, members of the community were able to come together on different tasks required to support the musical activities. For example, women participated in the design and production of costumes and decorations. Men were responsible for arranging chairs, adapting spaces and helping in heavy duty activities. Youngsters were responsible of ensuring the quality of performances and group activities. These unifying practices became regular thanks to the way the project was executed, creating spaces in which family ties were strengthened and communal bridges were built. Since the project was cost-free and open to the public, people had few material barriers to be part of it. This helped to unite people from different social groups, even from the *comuna* itself. People experienced this cultural space as a meeting point where, despite their ideological differences or the role they had during the periods of violence, they had a joint cultural project.

For example, when talking about the accomplishments of Sensory Expedition, Guiomar Acevedo suggested that:

What we have been able to achieve in Montes de María is remarkable. There, because of violence and conflict, all artistic expressions were completely eradicated, so community members did not have a way to express their emotions in a healthy environment. Thanks to the project we were able to bring back those scenarios, and it has allowed community members to express their view of the recent past, thus contributing to the efforts of memory-building in the community, and by extension, enriching the knowledge that we have on the impact of armed conflict in these regions.

Sensory Expedition quickly provided the space in which different families came together as one community. During the armed conflict, there were no festivals, concerts and public displays of cultural tradition, because people had little reason to celebrate in the midst of fear and so many deaths, threats and massacres. For decades, people did not hear the sound of guitar or drums publicly. One of the specific objectives of the Sensory Expedition project was to recover cultural expressions that were lost during the war. That is why, when music was played in Libertad, a town with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants, people came out of their houses to watch and listen. Previously, they had stopped listening to music in public places such as squares, streets and parks. Using music, the activities carried out in Sensory Expedition brought communities closer, opening up new future possibilities while also helping people recover what they had before the conflict.

6.3 Sensory Expedition: Through the Eyes of the Community

“Expedición Sensorial, por los Montes de María, es para la tierra mía proyecto trascendental, para el tejido social, su cultura y su folclor, preservar la tradición, sus costumbres, sus vivencias; fomentando convivencia para construir nación; estrategia cultural, cultura y cabildo que ha habido conflicto, apoyen zona rural y con esto resaltar sus activos culturales, riquezas patrimoniales, sus saberes y memoria que hacen parte de la historia en estas comunidades” (Oscar Contreras, musician, 39).

Sensory Expedition, through Montes de María, is a transcendental project for my land, for the social fabric, for its culture and its folklore; to preserve its traditions, its

customs, its experiences; promoting convivence to build a nation; cultural strategy, culture, and political discussion where conflict has existed. Support for the rural areas, to highlight their cultural assets, their patrimonial treasures, the memory, and knowledge that is part of the history of these communities³⁰.

The first quote is the original Spanish of one of the verses of a song written by Oscar, a 39-year-old musician and songwriter who opened the doors of his house and family to me. I was able to learn more about his life and personal background. Oscar works with Sensory Expedition in the towns of Macaján and Pueblo Viejo, and he uses song verses in more than half of his answers. Oscar is just one of the artists in the region who have obtained artistic knowledge through empirical learning, has enriched his abilities on the basis of the opportunities that the project has offered, and whose daily subsistence depends on the project's development.

The opening quote perfectly reflects the way the community of Montes de María perceives Sensory Expedition. It is a project that has been important to transform the everyday realities of people in the region. The project has also been highlighted as a success from the perspective of governmental institutions and their efforts to address structural violence. Sensory Expedition is the latest initiative of the Ministry of Culture that aims to contribute to the social transformation and social development of Montes de María. With this project, the Ministry and the national government faced the challenge of effectively using social investment to address the needs and demands of local inhabitants in a region that had been immersed in conflict for the past 20 years. Indeed, this situation was still evident in the testimonies of participants. As suggested by Luis, a 31-year-old musician who worked with Sensory Expedition in the small town of Pueblecito, in the department of Sucre: "I came to have a rifle in my hands, thank God I did not have to shoot or kill anybody". Luis was one of many people I spoke to who had to come face-to-face with the violence that engulfed the region in the early 2000s. Barely 13-year-old at the time, Luis was already a victim of conflict:

When I was 13 years old, there was some sort of law that allowed the recruitment of children between 10 and 15 years by paramilitary groups. They took me and detained me for almost three months. I had to wait for the end of year festivities and managed to escape from the place

³⁰ Translation by the author.

where they had me and other children. After I escaped, I did not communicate with my family for two years, because I was scared that they [the paramilitaries] would hurt them if they saw me alive.

Luis highlighted the importance of the arts in helping him to overcome this traumatizing experience: “[...] thanks to art, I managed to enrol myself in a project that allowed me to finish high school, and to acquire some artistic knowledge that I started to use and develop empirically. This knowledge allowed me to participate in other spaces and grow personally”. Similar stories to Luis’ were recurrent in Montes de María, where the armed conflict affected the lives of individuals and had a negative impact on the relationships between its inhabitants. Overall, participants’ opinions on the impact of the project create a positive view of themselves, which fosters self-empowerment and self-confidence, and helps to change their perception of their future. As said by Miguel, a 24-year-old rap artist from the small town of Libertad, in the department of Sucre, the armed conflict was a catalyst for the worsening of the relationships between different generations:

Because of conflict, we, the teenagers, became stigmatised and marginalised; we were seen as the drug addicts and conflict makers. No social reunion had teenagers invited; everything was controlled by the elders; we simply weren’t part of those spaces. As we became aware that this was something that should not be happening, we started looking for alternatives to re-introduce youngsters into the society. Rap and music were the means that allowed us to do so.

Figure 15. Libertad Music Process

Source: Author

Content redacted due to lack of consent from photographed individuals

Visiting Miguel's home (see Figure 14), and interacting with his family, his commitment to his town became clear — a town where children have to walk shoeless for hours just to get water and where poverty is endemic. Miguel's project in Libertad is supported by Sensory Expedition. The Ministry of Culture manages the project through a cultural organisation based in Montes de María. This organisation hires the music and dance teachers, and also purchases the instruments, as well as providing financial support for the beneficiaries of the programmes and teachers to travel to festivals and other events. It is through participation in these events and public presentations that many of the children benefiting from Sensory Expedition leave the town for the first time and meet other children from other territories, who, without knowing it, belong to the same region. In these scenarios, there is an interesting exchange of knowledge that enriches the training process, but also personal growth, where everyone is part of the same territory, and their points of agreement are more than their differences.

In Libertad, Sensory Expedition is the only space available in town for people to interact with any form of art and to access social development initiatives. As in Libertad, the conflict has affected the social dynamics and habits of entire communities. Night-time lockdowns imposed by armed groups have even conditioned the hours available for social interaction in towns and municipalities across the region of Montes de María. As Daniel, a 36-year-old accountant and

life-long inhabitant of Ovejas, in Sucre, highlighted: “[...] when I entered the university, everything here was marked by violence, we had dinner at 4:30 p.m., lights were completely off by 5:00 p.m., there were no cultural or social spaces at night, everything was completely silent”. His tainted memories of the past have been completely transformed by the existence of Sensory Expedition. He continued: “[...] when Sensory Expedition finally brought a cultural space after ten years [of absence], it allowed people to take back control of that space. Suddenly, you were able to sit next to someone with whom you had never spoken before and start a conversation around art and music”. This comment highlights one of the main findings of this case study: that the local population in the region valued the reconstruction of coexistent spaces provided by the project.

However, the project did more than recover tangible, physical spaces. There is evidence that it also had an impact on the reconstruction of social bonds and on the (re)formation of mutual trust among members of the community. According to Oscar, a songwriter who created the verse included in this section’s introduction, music played a key role in this rebirth. As he states:

[...] culture brings people together. When you come to a community carrying an instrument, people instantly know you are a good person, and they feel comfortable approaching you. Culture connects people, even in violent contexts, when you bring music with you any negative perception is blocked, because through music you carry joy. (Personal interview, 2019)

As Oscar suggested, the communities in Montes de María learned to transform music and culture into synonyms for safety and wellbeing: “This expression may be a cliché, but it’s real; whoever holds an instrument will never hold a gun”. In a context where guns, violence and bloodshed were a daily routine, the act of replacing guns with instruments helped to rebuild bridges between and within the community, building trust and confidence.

Furthermore, by rebuilding these bonds of trust, the project contributed to a change in the perception of others, while giving participants access to an emotional safe place, they could use to express their feelings, fears, and dreams. The creation of a safe space helped the project to move forward in the construction of memory. As recalled by Luis, one of the instructors of the project: “In one of my classes, I had a 15-year-old who was sexually abused by her father when she was 12. In one of our classes, she told me that she was scared of coming close to me

because she feared that I would do something inappropriate. A lot of confidence in people is required for a girl to openly say that she was abused and to do it in front of 20 of her classmates”. As Luis recalls, this was the tipping point for other participants to understand that the project was a safe space in which they could express their feelings and unburden themselves: “When the other kids heard that, they did not know what to do, but some of them started to share their own stories, many of them cried while doing so. There was one point where I had to talk one-to-one with each of them, to calm them down”. This was a clear example, on how emotional regulation and expression can be fostered through the arts as a fundamental aspect of rebuilding the social fabric: recovering networks or creating new ones to break isolation; and generating positive experiences with others to help regain trust and a bond with society.

As in Luis’ case, most of the instructors involved in Sensory Expedition started making music without even knowing how, simply by exploring feelings and expressions, and using voices and instruments to express themselves. This is an approach they share in their classes and activities, where they invite members of the community to see music as an extension of their feelings, rather than as a perfect discipline. In this regard, César Palacio, a 33-year-old instructor of Sensory Expedition from Ovejas, suggested:

[...] yes, there is an awareness among students that, when done properly, music can be a means for them to develop both socially and economically. But, for a lot of them, involvement in music starts by simply having a healthy hobby or having a socially supportive space in which they can express their feelings and explore their traumas and fears. When this outcome is possible, theory and excellence are a secondary goal.

The opening of new spaces (physical and psychological) has meant that the project has allowed children and adults in the community to re-engage with their emotions: the same emotions they had previously had to repress in order to survive during the violent conflict. Expressing these views allowed participants to realise that they were more alike than they thought. Sharing spaces with others who also had fears, traumas, and bad experiences to deal with was cathartic. As César, one of the instructors of Sensory Expedition, articulated: “Here in the project, participants were initially very shy and quiet, they did not express very much. But when they started to understand that everybody feels the things that they feel, they became more confident,

more open, suddenly they started to sing, dance, laugh and play, there was a spark that ignited inside them”.

I also found evidence that participants’ confidence in the project, especially the establishment of a space where their feelings were important and could be expressed, led to significant improvements in their personal lives. By providing teenagers with alternative leisure time activities, the project helped them to escape from negative practices that had become normalised in their lives. As disclosed by Chelly, one of the instructors of the project in the town of María La Baja and a mother of a 5-year-old boy: “There was one kid who told us that he was a drug addict, but when he talked to us, he said that he came to the project because when he was here playing his instrument, he completely forgot that he needed to smoke. When he was in the group, he did not need to use any drug or smoke anything”.

As Chelly testifies, for her having the opportunity to use her free time differently was key, but the sense of belonging that the project gave her was even more important. Again, Chelly related that:

[...] when we talked to the kid’s mom, she recognised that her son was always alone at home and that he had stopped using drugs because what he needed was to feel that he was a part of something. He needed to feel the affection of others, and he was able to feel that when he was participating in the project.

This sense of belonging produced positive effects in individuals and among members of the community. People from the community talked about participating in a project that created a bonding and bridging opportunity that they did not have before. As Oscar expressed:

[...] when the elder people started to see the transformation of young people, they became interested in the project, so we started to have elder wisemen, healers and craftsmen participating in the project. Thus, enabled a knowledge exchange between young and old participants, which allowed the whole community to be integrated through the project.

In addition, the project contributed to the strengthening of networks within the communities, while promoting the formation of personal links between members of the different communities. This was the case for Luis Morales, a 26-year-old instructor who served as a

Sensory Expedition teacher in his hometown of Sincelejo, the capital city of Sucre, and in another small town 30 km away. When talking about the ties he had created thanks to the project, he said: “It’s been already a year since I stopped buying a lot of my groceries because every two weeks, I receive a pack of groceries that they [project participants with their own allotments] cultivate there, and that they send me because we built a relationship that went beyond the project and became a friendship”. He added: “When I was working within the project there [Sincelejo], I bought 100 or 200 fish and shared them with the families of my students. To this day, whenever I go, I have to bring a big bag with me because they always give me presents that I cannot say no to”.

Testimonials from the participants are cited by the founders of Sensory Expedition as proof of success. As suggested by Guiomar Acevedo, the arts director of the Ministry of Culture from 2008 to 2018 and one of the directors of Sensory Expedition:

Things in Montes de María have never been easy, which is why it is important to be able to reconstruct these ties of trust among community members, they allow us to fully understand the history of what has happened in the region, and from that we can start to build a new society that becomes committed to the non-repetition of the mistakes of the past.

Then, she added:

Precisely what we did using culture as the mean of intervention in the region, was to bring back a core element of the communities that was taken away by conflict, and even though we expected positive outcomes, we were really surprised by how the investment that we did saw itself amplified by the will of the community to promote the project. Thanks to these high levels of involvement, we have seen how processes of confidence-building, bonding, memory construction and peacebuilding have accelerated through time and have overcome our expectations.

Local members of the community also agreed with these feelings, mentioning the positive impact the project has had on strengthening the social fabric of the community. As Luis again stated:

This project has even helped to reconcile people that had been fighting for many, many years. There are cases of people who have been fighting for over five years because of family

problems, and thanks to the spaces the project has created, they have been able to talk to each other and have been able to resolve their differences, just by expressing themselves and being open to listen to what the other has to say. This is something that authorities would never be able to do, simply because these are issues that they do not care to resolve.

Similarly, Oscar reflected on how even the language they use in their activities is purposeful and related to the objective of reconciliation and bonding. He exemplified this phenomenon by singing one of the verses that he often sings with students in his classes:

Te invito a que no peleemos, a que seamos hermanos, así juntos seremos mejores seres humanos, convivencia pacífica, la tomo con agrado porque yo miro al otro como territorio sagrado.

I invite you to avoid fighting, to become brothers, that way we can be better humans. Pacific coexistence, I hold it dearly, because I see others as sacred territory.³¹

Through this type of verse, Oscar emphasised the positive interactions between his students, and the importance of building trusting and respectful relationships between them. He added:

Whenever I see two kids who are going to start a fight, I joke with them and start singing ‘*Pacific coexistence, I hold it dearly...*’ and all the others start singing with me. Then, we invite the kids to hold hands to make them understand that each one of them is a sacred territory that must be respected.

These examples highlight some of the strategies the project uses to ensure that participants understand the goals of Sensory Expedition. These approaches also enable participants to comprehend their role in improving their community by emphasising values and principles such as optimism, empathy, empowerment, and creativity.

By providing spaces for meaningful, productive, and educational human interaction, the Sensory Expedition project enables individuals and communities to take the initiative to challenge the *status quo* and work towards a more just, humane, and peaceful future. The project invests in arts as a means to foster dialogue and leadership, leading to the cultivation of

³¹ Translation by the author.

personal growth, relationships and skills that can drive meaningful change. The project also encourages and supports individuals and communities, helping them to lead practical and positive efforts to transform conflict and to do what they can to accelerate their work. For example, by composing a song about hope, respect for life, and good values together with the members of the project, people not only work to produce the song, but they also sing it, interpret it, dance to it, live it and understand it. This process, in turn, has a positive effect on their behaviour and in how they see life.

Through the interactions that participants have with their families, friends, or acquaintances outside the project, Sensory Expedition aims to bring the values and principles it promotes to the majority of the community. One of the challenges the project faced, both in its conception and execution, was to understand how it could avoid being seen as a controversial initiative or a meaningless effort designed by remote government officials at their desks in a distant city, and instead, becoming a unifying force in the region. Evidence from this study suggests that the professionals in charge of the project turned this challenge into one of its main strengths and successes. As Guiomar recalls:

[...] all projects that were presented at the Ministry of Culture were social projects with the word post-conflict included in their titles. However, they did not include a single reflection on the way in which the project was going to impact post-conflict scenarios, or the way in which the communities were expected to perceive the project. That was the reason why I got upset and said, ‘no, we have to do this the other way around’.

This affirmation has become one of the key components for the project’s success, in the sense that it is not conceived as a professionally designed intervention imposed on the region from outside. Instead, is an effort designed from the bottom-up. Sensory Expedition began by identifying the needs, interests, and idiosyncrasies of local communities. Once this process was completed, its planners began producing methodological and practical activities that could serve the inhabitants of Montes de María. At the beginning, the communities were reluctant, due to long held distrust in institutions and to believing that organisations always start something, but do not finish it: “[...] they come for a few weeks and then leave, we [feel] used”, according to one project member in Libertad. The Ministry of Culture was aware of the frustration communities felt towards public institutions, so they decided to build the project with the community, adapting it to its needs.

To fulfil the strategic ambition and the co-production focussed approach, project instructors worked to create activities and repertoires in sync with the local culture that made sense to all members of the community participating in the project. This focus on local cultural traditions was important, as suggested by Daniel Montez, a 36-year-old instructor for Sensory Expedition:

Because of violence, there has been a disconnection between the community and its cultural traditions, which have become lost over time. Because of this, whenever music was brought to a project, they always included artists who play genres that are different from the traditional genres from this region.

Javier, another instructor, agreed arguing that:

For example, there are instructors who are very good at teaching *cumbia*, so they decide to give a course around *cumbia*, however, they do so in a region that is defined and identified by *son de negro*. When this happens, people start to disconnect from the project, and it makes it more difficult for the project to succeed.

Seeking to avoid the importation of other cultural tastes and traditions, Sensory Expedition is a project delivered in a flexible and fluid manner that does not begin from pre-conceived notions of the region. Rather, it uses conversations within the community as the raw material translated into activities that reflect the community's interests, desires, and traditions. Thanks to this approach, the project has been able to integrate members of the community who come from very different backgrounds and age groups, and who bring very different abilities and resources to the project. This is where organisers and participants agree that the project has shown its most remarkable feature: being positively embraced by the community.

In this sense, Jennifer Mesa, a 29-year-old dance instructor from Sensory Expedition, highlighted how the project focuses on benefiting the local community and making it the core element of the project:

The most important thing that the project did was not to bring professionals from other cities as they usually do, but rather focus on giving opportunities to us — the locals. Thanks to the project, we have been able to acquire knowledge, to improve our abilities and to be better every

day. Also, in my case, I have been able to make a living out of the project and now I'm able to provide for [myself] and my children.

Similarly, Luis Morales reinforced the importance of the project in the life of local artists. He suggested that:

Sensory Expedition has changed my life, 300%! Thanks to the project, I have improved my economic situation. I was able to buy my own house, and now I can buy things that I like. But it's not just money and it's not just me. Thanks to the project I have seen change in my students and in their families, I have had kids who beat up their moms, I have had kids who do drugs, they are all tricked into being mean and into doing bad things. But, thanks to the project, they have been able to find a meaning to their lives, to grow personally and they have been able to get their lives back on track.

Furthermore, César Palacio emphasised the importance of music as a key resource for transformation in the region:

Kids now see music in very different — positive — ways. Some of them see it as a tool for social and economic mobility, others see it as their vocation, many of them see it as a hobby that gives them fun and peace of mind. Many others have learnt to see music as a means to forgetting about their traumatic past and to transform it into positive thoughts and the expression of happiness.

These affirmations resonate among members of the community in Montes de María, and I observed the way in which local inhabitants perceive Sensory Expedition as a project that has reshaped the realities of their lives and the interactions of the community. They are the 'living proof' of how a project that has been conceived from the grassroots, rather than as a top-down policy, can be successful. They show the value of engaging members of the community to produce outcomes that participants view as positive and, in many cases, as life changing. The involvement of families in the children's training programme was also a key component in the success of the project. The families supported the organisation of performances and festivals in which their children were participating. They arranged sound, catering, and other logistical elements of the productions, a teamwork that created bonds between them. Previously, these sorts of celebrations were unlikely due to mistrust.

Although the perception of the project among members of the community was unanimously positive, participants also recognised that cultural projects such as Sensory Expedition are not always prioritised or valued by local policymakers. Sometimes, policymakers fail to see how these interventions are productive or profitable, preferring to invest in projects that produce more tangible results (e.g. infrastructure, security, mobility, etc.). Local members of the community view this as the consequence of the usual political campaigning mindset. One that, in their view, clouds politicians' judgement and distracts them from focusing on policies that really benefit their communities. For example, reflecting on the politics of Sensory Expedition, Daniel Montez states:

Politicians do not care about culture because they cannot benefit from it. For example, last year, the Ministry of Culture was going to give us a donation of costumes for 16 pairs of dancers. However, when the mayor noticed that he was not going to be able to appear in propaganda saying that he was responsible for the donation, he refused to sign the agreement with the Ministry; they only care about personal benefit.

This clearly reflects the gap between national and local government. While the national government intends to invest in a cultural project like Sensory Expedition, the reality of these municipalities is that politicians and local authorities are not competent in these issues. Indeed, their tendency is to overlook investments or cultural projects completely. In a similar fashion, Oscar Contreras suggested that local government:

[...] only cares about money and finding the way to make a profit. So, because culture does not receive a significant budget, they do not care about it. They do not see it as good business, that's why they do not promote it, because they do not care about the people, they just care about filling their own pockets.

However, when analysing policymakers' involvement with culture, it is noticeable that even if local authorities have a genuine interest in investing in cultural interventions, they do not have an effective means to make informed decisions on the merit of utilising culture to address violence in the region. As Guiomar Acevedo stated:

Because of the lack of resources, we often have to decide between spending in policy evaluations or spending to sustain the projects in the region. I wish we had an area dedicated to policy evaluation, but the truth is that I am often confronting a situation in which I have only

1,000 million pesos and if I decide to use them for policy evaluation, I would have to use 600 million pesos to pay for the studies and would be left with only 400 million pesos to spend on projects.

As a result, cultural interventions in the region are not only non-profitable for those local governments focused on economic gains, but they are also unable to be translated into success indicators or concrete results. This occurs simply because they are never subject to comprehensive policy evaluation. In turn, cultural initiatives are never seen as contribute effort in the policymaking process, because they do not leave economic or political revenues, and even if they effectively contribute to the improvement of social indicators, there are no comprehensive evaluations that evidence this impact. Furthermore, as will be discussed in the following chapter, both of the problems that are presented here end up producing a cycle in which lack of results translates into lack of spending. On the contrary, lack of resources makes it impossible to invest in policy evaluation without significantly affecting the resources available for any cultural or artistic intervention in the field.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter has explored and elucidated one example of a relevant arts-based peacebuilding initiative in Colombia. Sensory Expedition represents an innovative attempt by the Ministry of Culture to address the effects of the perpetration of violence in the region of Montes de María. Its novelty is based on the project's conception as a grassroots effort in public policy, which contrasts with the history of policymaking, both in the region of Montes de María and in the general context of Colombia.

However, insights from participants and instructors at Sensory Expedition demonstrate that it is precisely the bottom-up nature of the project what has allowed it to be perceived positively by members of the community. Together with the popularity of musical and artistic expressions, it has encouraged participation not only from children and teenagers (who remain as the core beneficiaries), but also from mothers, fathers, elders and local leaders who benefit from the project *as well as* bringing additional abilities and resources that enrich the execution of its activities.

According to the perception of local participants, Sensory Expedition has brought many benefits. *Local capacity building* is one of such benefits, enabled by the development of local instructors who then become the key facilitators of the project. This process is also crucial for the project's long-term sustainability, ensuring — as it does — that there is capacity to continue the work in the future. The second factor is *social transformation*, achieved by giving instructors the opportunity to make a living out of the project, and enabling participants to find a possible career path and economic opportunities through the practice of arts and culture. The transformation is also achieved through the children who took part in the project, and their families. Through the collective work that music and dance bring about, the children establish long term relationships with their peers, promoting values of peace, such as solidarity, tolerance, and trust. In this case, the relationships are between members of the community who find a common place in which teamwork and collaboration become the means for strengthening social ties, known as *bonding*. The creation of spaces in which different social groups can come together through arts, finding mutual reasons to share experiences and build new social networks, is *bridging*. Finally, *peacebuilding*, *memory-building* and *reconciliation* are the main pillars of the Sensory Expedition project. Progress towards these goals is achieved by providing the local community with a space in which arts enable participants to express personal feelings, opinions, expectations and even traumas. This process contributes to the construction of a narrative that allows the community to overcome fearful memories of the past, and instead use them to initiate the construction of a narrative for the future.

The success and popularity of initiatives such as Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition demonstrate the importance of focusing social investment to support local initiatives, rather than creating projects at the national level that are then replicated as a model at a regional level. These cases are examples of how locally led driven projects can be socially engaged and produce significant effects in the effort towards peacebuilding in violence-affected regions. However, while a number of successes can be attributed to these projects, perceptions show that both Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition are also subject to the challenges that cultural projects often face in the context of peacebuilding efforts, and in general, in the context of public policymaking in Colombia. The lack of interest in culture, together with the lack of meaningful policy evaluation around cultural projects, becomes a cycle that is turning cultural projects into initiatives that have limited resources and are unable to show meaningful impact.

It is crucial to highlight the difference between the two projects discussed in the case studies above: Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition. The first point of difference is that one project is located in an urban area and the other in a rural region. Casa Kolacho is an initiative that is currently self-sustainable and does not depend on State resources. In this way, it differs from the Montes de María project, which depends on public investment from the State. Casa Kolacho is a grassroots initiative that emerged entirely from the community, Montes de María is a national government initiative, albeit built hand-in-hand with local communities. Although both projects emphasised community ownership, the reality of funding in local territories depends on political will. For example, in the case of Medellín, as explained throughout this thesis, there has been an unprecedented investment in the cultural sector in the last ten years. However, the reality in rural areas is completely different. For example, in rural areas there are few people with technical skills and investment in culture is almost non-existent.

Therefore, for the present work it is paramount to understand how culture is perceived at the governmental level, and how policymakers and politicians understand the importance of cultural interventions in the context of peacebuilding in Colombia. The evaluation of these perceptions sheds light on the factors that explain the historical disinterest in culture in the national policymaking process and can constitute a key resource to enable the proposal of significant transformations in policymaking that will allow cultural projects to play a more significant role in building the path towards peace in the future.

CHAPTER 7. CULTURE, PEACEBUILDING AND THE POLICYMAKING PROCESS

7.0 Introduction

In Chapter's 5 and 6, I have presented two case studies of cultural projects implemented in contexts where peacebuilding was a priority. Drawing on the perceptions of local participants and organisers, the analysis of these projects shed light on the way in which local communities value culture-based interventions. Both cases highlighted the positive perceptions of host communities to culture-based projects. Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition created spaces where narratives of the past could be transformed into memory building assets through engagement with various art forms. In these projects, positive stories of the future were created through art expressions that emphasised values of social dialogue, mutual understanding and collaboration as the core elements of peacebuilding processes.

In sum, the culture of peace aims to eradicate violence as a means of resolving conflicts and to replace it with dialogue and common understanding between citizens. This profound transformation of mentalities and social practices necessarily involves re-examining the place and the meaning of collective identities in our understanding of moral and political life. While the communities in Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition had positive perceptions of these projects, past experience suggests that they are not as highly valued by local and national authorities. Historically, these entities have seen culture as one of the least important sectors for government spending. In Colombia, national investment in culture has never exceeded 1% of the general budget. It is generally perceived that cultural policies have not been taking the citizens into account: neither those who work and live from culture, nor for those who enjoy, reflect on and learn from culture. On the contrary, these policies have been put in place to extract political and economic benefits that usually do not revert to the public. This brings us to analyze the value of culture and its instrumentalization as an economic or political resource for policymakers.

According to the pyramid model of John Paul Lederach (1997), peacebuilding requires to reach all levels of society, from the grassroots to the elites through peacebuilding initiatives. This is important because in order to mitigate the risk of violence, and to enable an environment of peace, a wide range of actors and measures are vital, and part of these actors includes

policymakers. Since they are the ones who design, execute and allocate State resources, it is important to take into account their perspective and exploration of their role in the design and delivery models for the peacebuilding process in Colombia through the arts and culture. While cities, including Medellín, have made significant public investments in culture due to their specific experience of the conflict and its effects, the national picture is less positive for the cultural sector.

In this chapter, I explore the decision-making processes that have left culture as one of the sectors least supported by public spending in Colombia, which has undermined efforts to support cultural-based projects that contribute to the peacebuilding process in the country. Findings are derived from a series of face-to-face interviews with high-level stakeholders involved in decision-making processes, and whose insights provide rich information on how culture is perceived as a public policy tool.

7.1 A Historical Disconnection with Culture

Culture has historically been one of the least favoured sectors in Colombia's national budget. For the past 15 years, expenditure on culture has been below 1% of the annual budget, and although investment has grown in the past decade from 0.25% in 2009 to 0.87 in 2019, the Ministry of Culture still has one of the lowest budget allocations of all government departments. Even with the arrival of the new administration of President Iván Duque, who used culture and the “orange economy”³² as his main campaign platforms, the Ministry of Culture ranked 16th of 17 Ministries in terms of the resources allocated in the 2020 budget. Indeed, only above the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation, created in 2019, was in receipt of a lower share of the national budget (Ministerio de Hacienda y Crédito Público, 2020).

Historically low levels of investment in culture appear to reflect a lack of confidence in the value of culture from decision-makers in successive national governments. Findings from this study support this diagnosis. Indeed, this viewpoint is advanced by both political decision-

³² *Orange economy* is a concept used by the administration of President Iván Duque to promote cultural industries. It is defined by the national government as “a development model in which cultural diversity and creativity are pillars of social transformation and economic development for the country's regions” (Ministerio de Cultura, n. d.).

makers and those advocating for greater investment in culture as a peacebuilding tool. For example, Jairo Rivera, a member of the ‘Voces de Paz y Reconciliación’³³ group, suggested that:

[...] the main problem is that, in Colombia, culture is wrongly perceived as mere entertainment and, as such, there is not a notion of the instrumentalisation of culture, because there’s no economic or political value assigned to it. The problem with this perspective is that it ignores the fact that culture has already been instrumental to the war that we have lived through. As a country, we have all the war rituals that you can imagine, and all these rituals can only be eliminated through the creation of a very different set of rituals based precisely in arts and culture.

In agreement with Mr. Rivera’s perspective, other stakeholders also explained the historical disconnection between culture and public policy in Colombia. Miguel Barreto, chief coordinator of the Observatory on Peacebuilding of the Universidad Jorge Tadeo Lozano, suggested that culture is not only rejected but is directly ignored in peacebuilding efforts, arguing that:

In peace studies, culture is the most undervalued dimension of them all, because, even being a multidisciplinary field, peacebuilding is a field that is highly dominated by disciplines such as political science, economy, anthropology, and sociology. These can be very comprehensive in their approaches, but they also have numerous gaps. In contrast, it is not common to see disciplines such as art theory or literary studies being applied to peacebuilding efforts, and I think that this is essential in a conflict where physical violence is usually accompanied by cultural violence.

Furthermore, Frank Pearl also shared his opinion on the cause for this historical disdain towards culture:

Colombia has ‘poor country syndrome’, we think that we must only invest in what is urgent. We feel that the only subjects that are urgent are those of security and of infrastructure, so we never make relevant, sustained and meaningful interventions that can translate into profound social transformations. We are barely learning to appreciate the value of culture.

³³ Voices of Peace and Reconciliation. A group which has been assigned the task of monitoring the progress of the implementation of the Peace Agreements in the Congress of Colombia.

This last perception was confirmed by decision-makers holding public office. Members of the House of Representatives in Colombia reaffirmed the notion that culture has value, but it does not feature heavily in political decision-making because of its perceived intangibility. Gabriel Santos, representative for Bogotá in the Congress of Colombia, son of former Vice-president Francisco Santos³⁴, was elected to office representing Centro Democrático, the party of President Iván Duque. Centro Democrático holds the executive branch of power and also the majority in both chambers of the Congress of Colombia. Representative Santos observed: “I haven’t really witnessed a cultural project that displays an objective approach to the issue of peace or that contributes to the construction of memory from the conflict”. Furthermore, he added:

In turn, there are some projects that I have seen, and that I really like, they are focused on gastronomy and involve female heads of family. [Such projects] are useful because they teach [participants] some new techniques and new knowledge that they can really use to make a living.

Summarising his general opinion, he said: “I think that in Colombia culture is reduced to festivals, for example the ‘Festival de la Gaviota’ or the ‘Festival del Caimán’, these festivals end up being sources of votes, so culture becomes a transactional subject”, from which politicians can obtain personal benefits, either in the form of financial gain or in the form of political recognition in their communities of interest, which can then translate into more votes.

These comments illustrate why culture is seen in governmental spheres as a secondary issue; primarily because it is not easily measured and does not appeal to them. Moreover, because the value of culture cannot be easily instrumentalised to produce readily understandable results, and evidence of its contribution to policymaking is seen as too anecdotal. This perception explains the historical disregard for culture and reinforces the affirmations of Mr. Rivera and Professor Barreto: that culture is perceived superficially and is understood poorly as a means of fostering dialogue, memory-building and community-bonding in peacebuilding scenarios. As a result, the widespread misunderstanding of the value of culture undermines the efforts

³⁴ He is also the nephew of former President Juan Manuel Santos.

made by cultural actors to secure support for their projects. This thinking translates into a scarcity of investment for the sector.

While lack of knowledge can be identified as a reason for the lack of interest in social investment through culture, perceptions like the ones expressed by Representative Santos also point to another challenge that culture has to face in its quest to become a relevant field, not only in peacebuilding processes, but also in general nation-building scenarios. The challenge resumes in producing both meaningful and measurable results that can influence decision-makers to see culture as an alternative component of public policy.

As the Swiss economist Bruno Frey proposes, “it is therefore not sufficient to demonstrate the existence of positive external effects of an arts project. Rather, it is necessary to analyse how these values enter into the political process, and to what extent they are taken into account” (2005, p. 6). In this context, willingness to pay or contingent valuation studies become a key mission for cultural organisations and public institutions to produce tangible results. However, since arts professionals often take artistic value for granted, although intrinsically meaningful, this also highlights a tension between cultural professionals, politicians, and policymakers. They often see no need to establish instrumental outcomes beyond intrinsic value. This position can place them at odds with elected politicians who consider it essential to establish the need for government support for arts and cultural projects. This aligns with the claim of Holden (2004) that there is a clear disconnection between the public’s idea of culture and how politics and policymakers talk about it. According to the author, this is reflected in the low status that political parties attribute to culture, and in terms of expenditure, in the fact that culture lies on the Colombian political margin.

7.2 Public Support for Arts and Culture

For cultural interventions, the lack of evidence of their impact upon indicators such as security, economic development and creation of social fabric is one of the main problems that they face in the Colombian context. This scarcity of visible and demonstrable results ends up deterring policymakers from having a more favourable approach towards culture. In comparison to the rest of the country, cases such as the city of Medellín represent outliers. Indeed, the continuity of investment there depends almost exclusively on the personal beliefs of policymakers who, with almost blind faith, make investment in culture a priority. Medellín’s politicians support

culture-based social projects in the hope of producing positive results for peacebuilding. As this approach runs counter to conventional policymaking approaches, other local or national governmental commitments to cultural investment are unusual.

Findings from this study confirmed that culture has not been purposefully ignored, but neither has it been considered effective as an alternative means of addressing social or economic problems. There has been an unwillingness to pay for impact studies that could establish the value of cultural interventions, including the cost-benefit of investments. Herein lies a challenge for those making the case for culture in Colombia. While culture is intrinsically valuable for many, in order to garner more political support, the cultural sector may need to engage with analysis of value that includes economic measures. Today, there are very few alternative means of assessing culture that influence policymakers. This is in spite of Klamer's (2002) view that cultural values are 'beyond the price' of a good. Representative Santos highlights the problem of assessing culture in a way that can be understood by policymakers:

[...] the problem with culture is that results are not immediate, or even visible. Therefore, the efforts are concentrated in other areas where people can see a more tangible impact. For example, if you build a highway, people can see it, people can use it, so it is something that you as a politician can use in your favour. However, if you build a theatre, and it is not used, and you don't see a change, then people can see it as a failure.

This perspective is in line with much of the international literature on policymakers' understandings of the value of culture (Holden, 2004; O'Brien, 2010). In this literature, it is argued that politicians and policymakers only invest in culture when it can produce another externality (e.g. health improvement, economic benefit or strengthening community). If political leaders are uncertain about the return on investment from culture, then they are less likely to prioritise spending in this area compared to other potential policy levers. This creates a problem for cultural actors as they are often grounded in competing value systems about what culture is for and what it can do. Often, the value of culture is difficult to quantify, especially in the short term. Until a rights-based idea of culture is established, it will always be fighting competing claims for resources. For example, it is not realistic to compare culture's role in facilitating structural change in a community or society with the immediate value of constructing a highway.

However, the findings of this study suggest that in Colombia there is still some way to go before culture is considered a right to be used as a basis for government investment decisions. For example, Representative Goebertus³⁵ agreed that the major limitation in prioritising cultural initiatives is the lack of measurement of indicators and policy evaluation:

I think there needs to be more efforts to measure impact. With these efforts, you could effectively see in numbers how these efforts contribute to reduce violence or to create peaceful coexistence scenarios. When this happens, there could be an increasing political will to promote conversation at the highest levels, thus making culture a more visible and relevant subject.

Representatives Santos and Goebertus highlight that city-based policymakers, in particular, tend to see social investment initiatives as efforts that need to demonstrate immediate and quantifiable measurable results. By reinforcing this perspective, efforts that cannot be easily translated into measurable indicators are perceived as ineffective, or not worthy. Findings of this study suggest that the majority of Colombian parliamentarian's support subsidising the arts only as a means to an end, rather than as an end in itself. This scenario explains the historical existence of a policymaking process in which "the value of cultural interventions has been an underplayed policy" (Davies & Selwood, 2012, p. 202).

In contrast to the views of Santos and Goebertus, cultural professionals suggested that while the lack of evaluation is a challenge, the positive impacts generated by cultural projects often transcend the reductive tendencies of immediate or quantitative results. They also suggested that the more significant results of these efforts are seen when observing the beneficiary communities, and how they embrace and interact with projects over time. For example, Guiomar Acevedo is convinced that the benefits of cultural interventions are not directly related to indicators or traditional results, arguing instead that:

Artistic expressions are closely linked to communitarian identities, and that is seen mostly in small towns and villages in the country, where artistic expressions are a way of reaffirming local history and traditions. Cities have a different way of interacting with culture, but small communities give high value to the opportunity of showing their background and expressing their cultural heritage. In that sense, our focus in the work that we do with communities through

³⁵ Goebertus is also a representative of the city of Bogotá in Congress and a member of Alianza Verde, a party with a centre-left ideology that identifies as the opposition to the ruling party.

training and cultural development projects is to promote scenarios in which we can contribute to the creation or the strengthening of social fabric.

For Acevedo, not everything that is measurable deserves to be evaluated. It is also not the case that everything that deserves to be evaluated can be measured, emphasising the transcendental value of culture. In State-subsidised institutions, there is a complex set of processes that need to be understood when assessing why culture might be the loser in resources claims. Part of the problem relates to how the value of culture can be captured and documented. For example, Professor Barreto argued that social transformation through culture depends on positive effects that escape the conventional analysis produced by measuring results quantitatively:

One of the highest values of culture relies in micro-transformations. There are a number of aspects that are almost completely intangible, and which are given very little value, but that proves to be highly important in social transformation. One person can change when you change how they see their context, and you can do that through music, for example. Music is a language that can unite, and it is a means of expressing personal emotions. So, when you allow someone to tell a story, and invite others to listen, you can promote empathy as a core value, and through artistic expressions you can start to build bridges between ethnic, religious, or social groups.

This testimony demonstrates that professionals immersed in cultural work are convinced that social transformation through art is more meaningful in small communities, and through intangible mechanisms that though are almost invisible, contribute significantly to the strengthening of social fabric in a community (including the promotion of reconciliation, memory, and peacebuilding). Their confidence in the value of cultural interventions is based on their experience of the effect that these projects have on participating members of the community. Unlike their politician counterparts, they are not focusing on how this impact can be shown in quantitative data and figures by local and national authorities. Although the benefits for communities are clear to those working closely with participants, an inability to translate these into the traditional policymaking language of short-term cost-benefit analysis continues to undermine the path for culture to become a meaningful subject in policymaking in Colombia. Professor Jairo Rivera explained the reason why culture is disadvantaged in national decision-making processes:

When you make public policy, there are two basic paths: American political science, and European political science. Historically, Colombia has chosen the first one, and because it is an approach that is based on results and indicators measurement, it has been a flawed experience. In the scenario of internal armed conflict, they have chosen to focus in areas that can produce short-term and tangible results such as security and defence, rather than areas that can produce more meaningful long term transformations such as education or culture.

From this perspective, the emphasis placed on the potential of the arts to help address the social problems related to the armed conflict represents an opportunity to contribute to the peacebuilding process in Colombia. Rivera added:

They have never seen education as a means to create conscience and to promote new social practices, but as a means to obtain a diploma and therefore be able to access the labour market. As such, they perceive education as too costly for the State, and prefer to invest billions into defence strategies which they see as the best means of tackling conflict.

The input shared by Professor Rivera effectively corresponds with the opinion of policymakers including Representative Santos, who are convinced that culture is not a subject that can produce immediate results and, therefore, is not an asset that policymakers and politicians can use to benefit their political ambitions. In addition, it illustrates the way in which Colombian local and national authorities are reliant on decision-making processes focused on short-term results, which has led to a historical rejection of meaningful long term positive outcomes that could be achieved through sectors such as education, culture, and science and innovation (Ministry of Culture, 2013).

In spite of the existence of the negative scenario that constrains the emergence of culture as an important subject for social development in the country, the end of the armed conflict in Colombia represents an opportunity to re-examine the role that culture can play in helping communities working towards overcoming their painful past to construct a better society. In the post-conflict scenario, there is a need to explore alternative interventions that can enable communities to grow from past harmful experiences. Culture can become a catalyst for social transformation processes.

While findings from this study confirm a lack of cultural investment in Colombia, there is also some evidence that policymakers are beginning to acknowledge that culture can become a key asset in the strategies being put in place to address the challenge of building a country in a post-conflict scenario. Frank Pearl articulated an alternative vision that policymakers can forge to maximise the impact of culture in peacebuilding scenarios. In his role as lead negotiator in peace talks, Mr. Pearl has been able to understand the context of conflict and has participated in numerous projects in the regions, which have allowed him to understand the particularities of the conflict through the eyes of affected communities. From these experiences, he agreed that culture has value beyond quantitative measurement:

I'm going to tell you something, there are things that can't be measured, but the fact that they are not measurable does not mean they don't exist, or that they are not positive. The impact of these things can only be seen by interacting with people, talking to them, working in the field, experimenting, and being willing to risk everything and do stuff that may not have the impact you expect [...]. We did perform psychological and social studies, and we were able to see that individuals had better clinical results, but I am absolutely certain that those studies did not even come close to showing the real impact of what we saw. We saw whole communities that were full of aggression, mistrust, and violence, and that, at the end of the projects, showed not only evident but meaningful transformations.

Mr. Pearl also elaborated on the contribution of culture as a catalyst in social transformation, stating that:

I have participated in projects in over 120 municipalities, in which we used arts and culture to promote reconciliation. Through these projects I was able to see how people in Colombia are filled with emotions that we haven't even recognised; there is fear, anger, indifference and even a thirst for vengeance. So, when a society does not have democratic means to channel those feelings, people end up channeling them through violence.

This testimony represents a call to policymakers to become more immersed in local contexts, listening to the everyday realities of post-conflict and seeking to understand the potential value of arts and cultural projects for social transformation. Mr. Pearl himself became convinced of the value of cultural projects when he was High Commissioner for Peace and Senior Presidential Advisor for the Social and Economic Reintegration of Armed Individuals and Groups. He highlighted one project (*Canta conmigo*) that brought together people on opposing

sides of the conflict and gave them the opportunity to work with renowned artists, who created a space for them to work together, giving them the opportunity to channel their fears, anger and hatred in ways that did not harm anyone. They were able to express their harshest feelings, but they were able to do so without causing any harm; by having a common goal they were able to build relationships and by recognising and focusing on what unites them, not what divides them.

It is precisely in this process of managing emotions that culture finds one of its strongest features, and where it can be more than valuable for the context of Colombia. According to Professor Álvaro Martínez, director of the Villa Mayor Theatre in Bogotá and a renowned expert in the cultural field, artistic activities such as dancing, singing, composition and painting are a perfect way to make initial approaches to negative feelings that emerged from conflict and that have been either ignored or hidden because of the communities' fear of embracing them. In the words of Professor Martínez:

We are just starting to understand post-conflict and the challenges that come with it, and offering communities cultural alternatives can allow us to increase our understanding of the most basic feelings and needs of the affected communities. Through art expressions such as singing, dancing, acting or engaging in visual arts practices, communities can start by getting in touch with their hidden emotions in a safe environment. [They] can later transcend to transform these feelings into stories that can contribute to the memory-building process. Through these processes, and with the key role that arts can play in them, we can start to get a grasp on what happened in this communities and the way in which conflict shaped their stories.

This perspective on the benefits of cultural projects was supported by other cultural experts. As Guiomar Acevedo stated, thanks to these expressions they were able to understand the needs of the community and design the project according to the community's interest. She said:

When you give these communities a risk-free space to express, you end up being surprised by all the things they say that you did not know before. For example, we invited community members to write songs and texts about their stories, and we found out that there was a shared feeling that we haven't identified: they were hungry. Since they have had their land stolen from them, they were unable to cultivate their food and sustain themselves, so they had to rely on other forms of work that did not always meet their needs. As a result of that context, we created a section in the project in which we gave them the raw materials; they were the ones who created

the recipes and the dishes that we would serve as the snacks during the project activities. This later became a space in which mainly adult women could regain ancestral knowledge and demonstrate it through culinary arts. It not only allowed them to reconstruct ties with their cultural heritage, but also allowed them to have an economic alternative to sustain their families.

These spaces, where communities have the opportunity to connect with their feelings and memories, are fundamental to the process of comprehending conflict and, consequently, understanding ways in which these communities need to be supported to help them recover from the effects that violence has caused in their lives. According to Professor Barreto, these are spaces where unmeasurable but meaningful results can occur:

There are key interactions in the process of peacebuilding that are closely linked to symbolic and intangible elements. With art, you can reach a village of people with very low levels of education, you can even work with people who do not know how to write or read, and through music, for example, you can enable them to express themselves and share stories that they otherwise would not be able to share. When they come back to you and say things like '*this changed my life*', '*this broadened my horizons*' or '*this project was a flower in the desert*', that is the moment when you notice the real impact of culture-based social interventions.

As discussed previously, these findings have historically escaped the eyes of policymakers who have been unable to recognise the value of these interventions since they cannot be placed in a Cartesian diagram showing measurable results. As a consequence, culture has been historically misinterpreted as a means of entertainment or has been valued only for the visible results it has produced. In this way, the real meaningful effects obtained from culture have not been adequately valued. In response to this, findings of this study suggest that a greater emphasis needs to be placed on articulating the specific role culture can play in the peacebuilding process. According to Professor Barreto, empathy is the key factor in this process:

The key to these programs is to focus on empathy. When you bring a guerrilla man, who maybe was recruited when he was a child, and a mother who had to see her son killed in conflict, and then you allow them to share their experiences in a safe environment, you allow them to understand the difficulties that the other had to face, you allow them to connect with the human side of their counterpart and enable them to get in touch with the feelings of the other. Through the repetition of these scenarios, you can start erasing the lines that have historically separated people because of conflict, or even because of their political, religious or social beliefs.

Furthermore, findings suggest that empathy can also help to erase the line that has separated urban and rural communities due to the different ways in which they perceive conflict. In this regard, Professor Barreto observed:

Art is a way in which you can easily express a very complex phenomenon such as conflict, and when someone is provided with a resource that allows them to understand that complexity of that phenomenon, they can raise their awareness on its effects. People, usually city people, live in their comfortable bubbles and usually see conflict from an external point of view, so they never fully understand the extent of it and the effect it has on other people. Thanks to art, they come in touch with that reality and are able to see the most difficult side of conflict, which is usually what happened in rural communities.

In the post-conflict scenario, Cohen (2005) and Lederach (1996) have argued that the generation of empathy through cultural expressions can be important in contributing to memory-building processes and the reconstructing a fragmented social fabric. However, the task that peacebuilding practitioners face is how to incorporate the arts into their work so that the victims of violence can express themselves, heal, and be reconciled with those on the other side of the conflict. Arts and cultural projects can be particularly valuable in their ability to connect people and address competing rural and urban narratives of conflict. This study found some evidence that policymakers are beginning to recognise the potential of arts and culture, including Representative Juanita Goebertus and Mr. Frank Pearl. For example, Representative Goebertus suggested that:

The different forms of artistic expression work as a means to communicate the particularities of a scenario as hard as war and the pain it has brought. These expressions enable the generation of conscience in people who, like me, have not suffered the effects of war directly. They allow us to abandon our context of political polarisation and get into the shoes of people who suffered the consequences of conflict. It also allows skeptical people to get in touch with a reality that is there, and that really affected others.

With this mindset, she and other members of Congress have already begun to use cultural expressions as a resource to sensitise their fellow representatives and senators to the impact of conflict. As she expressed:

We have started to bring art expressions as a means of supporting the projects that we are trying to promote, and it is sometimes more helpful than a speech or a written document. One example of this is an art exhibition that we did this semester, we showed the pictures by photographer Juan Manuel Echavarría in which he showed eighteen schools in the region of Montes de María that have been abandoned because of the conflict. We placed this exhibition in the hall that Congress members have to cross everyday to get to their offices and, thanks to it, we were able to sensitise them to the debating of a bill that would allow us to provide rural communities with useful and adequate means of transportation that guarantee children in those communities are able to get to their schools safely.

Moreover, according to Mr. Pearl, the instrumentalisation of culture is important to open a space for cultural initiatives to influence decision-making processes. As he explained:

I think art is very useful for showing the stories of conflict. So, to promote art, I would use testimonies of the youngsters who have participated in these projects and would allow them to express the way in which being involved in artistic and cultural interventions helped them, their family, and their community to change their reality and re-shape their context.

Thus, while culture still remains a low priority in governmental decision-making processes, there is some evidence of a growing awareness of its value as part of post-conflict peacebuilding processes. There is recognition from politicians and policymakers that projects like Sensory Expedition and Casa Kolacho produce tangible benefits to the communities they serve. In particular, politicians are increasingly sensitised to the notion that arts and cultural activities can encourage empathy, dialogue, and mutual understanding, which are foundations of the (re)building of the social fabric of the affected areas. As decision-makers become aware of these benefits, they are more likely to look favourably on efforts to pressure the government to invest in arts and culture as a right.

7.3 Conclusion

In this chapter, I have outlined the historical disconnection between culture and policymaking in the Colombian context. As testimonies from political actors, policymakers and cultural project coordinators highlight, policymakers tend to see State investment as a transactional issue. A perceived lack of rigorous evaluation and measurable quantitative data means

Colombian policymakers are disinclined to allocate public spending on initiatives that they view as too intangible.

This chapter concludes that cultural projects are often unable to demonstrate immediate quantitative results, and they find standardised indicators difficult to achieve. This is because projects often respond to different contexts and evolve in line with the interests and needs of benefitted communities, which means that they can operate with different goals. The impact of cultural projects still needs to be evaluated, but the way they are assessed should reflect their objectives and the complexity of the issues they seek to solve. To achieve this, it might be necessary to measure investments over a longer period of time, or to develop methodologies that can more accurately capture and document the impact of experience of accessing arts and cultural opportunities for people affected by conflict. If alternative measures of success can be developed, then the value of arts and cultural interventions will be further legitimised. In turn, this will strengthen the case for greater public investment in culture.

In this chapter, I have also highlighted a significant difference in the way culture is perceived in large urban zones, in comparison to small communities or rural areas. This difference leads to misconceptions of the social value of culture at the urban municipal level. Study findings suggest that urban policymakers associate culture with entertainment, in the form of creative industries, and with an economic contribution. However, for small urban or rural communities affected by conflict, arts and culture can act as a catalyst for social transformation. This nuance needs to be recognised by policymakers.

In essence, I have shown that the cultural sector in Colombia is in a position where its efforts and accomplishments do not respond to the interests and ambitions of policymakers, and yet are valued highly by communities because they contribute to the creation of spaces for dialogue, mutual understanding, and reconciliation.

To conclude this chapter, it is clear that there is an opportunity for culture to become more relevant in the post-conflict context of Colombia. Since the primary focus of post-conflict efforts is to reconnect State institutions with historically forgotten and even abandoned regions of the country, culture can become a key asset in rebuilding bridges between urban spheres and small rural communities. The expressive arts can be an important means to encourage affected communities to tell their stories and work on post-conflict memory-building.

CHAPTER 8: RETURNING CULTURE TO PEACEBUILDING

8.0 Introduction

In this analysis chapter, I reflect on insights that emerge from the two case studies by discussing a number of key themes, including social capital, social cohesion, community rebuilding, and the cultural dimension of peace. Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition both represent two arts and cultural programmes that were conceived in an effort to build sustainable peace in a country that is emerging from conflict. In this chapter, I outline the advantages and limitations of cultural conflict management initiatives and offer suggestions on the basic principles that should guide their planning and implementation, analysing the most effective design and delivery models to produce beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture.

Based on the literature review and the findings presented in the preceding chapters, I outline the benefits of approaching the Colombian peacebuilding process from a cultural perspective. In particular, I show how arts and culture have the power to redefine the necessary conditions for coexistence, because of their ability to enhance mutual understanding, foster dialogue and collaboration networks, and encourage a process of participation, inclusion and associativity. I offer insights on how arts-based programmes can help communities affected by conflict redefine themselves, restoring broken ties, and recovering the cultural roots and traditions that provide the social glue that is necessary to repair the fabric of communities often torn apart by conflict.

8.1 The Strengthening of Social Capital through Peacebuilding

Economic analyses of the armed conflict have been prevalent in recent years (Sánchez & Díaz, 2005). However, most studies have focused on explaining the causes and determinants of the persistent conflicts around the world, rather than focusing on analysing the consequences of those conflicts. A smaller body of work deals with the social impact of conflict and the measures designed to reconstruct the social fabric of the affected areas.

After periods of armed conflicts, the bonds of trust and dialogue are weakened among the inhabitants of the affected areas (Paloutzian & Kalayjian, 2009). Internal conflict has a devastating impact on the social development of the affected country, including the loss, or

destruction, of social capital and the dismantling of social cohesion. Studies (Sánchez & Díaz, 2005) reveal that the damaging effect of conflict profoundly alters the lives of thousands of people and their families, limiting their possibility for a better future, and undermining democratic development. My study has examined the negative effects of conflict on social and human capital, through the cases studies of Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition. In these enquiries, I found evidence of displacement, loss of opportunities, loss of sense of belonging, and emotional effects, including hatred, anger, and frustration. The psychologists Long and Brecke (2003) suggest that, to achieve reconciliation, it is necessary to transform emotionally driven patterns like aggression into empathy, and desire for revenge into desire for affiliation. The lack of trust and solidarity generated by armed conflicts can threaten the (re)building of social capital and thus the establishment of the conditions for a stable and lasting peace.

The social dimension of culture is provided by the characteristics of the creative processes; that is, the participatory relationship of the members of a community in an arts-based intervention is what gives it its social character. Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition no longer think of art with the aim of producing only a cultural good, but as a means to think and create new realities, generating new imaginaries and social paradigms. The two case studies have in common an active participation of the population, a process of collective creation and expression of social problems. These participatory arts have great transformative potential in terms of forming bonds of solidarity among the community.

The process of collective creation allows the members of Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition to think and build possible futures in order to address together and transform one's own reality through art, which is what is required to build a culture of peace: social interrelations and interactions based on the principles of freedom, justice, democracy, tolerance, and solidarity.

Furthermore, a culture of peace is a process of consolidation of a new way of seeing, understanding, and living in the world, starting with the self, and continuing with others, horizontally. It is about forming networks, promoting mutual exchanges, and overcoming differences from a local and global perspective. The development of a culture of peace requires society to be inspired, to trust, and to break through indifference. It needs people to overcome the overwhelming burdens of the past, to leave a comfort zone, and to risk building a culture of peace (Lederach, 2005). Besides, conflict demonstrates that society is experiencing a crisis

of values (Liebmann, 1996), thus, to overcome this state, it is necessary to deploy a new set of values as a way of (re)solving problems.

The findings of this study demonstrate that social capital is created through behaviours that express social cohesion and collective effectiveness. In this sense, as long as there are structured and goal-oriented social networks, the result will be commitment, reciprocity and, as a consequence, trust. In both Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition, there was evidence of values and feelings being transformed, partly due to the role of arts and culture — including feelings of hatred, resentment, and mistrust. In these cases, values associated with a culture of violence were replaced with those associated with understanding, solidarity, and empathy. As highlighted in chapters 5 and 6, negative feelings and emotions generated by the war were transformed into positive feelings, based on trust.

Drawing on the example of Casa Kolacho, a hip-hop lifestyle can promote freedom of expression, tolerance, disarming, and respect for human rights, by seeing, experiencing, understanding, and commenting on life and the world. Through the medium of song and graffiti, members of Casa Kolacho communicated about what was happening in their neighbourhoods and their country. The lyrics called out gender discrimination, violence, and offered solutions to these problems, calling for love, social justice, and peace. As Pruitt (2011) states, music can be used as a non-violent means to stimulate changes in attitudes and behaviours, and to even challenge opinions from different perspectives in the service of a more balanced and inclusive society. In the same way, Blommfield *et al.* (2003) suggest that music can be a form of storytelling, a way to reimagine lives and realities that engages all the senses, helping people to relate to each other and be moved emotionally. Following this reasoning, lyrics can create a deeper connection, helping to remind us of the message they want to communicate, be it peace or love, and represent a starting point to affect behaviour in a positive way. Likewise, music can contribute to generate trust, empathy and even forgiveness between groups, trying to find a way forward to build a lasting peace, as according to Cohen (2005) and Paloutzian & Kalayjian (2009), arts and culture can play an important role in contributing to this culture of peace.

The social networks in which social capital is embedded are the product of the investment strategies of individuals who seek to guarantee their access to certain resources (Bourdieu, 1986). In this study, the two cases demonstrate the fulfilment of a strategic approach that

achieves symbolic exchanges to help generate a type of group solidarity that transforms momentary or sporadic relationships into enduring ones, based on the mutual recognition of individuals and their qualities. This condition of reinforcement of social interaction, which makes the term social capital pertinent, can be possible through arts-based initiatives, as Stephenson and Zanotti (2016) note. This perception resonates with the findings of this study, where there was clear evidence that artistic and cultural activities from a participatory arts approach can bring people from the same community together to help build bridges between them. Through the implementation of participatory art encounters, different problematics were addressed, highlighting the possibility of generating actions that can, among other things, improve the quality of links in the community. The two case studies demonstrated that participatory art can encompass a wide range of art forms, including visual arts, music, and dance, and can also take many forms, from workshops and community events to public art installations and performances. What Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition showed is that the uniqueness of art-based approaches relies on a variety of backgrounds of participants who have different levels of artistic ability, but they are all encouraged to contribute with their own unique perspective to the project, helping to raise awareness of important social and political issues and promoting dialogue between different communities.

Crucially, both projects sought to avoid judging people on whether they supported guerrilla or paramilitary groups, since during the period of violence many people were pressured into helping criminal gangs. However, conflict generated a marked sense of distrust within the affected communities, because it was difficult to differentiate between the people who supported the guerrilla and paramilitary groups and those who did not. Nevertheless, participation in music and graffiti art activities opened the opportunity to welcome those who wanted to be a part of it, regardless of their past. The participants engaged in the arts-based initiatives of both projects confirmed that music and dance brought them together. Their cultural interests provided a communicating vessel to enter dialogue and listen to each other from another perspective. As Lederach (2005) argues, in order to establish a lasting peace, it is important to bring together divided parties to mitigate conflict by discussing and finding common grounds. This last example illustrates the definition of bridging social capital (Putnam, 2000), as it describes connections that link people across a fissure that usually divides society.

As illustrated by the testimonials from the two cases, beneficiaries of the arts-based and cultural initiatives were happy to participate in an opportunity to learn something new, to bond and make new friends. In the same line, Igor Stokfiszewski's (2016) *social culture* refers to characteristics that include — among others — interaction, collaboration, trust, and empathy. This conceptualization addresses arts and cultural initiatives as places where people can come together to create collective bonds, build trust through activity, achieve consensus, and to reconcile differences, antagonisms, and conflicts. It is the respect of individual qualities, desires, preferences and interests through arts that makes it possible to arrive at a result that belongs to all of those involved in the process. This idea of creating collective bonds was corroborated by participants in both case studies, who agreed that they had expanded their network of friends since the artistic process began. Participants talked about meeting new people or approaching those people they had seen in the neighbourhood but never said hello to before — which reduced feelings of loneliness and increasing trust among participants. Arts-based activities, from this perspective, can be a means to develop bonding and bridging social capital (Putnam, 2000) as the beneficiaries of the cultural initiatives assert that they made new friends outside of their families and their usual social circle, and on the other hand it helped them to strengthen connections with existing friends and family. LeBaron echoes this understanding claiming that “arts’ powerful role in bridging differences within and between groups is increasingly being recognised by peacemakers” (2011, p. 29). For example, thanks to the festivals that were organised during the cultural initiatives in both case studies, families and friends came together to celebrate, and since the artistic programmes were free and open to the public, it encouraged people from the community to participate by providing them with spaces to interact.

As a result, it is possible to see in these projects the rebuilding of the community, which is a key task for the strengthening of the social cohesion and the ability to manage, prevent and mitigate conflicts. In fact, it is one of the essential elements in the peacebuilding process, in order to improve social relations (Cohen, 2005; Broome & Collier, 2012). In sum, peacebuilding works by addressing the deep-rooted, structural causes of violent conflict in a comprehensive manner (Doyle, 2016; Fukushima, 2011), and it requires education in a particular type of values, such as freedom, tolerance, cooperation, and justice. This study has shown that increased solidarity bonds as a facet of peacebuilding can strengthen the resilience of the social fabric through the reconstruction of social capital. Cultural projects like Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition offer opportunities for cooperation through the exchange of

common cultural experiences, involving and empowering people. Both projects are a good example of a scenario where communities could understand peace as a way of life, as a daily way of being, surpassing personal interests, where only then a process of peaceful coexistence will be possible.

As shown in this section, the construction of social capital is an essential element in the process of rebuilding the social fabric and, therefore, in establishing a culture of peace. However, to achieve this, innovative ways and conditions are needed.

8.2 Peaceful Ways of Dealing with Conflict

Evidence from the two case studies that form the basis of this study demonstrate how arts and culture work as a catalyst to break cycles of violence. According to the conflict logical lifecycle theory of Galtung (1996), to counteract the attitudes, behaviours and contradictions that arise during and after conflict situations, 3Rs must be set in motion: reconstruction, reconciliation and resolution, on the understanding that peace is the ability to handle conflicts with empathy, nonviolence, and creativity. Although there is no linear mainstream conflict resolution practice, this research covers the possible peaceful avenues of arts and culture that can be used to reconcile the past with the future, to contribute to break the cycles of violence, and to prevent future conflicts from arising.

According to Galtung (1996), the more a society promotes, protects and fulfils human rights, the greater the chance of stopping violence and resolving conflicts peacefully. In this regard, the strengthening of civil society can help in the transition from war to peace. This condition also applies to the efforts of Sensory Expedition to build a culture of peace through arts and culture, discrediting all those social behaviours that glorify, idealise or naturalise the use of force and violence. For example, through dance, the participants of the project regained a sense of belonging to their territory, as well as a sense of memory and cultural identity. It also became a means to share with other children from the region what war and conflict had taken away from them. This included creating spaces for recreation and well-being without the pressure to compete. In Casa Kolacho, painting walls in the community also had transformative effects. Seeing messages of hope and peace or calming and inspirational images was fundamentally different from the prior experience of seeing walls daubed with threatening, fear-laced messages from armed groups. With this in mind, Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition

contribute to an increased mutual understanding and to the rebuilding of trust, which are key principles of peacebuilding processes (Lederach, 2005).

In this study, peace is more than just the absence of violence, because it also involves the strengthening of social structures that characterise peaceful societies (Kramer *et al.*, 2013). From this perspective, the ongoing development and implementation of local peace requires collective efforts³⁶. Hence, the construction of strong social networks can be translated into the consolidation of social and cultural capital (Colleta & Cullen, 2000), which allows the rebuilding of social ties and peaceful coexistence, changing the cycle of hatred and retaliation that has fuelled the armed conflict.

Recognising that reconciliation is a determining factor in peacebuilding (Galtung, 2000), this thesis has identified, based on its findings, three factors that are developed through artistic practices and offer the main conditions for changing attitudes and behaviours that are necessary to promote conflict resolution.

8.2.1 Creative Solutions

Rigid processes don't create space for a free enough thought pattern to allow people living in violence to begin thinking in terms of radically different futures. But because there are no facts in the future, when we enter the realm of the future, we are forced to enter our imagination. (Finlev, 2012, p. 58).

According to Tillett (2005), innovative thinking is one of the keys to conflict resolution; it means to be open to change and to consider creative and imaginative problem solving. Arai (2009) also promotes the use of creativity as a conflict resolution practice. According to Tillett (2005), a range of innovative methods can help to allow participants to externalise emotions and understand conflict. He proposes activities that enhance common purposes and include as much as cooperation and communication as possible. Lumsden (1997) suggested that the arts can help to foster a creative process to rebuild social relations, considering creativity as an intrinsic characteristic facilitated by art-based programmes.

³⁶ Peacebuilding requires collaborative work and co-responsibility between local/national public institutions and civil society — which brings together leaders, social organisations, cultural and environmental networks, universities, media, churches, and non-governmental organisations from various regions of the country.

In Comuna 13, the citizens experienced over time a transformation in their way of thinking and acting. For example, through positive messages in the graffiti, and with actions that motivated other young people to be part of the artistic process of Casa Kolacho, they themselves started to become part of the solution rather than part of the problem. This example corroborates the study of the British Council (2012) that found that the arts stimulate problem-solving. However, in the process of peacebuilding the ongoing collaboration of the participants “is usually essential if the process is to be effective” (Tillett, 2005, p. 63), which means that it requires levels of cooperation. This argument aligns with Winner *et al.* (2013), who pointed out that social relations are crucial in peace theory.

Participatory and community art in Comuna 13 allowed the construction of a culture of peace, citizens developed the skills to resolve conflicts and fight for justice in a non-violent way, respecting their territory and each individual. A clear example are the music festivals and dance activities Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition organised outdoors in the territory, where the locals took part to try and break invisible borders³⁷. The report of the Arts Council of England (2014) evidenced the benefits of dance for “reducing loneliness and alleviating depression and anxiety among people in social care environments. Dance has the ability to promote creativity and social integration and allow nonverbal stimulation and communication” (2014, p. 26). Artistic and cultural activities took to the streets, replacing guns with the joyful sound of percussion. The improvisation and creation of songs, as well as dance-steps and murals, allowed people to express themselves freely, offering scenarios that involved situations and imaginary settings. This demonstration opened the way for dialogue between armed groups from different neighbourhoods, which allowed the inhabitants of these areas to come out of isolation and reject violence, as well as to participate in different social and cultural activities. This reflects how cultural activities in Montes de María and Comuna 13 helped to reject the use of violence as a means of resolving conflicts, reinforcing the argument of Lederach (2005) of how the construction of peace begins.

³⁷ Invisible borders are strategies for armed confrontation involving different actors, who fight for supremacy or authority in a territory. Invisible borders refer to the lack of sovereignty in the territory. In this way, because of the invisible borders, the inhabitants have to get used to different lifestyles, where micro-power practices within a given territory are commonplace. Invisible borders generate a factor of insecurity for both the actors in the conflict and the inhabitants of the area, who consciously or unconsciously need to adapt to other daily activities or lifestyles (Suárez *et al.*, 2018).

In sum, this section has explored the relationship between arts-based approaches and creativity, as well as the importance of collective social artistic activities recognising the potential of arts to invoke the capacity for creativity by having the ability to formulate unconventional thinking to solve problems. To this end, I would like to address the implication of engaging in a peaceful dialogue as a way of reducing and transforming the tension of the parties.

8.2.2 Peaceful Dialogue

All conflict and conflict resolution are based on communication and language. Even physical violence usually begins with an exchange of words prior to the exchange of blows or bullets. (Tillett, 2005, p. 33). When referring to social relations, dialogue is the means of peacebuilding (Fukushima, 2011). As evidenced in this study, at the heart of every conflict there is a contradiction or a problem — something that stands in the way of progress. The case studies of Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition reflect how collective artistic practices can offer channels of communication for people to express themselves, in a neutral and peaceful space. The fact that collective activities have common objectives means that individuals have to interact and communicate with each other to achieve the expected results. Here, communication includes both listening and expressing oneself so that the other person can hear, which is the first step in conflict resolution (Fukushima, 2011).

Insofar, as collective action is only possible when there is a common interest between different actors, building social capital is a decisive factor to facilitate consensus in a group (Tepper, 2004). Likewise, Tepper also argues that teamwork evokes creativity, building trust and seeding the ground for future collaboration, because individuals can feed the potential and energy of others. Sensory Expedition, through collective song-writing activities provided a space for people involved in the project to engage in difficult conversations around personal issues, opening and expressing their personal experiences, fears, aspirations, and motivations. This resonates with Cohen (2005), when she states that art can be seen as a communicative action tool that has a lasting effect on the spheres of politics and culture as a true emancipatory force. By disrupting and reconfiguring roles and patterns of communications in the communities shattered by conflict, people who had never had a space to communicate were able to put themselves in the shoes of others thanks to the cultural and artistic spaces created by the two projects. That led to agreements based on the recognition of the other, facilitating

empathy and mutual understanding, forging social bonds, and bringing relations between individuals (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004).

8.2.3 Mutual Understanding and Empathy

Uniting a group under a common vision allows people to create new realities, to self-reflect to adjust their personal experiences and to help gain new insights about the future that people can collectively contribute to create (Rubinstein, 2011). Although creating unity is an important element in creating peace (Rubinstein, 2011), the cases of Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition focus on the process, rather than the artistic result or product, showing that it is possible to envision a future together. It is the only way the participants of the projects were willing to take risks together and fail. This builds the strongest foundation for future collaboration (McPherson *et al.*, 2019). For example, Casa Kolacho members entered the artistic process as arts explorers, rather than experts. It was important for the members of Casa Kolacho to align themselves with the values of a culture of peace, which are the axis on which the organisation was created. This means that they developed shared values, understanding and recognising each other as human beings with rights, and influencing the generation of empathy. This scenario facilitates an exchange of ideas, helping people to learn from each other, and allowing them to engage in difficult conversations. This is especially important, because to recover from conflict, being able to sincerely care for others enables the development of empathy, which is an important skill for forgiveness (Ishaq, 2006). The joint action and shared experiences of the arts-based initiatives presented in both case studies were important in helping to develop the capacity of individuals to foster awareness of themselves and others, changing perceptions and behaviours that, according to LeBaron (2011), will ultimately lead to the generation of empathy.

Based on the findings of this study, it is possible to link the concept of peacebuilding with the conditions associated with the construction of social capital, for which arts-based programmes offer a variety of innovative approaches. However, for arts and culture to be a focus of attention and an innovative way of addressing conflict, time and trust are needed. There is also a need to address political and economic barriers that limit the impact and sustainability of projects and threaten to undermine the pursuit of lasting peace.

8.3. Rethinking a Peacebuilding Model

There is no easy solution for countries emerging from conflict. Peacebuilding is a joint effort involving different people concerned on the ground (Alger, 2014). According to Galtung (2000), inclusiveness is a key to success in the long-term process of peacebuilding. There is evidence that peace agreements are only sustainable in the long term if they are monitored by the people involved, which means that power and resources must be shifted to local actors.

In this section, drawing on my findings, I outline three principles that emerged from my research and that I identified as requirements for art-based projects to have a meaningful impact in post-conflict communities. The first principle is that projects need the communities not only as beneficiaries, but also as the designers of the interventions themselves. The commitment and level of ownership of the projects come from the fact that the people of the community are a part of the whole process of design and implementation. The participation of civil society is the foundation for the construction of a culture of peace, increasing the likelihood of transparency in the process (Alger, 2014; Lederach, 1996). Moreover, cultural projects must be adapted to the specific needs of the territory in order to succeed. This resonates with the argument of Premaratna & Bleiker (2016) that there is no standard structure that could be replicated exactly in another community or location.

The second principle relates to the financial resources. I found evidence that, without financial support, the impact of the two case study projects would have been extremely limited, in terms of scope, number of beneficiaries, and quality. In addition, resources are required to be able to measure the impact of projects, which goes hand in hand with political will (Gray, 2007), the third principle. Political interest is linked to the development and funding of the arts sector. This is a weakness of the two projects, since neither had impact studies over the four years of their implementation, which limits the confidence of policymakers. Coalter (2001) corroborates this reasoning, arguing that there is a failure in defining the outcomes of cultural services and in measuring their contribution to policy agendas.

With this in mind, the two cases on which this study focused benefited from the social investments made in their territories. In the case of Comuna 13, the construction of the public library, the electric stairs and the participative projects generated favourable conditions for the artists to come together and create a successful cultural project: Casa Kolacho. The second case

study, Sensory Expedition, was financed entirely by the State through the Ministry of Culture, but it is now going through uncertain times as its continuity depends too much on political will. This reflects the relevance of the articulation between arts practitioners, their audiences, government institutions and policymakers, as well as the need for a greater understanding of the value of arts and culture in Colombia.

8.3.1 Civic Engagement and Participatory Art at a Local Community Level

As Gielen *et al.* (2015) highlights, citizens are not just important for legitimising or consulting an intervention. Instead, he pointed out that they must be an integral part of the whole process, from the conception of the idea and beyond. Achieving this successfully implies understanding the community as a subject of knowledge that knows its environment better than any external agent, and as a subject of action, important to be taken into account to be part of the peace projects designed to transform their realities. Equally so, Laaksonen (2008) highlights that an essential part of successful policies and programmes is the participation of those who are the intended beneficiaries. In the same vein, Kliksberg (1999) argues that the mobilisation of social capital and culture as active agents of economic and social development requires a broad consensus between the State and the civil society. In other words, “one of the most important roles of art in post-conflict societies is its ability to restore victims’ capacities to participate in reconciliation processes” (Naidu-Silverman, 2015, p. 11).

As demonstrated in the findings of this study, projects born from affected communities have a greater level of acceptance and success. This is corroborated by Naidu-Silverman, who argues that “rebuilding of society in the aftermath of violence requires careful context-specific interventions” (2015, p. 9). This relates to Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition projects, which have been implemented in their territories for more than four years, generating trust and legitimacy for the work carried out. In parallel, Premaratna and Bleiker (2016) emphasise that artistic processes and activities can offer valuable context-specific solutions in the aftermath of conflict. Both projects built local capacity, which served to generate greater ownership by the local community, reinforcing the view of Stokfiszewski (2016) that the social realm of culture can transform individuals and their everyday realities.

Casa Kolacho is an exemplary case of a cultural intervention that contributes to peacebuilding processes. The project was the result of a grassroots initiative born from the ideas and hopes of

its own members of the community. The project grew organically to respond to the community's particular needs and interests. Its most important effect on the peacebuilding process in the Comuna 13 of Medellín was its capacity to foster a sense of local ownership among its participants, who, through the use of the arts, were able to reclaim a territory that had previously been dominated by violence, fear and hatred, and were able to re-signify it by making it a territory of art, culture, and peace. McCarthy *et al.* (2014) argue that the local ownership deepens the link between the benefits of the arts and the participation of the community in its creation. The authors underline with this argument that successful community mobilization in a specific issue in one region builds networks, trust, and cooperation on another region.

Using different forms of artistic expression, especially graffiti and rap music, Casa Kolacho created a process in which members of the community were supported to take control of their territory, painting new hopeful stories on walls that were once marked by blood, and deciding how they wanted to tell the stories of the past. As Naidu-Silverman (2015) recommends, for art and culture to meet peacebuilding goals it is important to use local tools and traditions. With graffiti, people were able to literally change the look of the *comuna*, and to transform its dark history into a hopeful, colourful future. With rap music, they were able to transform painful memories and feelings into a high-level artistic product that allowed young people to channel negative feelings of anger and fear through the beautiful and peaceful expressions of art. Most importantly, by these means, they were able to shape their territory and their history in a way that they could *choose* as members of the community. Some scholars (Cohen, 2005; Lederach, 2005; Liebmann, 1996) refer to the importance of relationships in peacebuilding processes, and how arts-based initiatives can help to materialise them. Here, the notion of ownership is key because breaking the chains of violence requires people to embrace who they are, who they have been and what they want to be. That process of recognition can emerge in understanding the dynamics and potentials of networking and creativity through arts. While those who experience violence often express a desire for change, if their environment works against being able to take personal responsibility and acknowledge relational mutuality, then peacebuilding processes can collapse. This study has demonstrated that arts and culture can bring people together and function as a medium to empower people in their territories, which can be directly linked to breaking the patterns of violence. According to Lederach:

Art is what the human hand touches, shapes, and creates and in turn what touches our deeper sense of being, our experience. The artistic process has this dialectic nature: It arises from human experience and then shapes, gives expression and meaning to, that experience. (2005, p. 34)

One of the principal qualities of arts-based approaches relates to the process of its creation. The creative dimension can be perceived either as a social process, or as the production of a work of art. In both cases, new understandings are possible, which can be the basis for opening up discussion in communities. Making and creating can be the basis for building self-esteem and empowering people. As Fukushima argues, “cultural contributions can be effective mediums for the empowerment of local people and prevent conflicts from recurring” (2001, p. 9).

By way of contrast, the Sensory Expedition project was always designed to be flexible, adapting itself to the dynamics and interests of the community. In contrast to previous governmental interventions, Sensory Expedition was not pre-designed by professional experts in the capital city and then imposed on the recipient region. The Diagnosis of Cultural Development in Colombia, commissioned by the Ministry of Culture (Ministerio de Cultura, 2013), reported that there was a disconnection between the national policies and the local cultural practices, which undermined the impact and scope of the projects and policies. The co-creation approach in which Sensory Expedition was based was intended to avoid this problem. Thanks to Sensory Expedition, local inhabitants were able to tell their own stories and to come to know the stories of others. They were able to reclaim the nocturnal hours from the claws of fear, and to transform them into a time for happiness and healing. Furthermore, they were able to recover their historical traditions which had been stripped from them because of the conflict. In a similar vein, Fukushima comprehends the inherent difficulty of this phenomena in a post conflict setting where cultural traditions “may be on the brink of disappearing as a result of prolonged conflict” (2011, p. 9), and where arts can contribute to preserve traditional local culture and provide hope for the future. The findings of this study corroborate this view, showing that through cultural and art-based approaches it is possible to develop local capacity in the community involved. Fukushima explained that the arts are means to assist:

[...] in reactivating local cultural activities, such as fabric weaving and pottery making, and cultural heritage can also help people to regain their self-esteem while empowering

local people to restart traditional industries. This enables localities to attract tourists and generate income. (2011, p. 13)

One example is the community of Montes de María that benefited from training local members of the community as project leaders, rather than bringing cultural experts from elsewhere in the country. This created an increased local capacity so that members of the community with basic knowledge in music, dance or visual arts received training and the opportunity to grow professionally, and to make a living out of their work. The same outcome was found in Casa Kolacho where members of the project were able to generate income from the graffiti tour and to contribute to the economy in the territory, resulting in its revitalisation. However, although it is vital to grow the capacity of local communities to shape the way projects evolve, these projects cannot be sustainable over time without appropriate funding and support from either national or local government, as it will be illustrated in the next section.

8.3.2 Culture through the Policymakers and Politician's Lens

The case studies that were analysed in this thesis have shown that the success of cultural interventions is influenced by the active participation of members of the community. In shaping the interventions that take place in their territory, there is also a need for adequate funding to make cultural interventions sustainable over time. As Kahane (2010) suggests, peace cannot be found in a peace agreement alone. Rather, the success of cultural interventions is highly dependent on the will of policymakers at national and local levels to deliver on policies that advocate for cultural projects and provide the funding for them to thrive. As Tobelem (2013) explains, a decision-maker from a political background may have priorities and a career plan that are not necessarily aligned with the cultural sector. This argument highlights the dilemma of the instrumentalization of arts and culture, and the need to commission economic and social impact assessments.

This opens a debate about the value of culture that has been studied broadly by different academics in the United Kingdom and by mostly western intellectuals (Holden, 2006; Belfiore, 2004; Gibson, 2008). Belfiore, for example, states that “culture is not a means to an end. It is an end itself” (2004, p. 104), referring to the intrinsic value of culture, while Gibson (2008) suggests that it is important to recognise the complexity of institutions, policies and programmes, instead of falling into simplicity to de-construct the “instrumentalist” cultural

policy agenda. These two perceptions are conceived in the triangular conceptual model proposed by Holden (2006), which brings the three types of value into dialogue: intrinsic value, instrumental value, and institutional value. It responds to the need to reconcile different interests and expectations based on a dynamic relationship between the three vertices of value.

The findings of this study demonstrate that the value that politicians assign to the arts and culture in Colombia is directly related to the economic or social impact they have on society. In other words, in Colombia the value of the arts and culture is based on their capacity to effect change, either through a reduction of violence or of the poverty gap, or through increased economic development. Although there is some recognition that instrumental values should not be the sole purpose of culture, they still dominate the discourse. Besides, according to Holden (2006), this type of value is often captured in economic impact or social studies documenting the importance of investing in culture. Conceiving arts and culture in these terms means that State investment must have a return and that impact must be measurable. As the Arts Council of England reports:

Quantifying the benefits and expressing them in terms of facts and figures that can evidence the contribution made to our collective and individual lives has always presented a problem, but it is something that arts and culture organisations will always have to do in order to secure funding from both public and private sources. (2014, p. 4)

According to Tobelem (2013), it is far from certain that culture produces more economic value than other activities. Finally, he suggests that a political strategy is needed to provide opportunities for the arts and cultural sectors; otherwise, cultural creation will be put at risk, because “while culture may be profitable, it also has a cost” (Tobelem, 2013, p. 59). In the same line, Peter Bazalgette, Chair at the Arts Council of England (2014), claims that it is crucial to raise awareness about the value of culture among those influencing investment in public and private sectors. Here, information and data can help people think of arts and culture as a “strategic national resource” (Arts Council of England, 2014, p. 4). This resonates with Mennell’s (1976) perspective that culture is a right and a social need. In parallel to this, Mennell (1976) and Klamer (2002) suggest that governments should invest in arts to ensure that access to culture is available to everyone. Furthermore, Klamer (2002) recognises the positive benefits provided by arts and culture, identifying them as public goods. In sum, this means that to

overcome social inequalities and assure equitable and broader access — thus accumulating social and cultural capital — the State must subsidise arts-based initiatives and culture.

This creates a problem for artistic and cultural organisations in Colombia, as well as for public institutions, since investments in culture are small and resources are rarely sufficient to carry out measurements or impact studies³⁸. The fact that there are insufficient resources to carry out studies — and without studies to demonstrate progress the case for increased spending is weakened — generates a vicious cycle regarding investment in culture. Until this cycle is broken and evidence supporting the social impact of the arts is assessed, culture will continue to lag behind other areas in State investment. In the testimonies of the policymakers that were interviewed for this study, politicians recognise the importance of culture and their contribution to peacebuilding but require more evidence to justify further investments and secure greater support. This argument is not only related to Colombia, but can be found worldwide (Belfiore & Bennett, 2010). Although the participants in the cultural projects are convinced of the importance of these interventions to transform their social contexts, the challenge of showing compelling results is still yet to be effectively addressed. However, without a solution to this challenge, culture will still be perceived as one of the least relevant sectors in the Colombian political sphere.

As an example, paraphrasing the statements of policymakers, it is easier for voters to see the positive impact of a bridge than the impact of a music school. Politicians can secure more popular electoral success, or economic benefits, by investing in sectors other than culture. The fact that politicians depend on votes to be re-elected, and that they see their investment in culture as a transaction to get more votes, means that the results of cultural programmes have to be easily measurable to help them win (re)election. The reality of Colombia leads to the need to develop a rigorous approach to evaluate the social impacts resulting from engagement with arts and culture, as evidence in cultural policymaking (Belfiore & Bennett, 2010). As a result, decision-making processes are constrained by these transactional results-focussed approaches. Betting on culture without being able to measure the effects is a gamble for many politicians. This short-termism is a serious problem for Colombia that prevents long term investment in

³⁸ According to the Inter-American Development Bank (2021), it is possible to state that the Latin American countries with the highest percentage share of culture in the total government budget are Costa Rica, with 0.79%, Trinidad and Tobago, with 0.69%, and Uruguay, with 0.56%. The participation of Colombia is 0.19%, with the average for the countries analysed being 0.34%.

social projects such as Sensory Expedition and Casa Kolacho. This shows how and why some politicians pursue their own utility. Moreover, as Frey (2005) points out, culture is probably not a very important argument in their utility function; others are income, prestige, and power.

Still, cases like the city of Medellín represent outliers in the decision-making efforts regarding culture. In the case of Medellín, the policy-making process works in a seemingly counter-intuitive way. Here, the local authorities did not decide to invest heavily in culture because of demonstrable results, but rather because of a conviction in how culture could become a key asset in their social transformation efforts. When evidence suggested that the usual approach of addressing violence and crime through investment in security was to be put in place again, a specific administration (Sergio Fajardo's administration in 2004) decided to pursue a different approach focused on culture and social transformation. Moreover, this conviction was sustained by the subsequent administrations that continued the commitment to arts and culture. This allowed cultural initiatives to transcend narrow administration goals to become city-wide goals. As the cases of Casa Kolacho and Comuna 13 show, the political will of city administrators was a crucial element of supporting social transformation in this troubled territory. As the findings of the case study of Casa Kolacho demonstrate, the model of Medellín has been successful in its commitment to long-term thinking about building post-conflict social capital. This approach has become an essential part of the public policy agenda and has led to the improvements in the quality of life of its inhabitants, which has gone hand in hand with economic growth³⁹.

Similarly, the case of Sensory Expedition shows how arts-based and cultural interventions are perceived as important bids that institutions have to make in order to promote culture as a transformative agent. Currently, the design and execution of cultural projects in the country is not supported by a public policy evaluation process that allows institutions to understand the impact they can expect from a project. Instead, decisions are made on the basis of a constant learning process of what was successful or unsuccessful in a project as it is implemented. This characteristic of cultural initiatives in terms of the lack of a solid empirical basis represents the need for an informed policy on arts impact assessment (Belfiore & Bennett, 2010).

³⁹ Medellín is the second largest contributor to the GDP (The Gross Domestic Product) after Bogota in Colombia (*Revista Semana*, September 23th, 2021).

To break the vicious cycle that surrounds culture in policymaking, political will is needed. As the case of Medellín shows, cultural initiatives can benefit from a blind leap of faith on the part of decision-makers who ‘dare’ to invest significantly in culture not because they are sure of the effects it can produce in terms of numbers and statistics, but because they recognise the intangible and intrinsic value that cultural initiatives can have on the affected communities. The sector needs to find the right mechanisms to ensure that the will of policymakers is transformed to the benefit of the cultural sector in a more meaningful way. Recommendations in this regard will be addressed in the next chapter.

8.3.3 Shaping the Role of Public Funding in Arts and Culture

LeBaron reminds us that “the most effective and durable interventions are those accompanied by ongoing cultural analysis” (2001, p. 3), considering the fact that it is important to develop methodologies and evidence that might be used to evaluate the components of cultural value. McCarthy *et al.* agree with this insight, highlighting “a prevailing attitude toward government that emphasises accountability and empirical justification for public support” (2004, p. 67). In a practical sense, public funding in the areas of arts and culture requires quantitative measurement of its benefits and empirical demonstration of its effects in support of the arts, which implies studies or evaluations in this regard.

The findings of this study show that the two case studies in Colombia continue to suffer from a lack of effective strategies to translate their efforts into visible results. In this sense, Naidu-Silverman (2015) outline the different challenges in assessing whether art and cultural activities contribute to the goal of peacebuilding and social reconstruction. She argues that although some organisations submit the Logical Framework Approach form to secure funding as a donor requirement, in effect the information recorded is not evidence of the project’s success, as it is more of an obligation they must comply with. In the same way, she stresses that these traditional evaluation methods must be enriched, through testimonies and anecdotes, to really demonstrate the transformation of each person’s life.

For example, Casa Kolacho adopted a self-sustaining strategy, whereby, through the creation of a strong business plan, they were able to instrumentalise their artistic expressions, transforming them into income generating activities. Through the creation of a graffiti tour, and a comprehensive set of merchandising materials, they were able to ensure the economic

sustainability of their project and have been able to address the challenges of permanent funding. Although it remains to be a community-led initiative, Comuna 13 has also been aided by the fact that the city of Medellín has made a significant contribution to support the arts and culture as a means of social development (see Figures 12 and 13). That is why Cohen analyses the role of private and public funding to foster arts and culture and recommends “specific lines of funding for peace building performance in granting programmes at private and public agencies and foundations” (2011, p. 42). In the case of Casa Kolacho, the commitment of the local government to improve the area’s infrastructure has also helped local inhabitants to develop a sense of pride in their territory. This has contributed to the local ownership of the *comuna*’s tangible and intangible assets. As Fukushima mentioned, “it is hard to gauge the outcome of cultural contributions, and it takes time for them to bear fruit, making it difficult for actors to secure funding” (2011, p. 13).

Similarly, the same argument applies to Sensory Expedition in Montes de María, where the importance of funding is even more evident. Although the project is strong and responsive, adapting to the needs of the local community, its existence would have been threatened without the effort and funding that the national government has provided. This project found strength in offering communities enough resources to foster and support local capacity building processes. Without the injection of resources that came from the national government, professional training or equipment endowment would have been almost impossible. Fukushima address this as a limitation of cultural contributions, claiming that:

Cultural contributions from outside can be conducted for a certain length of time, but cannot continue forever, so actors must find a way of enabling local people to develop ownership of cultural activities. (2011, p. 13)

In sum, adequate funding and support are crucial to facilitate the effective operation and maintenance of cultural projects in the medium and long term. One of The Gift of The Muse’s reports of conclusions (McCarthy *et al.*, 2004) is that, to achieve and gain benefits from intrinsic and instrumental value of the arts and culture, people should participate in artistic experiences for prolonged periods of time. In other words, it assumes that benefits increase in direct proportion to the level of participation in the arts. This implies that funding must be guaranteed for a sufficient period of time for people to achieve the expected results. Besides, funding is also needed to carry out impact evaluations.

Figure 16. The vicious cycle of culture in policymaking

Source: Authors' own elaboration

In this regard, the cultural sector in Colombia has become the victim of a vicious cycle that undermines its effort to contribute to nation (re)building in the context of conflict and post-conflict. For example, the Ministry of Culture faces a conundrum in which it has to decide whether to maintain the basic needs of its projects and ensure national coverage, or to carry out comprehensive policy evaluations to understand the real effects of cultural interventions in the process of social transformation. Therefore, the cultural sector is immersed in the negative cycle that is represented in Figure 16.

As Figure 16 shows, each of the elements that characterise this negative cycle work as both causes and consequences of the other elements. No matter where the cycle begins, it will encounter both a reality and a challenge that needs to be addressed. In words of O'Brien: "[...] the cultural sector faces the conundrum of proving its value in a way that can be understood by decision-makers" (2010, p. 4). In Colombia, this challenge has led to the allocation of scarce and insufficient resources, which in turn has left the cultural sector unable to develop monitoring and evaluation methods, thus unable to show how efforts translate into results that are attractive to policymakers and to politicians in charge of national and local administration. This limitation is not only present in Colombia, but more studies (Arts Council of England, 2014; Naidu-Silverman, 2015; O'Brien, 2010) illustrate the search for non-traditional

monitoring and evaluation methods to assess the benefits and value of the arts and culture that fit with evidence-based policymaking.

Measuring the success of artistic and cultural activities in contributing to peace and reconciliation efforts requires multiple strategies and the development of new and innovative assessment tools, not only from an economic and quantitative approach, but also from the intrinsic human aesthetic experience of the arts, which can come close to fully explaining the value of culture. In this sense, Naidu-Silverman states that “monitoring and evaluation is important for practitioners and policymakers because it highlights lessons learned and presents opportunities for sharing new models and identifying ways in which interventions can be improved” (2015, p. 44). Besides, it helps to inform budget allocations in the cultural field about the transformative power of the arts (Belfiore & Bennett, 2010).

Addressing the conditions of the negative cycle of culture in policymaking could allow culture not to be constantly ignored and deprived of crucial funding, enabling its development and improvement over time. Therefore, the success of culture as a means to contribute to peacebuilding is not only dependant on community participation and its frequency of engagement with arts and culture, or adequate funding, but ultimately depends on the existence of political will.

8.4 Conclusion

In this chapter I have addressed the two research questions: what role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities dealing with the legacy of the Colombian armed conflict? And what design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture? In addressing the first research question, the findings of this study corroborate existing theories on the importance of social capital, social cohesion, and post-conflict community reconstruction, and reinforce conceptualisations of the culture of peace by showing that peace in Colombia can — and should — have different approaches depending on the context. I have highlighted the relationship between the construction of social capital as an indispensable pillar for peacebuilding in Colombia and the power of culture in its capacity to reach the deepest part of the human being.

I have also highlighted, for post-conflict societies emerging such as Colombia, the correlation between the arts and the development of a culture of peace. For this purpose, three crucial premises were identified based on the analysis of the findings of this study, which can contribute to breaking the cycles of violence by preventing the emergence of future conflicts: i) creative collaboration in problem solving, ii) peaceful dialogue, and iii) mutual understanding and empathy. I have also outlined a peacebuilding model, addressing the second research question, which identifies the current challenges of design, assessment and long-term monitoring of participants and the effects of the arts on their lives. First, I explained the importance of civic engagement and cultural participation at the local community level. Second, I underlined the importance of sustainable funding to ensure investment in arts-based activities over time. Finally, I highlight the need to demonstrate the tangible impact from cultural projects in order to legitimise their value to a political system that instrumentalises public investment.

Having discussed my findings in this chapter, the final chapter explores my main conclusions, articulates my contribution to knowledge, acknowledges the limitations of the study, reflects on implications for future research, and offers recommendations for policymakers.

CHAPTER 9: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

9.0 Introduction

In this thesis, I have explored the role that arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in Colombia. I have focused on the legacy of the armed conflict and on the design and delivery models to produce beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture. By doing so, I have identified a gap between policy makers and the allocation of resources for peacebuilding efforts through art-based projects. I suggest that when policy evaluations are not conducted during and after the project development, the ability to demonstrate effective outcomes is undermined, leading to the sector being undervalued.

I have also analysed cultural value, the instrumental and intrinsic dichotomy, and its implications in the conception of peacebuilding projects by policy makers and participants of cultural programmes in Colombia. I have demonstrated the impact of two case study projects, highlighting their role as spaces for rebuilding relationships in the aftermath of armed conflict, and for stimulating the creation of bonding and bridging social capital. Moreover, I have addressed the importance of integrated and collaborative cultural projects involving multiple parties sharing a common goal, because they have the potential to facilitate a positive transformation in the lives of the participants. Also, I emphasised the fact that Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition no longer think of art with the aim of producing only a cultural good, but as a means to think and create new realities; in sum, those practices focus on the process rather than the result. Here, I demonstrate that bringing people together enables the promotion and strengthening of civil society, which is a necessary prerequisite for a peaceful future.

In this concluding chapter, I address the research objectives and questions that underpin the thesis and that reflect upon both the research process and its outcomes. The chapter is divided into seven sections. Following this introduction, there is a summary of the thesis and its key findings. The third section outlines my theoretical, policy and methodological contributions to knowledge, taking each of them separately and focusing on shaping public policy engagement with culture, and identifying different pitfalls in the use of arts and culture as an instrumental mechanism to achieve peace. Finally, I address the limitations of the study before presenting suggestions for future research, as well as recommendations for policy makers and arts

practitioners to enable a more meaningful involvement of arts and culture in the peacebuilding process in Colombia and other territories emerging from conflict.

9.1 Thesis Summary

Overall, this study has sought to explain how the culture of violence in Colombia has caused fractures in the construction of social capital in communities affected by the armed conflict. I have shown how arts-based activities, carried out hand in hand with the local community, can have a positive effect on the re-establishment of social relationships and on people's behaviours, thereby fostering a culture of peace. Lastly, the study explored the opportunities and challenges inherent to the integration of art and culture into Colombian peacebuilding processes. The study concludes that increased attention to grassroots cultural initiatives offers untapped potential for peacebuilding, although success depends on the interaction between policymakers and cultural organisations.

In chapter two, I argued that social capital, social culture, and social cohesion are the key concepts that provide the catalyst for social transformation through culture. Furthermore, I suggested that there are four core elements to address the outcomes of the armed conflict. First, *networks*, understood as the social interactions that occur inside cultural projects which foster scenarios for collaborative work and cooperation among project participants. Second, *trust*, an element that is usually missing in contexts that are influenced by the presence of violence. Thanks to the construction of spaces where non-violent interactions and peaceful expressions are promoted, communities can build bonds of trust among their members, and therefore, it is possible to transition from a culture of violence to a culture of peace. Third, *values and norms*, understood not as a rigid or tangible norm system, but rather as the formation of informal sets of rules that mediate the relations between members of the community. Finally, *mutual understanding and empathy*, a feeling that allows members of the community to act positively towards each other and in the full confidence of a positive reciprocal reaction. In this chapter, I also identified a lack of consensus on the most appropriate methodologies to gain understanding of the intangible effects that culture can have in processes of social cohesion and social capital formation. I suggested that cultural interventions are restricted by being bound to monetary or cost-effectiveness measurements. These traditional measurement techniques have undermined efforts for culture to be made more relevant to those in charge of policy and decision-making processes.

In chapter three, I analysed the ways peacebuilding processes benefit from the inclusion of cultural interventions as tools that can contribute to the process of healing societies in conflict. Here, I argued that reconciliation plays a crucial role in efforts towards conflict resolution. Even though different definitions of the concept of reconciliation exist, there is an agreement on the fact that these efforts depend on three steps: dialogue, empathy building, and creativity. Through the lens of cultural engagement in the case studies of Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition, I argued that the creation of these creative spaces, using art and culture as means of communication, is paramount in fostering environments for dialogue and empathy building. In essence, arts-based initiatives like those discussed in this thesis are assertive, nonviolent ways to address conflict. The case studies used arts to communicate the human experience in ways that have nurtured peace. For example, the testimonies of the participants of Sensory Expedition demonstrate how music was used as a tool to communicate and transform the way people think and act, changing the dynamic of the conflict. It is also important to understand that much like art, the approaches towards reconciliation are very diverse and cannot be easily replicated.

With the aim of analysing the role that arts and culture can play in peace-building processes — and the way in which they impact societies that have been stricken by conflict — I conducted field research activities with two existing arts-based projects in Colombia. Undertaking this research allowed me to explore the way in which the concepts, challenges and nuances identified in previous chapters come into play in the real world. In order to fulfil this purpose, chapter four explained the methodology applied through interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA), where the aim of the study was to capture the essence of project beneficiaries' experiences through interviews and participant observation. It also focused on two case studies and covered the ethical considerations of the study and its authenticity.

In chapter five, I presented the findings of the first case study, Casa Kolacho, a cultural centre created in 2009 in the city of Medellín, Colombia. The centre is based in Comuna 13, the area of the city with the highest incidence and prevalence of conflict, motivated by both the historical armed conflict in Colombia and the effects of drug trafficking in the city and in the country. Casa Kolacho was created by members of the community to provide children and young people with an alternative place to spend their free time and to escape the day-to-day violent context of Comuna 13. In chapter six, I presented the findings of the second case study,

Sensory Expedition, a State-led peacebuilding effort, located in the region of Montes de María. This chapter highlighted the project's conception as a grassroots effort in public policy, which contrasts with the history of policy creation, both in Montes de María and in the general context of Colombia.

The third findings chapter (chapter seven) focused on the importance of peacebuilding among all actors in society, including civil society, private enterprise, and the public sector. Given that funding for the arts is limited, this chapter relied on dialogue with Colombian policy makers and politicians to explore the limitations and opportunities for supporting arts and culture in the country. My findings revealed the importance of qualitative assessment of social value and the need to commission impact studies to assign value to the support of a given project in the cultural field, as the arts are in constant competition for funds with other sectors such as health and education.

In chapter 8, I analysed the study findings, highlighting the relationship between peacebuilding and the strengthening of the social fabric through the consolidation of collaborative networks that generate social capital. In the same way, I associated the arts with the generation of values for a culture of peace needed in the reconciliation and peacebuilding processes. I argued that peacebuilding involves creative collaboration in problem solving, peaceful dialogue, mutual understanding, and empathy. Finally, I addressed the challenges of designing a peacebuilding model that can contribute to conflict transformation.

9.2 Key study findings

This study has explored the role that arts-based and cultural interventions can play in peacebuilding processes in the aftermath of the Colombian armed conflict and, in by doing so, has examined what policymakers can do to demonstrate commitment to and support the functioning of cultural projects on the ground, so that they can address the precarious situation faced by communities in the aftermath of the Colombian conflict. To achieve this goal, I developed two research questions:

RQ1: What role do arts and cultural initiatives play in facilitating social cohesion and community rebuilding in communities dealing with the legacy of the Colombian conflict?

RQ2: What design and delivery models are most effective in producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture?

In order to answer the research questions, three research foci were pursued. First, the selection of two case studies (Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition) that allowed an insight into the arts-based approaches to the peacebuilding process. Second, the use of IPA along with participant observation of the case study cultural projects. And third, in-depth interviews that helped to illustrate how arts-based and cultural interventions can address and ameliorate the effects of conflict on people in different geographical settings. The next few sections summarise the main findings of my research.

9.2.1 Peacebuilding Requires Rebuilding Respectful Relationships

The war in Colombia has left deep fissures in the social fabric of the population, with feelings of hatred, revenge and frustration increasing over time. Spaces that were once for recreation and enjoyment were overshadowed by death and insecurity. It was unsafe to leave the house, or talk to anyone, because some members of the community could be supporting the guerrillas or the paramilitary groups. This accentuated a weakening of the social fabric and the dilution of social capital, which is based on trust, mutual respect, and reciprocity. Moreover, this study showed that without these values it is impossible to emerge from the conflict and establish new forms of relationships, which are necessary for peacebuilding. Findings from this study demonstrate that until the values associated with a culture of violence can be transformed into values aligned with a culture of peace, it will not be possible to achieve and maintain peace. Without social cohesion, it is very difficult to generate social capital, as there is a direct relationship between these two concepts.

The literature suggests that the formation of networks and connections is achieved through interaction based on common goals and shared interests. This interaction allows the creation of new relationships and the strengthening of community. Here, the formation of trust can help build a sense of belonging, community identity and social cohesion. As discussed in chapter three, the power of arts-based activities can help to facilitate dialogue, to solve problems in a creative manner, enhancing mutual understanding and promoting empathy, which are crucial conditions to achieve reconciliation. Specifically, I found by experimenting with new ways of

approaching their reality through graffiti painting, joining in a song composition or dancing, the project participants discover different ways to communicate and experience the intrinsic benefits of the arts, as individuals and as members of a group.

This study has found that, through participation in the arts, it is possible to access the benefits they offer, to create a new perception of oneself and others, to transform behaviours and relationships, and to be open to express feelings and emotions. Based on these insights, arts and cultural activities can be seen as a communicative experience that allows people to form social capital and contribute to the development of social cohesion.

9.2.2 Reconciliation is a Matter of Context

Reconciliation involves a set of processes designed to change relations of hate, revenge and mistrust into relationships of trust, mutual understanding, and empathy. Mechanisms to enshrine a culture of peace are necessary to move from a divided past to a shared future. That is why this study suggests that arts-based initiatives can help to change perceptions and open alternative communication channels in order to recognise the other as a subject of rights. This assertion assumes that peace is achieved when the whole society, involving different sectors and parties, come together collectively to make it happen — not simply by signing a peace agreement. I have demonstrated that reconciliation cannot be imposed from above, but rather needs to be built from the bottom up and with the active participation of the communities affected.

Secondly, the findings of this study suggest that reconciliation is a matter of context. Each case study operates in different settings, with different communities, which reflects the fact that the way to deal with conflict varies in each one of them. Communities have different roots, traditions, and customs. In turn, this basic fact is directly related to the way they choose to deal with peacebuilding, especially when it comes to the form of artistic expression that will function as their primary medium. While in Montes de María, through the Sensory Expedition project, people wanted to dance and celebrate their traditional music, in Comuna 13 people preferred urban art, street art, graffiti, rap and hip-hop. This study demonstrates that each territory where the conflict is taking place has its own particularities, which leads to a challenge of setting in place tailor-made measures that respond to the needs of each territory. Given this complexity, each case needs to be treated differently. In other words, context-specific

interventions are required, as what is simple in one place may be daring in another. Even peace is diverse because people understand it in many different ways.

Finally, I have suggested that while there is no magic formula to heal the wounds of the war and to rebuild the social fabric, arts-based projects can be adapted to the circumstances of each territory and each community to make a difference. Casa Kolacho and Sensory Expedition are a proof of this. Once recognised that peacebuilding is a complex and long-term process, it is important to respect the diversity of approaches that exist in different parts of the territory.

9.2.3 The Value of Co-Design in Conflict Resolution

This study has also shown that while arts-based interventions are certainly a means to facilitate dialogue and mutual understanding, it is also crucial that the communities affected are involved in the projects from their conception. This is necessary to ensure that projects are in tune with the local context and reality. This is fully in line with the approaches advocated by peacebuilding scholars and practitioners and their perceptions of the contribution of culture and the arts to the transformation of conflict. The ability to meaningfully involve members of the community in all phases of the projects was a clear element present in both case studies. For example, Casa Kolacho evolved from the ideas, interests, and hopes of the community members themselves. They shaped the project to correspond to the needs identified at the core of the community itself.

Perhaps more surprisingly, this co-design characteristic was also found in the Sensory Expedition initiative. This project was created with the understanding that, for a cultural intervention to be successful in a community, it cannot be designed in an office in the capital city where all the major decisions are taken — and then transplanted to a rural setting. Rather, the intervention needed to be flexible and responsive, so that it could be shaped by the interests and practices of the beneficiary communities. How this process would proceed could only be decided by community members themselves.

As shown by both cultural interventions and the wider findings of the study, the participation of the community at every stage of the project, from planning to implementation, was key to not be seen as an imposition or as a decontextualized effort to meet the needs of a region. Instead, the projects were viewed as initiatives created *by* community members *for* community

members. This crucial factor allowed the host communities to develop a sense of ownership around the projects, seeing them as part of their social wealth, which had to be protected and cared for every day.

However, the findings of this study also demonstrate that for cultural and arts practices to be effective in a peacebuilding scenario, they need to facilitate social interaction. In other words, it was found that participants needed to interact with each other, in order to stimulate the collaborative action to address their own problems and promote a peaceful dialogue, and thus the construction of social capital and social cohesion, which are essential for peacebuilding.

9.2.4 Cultivating Collective Cultural Practices

This study has also demonstrated that art and cultural activities alone cannot achieve peacebuilding outcomes. Instead, I have shown that people help achieve peacebuilding outcomes through the collective practice of music in a choir or band, working towards a common goal. These sorts of activities can contribute to the creation of values that promote peaceful situations, tolerance, solidarity, and result in the construction of networks and relationships, which are — according to Bourdieu — fundamental for social cohesion and social capital. Music is one example, but dance or painting (in the case of the murals in Medellín) also possess similar values. This study has shown that it is not possible to build peace if people are alone listening to music, or dancing, because togetherness and collaboration are also necessary.

Another conclusion from this study relates to the importance of the creation of participatory spaces that enabled the interaction between members of the community, which is called participatory art. In the case of Casa Kolacho, the commitment to collaborative work emerged from the beginning of the project and was crucial for its sustainability over time. As it is a locally-led initiative that does not depend on financial support from public or private institutions, the project members understood that the only way to maintain the project was to work in collaboration with the community and its assets. For example, as a result of the collaborations that took place among its members, Casa Kolacho became an efficient organisation. They succeeded in setting up marketing and business plans that included the creation of a graffiti tour through Comuna 13 (where they charged tourists a fee for guiding them through the art in the walls of the *comuna*), and other experiences such as composing a

song with local musicians, watching street dancers perform live, and offering tourists the opportunity to do graffiti themselves. Additionally, they created merchandise (t-shirts, stickers, hats, paints, and different types of souvenirs) to generate additional revenues.

Moreover, facilitating collaborative work also contributed to the peacebuilding efforts that were at the core of the projects. Members of the community helped each other by putting their best skills at the service of the project and contributing to peacebuilding in two main ways. First, through collaborative work, creating and strengthening networks among members of the community, which highlights the bonding and bridging social capital that was a key part of the conceptual underpinning of this study. People were able to identify individuals or groups in their community who possessed certain skills or capacities that could be useful for the project (and in other areas of community life). As a result, new networks of professional or informal collaboration were created through the projects. These enabled members of the community to develop closer relationships with their neighbours and former enemies. All of this demonstrates that the strengthening of social cohesion ties between the individuals who were part of the cultural initiatives did occur. Finally, in addition to the four factors outlined above, policymakers have a decisive role to play in this context.

9.3 Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to broader debates about the role of arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process, and also in other areas experiencing conflict. It makes a contribution to knowledge in three main areas: methodological, theoretical, and policy.

9.3.1 Methodological Contribution

This study makes an original methodological contribution in the way evidence from arts and cultural projects can be collected, curated, and shared. The study expands on the limited research on understanding and capturing the intrinsic benefits of the arts, especially in the Latin American context. It is the first study to make use of IPA as a methodological approach to assess the lived experience of people living in post-conflict environments and benefitting from access to art and cultural activities. This is original in the Colombian context, which helps to assess people's experiences in arts and cultural initiatives. Spending time with members of the community helps researchers to better understand the unique meanings they attach to their

cultural experiences. Few studies have been developed from the time spent in the territory, sharing experiences with participants in the arts-based projects. My study is original in its design and implementation, as I spent time with project members, participants, and their families, and gained greater insight into the lived experiences as a result. Other researchers may follow a similar approach, familiarising themselves with the host country environment before more formal research enquiries commence.

In Colombia, for budgetary reasons, it is not common to measure the impact of projects, and when it is done, the evaluator does not usually spend time in the territory. Instead, they send surveys digitally, or the enquiry is conducted by telephone, with multiple response options. In contrast, during the completion of this study, using the IPA method, I immersed myself in the field, conducting lengthy interviews with participants. This made it easier for participants to open up and express what they felt and thought about their cultural project.

However, research has demonstrated the importance of acknowledging the social impact of arts and culture (Arts Council of Northern Ireland, 2015). To date, most of the studies reviewed evidence of methodological gaps establishing causality between arts engagement and personal behaviours. As participation in the arts is not always tangible, it can be challenging to capture its benefits. For that reason, the IPA approach is valuable because it has the potential to explain the nature of things, the essence and veracity of phenomena. It is a method that can produce rich data on people's lived experiences, capturing in people's own words the nature of their cultural lives in their complexity, contributing to understand the nature of individual uniqueness and cultural experience in areas of conflict. Within this paradigm, it is not possible to analyse a phenomenon without accepting that it is anchored in the meaning of those who live it and of those who experience it. This makes it possible to see the world from the point of view of the participant in the artistic practice and capture its value — how the participant interprets the world through artistic practice provides a clearer understanding of culture's unique value.

While intrinsic benefits are mainly personal, they can also have spill-over effects on society. In summary, this thesis provides a useful new approach based on a broader understanding of the benefits of arts engagement in a peacebuilding environment.

9.3.2 Theoretical and Policy Contributions

This section addresses two innovative ways of changing and shifting policy engagement with culture in order to build a culture of peace and understand the value of culture in policymaking: the vicious cycle of culture in policymaking and the co-design strategy model.

9.3.2.1 The Vicious Cycle of Culture in Policy

This study makes a contribution to theory and policy in the field of arts, culture, and peacebuilding. This was achieved by shaping public policy engagement with culture, and by identifying and articulating the pitfalls of using arts and culture as an instrumental mechanism to achieve peace. Through this model cycle, I show how to overcome the current debates on the value of culture (Belfiore, 2004; Gray, 2009; Holden, 2004) and its relationship with funding and policy dilemmas. I demonstrate that in the case of Colombia, it is crucial to provide evidence to justify government investment and expenditure in arts and culture.

In the same line, building on Holden's theory, this study reaffirms the importance of the instrumental value of culture. It adds to the theoretical contribution of Holden (2006) and Gibson (2008), by integrating existing bottlenecks (see Figure 16) to understand the significance of culture with a social outcome, by showing four gaps that combine the vicious cycle of culture in the policy: i) insufficient resource allocation; ii) lack of comprehensive monitoring and evaluation methods; iii) incapacity to translate efforts into results; and iv) the cultural sector being overlooked. At the moment, the policy level in Colombia recognises the instrumental value of culture in the agenda as a crucial element.

My contribution to policy emphasises how an instrumental understanding of arts and culture can contribute to public welfare, increasing economic growth and social capital, for which politicians and policy makers require evidence to assess the social and economic benefits of the arts to secure public financial support. Although the instrumentalization of culture is frowned upon by some authors, throughout this study I have demonstrated that in Colombia it can be a fertile way to bring policy makers closer to the cultural projects that are being developed and others that can be carried out in post-conflict zones.

My contribution reveals the need to develop evaluation and impact studies to measure the peacebuilding outcomes of arts-based and cultural projects, in order to assess their need for funding. In turn, I have demonstrated the need for the cultural sector in Colombia to show quantifiable results to generate greater interest from politicians, which is reflected in greater funds. In summary, I have identified a direct relationship between policy makers, economic resources, and the demonstrable instrumental benefits of the arts, since there is a desire from policy makers and politicians to measure arts and cultural effects to prove their value in peacebuilding terms and contribution to social well-being, which results in a more stable cultural economy and one less likely to erupt in conflict.

My contribution to knowledge can help cultural and peace organisations commission studies and evaluations to measure the results of their activities. It also opens up a responsibility on the part of the public sector and institutions to train the arts sector in methodologies for measuring their impact and charting any changes in policy and practice as a result of planned interventions. Even if conflict resolution requires conventional political, military, and economic approaches, I have illustrated the contribution that culture can have in fostering peace, facilitating mutual understanding, dialogue, and creativity to solve problems. However, for culture to be an innovative way to deal with conflict, the sum of different actors is needed. Here, the role of policy makers is indispensable to allocate resources and advocate for secure funding.

In the same line, this study has demonstrated the need for the arts as a public good and a social need that should be subsidised by the State. When talking to Colombian policymakers and politicians, the short-termism of politicians who seek immediate measurable results was evident. As a consequence, money is invested in infrastructure, security, and housing where investment produces tangible results that can be translated into either political or economic capital. This creates a dilemma for the arts and cultural sector due to its relative immeasurability and intangibility.

9.3.2.2 The Co-Design Strategy Model

I also make a contribution by developing a model that can be employed when implementing projects that seek conflict resolution: a co-design strategy (see Figure 17). By recognising different theories of what is required for peacebuilding (Galtung, 2000; Paloutzian &

Kalayjian, 2009), I have demonstrated that there are a range of conditions that are essential for constructive conflict resolution: the establishment of a culture of peace, based on respectful relationships, and the development of collective cultural practices, which must be set according to the context and local reality of the area of conflict. All of the above by having the participation of the communities in the conception of the project at its core. I argue that the success of the projects relies on the development of participatory methodologies to understand the needs and realities of the people living in those contexts.

Figure 17. The co-design strategy

Source: Author

Finally, based on my findings, my contribution addresses research question two, dealing with current gaps on how arts-based approaches can be more effective as a means to resolve conflict. It also helps to understand the different dimensions of producing beneficial peacebuilding outcomes through arts and culture. Following this section, a set of recommendations derived from the research are proposed. These include implications for policy makers, politicians, and arts practitioners, proposing a future cultural and policy agenda.

9.4 Recommendations from the Research

This final section focuses on recommendations based on the research study as a whole and based on my professional experience as Secretary of Culture of Ibagué. The role I have occupied has allowed me to influence and change the policy process in the city of Ibagué. I have demonstrated that it is possible to defend culture and its value as an important part of the peacebuilding process. I successfully created the Observatory of Culture in the city and promoted the creation of the Institute of Cultural and Creative Industries to conduct research on suitable ways of measuring the contribution of different arts-based projects to the economy and the welfare of society. By showing the impact arts and culture have on society, the Mayor of Ibagué approved a doubling of the budget for culture in the city. This evidence a significant and unique contribution to knowledge in policy terms in a local government context. The following recommendations are addressed to an array of actors that can influence and strengthen the peacebuilding field: politicians, policy makers, cultural practitioners, stakeholders, and those who advocate for the field of arts and culture and its contribution to peacebuilding.

9.4.1 Recommendation 1: Engage Policy Makers Practically

Bring those in government (politicians and policy makers) closer to culture. Let them experience it, let them see the changes in the people who practice it and in their environment. It is important for them to learn that although it is a long-term investment, it has a positive impact. Similarly, it is my duty as an academic and a policy maker to encourage public and private cultural organisations to develop impact studies that show that the investment in projects like the ones presented in this thesis have a real positive impact. For example, the Peace Commission created by the Congress in Colombia should not only monitor the implementation of the peace agreement, but also recognise the social and cultural dynamics of

each territory that is seeking to mitigate the escalation of the conflict. In this sense, arts and culture can be recognised as a bridge for dialogue between the State and the different civil society actors, and as a cooperation space to oversee the construction of territorial peace.

9.4.2 Recommendation 2: Strengthen Partnerships among Peace Stakeholders

As mentioned in this thesis, peacebuilding is a complex and multifaceted process that requires the participation of a wide range of stakeholders. In this sense, fostering inclusion and participation is essential to ensure that all stakeholders are included and engaged in the peace process. This requires commitment, inclusiveness and cooperation among all relevant stakeholders, including individuals, groups or organisations that are directly or indirectly affected by the peacebuilding process or have a role to play in achieving sustainable peace.

In Colombia, it is common for different public institutions and international organisations to work in a disjointed manner. The Presidential Office for Stabilisation and Consolidation of Peace should be the entity that regulates and articulates inter-institutional work. Here, institutions and programmes that are in the same territory should join efforts. However, it is important to acknowledge that it is not possible to implement standardised public policies and projects for the whole country, and that is why the country's diversity should be recognised at the moment to implement and formulate projects. Here are some recommendations for stakeholders:

1. **Governments:** They play a key role in peacebuilding efforts, as they are responsible for creating and enforcing laws and policies that can either contribute to peace or exacerbate conflict. They can provide resources and infrastructure and support local peacebuilding initiatives.

2. **Civil society organisations:** These are non-governmental organisations that represent the interests of various social groups, such as women, youth, and marginalised communities. Civil society organisations can help facilitate dialogue and build trust in their territory.

3. **Communities:** Local communities affected by conflict often bear the brunt of violence and insecurity. It is essential to involve them in peacebuilding efforts and ensure that their perspectives and needs are taken into account when designing arts-based peacebuilding programmes.

4. International organisations: Such as the United Nations. They can provide technical assistance and funding for peacebuilding efforts.

5. Private sector: It can also contribute to peacebuilding by investing in local economies and creating jobs, which can reduce poverty and social inequality, both of which are drivers of conflict.

6. Academia and research institutions: Scholars and researchers can provide evidence-based analysis on the causes of conflict and the effectiveness of different peacebuilding approaches.

In light of the research findings, effective peacebuilding requires the active participation and cooperation of a wide range of stakeholders with different capacities, resources, and perspectives. Furthermore, it is recommended that these stakeholders engage in dialogue to identify common interests and find mutually acceptable solutions to the conflict.

In summary, networks of cooperation between different organisations need to be created and strengthened. The relationship cannot only be from the State to the organisations, but also between organisations in the territory. In this way, projects, policies, and programmes will respond better to local needs, and community organisations can be strengthened and more effective. This means that when there are many institutions and programmes in the same territory, they need to work in an articulated manner with the objective of optimising resources and generating a greater impact. Otherwise, their impact will fade away, because they all try to contribute to peace but in a disorganised way, ignoring the efforts of other programmes or organisations.

9.4.3 Recommendation 3: Empower the Ministry of Culture

The Colombian Ministry of Culture has a vital role to play in helping to share good practice and build capacity in both the cultural sector and local government. The local government should work jointly with the Ministry of Culture in order to find alternative funding mechanisms to support arts-based projects and diversify their funding. For this, the intrinsic and instrumental values of the arts must be recognised and addressed.

Similarly, it is necessary that the Ministry of Culture, as the most important cultural entity in the country, proposes guidelines to quantify and measure the impact of arts and cultural

activities to account for other dimensions of culture's transformative power. This is crucial, because an adequate understanding of cultural value will require a better account of the essence of the cultural and artistic experiences. To this end, I propose the creation of an Observatory of Arts and Culture as a centre for information and research which outlines suitable methodologies that can be employed to demonstrate the importance of the arts in the transformation of the armed conflict.

Besides, I propose that the Ministry of Culture should open a special funding method for community-based projects that promote dialogue, creativity, and mutual understanding. A clear example is the financial support for the development of projects like Sensory Expedition, built with the community, adapted to the needs of the territory, and achieving positive social impacts on the territory. The Ministry of Culture must recognise the key role it plays in the current peacebuilding process, mobilising resources and advocating for public policy.

9.4.4 Recommendation 4: Innovate in New Ways to Achieve Peace

The culture of peace is not only achieved through peace education. Investment in peacebuilding initiatives needs to be considered in a transversal way. Peace education should not only be given in a classroom and with people taking notes on how peace should be. The understanding of peace should be lived, it should be experienced, so one of the methods that can be viable is to use the arts as a medium, as a channel to transmit the message that people want to give. It needs to be interactive and experiential, as participants should explore group problem-solving processes.

9.5 Limitations of the Research

In this section, four main limitations are identified, related to the research practice and the analysis of data. Firstly, there was a limitation in achieving equal representation of women and men in the interviews conducted. This resulted in sampling limitations, with a majority of men due to the lack of available or accessible female participants in the arts-based programmes.

Although the research design was not biased towards male-centred experiences, it was clear that there were more men than women participating in artistic and cultural projects in conflict zones. This has to do with the power dynamics in society and the role of women in Colombia,

which is still within a conservative and patriarchal vision — with women being relegated mainly to housework and childcare — especially in rural areas and far from the urban centre. This is the case of Montes de María and Casa Kolacho, where teenage pregnancy is a recurring problem, which means that men have more opportunities than women for this type of activities.

However, this thesis recognises the lack of gender equality in the research process, which in turn is a reality in Colombia, and also acknowledges the importance of considering the perspectives and experiences of all genders in the design and implementation of the research.

Secondly, although I had the opportunity to undertake fieldwork in both case study areas, my time was nevertheless, short. For safety issues, I had a strict field visit schedule. This meant that I had limited time to interact with the participants in the project and gain a better understanding of their environment. I was, for example, unable to make contact with the parents of all project beneficiaries. I consider that doing so would have enriched the research by enabling insight into some of the longitudinal effects of project participation. In a similar line, this research focuses on individuals over the age of 18 years. It would be valuable to also interview individuals under the age of 18 alongside their parents. This would have allowed me to take a much broader look at the impact of the projects across all age groups and work with a range of different actors. In addition, another point that I consider it important for future research to propose to the project participants to keep a diary or record of their activities by video or audio, in which they themselves describe over a period of time the effect that working with the arts has on them, how they feel about the project and the experience they have lived. I aim to undertake such research in the future.

The other noticeable limitation was not taking into consideration other social or educational programmes that were being developed in the territory where the cultural projects were established. Although some investments that improved the lives of the participants were named, there was no identification of other investments in social activities that had a positive social effect on the community. This would also have enriched the study because it would have incorporated other points of view and generate new insights in achieving peace. This point would consider external factors that influence the development of the cultural project.

Finally, it would have been useful to assess impact from the beginning of the arts-based initiatives in order to be able to demonstrate, in greater detail and accuracy, the impact of arts

and culture on peacebuilding. For this reason, it is essential to have a reference point from the beginning of the project, as well as studies throughout the project, to have greater precision in its social impact.

9.6 Implications for Future Research

To ameliorate the limitations of this research and also to explore further the role of arts and culture in the Colombian peacebuilding process, I propose three further research avenues. First, there is a need to conduct fieldwork and explore more diverse voices in understanding the part played by the participants from arts-based programmes. In this sense, it is crucial to involve women more. Given that cultural activities such as theatre, literature, music and art have the potential to mitigate gender inequalities to some extent by challenging traditional gender stereotypes, cultural activities can portrait women and men in non-traditional roles and highlight the diversity of gender identities and expressions. Arts-based programmes can promote gender equality by celebrating the achievements and contributions of women and girls in cultural life; they can also provide opportunities for women and girls to develop skills and confidence, express themselves creatively and participate in public discourse, as well as offer educational opportunities such as music or crafts workshops, which can improve their access to knowledge and resources. Moreover, in the context of peacebuilding, it can foster a sense of community and solidarity among women and girls, providing a platform for networking, sharing experiences and building supportive relationships.

However, while cultural activities can have a positive impact on gender inequality, structural barriers must also be addressed to achieve meaningful and lasting change. Nevertheless, cultural activities can complement these efforts by promoting gender equality and empowering women and girls to participate fully in cultural life.

In order to achieve this, future studies would benefit from interviewing women, girls and the families of the participants. This would provide a broader view concerning their perceptions of the intervention and the impact that participation had on the individuals and their environment. I encourage researchers to spend more time in the field to gain a better understanding of project reality and to get to know the beneficiaries better. It is also recommended to increase the number of interviews in order to be able to cover more and include other points of view. Although, while this research acknowledges the absence of more women voices in the research

topic, at the same time it demonstrates a commitment to actively include gender equality in future studies, so that their experiences and perspectives are adequately represented.

Second, one of the key findings of this thesis is the fact that peace projects should be formulated and developed hand in hand with the community. However, there are limited co-design strategies or methodologies to achieve this. For this reason, I consider it relevant to study in depth participatory approaches as a creative practice in the peace and artistic fields, and to provide guidelines on how to build the project together. The collective design of arts-based peace projects has not been widely studied, and it opens ways for communities to participate through interactive methodologies from the grassroots level, identifying shared values, defining the phenomenon, and developing possible solutions and testing them.

Finally, it is important to value the role of arts and culture by making their impact visible. For that reason, the third further research avenue is the need to determine project impact and methodologies to gauge the project results from different perspectives: social, economic, and cultural. This warrants further examination in terms of their contribution to peacebuilding. Besides, by doing so, it is possible to inform policy makers and politicians about the positive benefits of arts in society. In other words, advocate for art in practice.

9.7 Chapter Summary

What if we bet on arts and culture, even if they do not have the immediate and visible effects that politicians and policy makers want and need to see? Why don't we try to approach arts and culture from another angle, and recognise their value? Why is it difficult to accept and conceive the instrumentalization of the arts as a transformative option to build more peaceful societies?

After decades of armed conflict and systemic violence, Colombia has a unique opportunity to leave behind feelings of hatred and resentment and work together towards a better future. However, big changes require time, resources, and political will, as well as the commitment of all citizens. As a scholar, cultural manager, and former Secretary of Culture in Ibagué, I have had the opportunity to put into practice the models presented here and see their positive effects on the community. This experience gave me the opportunity to double the resources allocated for culture in my city, and to carry out projects hand in hand with the communities. Therefore,

this thesis not only offers ideas related to theory, but also on how art-based projects should be implemented. I am a living expression of what I have said in my thesis.

This thesis opened up new alternatives for those countries and territories that, like Colombia, are recovering from armed and social conflicts, and want to transcend the ravages of violence. It also reminds us that arts and culture are indispensable to that goal. This thesis, above all, is a document of hope because a peaceful future is possible.

REFERENCES

- Adonis, C. K. (2017). Generational Victimhood in Post-Apartheid South Africa: Perspectives of Descendants of Victims of Apartheid Era Gross Human Rights Violations. *International Review of Victimology*, 24(1), 47-65.
- Adorno, T. (1970). *Aesthetic Theory*. Gretel Adorno & Rolf Tiedemann.
- Aguilera Díaz, M. (2013). *Montes de María: una subregión de economía campesina y empresarial*. Banco de la República.
- Alase, A. (2017). The Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA): A Guide to a Good Qualitative Research Approach. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 5(2), 9-19. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.5n.2p.9>
- Alcaldía de Medellín. (2018). *Informe del Sistema de Indicadores Turísticos de Medellín, Antioquia*. Alcaldía de Medellín.
- Alger, C. F. (2014). *Challenges for Peace Researches and Peace Builders in the Twenty-First Century: Education and Coordination of a Diversity of Actors in Applying What We are Learning* (H. G. Brauch, ed.). Springer International Publishing.
- Arai, T. (2006). A Journey Toward Cultural Fluency. In: M. LeBaron & V. Pillay, *Conflict Across Cultures: A Unique Experience of Bridging Differences* (pp. 57-79). Nicolas Brealey Press.
- Arai, T. (2009). *Creativity and Conflict Resolution*. Routledge.
- Archer, M. (1995). *Realist Social Theory: The Morphogenetic Approach*. Cambridge University Press.
- Arcodia, C. & Whitford, M. (2006). Festival Attendance and the Development of Social Capital. *Journal of Convention and Event Tourism*, 8(12), 1-18. https://doi.org/10.1300/J452v08n02_01
- Arts Council of England. (2014). *The Value of Arts and Culture to People and Society*. Arts Council of England.
- Arts Council of Northern Ireland. (2015). *Building Peace through Arts: Re-Imaging Communities*. Arts Council of Northern Ireland.
- Aspillaga Fariña, M. A. (2015). Teoría de Círculos Concéntricos de la Industria Creativa, adaptación al contexto chileno, y análisis de su pertinencia en la realidad actual nacional. *Políticas Culturais em Revista*, 8(2), 188-215.

- Baklien, B. (2009). Culture is Healthy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 7(2), 235-257.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630009358145>
- Bang, A. H. (2016). The Restorative and Transformative Power of the Arts in Conflict Resolution. *Journal of Transformative Education*, 14(4), 355-376.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1541344616655886>
- Bang, C. L. (2013). El arte participativo en el espacio público y la creación colectiva para la transformación social. *Creatividad y Sociedad*, 1-25.
- Barnes, H. & Peters, D. (2002). Translating Trauma: Using Arts Therapies with Survivors of Violence. *South African Theatre Journal*, 16(1), 157-183.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10137548.2002.9687747>
- Barrera Duque, E. (2007). La empresa social y su responsabilidad social. *INNOVAR: Revista de Ciencias Sociales y Administrativas*, 17(30), 59-75.
<https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/818/81803006.pdf>
- Bassey, M. (1999). *Case Study Research in Educational Settings*. Open University Press.
- Baú, V. (2015). Participatory Photography for Peace: Using Images to Open up Dialogue after Violence. *Journal of Peacebuilding & Development*, 10(3), 74-88.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/48602948>
- Beausoleil, E. & Lebaron, M. (2013). What Moves Us: Dance and Neuroscience Implications for Conflict Approaches. *Conflict Resolution Quarterly*, 31(2), 133-158.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/crq.21086>
- Belfiore, E. (2004). Auditing Culture. *International Journal for Cultural Policy*, 10(2), 183-202. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630042000255808>
- Belfiore, E. & Bennet, O. (2007). Rethinking the Social Impact of the Arts. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 13(2), 135-151.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630701342741>
- Belfiore, E. & Bennett, O. (2010). Beyond the “Toolkit Approach”: Arts Impact Evaluation Research and the Realities of Cultural Policy-Making. *Journal for Cultural Research*, 14(2), 121-142. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14797580903481280>
- Benhamou, F. (1997). *La economía de la cultura*. Ediciones Trilce.
- Bergh, A. & Sloboda, J. (2010). Music and Art in Conflict Transformation: A Review (M. A. Action, ed.). *Music and Arts in Action*, 2(2), 2-17.
<https://musicandartsinaction.net/index.php/maia/article/view/conflicttransformation>

- Bernard, P. (1999). La cohésion sociale : critique dialectique d'un quasi-concept. *Lien Social et Politiques*, (41), 47-59. <https://www.erudit.org/en/journals/lsp/1900-v1-n1-lsp352/005057ar.pdf>
- Bernstein, R. J. (1983). *Beyond Objectivism and Relativism: Science, Hermeneutics, and Praxis*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Bishop, C. (2012). *Artificial Hells Participatory Art and the Politics of Spectatorship*. London: Verso.
- Blommfield, D., Barnes, T. & Huysse, L. (2003). *Reconciliation after Violent Conflict*. International IDEA.
- Boal, A. (2008). *Theatre of the oppressed*. London: Pluto Press.
- Bornstein, J. (2015). Music and Peace. *Methodologies in Peace Psychology* (D. Bretherton & S. Fang Law, eds.). Springer International Publishing.
- Bosi, L. & De Fazio, G. (2017). *The Troubles in Northern Ireland and Theories of Social Movement*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984). Outline of a Sociological Theory of Art Perception. *International Science Journal*, 20(4), 589-612.
- Bourdieu, P. (1986). The Forms of Capital. In R. John, *Handbook of Theory and Research for the Sociology of Education* (p. 1-29). Greenwood.
- Bourdieu, P. & Wacquant, L. (2005). *Una invitación a la sociología reflexiva*. Siglo XXI Editores.
- British Council. (2012). *The Power of Culture*. British Council.
- British Council. (2019). *The Art of Peace: The Value of Culture in Post-Conflict Recovery*. British Council.
- Broome, B. J. (2009). Building Shared Meaning: Implications of a Relational Approach to Empathy for Teaching Intercultural Communication. *Communication Education*, 40(3), 235-249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634529109378847>
- Broome, B. J. & Collier, M. J. (2012). Culture, Communication, and Peacebuilding. *Journal of International and Intercultural Communication*, 5(4), 245-269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17513057.2012.716858>
- Brounéus, K. (2003). *Reconciliation: Theory and Practice for Development Cooperation*. Sida.
- Bryman, A. (2008). *Social Research Methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Burrell, G. & Morgan, G. (1979). *Sociological Paradigms and Organisational Analysis*. Ashgate Publishing Company.

- Bush, K. (2011). *The Evaluation of Storytelling as a Peace-Building Methodology*. INCORE and Irish Peace Centres.
- Byrom Hartwell, M. (1999). The Role of Forgiveness in Reconstructing Society after Conflict. *The Journal of Humanitarian Assistance*. <https://www.jha.ac/a048/>
- Casa Kolacho y Jeihhco Caminante. (2012, March 9th). *Almas en guerra* [video]. YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k4VYpb4_fBw
- Carlson, E. D., Engebretson, J. & Chamberlain, R. M. (2006). Photovoice as a Social Process of Critical Consciousness. *Qualitative Health Research*, 16(6), 836-852. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732306287525>
- Cehahic-Clancy, S. & Bilewicz, M. (2017). Fostering Reconciliation through Historical Moral Exemplars in a Postconflict Society. *Journal of Peace Psychology*, 23(3), 288-297. <https://doi.org/10.1037/pac0000210>
- Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica (CNMH). (2009). *La masacre de El Salado: esa guerra no era nuestra*. Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica.
- Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica (CNMH). (2018). *Paramilitarismo: balance de la contribución del CNMH al esclarecimiento histórico*. Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica.
- Cevallos, R. R. (2005). *¿Cultura y desarrollo? ¿Desarrollo y cultura?* Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo.
- Chan, J., To, H.-P. & Chan, E. (2006). Reconsidering Social Cohesion: Developing a Definition and Analytical Framework for Empirical Research. *Social Indicators Research*, 75(2), 273-302. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11205-005-2118-1>
- Chang, T. C. (1997). Heritage as a Tourism Commodity: Traversing the Tourist-Local Divide. *Singapore Journal of Tropical Geography*, 18(1), 46-68. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9493.00004>
- Clift, S. (2012). Creative Arts as A Public Health Resource: Moving from Practice-Based Research to Evidence-Based Practice. *Perspectives in Public Health*, 132(3), 120-127. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1757913912442269>
- Coalter, F. (2001). *Realising the Potential of Cultural Services: The Case for Sport*. Local Government Association.
- Cohen, R. I. (1994). *Arts in the Local Economy: Final Report*. National Assembly of Local Arts Agencies.

- https://www.americansforthearts.org/sites/default/files/Arts%20in%20the%20Local%20Economy_Final%20Report_0.pdf
- Cohen, C. (2003). Engaging with the Arts to Promote Coexistence. *Imagine Coexistence: Restoring Humanity after Violent Ethnic Conflict* (A. Chayes & M. L. Minow, eds.). Jossey-Bass.
- Cohen, C. (2005). *Creative Approaches to Reconciliation*. Brandeis University. <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.498.4233&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Cohen, C. (2011). *Acting Together: Performance and the Creative Transformation of Conflict*. Joint Research Institute for International Peace and Culture.
- Coleman, J. S. (1988). Social Capital in the Creation of Human Capital. *The American Journal of Sociolog*, 94, S95-S120. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2780243?origin=JSTOR-pdf>
- Colleta, N. & Cullen, M. (2000a). *The Nexus between Violent Conflict, Social Capital and Social Cohesion*. The World Bank Group.
- Colleta, N. & Cullen, M. (2000b). *Violent Conflict and the Transformation of Social Capital*. The World Bank Group.
- Collins, S. (2011, September 17th). *Modern Slavery: How a Drama Project in Ghana Educates Communities through the Stories of Survivors*. Berfrois. <https://www.berfrois.com/2022/09/performance-provides-an-alternative-perspective-to-modern-slavery/>
- Colombian Government. (2016). *Acuerdo Final para la terminación del conflicto y la construcción de una paz estable y duradera*. Editorial Temis. <https://www.jep.gov.co/Normativa/Paginas/Acuerdo-Final.aspx>
- Comisión para el Esclarecimiento de la Verdad, la Convivencia y la No Repetición. (2022). *Hay futuro si hay verdad. Informe final*. Comisión de la Verdad.
- Comisión Colombiana de Juristas. (n. d.). *¿Por qué en los Montes de María?* <https://coljuristas.org/elsilenciodelasgaitas/contexto.html>
- Conrad, P. (1987). The experience of illness: recent and new directions. *Research in the Sociology of Health Care*, 6, 1-32.
- Consultoría para los Derechos Humanos y el Desplazamiento. (2018). *Montes de María bajo fuego*. Comisión de la Verdad.
- Creswell, J. W., Hanson, W. E. & Clark, V. (2007). Qualitative Research Designs: Selection and Implementation. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 35(2), 236-264. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000006287390>

- Crossick, G. & Kaszynska, P. (2014). Underconstruction: Towards a Framework for Cultural Value. *Cultural Trends*, 23(4), 120-131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2014.897453>
- Crossick, G. & Kaszynska, P. (2016). *Understanding the Value of Arts and Culture: The AHRC Cultural Value Project*. Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- Cuéllar, J. A. (2008). *Fundación Nacional Batuta: impacto de la práctica musical educativa*. Escuela de Gobierno Alberto Lleras Camargo. <https://repositorio.uniandes.edu.co/bitstream/handle/1992/7620/u442253.pdf?sequence=1>
- Cwi, D. (1980). Public Support of the Arts: Three Arguments Examined. *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 4(2), 39-62. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41810278>
- Davies, M. & Selwood, S. (2012). In Search of Cultural Policy. *Cultural Trends*, 21(3), 201-204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2012.698470>
- Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística (DANE). (2016). *Monetary and Multidimensional Poverty in Colombia*. Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística.
- Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística (DANE). (2017). *Boletín Técnico de Pobreza Monetaria*. Departamento Administrativo Nacional de Estadística.
- Delgado, C. R. (2017). *Factores que evidencian sistematicidad en el asesinato de líderes sociales y defensores de derechos humanos en Colombia*. Indepaz.
- DeNora, T. (2004). *Music in Everyday Life*. Cambridge University Press.
- Denzin, N. (2006). *Sociological Methods: A Sourcebook*. Aldine Transaction.
- Deslauriers, J.-P. & López Estrada, R. E. (2011). La entrevista cualitativa como técnica para la investigación en Trabajo Social. *Revista de Trabajo Social y Ciencias Sociales*, (61). <https://www.margen.org/suscri/margen61/lopez.pdf>
- Doyle, L. (2016). *Creativity in Conflict: Performing Arts for Sustained Dialogue, Justice and Reconciliation*. Institute for Justice and Reconciliation.
- Dunphy, K., Elton, M. & Jordan, A. (2014). Exploring Dance/Movement Therapy in Post-Conflict Timor-Leste. *American Journal of Dance Therapy*, 36(2), 189-208.
- Duxbury, N. & Gillette, E. (2007). Culture as A Key Dimension of Sustainability: Exploring Concepts, Themes, and Models. *Centre of Expertise on Culture and Communities Working Paper No. 1*. <https://cercles.diba.cat/documentsdigitals/pdf/E130054.pdf>
- Edwards, B. & Foley, M. w. (1999). Social Capital and Civic Capacity. *Administrative Theory & Praxis*, 21(4), 523-531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10841806.1999.11643413>

- Efe, A. (2017, October 27th). A “razones personales” atribuye Santos la mayoría de homicidios líderes sociales. *El Espectador*. <https://www.elespectador.com/judicial/a-razones-personales-atribuye-santos-la-mayoria-de-homicidios-lideres-sociales-article-720188/>
- Escárzaga, F. (2001). Auge y caída de Sendero Luminoso. *Bajo el Volcán*, 2(3), 75-97.
- European Union. (2017). *International Cooperation and Development*. www.ec.europa.eu/europaid/case-studies
- Evans, M. (1993). Reading lives: How the personal might be social. *Sociology*, 27(1), 5-13. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/42855036>
- Evrard, Y. (1997). Democratizing Culture or Cultural Democracy? *The Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society*, 23(7), 167-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632929709596961>
- Finlev, T. (2012). Future Peace: Breaking Cycles of Violence through Futures Thinking. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 16(3), 47-62. <https://jfsdigital.org/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/163-A03.pdf>
- Flinn, J. & McPherson, G. (2007). *Culture Matters? The Role of Arts and Culture in the Development of Social Capital*. Antony Rowe.
- Flórez, E. (2018, February 1st). *Líderes sociales piden mayor presencia del Estado en zona rural de Montes de María*. (RCN Radio, entrevistador). <https://www.rcnradio.com/colombia/caribe/lideres-sociales-piden-mayor-presencia-del-estado-en-zona-rural-de-montes-de-maria>
- Frey, B. (2005). What Values Should Count in the Arts. *CREMA Working Paper No. 24*, pp. 1-12.
- Fukushima, A. (2011). Peace and Culture: Fostering Peace through Cultural Contributions. In Joint Research Institute for International Peace and Culture, Aoyama Gakuin University & The Japan Foundation London, *Conflict and Culture: Fostering Peace through Cultural Initiatives*. Joint Research Institute for International Peace and Culture.
- Fundación Ideas para la Paz. (2011). *Análisis regional de los Montes de María*. Fundación Ideas para la Paz.
- Gadamer, H.-G. (1993). *Verdad y método*. Ediciones Sígueme.
- Gal-Ed, H. (2009). Art and Meaning: ARTiculation as Modality in Processing Forgiveness and Peace Consciousness. In A. Kalayjian & R. F. Paloutzian, *Forgiveness and*

- Reconciliation: Psychological Pathways to Conflict Transformation and Peace Building* (p. 97-118). Springer International Publishing.
- Galloway, S. (2006). Cultural participation and individual quality of life a review of research findings. *Applied Research in Quality of Life*, (1), 323-342.
- Galtung, J. (1980). *The True Worlds: a Transnational Perspective*. Free Press.
- Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means*. SAGE Publications.
- Galtung, J. (2000). *Conflict Transformation by Peaceful Means*. United Nations.
- García-Canclini, N. (2004). *Diferentes, desiguales y desconectados. Mapas de la interculturalidad*. Editorial Gedisa.
- Gawn, R. (2007). Truth Cohabitation: A Truth Commission for Northern Ireland? *Irish Political Studies*, 22(3), 339-361. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07907180701527243>
- Gibson, L. (2008). In Defence of Instrumentality. *Cultural Trends*, 17(4), 247-257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548960802615380>
- Gielen, P., Braidotti, R. & De Boodt, L. (2015). *No Culture, No Europe: On the Foundation of Politics*. Valiz/Antennae Series.
- Gilmore, A. (2012). Counting Eyeballs, Sounbites and ‘Plings’: Arts Participation, Strategic Instrumentalism and the London 2012 Cultural Olimpiad. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 18(2), 151-167. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2011.577283>
- Giorgi, A. P., Giorgi, B. M. & Morley, J. (2003). The Descriptive Phenomenological Psychological Method. In: *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research In Psychology* (pp. 176-192). SAGE Publications.
- Goldstein, J. (2011). *Winning the War on War: The Decline of Armed Conflict Worldwide*. Penguin Books.
- Gray, C. (2007). Commodification and Instrumentality in Cultural Policy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 13(2), 203-215. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630701342899>
- Gray, C. (2009). Managing Cultural Policy: Pitfalls and Prospects. *Public Administration*, 87(3), 574-585. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9299.2008.01748.x>
- Grupo de Memoria Histórica. (2011). *La huella invisible de la guerra: desplazamiento forzado en la Comuna 13*. Comisión Nacional de Reparación y Reconciliación; Grupo de Memoria Histórica.
- Grupo de Memoria Histórica. (2015). *¡Basta ya! Colombia: memorias de guerra y dignidad*. Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica. Centro Nacional de Memoria Histórica

- Guba, E. & Lincoln, Y. (1994). *Competing Paradigms in Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications.
- Guetzkow, J. (2002). *How the Arts Impact Communities: An Introduction to the Literature on Arts Impact Studies*. Center for Arts and Cultural Policy Studies Working Paper Series No. 20. <https://www.mvgeorgia.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/07/art-and-community.pdf>
- Hanebrink, J. & Smith, A. (2013). *The Art of Peace in Northern Uganda*. Indiana University Press.
- Hangzhou International Congress. (2013). *The Hangzhou Declaration Placing Culture at the Heart of Sustainable Development Policies*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000221238>
- Hawkes, J. (2001). *The Fourth Pillar of Sustainability: Culture's Essential Role in Public Planning*. Cultural Development Network.
- Heidegger, M. (1962). *Being and Time*. Blackwell Publishing.
- Heilbrun, J. & Gray, C. (2001). *The Economics of Art and Culture*. Cambridge University Press.
- Herriott, R. & Firestone, W. (1983). *Multisite Qualitative Policy Research: Optimizing Description and Generalizability*. Educational Researcher.
- Hesmondhalgh, D. & Pratt, A. (2005). Cultural industries and cultural policy. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 11(1), 1-14. <https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/gcul20/11/1>
- Hofstede, G. (2011). Dimensionalizing Cultures: The Hofstede Model in Context. *Readings in Psychology and Culture*, 3-26.
- Holden, J. (2004). *Capturing Cultural Value*. Demos.
- Holden, J. (2006). *Cultural Value and the Crisis of Legitimacy*. Demos.
- Howland, T. (1 2017). “La situación es peor que el año pasado”: la advertencia del representante en Colombia del Alto Comisionado para los Derechos Humanos de la ONU sobre los asesinatos de defensores de DDHH en 2017. *BBC Mundo*. (N. Cosoy, entrevistador).
- Howson, P. & Dubber, J. (2014). *Culture Matters*. British Council.
- Husserl, E. (1949). *Ideas relativas a una fenomenología pura y una filosofía fenomenológica*. Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Husserl, E. (1992). *Invitación a la fenomenología*. Publicaciones UNAM.

- Indepaz. (2018, April 13th). *Boletín informe estadístico de homicidios de líderes sociales y defensores de DDHH del primer trimestre de 2018*. Unidad Investigativa del Instituto de Estudios para el Desarrollo y de la Paz. <https://indepaz.org.co/boletin-informe-estadistico-de-homicidios-de-lideres-sociales-y-defensores-de-ddhh-del-primer-trimestre-de-2018-indepaz-acpaz/>
- Instituto Cervantes. (2010). *III Jornada Profesional de la RBIC. Desarrollo, sostenibilidad y cultura: el papel social de las bibliotecas*. December 16th, 2010. https://www.cervantes.es/bibliotecas_documentacion_espanol/para_bibliotecarios/jornadas/jornada_3/jornada_3.htm
- Inter-American Development Bank. (2021). *Financiamiento público a la cultura y a la creatividad en América Latina y el Caribe: presupuestos, instrumentos y perspectivas*. IDB.
- International Alert. (2020). Create Syria Project. www.international-alert.org
- International Institute of Studies of the Caribbean. (2008). *The Laboratory of Peace in Montes de María. An Approach to their Context*. Observatory of Political Culture, Peace, Coexistence and Development of Montes de María.
- Ishaq, A. (2006). *Prosperity and Peace through Art*. International Child Art Foundation (ICAF).
- Jackson, M. R., Herranz, J. & Kabwasa-Green, F. (2006). *Cultural Vitality in Communities: Interpretation and Indicators*. The Urban Institute.
- Jeannotte, S. (1999). *The Different Facets of Diversity and Social Cohesion*. Department of Canadian Heritage.
- Jeannotte, S. (2003). *Social Cohesion: Insights from Canadian Research*. Department of Canadian Heritage.
- Jeannotte, S., Stanley, D., Pendakur, R., Jamieson, B., Williams, M. & Aizlewood, A. (2002). *Buying in or dropping out: the public policy implications of social cohesion research*. Department of Canadian Heritage.
- Jenson, J. (2002). Identifying the Links: Social Cohesion and Culture. *Canadian Journal of Communication*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.22230/cjc.2002v27n2a1289>
- Johnson, C. (2006). *El arte como herramienta para la transformación social*. La Casa Amarilla.
- Kahane, A. (2010). *Power and Love: A Theory and Practice of Social Change*. Berret-Koehler

Publishers.

- Kaszynska, P. (2018). *Cultural Value Scoping Project*. King's College London.
- Kawulich, B. B. (2005). Participant Observation as a Data Collection Method. *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 6(2). <https://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/466/996>
- Kilroy, A., Garner, C., Parkinson, C., Kagan, C. & Senior, P. (2007). *Towards Transformation: Exploring the Impact of Culture, Creativity and the Arts on Health and Wellbeing*. Arts for Health at Manchester.
- Klamer, A. (2002). Accounting for Social and Cultural Values. *De Economist*, 150(4), 453-473.
- Kliksberg, B. (1999). Social Capital and Culture Master Keys to Development. *CEPAL Review No. 69*. <https://repositorio.cepal.org/handle/11362/10699>
- Koelsch, S. (2013). From Social Contact to Social Cohesion — The 7 Cs. *Music and Medicine*, 5(4), 204-209. https://stefan-koelsch.de/papers/koelsch_2013_from_social_contact_to_social_cohesion_the_7_cs.pdf
- Kramer, G., Ernsbrunner, T. & Graf, W. (2013). Signification Spirals and Moral Imagination. *EUNIC Yearbook 2012/2013 Culture Report: Culture and Conflict*.
- Kroc Institute for International Peace Studies. (2019). *Estado efectivo de implementación del Acuerdo de Paz en Colombia. Diciembre de 2016-Abril de 2019. Resumen Ejecutivo*. University of Notre Dame. https://kroc.nd.edu/assets/333273/190610_resumen_ejecutivo_final_seminario_dc_3_.pdf
- Krondorfer, B. (1995). *Remembrance and Reconciliation*. Yale University Press.
- Laaksonen, A. (2008). *Access of Young People to Culture*. Interarts Foundation.
- Landry, C., Bianchini, F. & Maguire, M. (1993). *The Social Impact of the Arts: A Discussion*. Comedia.
- LeBaron, M. (2001). *Transforming Cultural Conflict in an Age of Complexity*. Berghof Foundation.
- LeBaron, M. (2011). Dancing at the Crossroads: Arts and Movement-Based Approaches to Conflict Resolution. In: A. Fukushima, *Culture, Conflict and Peace: Fostering Peace through Cultural Initiatives*. Joint Research Institute for International Peace and Culture.

- LeBaron, M. (2013). *The Choreography of Resolution: Conflict, Movement, and Neuroscience*. American Bar Association.
- Lederach, J. (1996). *Preparing for Peace: Conflict Transformation across Culture*. Syracuse University Press.
- Lederach, J. (1997). *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. Institute of Peace Press.
- Lederach, J. P. (2005). *The Moral Imagination*. Oxford University Press.
- Lederach, J. P. (2015, October 24th). “La paz la construye cada colombiano”. (D. S. Antolínez, entrevistador). *El Espectador*. <https://www.elespectador.com/colombia/mas-regiones/la-paz-la-construye-cada-colombiano-article-594867/>
- Lee, D. (2013). How the Arts Generate Social Capital to Foster Intergroup Social Cohesion. *The Journal of Arts Management, Law, And Society*, 43(1), 4-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632921.2012.761167>
- Leonard, M. (2004). Bonding and Bridging Social Capital: Reflections from Belfast. *Sociology*, 38(5), 927-944. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038504047176>
- Liebmann, M. (1996). *Arts Approaches to Conflict*. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Likes, B. (2001). Artes creativas y fotografía en investigación acción participativa en Guatemala. *Handbook of Action Research* (P. Reason & H. Bradbury, eds.; pp. 363-371). SAGE Publications.
- Lingayah, S., Mac Gillivray, A. & Raynard, P. (1996). *Creative Accounting*. Beyond the Bottom Line.
- Long, W. J. & Brecke, P. (2003). *War and Reconciliation: Reason and Emotion in Conflict Resolution*. MIT Press.
- López Fernández Cao, M. (2015). *Indicadores sobre prácticas artísticas comunitarias: algunas reflexiones*. *Arteterapia. Papeles de arteterapia y educación para inclusión social*, 209-234.
- López, W. & Taylor, L. (2021). *Transitioning to Peace: Promoting Global Social Justice and Non-Violence*. Springer.
- Lumsden, M. (1997). Breaking the Cycle of Violence. *Journal of Peace Research*, 34(4), 377-383. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343397034004001>
- Lund, B. & Chemi, T. (2015). *Dealing with Emotions: A Pegagogical Challenge to Innovative Learning*. Sense Publishers.

- Lykes, B. (2001). Artes creativas y fotografía en investigación acción participativa en Guatemala. *Handbook of Action Research* (P. Reason & H. Bradbury, eds.; pp. 363-371). SAGE Publications.
- Machlis, G. E. & Burch Jr., W. R. (1983). Relations between Strangers: Cycles of Structure and Meaning in Tourist System. *The Sociological Review*, 31(4), 666-692. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.1983.tb00726.x>
- Manojlovic, B. (2018). Peacebuilding through Education: Innovative Ways of Dealing with Conflict. *Zeitschrift für Beratungs- & Managementwissenschaften*, (4), 44-50.
- Marín, N. (2018, January 31st). Son 7 asesinados cada 10 días. *El Espectador*.
- Mark, S. & Seifert, S. (2008). From Creative Economy to Creative Society. *Culture and Community Revitalization: A: SIAP/Reinvestment Fund Collaboration 2007-2008*. https://repository.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1006&context=siap_revitalization
- Marshall, C. & Rossman, G. (1995). *Designing Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications.
- Martínez, M. (2004). *Ciencia y arte en la metodología cualitativa*. Trillas.
- Mason, J. (2002). *Qualitative Researching*. SAGE Publications.
- Matarasso, F. (1997). *Use or Ornament: The Social Impact of Participation in the Arts*. Comedia.
- McCarthy, K., Ondaatje, E., Zakaras, L. & Brooks, A. (2004). *Gifts of the Muse: Reframing the Debate about the Benefits of the Arts*. RAND Publications.
- McClain, L. (2010). The Art of Creative Conflict Resolution: A Critical Evaluation of Approaches to Post-Conflict Reconstruction in Northern Uganda. *The Journal of Undergraduate*, 1(1), 1-15. <https://trace.tennessee.edu/pursuit/vol1/iss1/9/>
- McIntyre, B. (2012). *Art Inspired by the Truth and Reconciliation Commission*. South African History Online. <https://www.sahistory.org.za/archive/art-inspired-truth-and-reconciliation-commission>
- McPherson, G., Mamattah, S., Moore, A., Cifuentes, G. & Moualla, Y. (2019). *The Art of Peace*. British Council.
- Mennell, S. (1976). *Cultural Policy in Towns*. Council of Europe.
- Mercer, D. (1973). The Concept of Recreational Need. *Journal of Leisure Research*, 5(1), 37-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.1973.11970110>

- Merli, P. (2002). Evaluating the Social Impact of Participating in Arts Activities. A Critical Review of Francois Matarasso's "Use or Ornament". *International Journal for Cultural Policy*, 8(1), 107-118. <https://romulusstudio.com/variant/19texts/socinc19.html>
- Michelle, R. (2002). *Measuring the Economic and Social Impact of the Arts*. Arts Council of England.
- Ministerio de Cultura. (2013). *Diagnóstico del desarrollo cultural en Colombia. Hacia la construcción del Índice de Desarrollo Cultural*. Ministerio de Cultura. https://www.mincultura.gov.co/areas/fomento-regional/Documents/L_DiagnosticoDlloCultural_2013.pdf
- Ministerio de Cultura. (2016). *Programa Expedición Sensorial*. <https://mincultura.gov.co/areas/artes/expedicionsensorial/programa/Paginas/default.aspx>
- Ministerio de Cultura. (2018). *Informe de gestión: 8 años transformando vidas*. MinCultura.
- Ministerio de Cultura. (2022, August 9th). *Ministerio de las Culturas, las Artes y los Saberes le apostará a la paz desde la integración de las comunidades*. Sala de Prensa. <https://www.mincultura.gov.co/prensa/noticias/Paginas/ministerio-de-las-culturas-las-artes-y-los-saberes-le-apostara-a-la-paz-desde-la-integracion-de-las-comunidades.aspx>
- Ministerio de Cultura. (n. d.). *ABC Economía Naranja*. <https://economianaranja.gov.co/abc-economia-naranja/>
- Ministerio de Hacienda y Crédito Público. (2020). *Presupuesto Ciudadano 2020*. <http://www.pte.gov.co/WebsitePTE/Documentos/PresupuestoGeneralNacion2020.pdf>
- Ministry of Culture. (2013). *Diagnosis of the cultural development of Colombia*. Ministry of Culture of Colombia.
- Mohammed, F. (2015). Psychological Effects of War and Violence on Children. *Journal of Psychological Abnormalities in Children*, 4(4). <https://www.iomcworld.com/open-access/psychological-effects-of-war-and-violence-on-children-jpab-1000e106.pdf>
- Morrow, S. L. (2007). Qualitative Research in Counseling Psychology: Conceptual Foundations. *The Counseling Psychologist*, 35(2), 209-235. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000006286990>
- Mouton, J. & Babbie, E. (2001). *The Practice of Social Research*. Oxford University Press.

- Myers, D. (2009). *Qualitative Research in Business & Management*. SAGE Publications.
- Naidu-Silverman, E. (2015). *The contribution of art and culture in peace and reconciliation processes in Asia*. Centre for Culture and Development (CKU).
- National Endowment for the Arts. (2015). *How Creativity Works in the Brain*. Santa Fe Institute Working Group.
- Nightingale, V. (2008). Why Observing Matters. *Research Methods for Cultural Studies* (M. Pickering, ed.). Edinburgh University Press.
- Nilsson, M. (2018). Building Peace Amidst Violence: An Analysis of Colombia's Policies to Address Security and Development Challenges. *Iberoamericana. Nordic Journal of Latin American and Caribbean Studies*, 47(1), 34-44. <https://doi.org/10.16993/iberoamericana.411>
- Northern Ireland Foundation. (s. f.). *Motivation*. www.northernireland.foundation/about-us/motivation
- Noticias Uno Colombia. (2017, December 16th). *El ministro de Defensa dice que a los líderes sociales los matan por líos de faldas y de vecinos* [video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=D7yix8oGoQQ>
- Nussbaum, M. (2001). *The Upheavals of Thought: The Intelligence of Emotions*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nutt Williams, E. & Morrow, S. L. (2009). Achieving Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research: A Pan-Paradigmatic Perspective. *Psychotherapy Research*, 19(4-5), 576-582. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10503300802702113>
- O'Brien, D. (2010). *Measuring the Value of Culture: A Report to the Department for Culture Media and Sport*. Arts & Humanities Research Council.
- O'Brien, D. & Oakley, K. (2015). *Cultural Value and Inequality: A Critical Literature Review. A Report commissioned by the Arts and Humanities Research Council's Cultural Value Project*. Arts and Humanities Research Council.
- O'Neill, K. L. (2005). Writing Guatemala's Genocide: Truth and Reconciliation Commission Reports and Christianity. *Journal of Genocide Research*, 7(3), 331-349. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14623520500190314>
- Oxfam. (2017). *A Snapshot of Inequality: What the Largest Agricultural Census Reveals about Land Distribution in Colombia*. https://www-cdn.oxfam.org/s3fs-public/file_attachments/colombia_-_snapshot_of_inequality.pdf

- Palacios, M. & Safford, F. (2002). *Colombia: Fragmented Land Divided Society*. Oxford University Press.
- Paloutzian, R. & Kalayjian, A. (2009). *Forgiveness and Reconciliation: Psychological Pathways to Conflict Transformation and Peace Building*. Springer International Publishing.
- Parramon, R. (2017). *Can Art Resolve Conflicts, or Does it Live on Them?* Creating Peace, 1-6.
- Pérez Serrano, G. (2004). *Investigación cualitativa. Retos e interrogantes*. La Muralla.
- Petro Urrego, G. & Márquez Mina, F. (2022). *Colombia, potencia mundial de la vida. Bases del Plan Nacional de Desarrollo 2022-2026*. https://colaboracion.dnp.gov.co/CDT/portalDNP/PND%202022/Bases-PND2022-2026_compilado-CEVC15-10-2022.pdf
- Pickering, M. (Ed.). (2008). *Research Methods for Cultural Studies*. Edinburgh University Press.
- Portes, A. (1998). Social Capital: its origins and applications in modern sociology. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 24(1), 1-24. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.24.1.1>
- Power, S. (2011). On Social Psychology and Conflict. *Psychology and Society*, 4(1), 1-6.
- Preis, A.-B. & Stanca Mustea, C. (2013). *Peace and Reconciliation: How Culture Makes the Difference*. UNESCO.
- Premaratna, N. & Bleiker, R. (2016). Arts and Theatre for Peacebuilding. *The Palgrave Handbook of Disciplinary and Regional Approaches to Peace* (O. Richmond, S. Pogodda & J. Ramovic, eds.). Palgrave Macmillan.
- Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). (2010). *Los Montes de María: análisis de la conflictividad*. PNUD.
- Programa de las Naciones Unidas para el Desarrollo (PNUD). (2020). *Fortalecimiento de la cohesión social*. PNUD.
- Pruitt, L. (2011). Music, Youth and Peacebuilding in Northern Ireland. *Global Change, Peace and Security*, 23(2), 207-222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14781158.2011.580961>
- Punch, K. (2009). *Introduction to Research Methods in Education*. SAGE Publications.
- Putnam, R. (2000). *Bowling Alone: The Collapse and Revival of American Community*. Simon & Schuster.
- Putnam, R. (2001, December 19th). The Prosperous Community: Social Capital and Public Life. *The American Prospect*. <https://prospect.org/infrastructure/prosperous-community->

social-capital-public-life/

- Putnam, R. & Goss, K. (2002). *The Evolution of Social Capital in Contemporary Society*. Oxford University Press.
- Quinn, B. (2010). Arts Festivals, Urban Tourism and Cultural Policy. *Journal of Policy Research in Tourism, Leisure and Events*, 2(3), 265-279. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19407963.2010.512207>
- Ramsey White, T. & Rentschler, R. (2005). *Toward a New Understanding of Social Impact of the Arts*. Deakin University of Australia Press.
- Randazzo, E., & Ignasi, T. (2021). Reframing agency in complexity sensitive peacebuilding. *Security Dialogue*.
- Red Cross International Committee. (2008). *Armed Conflict*. International Humanitarian Law.
- Remijnse, S. (2005). Dealing with the past: conflicting memories in Joyabaj, Guatemala. *Journal of International Political Theory*, 1(1), 70-80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1743453X0500100107>
- Robertson, C. (2016). Musicological Ethnography and Peacebuilding. *Journal of Peace Education*, 13(3), 252-265. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17400201.2016.1234618>
- Red de Bibliotecas del Instituto Cervantes (RBIC). (2012, April 10th). *Sergio Fajardo Valderrama: «La cultura como eje de la Transformación Social de Medellín»* [video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Se6K2EG-U-I>
- Restrepo, V. (2018, January 1st). Medellín cerró el año con 577 homicidios. *El Colombiano*. <https://www.elcolombiano.com/antioquia/seguridad/homicidios-en-medellin-durante-2017-FD7948557>
- Revista Semana*. (2017, July 7th). Los beneficios de la ley naranja en el emprendimiento en Colombia. <https://www.semana.com/emprendimiento/articulo/ley-naranja-y-economia-naranja-en-colombia/247374/>
- Revista Semana*. (2021, September 23rd). ¡Sigue la recuperación! PIB de Bogotá aumentó más de 17 % en el segundo trimestre. <https://www.semana.com/economia/macroeconomia/articulo/sigue-la-recuperacion-pib-de-bogota-aumento-mas-de-17-en-el-segundo-trimestre/202157/>
- Rohr, E. (2013). From Conflict to Recognition: Cultural Transformation through Group Supervision in Guatemala. *Group Analysis*, 46(3), 272-285. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0533316413495488>

- Rowland, G. (1995). Archetypes of systems design. *Systems Practice*, 8, 277-288.
- Rubinstein, R. (2011). Representation and Response: Culture and Conflict Transformation. In: Joint Research Institute for International Peace and Culture & Aoyama Gakuin University, *Fostering Peace through Cultural Initiatives: From the Roundtable on Conflict and Culture* (pp. 65-73). The Japan Foundation London.
- Runco, M. (2007). *Creativity Theories and Themes: Research, Development, and Practice*. Burlington Academic Press.
- Salazar Tetzagüic, M. (2009). *Multiculturalidad e interculturalidad en el ámbito educativo*. Instituto Interamericano de Derechos Humanos.
- Salzburg Global Seminar. (2014). *Conflict Transformation through Culture: Peace-Building and the Arts*. British Council.
- Sambanis, N. (2004). What is Civil War? Conceptual and Empirical Complexities of an Operational Definition. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 48(6), 814-858. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4149797>
- Sánchez, G. (2011). *La huella invisible de la guerra: desplazamiento forzado en la Comuna 13*. Editorial Taurus.
- Sánchez Torres, F. J. & Díaz Escobar, A. M. (2005). Los efectos del conflicto armado en el desarrollo social colombiano 1990-2002. *Documento CEDE* 2005-58. <http://hdl.handle.net/1992/7966>
- Schaffer, B., Yuen, C. & Korza, P. (1999). *Animating Democracy: The Artistic Imagination as a Force in Civic Dialogue*. American for the Arts.
- Scher, A. (2006). *Can the Arts Change the World*. Research Center for Leadership in Action.
- Schmid, K. & Muldoon, O. (2013). Perceived Threat, Social Identification and Psychological Well-Being. *Political Psychology*, 36(1). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/43783835>
- Schmuck, R. (1997). *Practical Action Research for Change*. SAGE Publications.
- Schwandt, T. (2000). *Three Epistemological Stances for Qualitative Inquiry: Interpretivism, Hermeneutics, and Social Constructionism*. SAGE Publications.
- Schwandt, T. (2001). *Dictionary of Qualitative Inquiry*. SAGE Publications.
- Scott, C. (2011). *Measuring the Immeasurable: Capturing Intangible Values*. International Council of Museums.
- Scott, C. (2014). Emerging paradigms: national approaches for measuring cultural value. *Cultural Trends*, 23(2), 79-81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09548963.2014.897448>

- Seidman, I. (2006). *Interviewing as Qualitative Research*. Teachers College Press.
- Selwood, S. (2006). A Part to Play? The Academic Contribution to the Development of Cultural Policy in England. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 12(1), 35-53. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286630600613200>
- Shank, M. & Schirch, L. (2008). *Strategic Arts-Based Peacebuilding*. Blackwell Publishing.
- Shinebourne, P. (2011). The Theoretical Underpinnings of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA). *Existential Analysis*, 22(1), 16-31.
- Silva, H. (2014). *O lugar da residência, o local de moradia, estigma de localização, critério de residência no Grande Rio — O caso da Baixada Fluminense*. Universidad Federal de Rio de Janeiro [unpublished manuscript].
- Sloan, A. & Bowe, B. (2014). Phenomenology and Hermeneutic Phenomenology: The Philosophy, the Methodologies and Using Hermeneutic Phenomenology to Investigate Lecturer's Experiences of Curriculum Design. *Quality & Quantity: International Journal of Methodology*, 48(3). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-013-9835-3>
- Smith, J. (2009). *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method and Research*. SAGE.
- Smith, J. & Eatough, V. (2007). Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research in Psychology* (C. Willig & W. Stainton Rogers, eds.). SAGE Publications.
- Smith, J. A. & Shinebourne, P. (2012). Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. *APA Handbook of Research Methods in Psychology, Vol. 2. Research Designs: Quantitative, Qualitative, Neuropsychological, and Biological* (H. Cooper, P. M. Camic, D. L. Long, A. T. Panter, D. Rindskopf & K. J. Sher, eds.; pp. 73-82). American Psychological Association. <https://doi.org/10.1037/13620-005>
- Snowball, J. (2008). *Measuring the value of culture*. Springer International Publishing.
- Sousa Santos, B. (2014). *Epistemologies of the South*. Routledge.
- Stake, R. (2006). *Multiple Case Study Analysis*. The Guilford Press.
- Stebbins, R. (1990). *Sociology: The Study of Society*. Harper & Row.
- Stephenson Jr., M. & Zanotti, L. (2016). Exploring the Intersection of Theory and Practice of Arts for Peacebuilding. *Global Society*, 31(3), 336-352. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600826.2016.1255932>

- Stern, M. & Seifert, S. (2017). Culture and Social Wellbeing in New York City: Highlights of a Two-Year Research Project. *Culture and Social Wellbeing in New York City 2014-2017*.
https://repository.upenn.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1000&context=siap_culture_nyc
- Stiglitz, J. E. (1998). *Towards a New Paradigm for Development: Strategies, Policies and Processes*. UNCTAD. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/1491127>
- Stokfiszewski, I. (2016). On Social Culture. *Polish Theatre Journal*, 1(2).
<https://www.polishtheatrejournal.com/index.php/ptj/article/view/71>
- Stout, C. J. (1999). The Art of Empathy: Teaching Students to Care. *The Journal of Art Education*, 52(2), 21-34. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00043125.1997.11650892>
- Suárez, J., Ramírez, E. & Nieto, J. R. (2018). Las fronteras invisibles en las comunas 16 y 70 de Medellín (2008-2013): poder, territorio y resistencia. *El Ágora: Revista de Ciencias Sociales*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.21500/16578031.3825>
- Tarbell, D. & Saaty, T. (1980). The Conflict in South Africa: Directed of Chaotic. *Journal of Peace Science*, 4(2), 151-168. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26281643>
- Taylor, L. K., Nilsson, M., Forero, P. & Restrepo, M. (2020). Conducting Field Research amid Violence: Experiences from Colombia. *Researching peace and conflict: Field experiences and methodological* (Y. Gülsüm Acar, S. M. Moss & Ö. M. Uluğ, eds.; pp. 9-28). Springer.
- Taylor, L. K., O'Driscoll, D., Merrilees, C. E., Goeke-Morey, M., Shirlow, P. & Cummings, E. M. (2021). Trust, Forgiveness, and Peace: The Influence of Adolescent Social Identity in a Setting of Intergroup Conflict. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 46(2). <https://doi.org/10.1177/01650254211066768>
- Tepper, S. J. (2004). The Creative Campus: Who's No. 1? *The Chronicle of Higher Education*, 51(6). <https://www.chronicle.com/article/the-creative-campus-whos-no-1/>
- The Fund For Peace. (2000). *Fragile States Index*. <https://fragilestatesindex.org/>
- The Institute for Justice and Reconciliation. (2014). *Reconciliation Barometer Survey: 2014 Report*. The Institute for Justice and Reconciliation.
- Throsby, D. (2001). *Economics and Culture*. Cambridge University Press.
- Tillett, G. (2005). *Resolving Conflict: A Practical Approach*. Oxford University Press.

- Tobelem, J.-M. (2013). The Arts and Culture: A Financial Burden or a Way Out of the Crisis? *Journal of Cultural Management and Policy*, 3(1), 52-60. https://www.encatc.org/media/2689-encatc_journal_vol3_issue_1_20135361.pdf
- Tolstoy, L. (1904). *What is Art*. Funk & Wagnalls Company.
- Towse, R. (2011). *A Handbook of Cultural Economics*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Tylor, E. (1971). *Primitive Culture: Researches into the Development of Mythology, Philosophy, Religion, Language, Art and Custom*. Bradbury, Evans & Co. Printers Whitefriars.
- United Nations. (2008). *United Nations Peacekeeping Operations, Special Political Missions and Other Political Presences*. <https://www.unmissions.org/>
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2009). *Community Security and Social Cohesion*. UNDP.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (1982). *Mexico City Declaration on Cultural Policies*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000052505>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2018). Obtained from Intangible cultural heritage as a basis for resilience, reconciliation and construction of peace environments in Colombia's post-agreements: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/assistances/intangible-cultural-heritage-as-a-basis-for-resilience-reconciliation-and-construction-of-peace-environments-in-colombia-s-post-agreements-01522>
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (1996). *From a Culture of Violence to a Culture of Peace*. UNESCO Publishing.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2001). *Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity*. United Nations.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2009a). *Qué es la UNESCO*. United Nations.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2009b). *UNESCO Framework for Cultural Statistics*. United Nations.
- United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). (2012). Measuring Cultural Participation. In *UNESCO Framework for Cultural Statistics Handbook No. 2*. UNESCO Institute for Statistics.

- United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF). (2005). *The Effects of Conflict on Health and Well-being of Women and Girls in Darfur*. UNICEF; UNFPA.
- United Nations Secretary-General's Policy Committee. (2007). *Peacebuilding and the United Nations*. www.un.org/en/peacebuilding/pbso/pbun.shtml
- Uprimny, R. (2001). *El laboratorio colombiano: narcotráfico y administración de justicia en Colombia*. Ediciones Uniandes.
- Vasilachis de Gialdino, I. (2009). Ontological and Epistemological Foundations of Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Social Research*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-10.2.1299>
- Verdad Abierta. (2021, October 10th). De reclamantes a desarraigados: un drama en Montes de María. <https://verdadabierta.com/de-reclamantes-a-desarraigados-un-drama-en-montes-de-maria/>
- Vestheim, G. (1994). Instrumental Cultural Policy in Scandinavian Countries: A Critique Perspective. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 1(1), 57-71. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286639409357969>
- Wallace Consulting. (2016). *Evaluation of the Building Peace through the Arts: Re-Imaging Communities Programme*. Arts Council of Northern Ireland.
- Widmalm, S. (2006). The Utility of Bonding Social Capital. *Journal of Civil Society*, 1(1), 75-95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448680500210680>
- Williams, R. (1958). Culture is Ordinary. *Resources of Hope: Culture, Democracy, Socialism* (R. Gable, ed.; pp. 3-14). Verso Books.
- Williams, R. (1983). *Keywords*. Oxford University Press.
- Willig, C. (2017). *Interpretation in Qualitative Research*. SAGE Publications.
- Winner, E., Goldstein, T. & Vicent-Lancrin, S. (2013). *Art for Art's Sake?* Center for Educational Research and Innovation.
- Woods, R., Dobbs, L., Moore, C., Gordon, C. & Simpson, G. (2004). *Report of a Thematic Study Using Transnational Comparisons to Analyse and Identify Cultural Policies and Programmes that Contribute to Preventing and Reducing Poverty and Social Exclusion*. Northumbria University Press.
- World Bank. (2016a). *Poverty and Shared Prosperity*. The World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2016b). *Worldwide Governance Indicators*. The World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2017). *GINI Index. Poverty and Inequality Platform*. https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SI.POV.GINI?end=2020&name_desc=true&start=2020&view=map

- World Bank. (2021). *Data Bank*. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SI.DST.10TH.10>
- Yin, R. (1984). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*. SAGE Publications.
- Zainal, Z. (2007). Case Study as a Research Method. *Jurnal Kemanusiaan*, 5(1).
<https://jurnalkemanusiaan.utm.my/index.php/kemanusiaan/article/view/165>
- Zelizer, C. (2003). The Role of Artistic Processes in Peace-Building in Bosnia-Herzegovina. *Peace and Conflict Studies*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.46743/1082-7307/2003.1039>
- Zembylas, M. (2003). Emotions and Teacher Identity: A Post-Structural Perspective. *Teachers and Teaching: Theory and Practice*, 9(3), 213-238.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/13540600309378>
- Zapata, G. (2017). Arte y construcción de paz: la experiencia musical vital. *Calle14: revista de investigación en el campo del arte*, 240.252

APPENDICES

A1: Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

The Role of Arts and Culture in a Post-conflict Colombia

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

Who are we?

I am a PhD student from the School of Media, Culture & Society at the University of the West of Scotland. I have a bachelor's degree in International Relations from Universidad Externado de Colombia, and master's in International Cooperation and Development from the University of Montpellier in France.

Also, work experience as Project Assistant in the German-American Fulbright Commission in Berlin, Alumni Coordinator in Fulbright Colombia, as an advisor in multilateral cooperation and affairs of the International Affairs and Cooperation Office in the Ministry of Culture of Colombia. Previously, project manager in the Arab Colombian Chamber of Commerce. Besides, professional experience in the Delegation of the European Union in Colombia and the Colombian Consulate in New York.

What is the purpose of this research?

The overall aim of this study is to explore the role that arts and cultural activity can play in the Colombian peacebuilding process. This research is intended to assist and inform policy makers and those making funding decisions about the social impact of arts and culture, providing a review of theoretical background and evidence of current arts and cultural programmes that are taking place in Colombia.

For that a small sample research is employ in two different case studies (Casa Kolacho in Medellín and Sensory Expedition in Montes de María), looking at the contribution of arts and

cultural interventions facilitating dialogue, mutual understanding and enhance social cohesion in the reconciliation process in Colombia.

Why have I been chosen, and what am I being asked to do?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you have been engage in an arts and cultural project in one of our case study, or have experience directing a cultural intervention, or experience in funding or policy making.

We are interested in your experience as beneficiary of the art and cultural project, the impact and meaning it has for you, or in your experience delivering the project, its priorities, aims and objectives and the achievements and challenges of the project and its contribution to the peacebuilding process in Colombia. We would like to conduct an interview with you to explore your views and experiences of delivering the project, design a public policy or being part of it.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen if I decide to take part?

If you decide to take part in an interview, you will be asked a series of questions that have been designed to explore either your project and its delivery, aims, objectives and achievements or your experience from a funding and policy perspective, or in other side, to capture the ‘essence’ of the experience from the beneficiary and understand from the participants the ‘meaning’ of their individual perception.

The questions are of a general nature and the interviews tend to take the form of a conversation, rather than a fixed set of questions. With your permission, we would like to use an audio-recorder to keep a record of what was discussed. The recording will be transcribed by the researcher (Greis Cifuentes), who will keep your details confidential. If you decide to take part, you are free to answer, as many of the questions are you like. You can end the interview at any point and, if you decide to end the interview, you will not be asked to give a reason why. *The interview should last no longer than 2 hours.*

How will the data be managed?

Your data will be kept strictly confidential in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2018. The data won't have your name on it but will be linked to you by a unique ID number until the study ends, after which it will be fully anonymised. Data will be stored either in a locked filing cabinet or on a password-protected computer until after the study finishes, after which it will be destroyed. The findings from this study will be written up as part of the researcher's PhD thesis, as peer reviewed journal articles, and/or presented at conferences/seminars. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. All data will be reported anonymously.

Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/>

How will the data be used?

Your responses will be anonymised and used in the case study exploring examples of the contribution of arts and culture to peacebuilding process in Colombia. Through this, we will build a general understanding of the factors that contribute to the success of such projects the challenges faced in delivering them, and the arts and cultural intervention that facilitate dialogue, mutual understanding and social cohesion. *Please note: your name or any other information that would identify you will **not** be included in the final report, or in any other publication arising from this research.*

Are there any risks to taking part?

Some people can feel awkward during interviews and can feel uncomfortable about expressing their opinions on certain things. You will be interviewed by a trained and experienced researcher, who will do their utmost to ensure you find taking part in the research to be an enjoyable and rewarding experience. However, you will not be required to answer any questions that you do not feel comfortable with. If you decide not to answer a question or elaborate on an answer you have already given, you will not be asked to give a reason why.

Are there any benefits to taking part?

There are no immediate benefits to you personally in taking part. However, by sharing your views and experiences you will be contributing to informing future approaches to promoting

arts and culture as an important factor in developing localised approaches to reconciliation processes.

Who can I contact for further information?

If you have any questions about the research, you can contact PhD Student Greis Cifuentes on [REDACTED]

Professor David McGillivray – Director of Studies School of Media, Culture and Society, University of the West of Scotland on [REDACTED]

Who organised, funded, and approved the research?

This research is organised by Greis Cifuentes, a PhD student at UWS. The PhD is fully funded by the PhD student. The design of this study was reviewed by the Media, Culture & Society Research Ethics Committee at the University of the West of Scotland. The Committee approved the study on 19.12. 2018, it has ethics number: 4700.

Who can I contact if I have any concerns or complaints?

If you are in any way unhappy with how this research has been conducted, you can contact Dr Christopher O'Donnell, Chair of the Media, Culture & Society Research Ethics Committee, on [REDACTED] or you can write to him at the Media, Culture & Society Research Ethics Committee, University of the West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE.

All complaints will be handled in strict accordance with the University of the West of Scotland's formal complaints policy.

Thank you for considering taking part in this research

Personal details withheld.

A2: Consent Form

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: The Role of Arts and Culture in a Post-conflict Colombia
Ethics Approval Number: Reference 4700/ 6251
Investigator: Greis Cifuentes
Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm agreement:

STATEMENT	INITIALS
I confirm that I am happy to participate in this interview discussing my experience being involve in the arts and cultural processes that have been develop in this community through Casa Kolacho or Sensory Expedition.	
I confirm that I am happy to participate in this interview discussing the contribution of arts and culture in a post-conflict Colombia.	
The purpose of the research has been explained to me, I have read the participants Information sheet and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time – both prior to and after the interview – or refuse to answer any question without giving any reason.	
I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my interview after the interview, in which case the material will be deleted.	
I understand that my data will be treated confidentially and comply with GDPR guidelines and any publication resulting from this work will report only data that does not identify me.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (provide information on what personal information specifically will be collected) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	

I understand that I will not be paid for my participation or received any benefit directly from participating in this research.	
I agree to the interview being audio recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	
I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals)

Name of researcher (block capitals)

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

If you would like a copy of this consent form to keep, please ask the researcher. If you have any complaints or concerns about this research, you can direct these, in writing, to the Chair of the MCS Ethics Committee by email [REDACTED] Alternatively, you can contact us by post at: Ethics Committee Chair, School of Media, Culture and Society, University of West of Scotland, Paisley, PA1 2BE

A3: Interview Structure for Policy Makers

THE ROLE OF ARTS & CULTURE IN A POSTCONFLICT COLOMBIA INFORMANT INTERVIEW TOPIC GUIDE & REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR THE POLICY MAKERS

Participant REF	Date of Interview	Researcher
		Greis Cifuentes

Checklist for interviewer (pre-interview):

Yes / No/ NA

Has the participant received the e-information sheet & e-consent form?	
Has the participant completed, signed & returned the e-consent form?	
Has the participant agreed to the interview being audio recorded?	
Is the participant happy to proceed with the interview?	

SECTION 1: CONTEXT

1. Would you briefly tell us about you (current position, your role in the Colombian post-conflict, your involvement in arts and cultural projects)?
2. How in your work agenda is embedded arts and culture as a means for reconciliation/
In your position how do you advocate for the arts and culture as a tool for social change?

SECTION 2: PROGRAMMES AND PROJECTS

3. What are your own views on the role of arts and culture in post-conflict?
4. What does wellbeing and reconciliation mean to you?
5. How do you view the contribution of the arts and culture in achieving reconciliation?
(Probe on whether it's about artistic engagement, generating people-to-people contacts, positive media coverage and sentiment, reach, exchange opportunities; confidence building etc.)
6. What do you believe are the main challenges for arts and cultural projects working in the peacebuilding process at this time? ^{[[]]}_[SEP]

5. Arts and culture are presented as means that foster dialogue, mutual understanding, and social cohesion, and move peace processes forward by enabling bridges to be constructed between communities and between people. What is your view of this as a benefit and do you believe this statement to be true?
6. Have you personally experienced the positive effects of arts activities, and what are your views on the potential of arts and cultural interventions in investing for the Colombian reconciliation process?
7. In what ways do cultural activity provide different and effective ways of enabling individuals and communities to explore complex issues of memory, trauma, and reconciliation?
8. According to your expertise/knowledge, what art and cultural intervention contribute to peacebuilding process in Colombia.
9. There has been some media coverage around the use of arts for wellbeing that has suggested this work is a waste of resources... Can you tell me what your own view is on this? And how this perception might best be tackled?
10. How in the aftermath of conflict do state-supported institutions and state funding determine the ways in which different kinds of cultural activity and practice legitimise and sustain some while marginalising and even rejecting others?
11. Which reasons do you think are due to the fact that the Ministry of Culture has the lowest budget among the other Ministries, and it continues to decrease?

SECTION 3: SUCCESS MEASURES

12. This research process as you know is looking to measure or evidence the changes or benefits cultural and art projects have on participants. Some people feel aspects of arts and culture can be immeasurable. I wonder what your views are.

13. What kinds of information do you believe it would be most useful for arts projects to generate to demonstrate benefit and why? What type of information about this work do you believe would impact most positively on commissioning or funding of arts projects?

14. In your experience what are the most useful approaches to assessing the value of arts and culture in the achievement mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion in a region or area? (*Probe on techniques for assessing success, is it change in behaviour, growth of young people, confidence, resilience etc.*)

15. What are the principal impediments to assessing the contribution of arts and culture in the achievement mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion? Please detail. *(Probe on the intangible factors, long term assessment, competing interest of funders, assessment of satisfaction over outcomes or conflict in the region; religious groups, power of key groups or individuals over others?)*

SECTION 4: LESSONS LEARNED

16. Have you any examples of art and cultural contributions that you have been involved in/are aware of that you feel are particularly good examples and can you share that with us?

17. Can you tell me a story of a time when you witnessed someone achieve a real change or benefit to his or her wellbeing as a result of engaging with some form of the arts?

18. How would you like to see arts and culture develop in the future?

19. What do you see as being your key strengths, values or qualities that allow you to achieve what you do? (Personally, professionally and as a team).

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR TAKING THE TIME TO COMPLETE THIS INTERVIEW

Checklist for interviewer (post-interview)

Yes/No/NA

Have you thanked the participant for their time and contribution?	
Have you provided a full debrief, including details of who to contact if the participant has any questions or would like to know more about the evaluation?	
Was the interview recorded successfully?	
Has the audio file been labelled and stored in accordance with the 1998 Data Protection Act?	
Post-Interview Notes	

A4: Interview Structure for Cultural Agents

THE ROLE OF ARTS & CULTURE IN A POSTCONFLICT COLOMBIA INFORMANT INTERVIEW TOPIC GUIDE & REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR THE CULTURAL AGENTS

Participant REF	Date of Interview	Researcher
		Greis Cifuentes

Checklist for interviewer (pre-interview):

Yes / No/ NA

Has the participant received the e-information sheet & e-consent form?	
Has the participant completed, signed & returned the e-consent form?	
Has the participant agreed to the interview being audio recorded?	
Is the participant happy to proceed with the interview?	

SECTION 1: CONTEXT

1. Can you remember the first time you got involved with arts and cultural work, (*what attracted you to it? Has it been what you expected? What inspires you about it? What do you believe is its potential?*)
2. Would you briefly tell us about your role and position and the aims of the programme/project that you manage?
3. Is your project funded by government, an NGO, or cultural institute or other means? Or which type of organisations do you fund?
4. Does your project or programme that you manage have processes or outcomes that promote reconciliation or post conflict resolution?
5. Is your project or programme that you manage aimed at helping people in a conflict zone and/or aimed at building peace, mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion?

SECTION 2: PROGRAMMES AND PROJECTS

6. To what extent does your organisation fund or receive funds for programmes or projects that seek to use arts and culture to peacebuilding process in Colombia? Please detail

(Probe: if not, who volunteers, organisations or individuals and why?)

7. What are the strengths of the programmes or projects you are, or have been involved in, and why?

(Probe what they feel worked and what were the characteristics, did they have security and stability objectives at the start; or were the objectives about facilitating dialogue, mutual understanding, social cohesion, and/or securing peace?)

8. What are the limitations of the programmes or projects you have been involved in and why?

(Probe what they feel didn't work and what were the reasons e.g. resources, political turbulence, levels of violence, safety reasons, etc.)

9. According to your project and experience, what art and cultural intervention contribute to peacebuilding process in Colombia.

SECTION 3: SUCCESS MEASURES

10. How do you view the contribution of the arts and culture in achieving reconciliation?

(Probe on whether it's about artistic engagement, generating people-to-people contacts, positive media coverage and sentiment, reach, exchange opportunities; confidence building etc.)

11. What does wellbeing and reconciliation mean to you?

12. This research process as you know is looking to measure or evidence the changes or benefits your project has on participants. Some people feel aspects of arts and culture can be immeasurable. I wonder what your views are.

13. In your experience what are the most useful approaches to assessing the value of arts and culture in the achievement mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion in a region or area? *(Probe on techniques for assessing success, is it change in behaviour, growth of young people, confidence, resilience etc.)*

14. What are the principal impediments to assessing the contribution of arts and culture in the achievement mutual understanding, dialogue, and social cohesion? Please detail. *(Probe on the intangible factors, long term assessment, competing interest of funders, assessment of*

satisfaction over outcomes or conflict in the region; religious groups, power of key groups or individuals over others?)

15. How do you report on process as well as outcomes and outputs, e.g. the development of trust, relationships, how do you evaluate this? *(Probe on how the interviewees would measure influence of key individuals on confidence building, resilience, trust, etc.)*

16. Can you tell me a story of a time when you witnessed someone achieve a real change or benefit to their wellbeing as a result of engaging with some form of the arts?

SECTION 4: LESSONS LEARNED

17. Have you any examples of art and cultural contributions that you have been involved in/are aware of that you feel are particularly good examples and can you share that with us?

18. What do you see as being your key strengths, values or qualities that allow you to achieve what you do? (Personally, professionally and as a team)

19. In an ideal world what would your project look like in the future? Where do you hope to get to and what do you hope to achieve?

20. Looking back is there anything you would have done differently and why?

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR TAKING THE TIME TO COMPLETE THIS INTERVIEW

Checklist for interviewer (post-interview)

Yes/No/NA

Have you thanked the participant for their time and contribution?	
Have you provided a full debrief, including details of who to contact if the participant has any questions or would like to know more about the evaluation?	
Was the interview recorded successfully?	
Has the audio file been labelled and stored in accordance with the 1998 Data Protection Act?	
Post-Interview Notes	

A5: Interview Structure for Research Participants

THE ROLE OF ARTS & CULTURE IN A POSTCONFLICT COLOMBIA INFORMANT INTERVIEW TOPIC GUIDE & REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR THE RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

Participant REF	Date of Interview	Researcher
		Greis Cifuentes

Checklist for interviewer (pre-interview):

Yes / No/ NA

Has the participant received the e-information sheet & e-consent form?	
Has the participant completed, signed & returned the e-consent form?	
Has the participant agreed to the interview being audio recorded?	
Is the participant happy to proceed with the interview?	

SECTION 1:

1. Tell me about yourself (age, what to do study/work, how long have you been living here, with whom do you live with, how many people do you have in charge).

SECTION 2: COLOMBIA CONTEXT

2. What do you think about the Colombian Peace Agreement and the current post-conflict process Colombia is going through?
3. It has decreased the level of violence and insecurity in the area after the signing of the peace agreement with the FARC. Do you feel more presence of the State? Do you feel safe?
4. How was your situation before and after the Colombian peace agreement?
5. Do you believe that the investment in arts and culture in the area has changed by comparing the current government and the predecessor, or you consider is remains the same?

SECTION 3: ENGAGEMENT WITH ARTS

6. How you came to participate in the art and cultural project?
7. What would you say you value most with regards to each of the following:
 - a) your involvement in the arts

b) The lead artist that you work with

c) Being in a group

d) All above

e) Other, specify which and why.

8. What about your involvement with the arts, is that something you have experienced prior to this project?

9. Do you see yourself as an artist?

10. How long have you been involved with the project? What would you say you are getting out of it? (personally/in life/with the arts)

11. What would you say has been challenging for you about participating in the project?

12. Has the project changed your ideas about anything?

13. Was doing something important creative important to you? Why?

Since we are looking how working with the arts might facilitate dialogue, mutual understanding, and social cohesion in a post-conflict Colombia. We would like to ask you a bit about your own views/experiences on that.

14. When I say dialogue, mutual understanding, and social cohesion, what does that mean to you? Do you think there's any difference between them?

15. What kind of things do you do since you are being involve (better, happier)?

16. Do you think your wellbeing has changed in any way during the project?

17. Has taking part had any bad effects for you?

18. Have you noticed any changes since you have been part of the project in the way that you feel in yourself? (Mentally or emotionally) Can you tell me something about that.

SOCIAL COHESION

Since you have been involved:

19. Have you make new friends, develop new relationship during the Project? If yes, how do you think arts and culture contribute to that.

20. Have the Project strength the bonds with the people your already knew (that are also involve in the Project)?

21. Do you want to be involved in further projects?

22. Do you feel more positive about where you live?

23. Have you become keen to help in local projects?

24. Do you think arts develop community networks and sociability?

25. Does the Project help to strength community cooperation and networking?

26. Does the Project strength your cultural identity/ traditions?
27. What particular arts and cultural intervention do you think facilitate social cohesion?
28. Is the community more unify since the project started?

MUTUAL UNDERSTANDING

29. Do you think arts promote tolerance and contribute to conflict resolution. Has its being your case, why?
30. Do you think arts contribute to a more relax atmosphere in the area? Why?
31. Have you learn more about other people, understand them and develop empathy thanks do the Project?
32. Do you feel more open to listen other points of views/perspectives?
33. Do you feel that you can work together with people that think different to you or belong to a different religion/race/culture?
34. What particular arts and cultural intervention do you think facilitate mutual understanding?

DIALOGUE

35. How do you think arts and culture have opened and channel of dialogue in the community and/or in your personal life.
36. Have you been able to express ideas that are important to you?
37. Has the Project help/facilitate to express your emotions (such as disruption, fear, loss, happiness).
38. Do you think (in this case) arts and cultural interventions are safe spaces where you can express freely your opinions and feelings.
39. What particular arts and cultural intervention do you think facilitate dialogue?

RECONCILIATION

40. In your experience, do you think and feel arts and culture facilitates reconciliation in an area that has been hardly bit by violence for more than 50 years?
41. Do you think that being in an arts and cultural project have given you the tools and strengths to revealing the past?
42. Are you more optimistic about your future?

PROGRAMMES AND PROJECTS

43. What are the strengths of the project you have been involved in, and why? (Clear objectives, guide, activities schedule, professors, etc).

44. What are the limitations of the project you have been involved in, and why?

(Probe what they feel didn't work and what were the reasons e.g. resources, political turbulence, levels of violence, safety reasons, etc.)

45. Would you like to be involved in more projects like this? If yes, would you like to help organise it?

SECTION 4: LESSONS LEARNED

46. Have you any examples of art and cultural contributions that you have been involved in/are aware of that you feel are particularly good examples and can you share that with us?

47. Are you doing any artwork outside of attending the project? Do you think this is something that you would like to continue with? If yes, then how and why?

48. Are there any other types of activities that you would like to try?

49. What do you think will happen at the end of the programme? Do you have any thoughts about what will come next?

50. What would you ideally like to achieve?

51. Looking back is there anything you would have done differently and why?

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR TAKING THE TIME TO COMPLETE THIS INTERVIEW

Checklist for interviewer (post-interview)

Yes/No/NA

Have you thanked the participant for their time and contribution?	
Have you provided a full debrief, including details of who to contact if the participant has any questions or would like to know more about the evaluation?	
Was the interview recorded successfully?	
Has the audio file been labelled and stored in accordance with the 1998 Data Protection Act?	

Post-Interview Notes